

Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (06)

**A.E. Bras
V.H.J. van der Velden**

Laboratory Medical Immunology (LMI), Department of Immunology, Erasmus Medical Center, Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Correspondence: a.e.bras@gmail.com / a.bras@erasmusmc.nl / v.h.j.vandervelden@erasmusmc.nl

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.3342607

License

Creative Commons - Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰
07-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Authors published four papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 3 through 9):

Date	Title
13-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888) ³²
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777) ³³
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666) ³⁴
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 3 up to 9 ³⁵

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^{6_{11}}+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{8_{11}-7_{11}}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^{6_{12}}+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{8_{12}-7_{12}}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^{6_{13}}+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{8_{13}-7_{13}}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^{6_{14}}+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{8_{14}-7_{14}}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^{6_{15}}+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{8_{15}-7_{15}}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^{6_{16}}+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{8_{16}-7_{16}}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results in an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45*-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$-(1+2+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Note

Previously, authors used 'CSR' to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to natural numbers (as originally introduced by Inder Taneja) and 'NCSR' to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to negative integers (as introduced by ourselves). Authors always avoided 'PCSR' as this might introduce ambiguity (pseudo vs. positive CSR).

From this point forward, authors will use the following:

- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any integer value
- +CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any positive integer
- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any negative integer

Aim

Attempt to ‘fill the gaps’ in our previous work ^{6,7,8,12,13,14,15,25,30,31} by identifying...

- increasing genuine CSR for integers without any increasing genuine CSR.
- decreasing genuine CSR for integers without any decreasing genuine CSR.

Results

Authors identified 16501 previously unknown genuine CSR, see supplements.

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	2928	5109	2979	5485

Overview

Currently, within the -2147483647 up to 2147483647 range, increasing CSR are available for 1757914 integers, and decreasing CSR are available for 2451639 integers:

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	876906	1225677	873572	1202753
Pseudo	2083	295	5353	22914
Total	878989	1225972	878925	1225667

Note

Authors consider CSR to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published CSR are the shortest in existence.
- Published CSR are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable CSR do not exists.

References

1. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v1>
Natural Numbers from 44 to 1000 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 6 Feb 2013.
2. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v2>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 44 to 4444 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Tuesday 19 Mar 2013
3. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v3>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 1 to 11111 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 5 Jun 2013
4. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v4>
More on Crazy Sequential Representation of Natural Numbers with Subtraction
Inder J. Taneja. Monday 5 Aug 2013
5. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v5>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 0 to 11111 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 8 Jan 2014
6. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6483968>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1288822>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Tuesday 12 Jun 2018
7. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6516131>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1288892>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 14 Jun 2018
8. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6587117>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1292115>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Jun 2018
9. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a108.pdf>
MD5: BB89800FB86BDF830D28EB07241D78C1
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 12 Sep 2018

10. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a131.pdf>
MD5: D135C0F9A417B7221AEBB1225FDF7B8D
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000
Inder J. Taneja. Saturday 10 Nov 2018
11. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a132.pdf>
MD5: 87BF426B1827555F5FB701F7DAE33969
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000
Inder J. Taneja. Saturday 10 Nov 2018
12. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7429967>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1998118>
Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 06 Dec 2018
13. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7467665>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2276623>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 14 Dec 2018
14. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7505690>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2525823>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 24 Dec 2018
15. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7539311>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530025>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 02 Jan 2019
16. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.05070v1>
Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases
Tim Wylie. Thursday 11 Oct 2018
17. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546955>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530974>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
18. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546958>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530976>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
19. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546970>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530978>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

20. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546982>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530980>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
21. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546985>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530982>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
22. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546991>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530984>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
23. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7564973>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2536047>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 09 Jan 2019
24. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7547423>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.2531777>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
25. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7639799>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551565>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 28 Jan 2019
26. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7619648>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2547763>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 23 Jan 2019
27. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7665629>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555620>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Saturday 02 Feb 2019
28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543626>
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000
Inder J. Taneja. Monday 18 Jan 2019
29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2556036>
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000
Inder J. Taneja. Sunday 03 Feb 2019

30. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7683572>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2558454>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 06 Feb 2019
31. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7689386>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2559524>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 07 Feb 2019
32. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7713548>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2563944>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 13 Feb 2019
33. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7731674>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571496>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Feb 2019
34. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7731677>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571500>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Feb 2019
35. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7732883>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571998>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 3 up to 9
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Feb 2019

Supplement 1

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
24963	$(12^3+4+5^6/(7+8))^*9$	90952	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7+8/9)$
30070	$-12+(((3^4)^5)-67)^*89$	92186	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6+7)^*8+9$
31925	$((12+((3^4)^56))^*7)+89$	92231	$-1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7-8+9)$
34031	$1^*2-(3^4*5^*(-6-78)-9)$	92233	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7-8+9)$
38706	$-12+((3^4)^*(567-89))$	94655	$(1+(2/3))^*(4+56789)$
40110	$-12+(((3^4)^56)-78)^*9$	97204	$12-(((34-((5^6)^7))^*8)/9)$
44432	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6)-7^*89$	97238	$12+((34+(((5^6)^7)^*8))/9)$
44562	$12+((3^4)^*(567-(8+9)))$	97309	$(1+(((2/3)^4)^5))^*6789$
49643	$-1-(((2^*(3^4))-5678)^*9)$	99109	$-1-(2-3^4*(5+67))^*(8+9)$
49645	$1-(((2^*(3^4))-5678)^*9)$	99111	$1-(2-3^4*(5+67))^*(8+9)$
52048	$-1+(((2/3)^4)+5)^*6789$	101687	$-1-2^*(-3^4+5)^*(678-9)$
52337	$((1^*2)^*(34-(5/6)))^*789$	101688	$1^*2^*(3^4-5)^*(678-9)$
52964	$-1+2^*3^4*(5^*67-8)-9$	101689	$1-2^*(-3^4+5)^*(678-9)$
52966	$1+2^*3^4*(5^*67-8)-9$	103058	$-1-((2^3)^4-5^6+78)^*9$
53112	$1+((2^3)^4-5)^*(6+7)-8^*9$	103060	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6+78)^*9$
53138	$(1^*2)+((3^4)^*(567+89))$	103771	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6+7-8)^*9$
53148	$12+((3^4)^*(567+89))$	105262	$-1^*(2^3)^4+5^6*7-8-9$
53165	$-1+((2^3)^4-5)^*(6+7)-8-9$	105277	$-1-(2^3)^4+5^6*7+8-9$
53796	$12-((3^4)^*((5-678)+9))$	105278	$-1^*(2^3)^4+5^6*7+8-9$
54328	$12^*((3^4)^56)-(78/9)$	105787	$1+2^*3^4*(5^*6+7^*89)$
54341	$-1+2^*3^4*5^*67+8^*9$	106723	$((123^4)^*((5^6)-7))/(8^*9)$
54492	$-12-(((3^4)^*(5-678))+9)$	108091	$(-1^*2)+(((3^4)+56)^*789)$
54534	$(12-((3^4)^*(5-678)))+9$	108092	$(1-2)+(((3^4)+56)^*789)$
54968	$1+((2^*(34+(5/6)))^*789)$	108094	$(1^2)+(((3^4)+56)^*789)$
55221	$12^*3^4*56+789$	108967	$((12^*34)-((5^6)^7))^*(8-9)$
55517	$(-123+((4^*(5^6)-7))^*8)/9$	113398	$-1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7-8^*9$
55563	$(123+(((4^*(5^6))-7)^*8))/9$	113453	$-1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7-8-9$
59196	$-12^*((3^4)^*(5-67))+89$	113455	$1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7-8-9$
59295	$(1-(2/3))^*((456^*78)+9)$	116154	$((1+2)^*(3^4))^*(567-89)$
59361	$-12-3^4*(56-789)$	119939	$(1-(((2/3)-4)^5))^*6789$
60036	$12^*((((3^4)-5)^*67)-89)$	119957	$-1+((2/3+4^5)^*(6+7)+8)^*9$
60175	$((-12^*(3^4))^*(5-67))-89$	119959	$1+((2/3+4^5)^*(6+7)+8)^*9$
61193	$(12^*((3^4)-5))^*67+89$	122869	$-1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7-8-9$
61366	$1-((2^3)^4-5)^*(6*(7-8)-9)$	122948	$-1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7+8-9$
64686	$-12+(((3^4)-5)+6)^*789$	122966	$-1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7+8+9$
65129	$-1-(2^*3^4+5)^*6*(7-8^*9)$	122968	$1+(2^3)^4+5^6*7+8+9$
66118	$-12+(34^*((((5^6)+7)/8)-9))$	123769	$(-1^*2^*3^4+5^6+7)^*8+9$
66142	$12+(34^*((((5^6)+7)/8)-9))$	130126	$-1/2^*(3^4+5)-6^7-8+9$
66457	$(12+((34^*((5^6)+7)/8))+9)$	132752	$-1+2^*(3-4)^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
66730	$-12+(34^*((((5^6)+7)/8)+9))$	132754	$1+2^*(3-4)^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
67137	$1+(2^3)^4+5^6*(7+8-9)$	135362	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^*78))/9$
67350	$12-(((3^4)+5)^*(6-789))$	135462	$((12^*34)+((5^6)^*78))/9$
68322	$-1+((2^3)^4-(5+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	135997	$123^*((((4^5)/6)^*7)-89)$
68324	$1+((2^3)^4-(5+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	138887	$-1234+(((5^6)-(7^*8))^*9)$
68358	$-12+(((3^4)+5)^*(6+789))$	139515	$(-12^*34)+(((5^6)-78)^*9)$
68382	$12+(((3^4)+5)^*(6+789))$	139670	$-1-(2^*3^4-5^6-7^*8)^*9$
68834	$1+((2^3)^4-5-6^*7)^*(8+9)$	139688	$(-1-234)+(((5^6)-78)^*9)$
69002	$-1+((2^3)^4+5-6^*7)^*(8+9)$	139690	$(1-234)+(((5^6)-78)^*9)$
69004	$1+((2^3)^4+5-6^*7)^*(8+9)$	139713	$(-12^*34)+(((5^6)-(7^*8))^*9)$
69175	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7+8-9)$	140099	$(12-34)+(((5^6)-(7^*8))^*9)$
70158	$-123+(((4^*(5^6)-7))/8)^*9$	140143	$(-12+34)+(((5^6)-(7^*8))^*9)$
70404	$123+(((4^*(5^6)-7))/8)^*9$	140240	$(123-4)+(((5^6)-(7^*8))^*9)$
72416	$((1+(2/3))+4)+5)^*6789$	140268	$(-123^4)+(((5^6)+7)+8)^*9$
74996	$-1-2^*3^4*(5-6^*78)-9$	140371	$(-123+4)+(((5^6)-(7+8))^*9)$
74998	$1-2^*3^4*(5-6^*78)-9$	140879	$(123-4)+(((5^6)+7)+8)^*9$
79157	$-1+(2^*3^4+5)^*6*(7+8^*9)$	140982	$(123^4)+(((5^6)-(7+8))^*9)$
79861	$((1+(12+34)^*(5^6)+7)-8)/9$	141010	$(-123+4)+(((5^6)+7^*8))^*9$
80630	$-1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*7-8^*9$	141107	$(12-34)+(((5^6)+7^*8))^*9$
80632	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*7-8^*9$	141208	$(-123+4)+(((5^6)+78)^*9)$
80774	$-1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*7+8^*9$	141537	$(12^*34)+(((5^6)+7^*8))^*9$
80776	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*7+8^*9$	141560	$(-1+234)+(((5^6)+78)^*9)$
82433	$1+(2^3)^4*(5^*6-7/8-9)$	141724	$1234+(((5^6)-(7+8))^*9)$
85110	$((-1-(2/3))^*(4-5678))^*9$	141735	$(12^*34)+(((5^6)+78)^*9)$
85230	$((1+(2/3))^*(4+5678))^*9$	141850	$1234+(((5^6)+7)-8)^*9$
86507	$-1-((2^*(3^4))-567)^*89$	141868	$1234+(((5^6)-7)+8)^*9$
86509	$1-((2^*(3^4))-567)^*89$	141994	$1234+(((5^6)+7)+8)^*9$
87123	$(123+(((4^5)/6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	142784	$-1+(2^*3^4+5^6+78)^*9$
87567	$-12+(((3^4)+5^*6))^*789$	142786	$1+(2^*3^4+5^6+78)^*9$
87965	$-1+(((2^*(3^4))+5678)^*9)$	144853	$123^*((((4^5)/6)^*7)-(8+9))$
89875	$((1+(12+34)^*((5^6)+7))/8)-9$	145110	$(12^*(3-4+5)-6)^*7^*(-8+9)$
89893	$((1+(12+34)^*((5^6)+7))/8)+9$	145194	$(12^*(3-4+5)+6)^*7^*(-8+9)$
90950	$-1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7+8/9)$	145436	$-12^*(34-(((5^6)^7)+8)/9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
145951	$(123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) - 8) - 9$	212767	$((1 - 2)/3 + (45 * 6))^7 * 789$
145969	$(123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) - 8) + 9$	213293	$((1 - (2/3)) + (45 * 6))^7 * 789$
146252	$12^3 * (34 + (((5^6)^7) + 8)/9)$	213556	$((1^2)/3 + (45 * 6))^7 * 789$
146821	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) + 8 - 9$	213557	$1 + ((2/3) + (45 * 6))^7 * 789$
147067	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) - 8 + 9$	213815	$-123 * (4 - (((5^6) + (7 * 8))/9))$
148069	$(1 - ((2/3) - 4) * 56) * 789$	213992	$-1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5)^6 * (67 - 8) * 9$
149035	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) + 8 + 9$	213994	$1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5)^6 * (67 - 8) * 9$
149810	$1/2 * (3^{(4+5)} + 6^7 - 8 + 9)$	214515	$(12 * (34 + (((5^6) - 7)/8)))^9$
150852	$((12 * (3^4)) - 5)^6 * (67 + 89)$	214799	$123 * (4 + (((5^6) + (7 * 8))/9))$
151534	$-1 - (2^3)^4 * (5 - 6^7) - 8 - 9$	216016	$-1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5)^6 * 7 * 8 + 9$
151621	$(-1 + ((2/3) + 4) * 5)^6 * 789$	219488	$1/2 * (3^4 - 5)^{-6} * (-7 + 8) + 9$
151640	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * (5^6 + 7) + 89$	220472	$((123 + 4) * (((5^6) + 7) - 8))^9$
151642	$1 + (2^3)^4 * (5^6 + 7) + 89$	220486	$((123 + 4) * (5^6) + 7) - 8 / 9$
152412	$(12 * (3^4)) + 5)^6 * (67 + 89)$	220584	$((123 + 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) - 8 / 9$
153633	$(123 * ((5/6)^7) + 8) * 9$	220906	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5)^6 * 7 - 8 * 9$
155800	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) + (8 * 9)$	225782	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * (56 - 7/8) - 9$
157891	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7) + 89$	225784	$1 + (2^3)^4 * (56 - 7/8) - 9$
159877	$-123 + (4 * 5)^{-6} * ((-6 - 7) + 8) + 9$	227550	$(123 * 45)^6 * (6^7) - (8/9)$
163496	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6^7) * 8 - 9$	231703	$(123 + ((4^5)/6))^7 * 789$
163822	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 - 7) * 8 - 9$	232430	$((123 - 4) * (5^6) - 7) / 8 + 9$
163824	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 - 7) * 8 - 9$	232517	$((123 - 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) / 8 - 9$
163830	$-1 - (2^3)^4 * 5 * (6 - 7) * 8 - 9$	232535	$((123 - 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) / 8 + 9$
163842	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 - 7) * 8 + 9$	241370	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5)^6 * (6^7 + 8 + 9)$
163850	$1 - (2^3)^4 * 5 * (6 - 7) * 8 + 9$	245459	$-1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5)^6 * (7 - (8 + 9))$
165199	$(1 + ((2/3) + 4) * 5)^6 * 789$	246265	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 / 6 + 7) * 8 * 9$
166184	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) - 7) * 8) / 9)$	248055	$((123 + 4) * (5^6) - 7) / 8 + 9$
167000	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) - 7) * 8) / 9)$	248149	$((123 + 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) / 8 - 9$
167928	$1 + (2^3)^4 * (56 - 7 - 8) - 9$	248167	$((123 + 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) / 8 + 9$
172943	$-1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5^6) * (7 + 8) + 9$	248638	$-1 - (2 * (3^4 - 5^6) + 7) * 8 - 9$
175094	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6) * (7 + 8) * 9$	248658	$1 - (2 * (3^4 - 5^6) + 7) * 8 + 9$
175814	$-1 + (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^7 / 8 - 9$	257193	$(123^4 * ((4^5) - 6) / 7)^6 * (8 + 9)$
175816	$1 + (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^7 / 8 - 9$	257282	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6) * 7 - 8 * 9$
175832	$-1 + (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^7 / 8 + 9$	257284	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6) * 7 - 8 * 9$
175834	$1 + (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^7 / 8 + 9$	257912	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6) * 7 - 8 * 9$
177497	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5^6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	257914	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6) * 7 - 8 * 9$
177499	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5^6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	258812	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 + 6) * 7 + 8 * 9$
177625	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8) * 9$	258814	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 + 6) * 7 + 8 * 9$
179495	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6^7 * 8) * 9$	259368	$1 - (2^3)^4 * 5 + 6^7 - 89$
180672	$(12^3)^4 * (45 + ((6^7 * 8) / 9))$	265014	$(-123 * 4) + (((5^6) - 7) * (8 + 9))$
184013	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6^7 + 8) * 9$	265252	$(-123 * 4) + (((5^6) + 7) * (8 + 9))$
184015	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6^7 + 8) * 9$	265484	$(12 - 34) + (((5^6) - 7) * (8 + 9))$
184274	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	265998	$(123 * 4) + (((5^6) - 7) * (8 + 9))$
184276	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	266230	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 / 6 * 78 - 9$
184364	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 + 7 - 8) * 9$	266232	$1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 / 6 * 78 - 9$
184373	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 * (7 - 8)) * 9$	266236	$123 * 4 + (5^6 + 7) * (8 + 9)$
184382	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	267362	$((1 - 12 + 34) * (5^6) * 7) + 8 / 9$
184508	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) * 9$	272024	$-1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5)^6 * (67 + 8) * 9$
184510	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) * 9$	272026	$1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5)^6 * (67 + 8) * 9$
184967	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 * 9$	274724	$-1 + (2 + 3^4 * 5)^6 * (67 + 8) * 9$
184969	$1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 * 9$	280658	$1 + 2 * 3^4 * 5 + 6^7 - 89$
195143	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 56) * (7 * 8 - 9)$	280801	$1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5^6 - 7 * 8) * 9$
195145	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 56) * (7 * 8 - 9)$	281699	$-1 + 2 * (3^4 + 5^6 - 7 * 8) * 9$
196908	$((-1 + ((2345/6) * 7)) * 8) * 9$	284796	$12 * 3^4 * 5 - 6^7 * (8 - 9)$
199097	$1 + (2 - 3^4 * 5^6) * (7 - 89)$	288695	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 * (5/6 + 7) - 8) * 9$
199332	$12 + 3 * ((4 + 5)^6 + 7) / 8 + 9$	288697	$1 + ((2^3)^4 * (5/6 + 7) - 8) * 9$
204861	$1 - ((2^3)^4 * 5 + 6) * (7 - 8 - 9)$	289369	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - (5 + 6) * 7) * 8 * 9$
205212	$((12 * 34) - (5/6) * 7) * 8 * 9$	290462	$1 + (2^3)^4 - 5)^6 * (6 + 7 * 8 + 9)$
205403	$(-1 + ((2/3) + 4) * 56) * 789$	290520	$(1 + 2^3 * 4 + 5 - 6) * 8 * 9$
206591	$((123 - 4) * (5^6)) - (7 * 8) / 9$	291527	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 * 7) * 8 * 9$
206981	$(1 + ((2/3) + 4) * 56) * 789$	291529	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 * 7) * 8 * 9$
207171	$(-12 * (34 - (((5^6) - 7) / 8))) * 9$	292247	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6 * 7) * 8 * 9$
210365	$-1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5) * 6 * (78 + 9)$	292249	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6 * 7) * 8 * 9$
210367	$1 - (2 - 3^4 * 5) * 6 * (78 + 9)$	293615	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 - 7) * 8 * 9$
210887	$-1 + 2 * (3/4 * (5^6 + 7) - 8) * 9$	293617	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 - 7) * 8 * 9$
210889	$1 + 2 * (3/4 * (5^6 + 7) - 8) * 9$	293805	$(-123 + ((4^5) * (5 - 6) + 7)) * 8 * 9$
210988	$1 + 2 * (3/4 * (5^6 - 7) + 8) * 9$	294623	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 4 - 5 - 6 + 7) * 8 * 9$
211177	$1 + 2 * (3/4 * (5^6 + 7) + 8) * 9$	294625	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7) * 8 * 9$
211715	$((-1 - (2/3)) + (45 * 6))^7 * 789$	294789	$-123 + ((4^5) * (5 - 6) + 7) * 8 * 9$
212503	$-1 - (((2/3) - (45 * 6))^7) * 789$	294824	$1 + (2^3)^4 * (5 + 67) - 89$
212504	$((-1 * 2) / 3) + (45 * 6))^7 * 789$	299377	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 67) * 8 * 9$
212505	$1 - (((2/3) - (45 * 6))^7) * 789$	300326	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 + 6^7 - 89$
212731	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5) * 6^7 / 8 - 9$	300328	$1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 + 6^7 - 89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
306251	$-1+(2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot 6^7 + 8)^9$	420259	$1+((23^4 - 5)/6 + 7^8)^9$
306253	$1+(2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot 6^7 + 8)^9$	420362	$-1+(2-3+4)^5(5^6 - 7^8)^9$
307719	$(12 - ((3^4)^5))^*(6-789)$	420364	$1+(2-3+4)^5(5^6 - 7^8)^9$
310879	$-1+2^*(3^4 - 5^6)^*(7-8-9)$	422819	$-1+2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot 6^*(78+9)$
310881	$1+2^*(3^4 - 5^6)^*(7-8-9)$	422821	$1+2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot 6^*(78+9)$
310969	$1+(2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot 6^7 - 8)^9$	423386	$-1+(2-3+4)^5(5^6 + 7^8)^9$
311111	$-1+(2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot 6^7 + 8)^9$	423980	$-1+(2-3+4)^5(5^6 + 7^8)^9$
312092	$-12^*(34 - (((5^6)^*(7+8))/9))$	431567	$-1-2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot (5-6^7)^8 \cdot 9$
312908	$12^*(34 + (((5^6)^*(7+8))/9))$	431569	$1-2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot (5-6^7)^8 \cdot 9$
314121	$1-2^*(3^4 + 5^6)^*(7-8-9)$	437021	$-123+(4^*((5^6)^7) - 89))$
315382	$-1+(2^3)^4 \cdot (5-6+78) - 9$	437309	$-123+(4^*((5^6)^7) - (8+9)))$
315384	$1+(2^3)^4 \cdot (5-6+78) - 9$	437335	$123+(4^*((5^6)^7) - (8^9)))$
316430	$-1+(2^3 \cdot 4^5 + 6^7/8)^9$	437336	$(-123+(4^*((5^6)^7) - 8))) - 9$
316432	$1+(2^3 \cdot 4^5 + 6^7/8)^9$	437664	$(123+(4^*((5^6)^7 + 8))) + 9$
320093	$-1-(2-(3^4 - 5)^6 \cdot 78)^9$	437665	$-123+(4^*((5^6)^7) + (8^9)))$
320095	$1-(2-(3^4 - 5)^6 \cdot 78)^9$	437691	$123+(4^*((5^6)^7 + 8) + 9))$
320129	$-1-(-2-(3^4 - 5)^6 \cdot 78)^9$	437979	$123+(4^*((5^6)^7 + 89))$
320131	$1-(-2-(3^4 - 5)^6 \cdot 78)^9$	439872	$(1+2^*(3/4)^{-5})/6^{\wedge}(-7-8+9)$
323504	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6)^*(7+8^9)$	446976	$((12^3)^4)^*(56+(78/9))$
323506	$1+((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6)^*(7+8^9)$	459016	$-1-(2-3^4 \cdot 5)^6 \cdot 7^*(8+9)$
323662	$-1+((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6)^*(7+8^9)$	459018	$1-(2-3^4 \cdot 5)^6 \cdot 7^*(8+9)$
323664	$1+((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6)^*(7+8^9)$	463644	$(-12+(((3^4) - 5)^6 \cdot 78))^9$
325953	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 5^6)^*(7+8^9)$	463860	$(12+(((3^4) - 5)^6 \cdot 78))^9$
326511	$(-12 - ((3^4)^5))^*(6-789)$	472456	$((1+2)^3)^4 + 5 + 6^7 \cdot 8/9$
326988	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^4 + 5))^*(6/7+8)^9$	473480	$((1+(2/3))^4 \cdot 56)^7 \cdot 89$
332182	$1-((2^3)^4 + 5)^*(6-78-9)$	481464	$12^*(((3^4)^5 \cdot 56) - 78))^9$
335735	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 567)^8 \cdot 9$	481536	$(12^3)^*(45^6 + (78/9))$
335737	$1+((2^3)^4 + 567)^8 \cdot 9$	486709	$-1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4+5) - 6)^7 \cdot (8+9)$
337257	$(1+2)^3 \cdot (4^5 \cdot (6+7-8) - 9)$	486711	$1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4+5) - 6)^7 \cdot (8+9)$
337743	$(1+2)^3 \cdot (4^5 \cdot (6+7-8) + 9)$	487542	$-1+((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6)^7 \cdot (8+9)$
340680	$((1+(2/3))^4)^5 \cdot 678)^9$	487544	$1+((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6)^7 \cdot (8+9)$
341189	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}(-4+5+6)^7 \cdot 8+9)$	489186	$((12^*(3^4))^5 \cdot 56) - 78)^9$
341191	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}(-4+5+6)^7 \cdot 8+9)$	490509	$(-12 - ((3^4)^5 \cdot (5-678)))^9$
346560	$(-1+2^*(3/4)^{-5})/6^{\wedge}(-7-8+9)$	490605	$-12 - ((3^4)^5 \cdot (5-678))^9$
346800	$12/((34^5)^{\wedge}(((6-7)+8) - 9))$	490629	$12 - ((3^4)^5 \cdot (5-678))^9$
347020	$-1+((2^3)^4 \cdot 5 - 67)^*(8+9)$	490725	$(12 - ((3^4)^5 \cdot (5-678)))^9$
347022	$1+((2^3)^4 \cdot 5 - 67)^*(8+9)$	494022	$(12/34)^*(5^*(6^7 + 8) + 9)$
350774	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge} - 4 + 5)^6 \cdot 7/8 - 9$	497895	$-12+(((3^4)^5 \cdot (5+678))^9)$
350776	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge} - 4 + 5)^6 \cdot 7/8 - 9$	499617	$-123+(4^*((5^6) - 7)^8) - 9))$
350792	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge} - 4 + 5)^6 \cdot 7/8 + 9$	499689	$-123+(4^*((5^6) - 7)^8) + 9))$
350794	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge} - 4 + 5)^6 \cdot 7/8 + 9$	500311	$123+(4^*((5^6) + 7)^8) - 9))$
352863	$((-12+((3^4)^5 \cdot 56))^7 \cdot 8) - 9$	500383	$123+(4^*((5^6) + 7)^8) + 9))$
352881	$((-12+((3^4)^5 \cdot 56))^7 \cdot 8) + 9$	512624	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 5)^6 \cdot (6+7^*(8+9))$
353067	$-12+((3^4)^5 \cdot (56^7 \cdot 8) - 9))$	512626	$1+((2^3)^4 + 5)^6 \cdot (6+7^*(8+9))$
353091	$12+((3^4)^5 \cdot (56^7 \cdot 8) - 9))$	528581	$(1+23^4 - 5)^*(-6+7+8/9)$
354525	$-12+((3^4)^5 \cdot (56^7 \cdot 8) + 9))$	551035	$((12^*(3^4))^5 \cdot 567) - 89$
354549	$12+((3^4)^5 \cdot (56^7 \cdot 8) + 9))$	551213	$((12^*(3^4))^5 \cdot 567) + 89$
358961	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 5^6)^*(78+9)$	552824	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6)^*(7+8)^9$
360007	$-1+((2^3)^4 - 5)^*(6-7+89)$	552826	$1+((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6)^*(7+8)^9$
362249	$-1-(-2-(3^4 + 5)^6 \cdot 78)^9$	553094	$-1+((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6)^*(7+8)^9$
362251	$1-(-2-(3^4 + 5)^6 \cdot 78)^9$	553096	$1+((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6)^*(7+8)^9$
364187	$-1+((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7)^8 \cdot 9$	560361	$-123+((4^*((5^6) - (7^8)))^9)$
364189	$1+((2^3)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7)^8 \cdot 9$	560519	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 56)^*(7+8)^9$
364499	$-1-2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot (6-7^8)^9$	560521	$1+((2^3)^4 + 56)^*(7+8)^9$
364501	$1-2^3 \cdot 4^5 \cdot (6-7^8)^9$	560607	$123+((4^*((5^6) - (7^8)))^9)$
364554	$1+(2^3)^4 \cdot (5+6+78) + 9$	562053	$-123+(((4^*((5^6) - 7)) - 8)^9)$
364899	$-1+((2^3)^4 + 5 + 6 - 7)^8 \cdot 9$	562083	$123+(((4^*((5^6) - (7+8)))^9)$
364901	$1+((2^3)^4 + 5 + 6 - 7)^8 \cdot 9$	562119	$123+(((4^*((5^6) - (7^8)))^9)$
373174	$-1+((23^4 + 5)/6 + 7)^8 \cdot 9$	562242	$-123+(((4^*((5^6) - (7+8)))^9)$
373192	$-1+((23^4 + 5)/6 + 7)^8 \cdot 9$	562758	$123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
380927	$-1+(2^3)^4 \cdot (5+6-7+89)$	562881	$-123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
380929	$1+(2^3)^4 \cdot (5+6-7+89)$	562917	$-123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
395676	$(12+((3^4)^5 \cdot 56))^*(78+9)$	562947	$123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
398615	$-1+2^3/4^5 \cdot (5^6 + 7)^*(8+9)$	563039	$-1-(2-3)^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7 + 8)^9$
398617	$1+2^3/4^5 \cdot (5^6 + 7)^*(8+9)$	563041	$1-(2-3)^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7 + 8)^9$
405010	$1+((2^3)^4 - 5)^*(6^*(7+8) + 9)$	563127	$123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
407403	$(-12+((3^4)^5 \cdot (567-8)))^9$	564393	$-123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
413163	$(-12+3^4 \cdot 567 - 8)^9$	564639	$123+(((4^*((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
413226	$(12+(34^*(5^6)^7 + 8))) / 9$	565307	$-1-(2-3)^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7 + 8)^9$
413259	$-12+(((3^4)^5 \cdot 567) - 8)^9$	565309	$1-(2-3)^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7 + 8)^9$
413427	$12+(((3^4)^5 \cdot 567) + 8)^9$	589103	$-1+((2^3)^4 - 5)^6 \cdot (7 - (-8-9))$
413523	$((12+((3^4)^5 \cdot 567)) + 8)^9$	589105	$1+((2^3)^4 - 5)^6 \cdot (7 - (-8-9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
589629	$-123+((4^{(56/7)})-8)^*9$	982846	$1-(2^3 \cdot 4-5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
590019	$123+(((4^{(56/7)})+8)^*9)$	983069	$-1234+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
590543	$-1+((2^3)^4+5)^*6*(7-(-8-9))$	983213	$-1234+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
590545	$1+((2^3)^4+5)^*6*(7-(-8-9))$	983671	$1^*-2+((3+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$
597912	$-12+(((34^*(5^6+7))/8)^*9)$	983675	$1^*2+((3+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$
597936	$12+(((34^*(5^6+7))/8)^*9)$	983811	$(-123^4)+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
598032	$(12+((34^*(5^6+7))/8))^*9$	983955	$(-123^4)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
602339	$((12-34)^*(5^6))+((7^8))/9$	983985	$-12-(((34-((5^6)^7))+8)^*9)$
612681	$(-1234^*((5/6)-(7^8)))^*9$	984039	$(-12^*34)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
624696	$((1-23)^4+5)^*(-6+78/9)$	984216	$-123+((4+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9$
627912	$(-12^*(3^4))^*(56-(78^9))$	984281	$(12-34)+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
628487	$-1-2^*(3^4-5-6^7/8)^*9$	984288	$-123-((4-((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$
628489	$1-2^*(3^4-5-6^7/8)^*9$	984325	$(-12+34)+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
631403	$-1+2^*(3^4+5+6^7/8)^*9$	984328	$(-123+4)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
631405	$1+2^*(3^4+5+6^7/8)^*9$	984422	$(123-4)+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
633466	$-123-(((4^*(5^6))-7^8))/9$	984425	$(12-34)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
633712	$123-(((4^*(5^6))-7^8))/9$	984462	$123+((4+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9$
649295	$-1+(2^3 \cdot 4+5)^*6^7/(8^9)$	984469	$(-12+34)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
649297	$1+(2^3 \cdot 4+5)^*6^7/(8^9)$	984534	$123-((4-((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$
654048	$-12^*((3^4)^*(5-678))+9$	984566	$(123-4)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
656207	$-1+(2/3+4)^*(5^6+7-8)^*9$	984597	$-12+(((34+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9)$
656209	$1+(2/3+4)^*(5^6+7-8)^*9$	984606	$123+(4+5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
693531	$(-12+((3^4)^*(5+6)))^*789$	984621	$12+(((34+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9)$
699616	$1-(2-3-4)^*(5^6-78)^*9$	984711	$(12^*34)+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
699623	$-1+(23^4+5)/(6/(7+8))+9$	984765	$12+(((34+((5^6)^7))+8)^*9)$
699625	$1+(23^4+5)/(6/(7+8))+9$	984795	$(123^4)+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
702422	$-1-((2-3-4)^*5^6+78)^*9$	984855	$(12^*34)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
702424	$1-((2-3-4)^*5^6+78)^*9$	984939	$(123^4)+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
706311	$((1+2)^{-3+4})^*5/(6^{\wedge-7} \cdot 8)^{-9}$	985075	$1^*-2+((3+4)^*5^6+78)^*9$
706329	$((1+2)^{-3+4})^*5/(6^{\wedge-7} \cdot 8)^{-9}$	985079	$1^*2+((3+4)^*5^6+78)^*9$
708288	$((12^*34)^*((5^6+7)-8))/9$	985537	$1234+(((5^6)^7)-8)^*9$
708335	$((12^*34)^*((5^6+7)+8))/9$	985681	$1234+(((5^6)^7)+8)^*9$
708408	$(12^*((34^*(5^6))+7^8))/9$	985904	$-1+(2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
708640	$(12^*((34^*(5^6+7))-8))/9$	985905	$1^*(2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
712467	$(12+((3^4)^*(5+6)))^*789$	985906	$1+(2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
730795	$-1+(2+3/4)^*(5^6+7)^*(8+9)$	986552	$-1+(234+5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
730797	$1+(2+3/4)^*(5^6+7)^*(8+9)$	986554	$1+(234+5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$
737748	$(-12^*(3^4))^*(5^6-789)$	987135	$-1-(2^3)^4 \cdot 5^*(6-7^8)+9$
746111	$-1-2^*(3^4-5^6)^*(7+8+9)$	987975	$((12^*34)+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9$
746113	$1-2^*(3^4-5^6)^*(7+8+9)$	988119	$((12^*34)+((5^6)^7))+8)^*9$
753887	$-1+2^*(3^4+5^6)^*(7+8+9)$	988875	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7))+8)^*9$
753889	$1+2^*(3^4+5^6)^*(7+8+9)$	995553	$(1234+((5^6)^7))+8)^*9$
759018	$(12^*((3^4)-(5/6)))^*789$	998399	$-1-(2^3)^4 \cdot 5^*6^*(7/8-9)$
793015	$-1+(23^4+5)/6+7)^*(8+9)$	998401	$1-(2^3)^4 \cdot 5^*6^*(7/8-9)$
808956	$((12+34)^*((5^6+7))/8)^*9$	1015131	$((1-23)^4+5)^*(6-(7+8))/9$
839605	$1+(23^4/5+6)^*(7+8)^{-9}$	1050948	$(12^*((3^4)+(5^6)))^*789$
857228	$((123^4)^*((5^6)+(7^8)))/9$	1061901	$-123+((4^*((5^6)-7))^*(8+9))$
871055	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)^{-9}$	1062147	$123+((4^*((5^6)-7))^*(8+9))$
871073	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)+9$	1062258	$-123+(((4^*(5^6))-7)^*(8+9))$
873975	$(((-123-4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)^{-9}$	1063099	$123+((4^*((5^6)+7))^*(8+9))$
873993	$(((-123-4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)+9$	1077962	$-1-2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot (78-9)$
874707	$-12-(((34-((5^6)^7))^*8)+9)$	1077963	$-1^*2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot (78-9)$
874798	$-1-(2^3 \cdot 4-5^6 \cdot 7)^*8-9$	1078287	$1^*2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot (78-9)$
874818	$1-(2^3 \cdot 4-5^6 \cdot 7)^*8+9$	1078288	$1+2^3 \cdot 4+5^6 \cdot (78-9)$
875293	$(12+((34+((5^6)^7))^*8))+9$	1089288	$((123^{\wedge}((4^*5)-6)/7))^*8)^*9$
876007	$((123+4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)^{-9}$	1106783	$-1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7+89)$
878927	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)^{-9}$	1106785	$1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7+89)$
878945	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7))^*8)+9$	1113390	$(-1234+(((5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
895768	$(123^*((4^{\wedge}(56/7))+8))/9$	1113989	$-123+((4^{\wedge}(56/7))^*(8+9))$
899712	$(-1+2-(3/4)^{-5})^*6^7 \cdot (8-9)$	1114235	$123+((4^{\wedge}(56/7))^*(8+9))$
937341	$-123+4^*((5^6)^*(7+8))-9$	1114398	$(-1234+(((5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
937659	$123+4^*((5^6)^*(7+8))+9$	1121076	$((-123^4)+(((5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
945377	$-1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7-89)$	1123353	$((-123-4)+(((5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
945379	$1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7-89)$	1123425	$((-123+4)+(((5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
973197	$((-1234+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9$	1124377	$(-123+4)+(((5^6)-7)^*8)^*9$
973341	$((-1234+((5^6)^7))+8)^*9$	1124409	$-123+((4+((5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
979875	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9$	1124583	$123-((4-((5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
980631	$(((-12^*34)+((5^6)^7))-8)^*9$	1124615	$(123-4)+(((5^6)-7)^*8)^*9$
980775	$(((-12^*34)+((5^6)^7))+8)^*9$	1124655	$123+((4+((5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
982196	$-1-(234-5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$	1125066	$1+((2+3+4)^*5^6+7)^*8+9$
982198	$1-(234-5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$	1125345	$-123-((4-((5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
982844	$-1-(2^3 \cdot 4-5^6 \cdot 7+8)^*9$	1125385	$(-123+4)+(((5^6)+7)^*8)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1125417	$-123 + ((4 + ((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1328719	$-1 - (2 - 3 - 4)^*(5^6 + 7)^*(8 + 9)$
1125591	$123 - ((4 - ((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1328721	$1 - (2 - 3 - 4)^*(5^6 + 7)^*(8 + 9)$
1125623	$(123 - 4) + (((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1329522	$-12 + ((3^4)^*(5^6 + 789))$
1126575	$((123 - 4) + (((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1329546	$12 + ((3^4)^*(5^6 + 789))$
1126647	$((123 + 4) + (((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1331352	$(123 * (((4^5)/6)^7 + 8))^9$
1128924	$((123 * 4) + (((5^6 - 7)^8))^9)$	1356422	$(-12/34)^*(5 - ((6*(7^8))/9))$
1129176	$((12 * 34) + (((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1372158	$-1 + (2^3)^{4*5*6*7+8-9}$
1129932	$((123 * 4) + (((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1372176	$-1 + (2^3)^{4*5*6*7+8+9}$
1135602	$(1234 + (((5^6 - 7)^8))^9)$	1372178	$1 + (2^3)^{4*5*6*7+8+9}$
1136159	$-1 + (2^3)^{4+5^6-7} * 8^9$	1392750	$-1 - (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7-8-9$
1136161	$1 + (2^3)^{4+5^6-7} * 8^9$	1392752	$1 - (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7-8-9$
1136610	$(1234 + (((5^6 + 7)^8))^9)$	1392784	$-1 - (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7+8+9$
1159683	$(-1 + 2^3)^{4-5+6} * (78-9)$	1392786	$1 - (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7+8+9$
1166304	$((-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7)))^8)/9$	1406502	$-1 + (2/3^4 + 5)^6 * 7-89$
1166712	$(12 * (34 + (((5^6)^7)^8)))^9$	1406504	$1 + (2/3^4 + 5)^6 * 7-89$
1174445	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7)^8 - 9$	1406519	$-1 + (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7-8^9$
1175551	$-1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (5^6 + 7)^8 - 9$	1406521	$1 + (2^3)^{4+5} * 6^7-8^9$
1175553	$1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (5^6 + 7)^8 - 9$	1406574	$-1 + (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7-8-9$
1176659	$123 * (((4^5)/6)^7)^8 + 9$	1406576	$1 + (2^3)^{4+5} * 6^7-8-9$
1201704	$-12 + ((3^4)^*(5^6 - 789))$	1406590	$-1 + (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7+8-9$
1201728	$12 + ((3^4)^*(5^6 - 789))$	1406594	$1 + (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7+8+9$
1208319	$-1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (6^7+8+9)$	1406608	$-1 + (2^3)^{4+5} * 6^7+8+9$
1208321	$1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (6^7+8+9)$	1406680	$-1 + (2/3^4 + 5)^6 * 7+89$
1217463	$-1 * (2^3)^{4+5^6} * 78+9$	1462209	$(1 - 2^3)^{4-5+6} * (-78-9)$
1233967	$(-12 * 34) + ((5^6)^*(7 + (8^9)))$	1468911	$-1 + 2 * (3^4 + 5^6)^*(7^8-9)$
1234783	$(12 * 34) + ((5^6)^*(7 + (8^9)))$	1468912	$1 * 2 * (3^4 + 5^6)^*(7^8-9)$
1238015	$-1 - (2^3)^{4-5} / 6^{\wedge-7} * 8/9$	1468913	$1 + 2 * (3^4 + 5^6)^*(7^8-9)$
1238017	$1 - (2^3)^{4-5} / 6^{\wedge-7} * 8/9$	1473623	$-1 + ((2^3)^{4*5-6-7})^8 * 9$
1250303	$-1 + (2^3)^{4+5} / 6^{\wedge-7} * 8/9$	1473625	$1 + ((2^3)^{4*5-6-7})^8 * 9$
1250305	$1 + (2^3)^{4+5} / 6^{\wedge-7} * 8/9$	1494409	$-123 * (4 - (((5^6)^7 + 8))/9)$
1259306	$-1 + (2+3+4)^*(5^6-78)^9$	1494737	$(123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^7)) - 8))/9$
1259308	$1 + (2+3+4)^*(5^6-78)^9$	1495393	$123 * (4 + (((5^6)^7 + 8))/9)$
1281864	$-1 + ((2^3)^{4+5^6})^*(7^8+9)$	1503366	$-12 + (((34^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7))/8)^9$
1281866	$1 + ((2^3)^{4+5^6})^*(7^8+9)$	1503390	$12 + (((34^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7))/8)^9$
1290239	$-1 - (2^3)^{4*5} * (6-78+9)$	1531247	$-1 + 2 * ((3+4)^5 * 6^7+8-9)$
1290241	$1 - (2^3)^{4*5} * (6-78+9)$	1531253	$1 + 2 * ((3+4)^5 * 6^7+8-9)$
1305696	$12 * (3^4 - 5^6)^7 * (8-9)$	1566863	$-1 - (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7/8^9$
1311024	$-12 * ((34 - ((5^6)^7)) + 89)$	1566865	$1 - (2^3)^{4-5} * 6^7/8^9$
1311228	$-12 * ((34 - ((5^6)^7)) + (8^9))$	1582415	$-1 + (2^3)^{4+5} * 6^7/8^9$
1311888	$-12 * (((34 - ((5^6)^7)) + 8) + 9)$	1582417	$1 + (2^3)^{4+5} * 6^7/8^9$
1311987	$(-12 * ((34 - ((5^6)^7)) + 8)) - 9$	1595489	$-1 - ((2^3)^{4-5})^6 * (7-8^9)$
1312003	$(-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) - 89$	1595491	$1 - ((2^3)^{4-5})^6 * (7-8^9)$
1312005	$(-12 * ((34 - ((5^6)^7)) + 8)) + 9$	1624592	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^7 + 8))/9)$
1312044	$12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) - (8^9))$	1625408	$12 * (34 + (((5^6)^7 + 8))/9)$
1312075	$(-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) - (8+9)$	1638408	$-1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (56^7+8)^9$
1312080	$-12 * ((34 - (((5^6)^7 + 8)) + 9)$	1638410	$1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (56^7+8)^9$
1312091	$((-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) + 8) - 9$	1642497	$1 + (2^3)^{4*5} * (56-7)^8+9$
1312092	$(12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) * (8-9)$	1652784	$((((123-4)^*(5^6)+7)^8)/9)$
1312093	$((-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) - 8) + 9$	1678668	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) - 78)^9))$
1312104	$-12 * (((34 - ((5^6)^7)) + 8) - 9)$	1678948	$1 + (23^4 - 5)^6 - 78 + 9$
1312109	$((-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) + 8) + 9$	1681044	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) - (7^8))^9))$
1312179	$(-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^7 + 8))) - 9$	1681860	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) - (7^8))^9))$
1312181	$(-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) + 89$	1685472	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) - (7+8))^9))$
1312197	$(-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^7 + 8))) + 9$	1686288	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) - (7+8))^9))$
1312803	$(12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) - 8)) - 9$	1686671	$-1 + ((2^3 + 4)^5 * (5^6 - 7) - 8)^9$
1312819	$(12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) - 89$	1686673	$1 + ((2^3 + 4)^5 * (5^6 - 7) - 8)^9$
1312821	$(12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) - 8)) + 9$	1686984	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) + 7) - 8)^9)$
1312891	$(12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) - (8+9)$	1686995	$-1 + (2^3/4 * 5^6 - 7)^8 * 9$
1312896	$12 * (((34 + ((5^6)^7)) + 8) - 9)$	1686997	$1 + (2^3/4 * 5^6 - 7)^8 * 9$
1312907	$((12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) + 8) - 9$	1687200	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) - 7) + 8)^9)$
1312908	$12 * (34 + ((5^6)/7^{\wedge}(8-9)))$	1687800	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) + 7) - 8)^9)$
1312909	$((12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) - 8) + 9$	1688016	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) - 7) + 8)^9)$
1312920	$12 * (((34 + ((5^6)^7)) - 8) + 9)$	1688712	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
1312925	$((12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) + 8) + 9$	1689528	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) + 7) + 8)^9)$
1312956	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^7) + (8^9)))$	1693140	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) + (7^8))^9))$
1312995	$(12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) + 8)) - 9$	1693956	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) + (7^8))^9))$
1312997	$(12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) + 89$	1695516	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6) + 78)^9))$
1313013	$(12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) + 8)) + 9$	1696332	$12 * (34 + (((5^6) + 78)^9))$
1313112	$12 * (((34 + ((5^6)^7)) + 8) + 9)$	1697813	$-1 + ((2^3)^{4+5})^6 * (78-9)$
1313640	$(123 * (((4^5)/6)^7)^8 - 9)$	1697815	$1 + ((2^3)^{4+5})^6 * (78-9)$
1313772	$12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) + (8^9))$	1707076	$-123 * (4 - (((5^6) - 7)^8)/9)$
1313976	$12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)) + 89)$	1708060	$123 * (4 + (((5^6) - 7)^8)/9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1709044	$(-123*(4-((5^6)+7)*8))/9$	2109534	$123+((4+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9)$
1751562	$((1+2)*((3^4)+5))^6*789$	2109669	$-12+((34+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9)$
1767815	$-1+(((2^3)^4-5)^6+7)^8*9$	2109693	$12+((34+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9)$
1767817	$1+(((2^3)^4-5)^6+7)^8*9$	2110446	$((123-4)+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9$
1771127	$-1+(((2^3)^4+5)^6-7)^8*9$	2110518	$((123+4)+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9$
1835054	$-1+(((2^3)^4+5^6+7)^8-9$	2113047	$((12*34)+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9$
1835056	$1+(((2^3)^4+5^6+7)^8-9$	2113803	$((123*4)+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9$
1838397	$(-1234+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9)$	2120481	$(1234+((5^6)*(7+8)))^9$
1851011	$((-123*4)+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9)$	2124991	$((((123-4)^*(5^6))/7)^8)-9$
1857216	$((-123-4)+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9)$	2125009	$((((123-4)^*(5^6))/7)^8)+9$
1858785	$-12-((34-((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$	2161226	$-1+((2^3)^4+5)^*(67*8-9)$
1858809	$12-((34-((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$	2161228	$1+((2^3)^4+5)^*(67*8-9)$
1859333	$(((-12/34)+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$	2162586	$-123*(4-(((5^6)+7)/8)^9)$
1859417	$(((-12/34)+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$	2163570	$123*(4+(((5^6)+7)/8)^9)$
1859941	$-12+((34+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$	2167506	$(123*(4+(((5^6)+7)/8)))^9$
1860748	$(123^((4+5)-6))-((7*(8+9)))$	2187498	$-1+(2+3)^4*5^6*7+8-9$
1860938	$-1+(23^4+5^6*7)^*(8+9)$	2187502	$1+(2+3)^4*5^6*7+8-9$
1860940	$1+(23^4+5^6*7)^*(8+9)$	2187886	$-1+(2^((3+4+5)^6+7))^8*9$
1860986	$(123^((4+5)-6))+((7*(8+9)))$	2187888	$1+(2^((3+4+5)^6+7))^8*9$
1861534	$((123+4)+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9)$	2232414	$((((123+4)^*(5^6))-7)/8)^9$
1867739	$((123*4)+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9)$	2233422	$((((123+4)^*(5^6)+7)/8))^9$
1880353	$(1234+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9)$	2335175	$-1-((2^3)^4*5-6^7-8)^9$
1882358	$-1+(((2^3)^4+5)^*(6*78-9))$	2335177	$1-((2^3)^4*5-6^7-8)^9$
1882360	$1+(((2^3)^4+5)^*(6*78-9))$	2355190	$-1+(2^3)^4*(567+8)-9$
1933311	$-1-((2^3)^4*(5-6*78-9))$	2355192	$1+(2^3)^4*(567+8)-9$
1933313	$1-((2^3)^4*(5-6*78-9))$	2355208	$-1+(2^3)^4*(567+8)+9$
1939133	$-1+(((2^3)^4-5)^6*(7+8*9))$	2355210	$1+(2^3)^4*(567+8)+9$
1939135	$1+(((2^3)^4-5)^6*(7+8*9))$	2373926	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)^8-9$
1967219	$-1-((2*(3^4-5^6*7)+8)^9)$	2373928	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)^8-9$
1967220	$-1*(2*(3^4-5^6*7)+8)^9$	2373944	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)^8+9$
1967221	$1-((2*(3^4-5^6*7)+8)^9)$	2373946	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)^8+9$
1967363	$-1-((2*(3^4-5^6*7)-8)^9)$	2382057	$(123-4)^*(5^6/7-8)^9$
1967364	$1*(2*(3^4-5^6*7)+8)^9$	2389553	$-1+(2+3+4)^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
1967365	$1-((2*(3^4-5^6*7)-8)^9)$	2389555	$1+(2+3+4)^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
1970135	$-1+(2*(3^4+5^6*7)-8)^9$	2390553	$((((123-4)^*(5^6))/7)-8)^9$
1970136	$1*(2*(3^4+5^6*7)-8)^9$	2390697	$((((123-4)^*(5^6))/7)+8)^9$
1970137	$1+(2*(3^4+5^6*7)-8)^9$	2391695	$-1+(2+3+4)^*(5^6+7)^*(8+9)$
1989295	$(1-((2-3)^(4+5)))/6*(7-8/9)$	2399193	$(123-4)^*(5^6/7+8)^9$
2004495	$((12*(34^((5+6)-7)))/8)-9$	2404292	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-89)$
2004513	$((12*(34^((5+6)-7)))/8)+9$	2404666	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-(8*9))$
2017691	$-1-(((2^3)^4+5)^6*(7-89))$	2405876	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-(8+9))$
2017693	$1-(((2^3)^4+5)^6*(7-89))$	2406065	$((-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-8))-9$
2027519	$-1+(2^3)^4*(56+7)^8-9$	2406083	$((-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-8))+9$
2027521	$1+(2^3)^4*(56+7)^8-9$	2406161	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)-89)$
2031087	$-1-2*(3^4-5^6*(7*8+9))$	2406178	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)-(8*9))$
2031088	$-1*(2*(3^4-5^6*(7*8+9)))$	2406228	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)+8)-9$
2031089	$1-2*(3^4-5^6*(7*8+9))$	2406233	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)-(8+9))$
2031624	$-1-((2^3)^4*(5-67)^8+9$	2406249	$((((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)+8)-9$
2031626	$1-((2^3)^4*(5-67)^8+9$	2406250	$(((-12-34)^*(5^6)^7))^*(8-9)$
2034627	$(((-12/34)^*(5-(6+(7^8)))))-9$	2406251	$((((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)-8)+9$
2034645	$(((-12/34)^*(5-(6+(7^8)))))+9$	2406267	$((((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)+8)+9$
2064518	$-1+(2^((3^4)^5+6+7+8))^9$	2406272	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-8)+9$
2064520	$1+(2^((3^4)^5+6+7+8))^9$	2406322	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)+(8*9))$
2077801	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7-8-9)$	2406339	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)+89)$
2077803	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7-8-9)$	2406417	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)+8)-9$
2078105	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$	2406435	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6)^7)+8)+9$
2078145	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$	2407834	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)+(8*9))$
2078447	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7+8+9)$	2408208	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)+89)$
2078449	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7+8+9)$	2413947	$(-12+((3^4)^5)^67)^8*9$
2079360	$(1-2*(3/4)^5)^6*7/(8-9)$	2416083	$(12+(((3^4)^5)^67))^8*9$
2091789	$((((123-4)^*(5^6))-7)/8)^9$	2466944	$-1+(((2^3)^4-5)^6*7+8)^9$
2092734	$((((123-4)^*(5^6)+7)/8))^9$	2466946	$1+(((2^3)^4-5)^6*7+8)^9$
2098269	$(-1234+((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9$	2494463	$-1+2*(3^((4+5)/6)^7*8/9)$
2101247	$-1+(2^3)^4*(56+7)^8+9$	2494465	$1+2*(3^((4+5)/6)^7*8/9)$
2101249	$1+(2^3)^4*(56+7)^8+9$	2500046	$-1+(2+3)^4*5^6*7+8-9$
2104947	$((-123*4)+((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9$	2500048	$1+(2+3)^4*5^6*7+8-9$
2105703	$((-12*34)+((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9$	2500064	$-1+(2+3)^4*5^6*7+8+9$
2109057	$-12-((34-((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9)$	2500066	$1+(2+3)^4*5^6*7+8+9$
2109081	$12-((34-((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9)$	2515184	$-1+(23^4-(5+6*7)^8)^9$
2109216	$-123-((4-((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9)$	2515186	$1+(23^4-(5+6*7)^8)^9$
2109288	$-123+((4+((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9)$	2520098	$-1+(23^4+5*(6*7-8))^9$
2109462	$123-((4-((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9)$	2520100	$1+(23^4+5*(6*7-8))^9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2520854	$-1+(2^*3^4+5+6^7-8)^*9$	2953196	$-1+(23+4)^*5^6*7+8^*9$
2520856	$1+(2^*3^4+5+6^7-8)^*9$	2953198	$1+(23+4)^*5^6*7+8^*9$
2520908	$-1+(2^*3^4-5+6^7+8)^*9$	3078306	$((-12+34)^*((5^6)-78))^*9$
2520910	$1+(2^*3^4-5+6^7+8)^*9$	3082662	$((-12+34)^*((5^6)-(7^*8))))^*9$
2520998	$-1+(2^*3^4+5+6^7+8)^*9$	3090780	$((-12+34)^*((5^6)-(7+8))))^*9$
2521000	$1+(2^*3^4+5+6^7+8)^*9$	3093615	$((-12+34)^*(5^6))-(7+8))^*9$
2532239	$-1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7-8/9)$	3093741	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6))+7)-8)^*9$
2532240	$1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7-8/9)$	3093759	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6))-7)+8)^*9$
2532241	$1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7-8/9)$	3093885	$(((-12+34)^*(5^6))+7)+8)^*9$
2532386	$1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7)-8+9$	3093948	$((-12+34)^*((5^6)-7)+8))^*9$
2550527	$-1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7*(8+9))$	3094452	$((-12+34)^*(5^6))+78)^*9$
2550529	$1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7*(8+9))$	3095135	$-1+(2+3/4)^*(5^6+7)^*8^*9$
2555903	$-1-(2^3)^4*(5-6-7^*89)$	3095137	$1+(2+3/4)^*(5^6+7)^*8^*9$
2555905	$1-(2^3)^4*(5-6-7^*89)$	3104838	$((-12+34)^*((5^6)+(7^*8))))^*9$
2565991	$((1/(2^*3)+4)+5)^*6^7-89$	3108863	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6)^*(78-9)$
2566169	$((1/(2^*3)+4)+5)^*6^7+89$	3108865	$1+(2^3)^4*(5+6)^*(78-9)$
2584121	$(1+((2^3)^4)^*5678)/9$	3109194	$((-12+34)^*((5^6)+78))^*9$
2654137	$1+(2^3)^4*(5+67)-8)^*9$	3141503	$-1-2^*(3^4-4-5)/(6^7-7^*8)^*9$
2654279	$-1+((2^3)^4*(5+67)+8)^*9$	3141505	$1-2^*(3^4-4-5)/(6^7-7^*8)^*9$
2670605	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)-8)^*9$	3178982	$((123^4+56)+7)/(8^*9)$
2670607	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)-8)^*9$	3178989	$((123^4+567)/(8^*9)$
2670749	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)+8)^*9$	3185664	$-12*(34-((5^6)-7)^*(8+9)))$
2670751	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6-7)+8)^*9$	3186071	$-1+(2^3+4)^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
2671865	$-1+(23-4)^*5^6+7-8)^*9$	3186073	$1+(2^3+4)^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
2671867	$1+(23-4)^*5^6+7-8)^*9$	3189336	$12*(34+((5^6)+7)^*(8+9)))$
2671883	$-1+(23-4)^*5^6-7+8)^*9$	3202633	$-123*(4-(((5^6)^*(7+8))/9))$
2671885	$1+(23-4)^*5^6-7+8)^*9$	3203617	$123*(4+(((5^6)^*(7+8))/9))$
2748570	$(-12+34)^*((((5^6)-7)^*8)-9)$	3305880	$((-12+((3^4)^*567))^*8)^*9$
2748759	$(((-12+34)^*((5^6)-7))^*8)-9$	3307608	$((12+((3^4)^*567))^*8)^*9$
2748777	$(((-12+34)^*((5^6)-7))^*8)+9$	3357647	$-1+(23^4+5)/6-7)^*8^*9$
2748966	$(-12+34)^*((((5^6)-7)^*8)+9)$	3357649	$1+(23^4+5)/6-7)^*8^*9$
2751034	$(-12+34)^*((((5^6)+7)^*8)-9)$	3363312	$(123/4)^*((((5^6)^*7)-8)+9)$
2751223	$(((-12+34)^*((5^6)+7))^*8)-9$	3363804	$(123/4)^*((((5^6)^*7)+8)+9)$
2751241	$(((-12+34)^*((5^6)+7))^*8)+9$	3366018	$(123/4)^*((((5^6)^*7)+89)$
2751430	$(-12+34)^*((((5^6)+7)^*8)+9)$	3373919	$-1+2^*3*(4*(5^6-7)+8)^*9$
2785279	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5+(67+8)^*9)$	3373921	$1+2^*3*(4*(5^6-7)+8)^*9$
2785281	$1+(2^3)^4*(5+(67+8)^*9)$	3374981	$-1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7-8)^*9$
2792446	$-1-2^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8-9$	3374983	$1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7-8)^*9$
2792450	$1-2^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8+9$	3374990	$-1+(2^*3^4*5^6+7-8)^*9$
2797558	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5+678)-9$	3375010	$1+(2^*3^4*5^6-7+8)^*9$
2797560	$1+(2^3)^4*(5+678)-9$	3375017	$-1+2^*(3^4*5^6-7+8)^*9$
2797576	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5+678)+9$	3375019	$1+2^*(3^4*5^6-7+8)^*9$
2797578	$1+(2^3)^4*(5+678)+9$	3376079	$-1+2^*3*(4*(5^6+7)-8)^*9$
2806270	$-1+2^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8-9$	3376081	$1+2^*3*(4*(5^6+7)-8)^*9$
2806274	$1+2^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8+9$	3449251	$(-1+2^*(3^4-5))^6/(7-8)+9$
2811984	$-12*((34-((5^6)^*(7+8))))+9$	3499913	$-123+(4*((((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9))$
2812083	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+8))))-9$	3500087	$123+(4*((((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9))$
2812101	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+8))))+9$	3500975	$((123+((4*(5^6))^*7))^*8)-9$
2812200	$-12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+8)))^*9$	3500993	$((123+((4*(5^6))^*7))^*8)+9$
2812256	$-1+((2+3)^*(4/5^6-6-7)+8)^*9$	3633122	$((((123^4)-(5+6))/7)+8)^*9$
2812258	$1+((2+3)^*(4/5^6-6-7)+8)^*9$	3715712	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-89)))$
2812319	$-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^6+7-8)^*9$	3715736	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-89)))$
2812321	$1+(2+3)^*4*(5^6+7-8)^*9$	3716290	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-(8^*9))))$
2812679	$-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^6-7+8)^*9$	3716314	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-(8^*9))))$
2812681	$1+(2+3)^*4*(5^6-7+8)^*9$	3718160	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-(8+9))))$
2812742	$-1+((2+3)^*(4/5^6-6+7)-8)^*9$	3718184	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-(8+9))))$
2812744	$1+((2+3)^*(4/5^6-6+7)-8)^*9$	3718457	$(-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-8))))-9$
2812800	$12*((34+((5^6)^*(7+8))))-9$	3718475	$(-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-8))))+9$
2812899	$(12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+8))))-9$	3718481	$(12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-8))))-9$
2812917	$(12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+8))))+9$	3718499	$(12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-8))))+9$
2813016	$12*((34+((5^6)^*(7+8))))+9$	3718704	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8)-9))$
2937377	$-123+((4*(5^6))^*(7^*8)-9)$	3718796	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)-8)+9))$
2937499	$-1-(2-3)^*4*5^6*(7^*8-9)$	3719001	$(-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8))))-9$
2937501	$1-(2-3)^*4*5^6*(7^*8-9)$	3719019	$(-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8))))+9$
2937623	$123+((4*(5^6))^*(7^*8)-9)$	3719043	$(12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8))))+9$
2945023	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6^7*(8+9))$	3719316	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8))))$
2945025	$1+(2^3)^4*(5+6^7*(8+9))$	3719340	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8))))$
2953097	$-1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$	3721186	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8^*9))))$
2953099	$1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$	3721210	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+8^*9))))$
2953127	$1+(23+4)^*5^6*7-8+9$	3721764	$-12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+89)))$
2953151	$-1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$	3721788	$12+(34*((((5^6)^*7)+89)))$
2953153	$1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$	3796172	$-1+(23+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
5695707	$(1/2)*(((3/45)^{-6}+789)$	7877460	$12+(((34+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
5747010	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7)*8)-9)$	7879428	$((123^4)+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9$
5747415	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)*8)-9)$	7884144	$((123+4)+((5^6)^7))^8)*9$
5747433	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)*8)+9)$	7886106	$(1234+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9$
5747838	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7)*8)+9)$	7891847	$-1+(234+5^6*7)*8*9$
5752162	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7)*8)-9)$	7891849	$1+(234+5^6*7)*8*9$
5752567	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)*8)-9)$	7968432	$-12+(34*(((5^6)^7)*8))-9)$
5752585	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)*8)+9)$	7968456	$12+(34*(((5^6)^7)*8))-9)$
5752990	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7)*8)+9)$	7969044	$-12+(34*(((5^6)^7)*8))+9)$
5841132	$((-12+34)*((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	7969068	$12+(34*(((5^6)^7)*8))+9)$
5842160	$-1+(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7/8-9)$	8036351	$-1+(2^3)^4*(5^6*7+8)*9$
5842162	$1+(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7/8-9)$	8036353	$1+(2^3)^4*(5^6*7+8)*9$
5843631	$((-12+34)*((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	8169906	$123*(((4+5)^6)/8)-9)$
5843869	$((-12+34)*((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	8437377	$-123+((4*(5^6)^7)*8)*9)$
5845166	$-1+(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7/8+9)$	8437623	$123+((4*(5^6)^7)*8)*9)$
5845168	$1+(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7/8+9)$	8485560	$(1+(2/3)^{-4})^5*6^7*(-8+9)$
5846368	$((-12+34)*((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	8644563	$((123^4)*((5^6)^7))/8)*9)$
5979276	$(123*(((4*(5^6)^7)+8))/9)$	8652312	$((123^4)*(((5^6)^7)/8))^9$
5979604	$((123^4)*(((5^6)^7)+8))/9)$	8812092	$-12*(34-((5^6)^7*(7*8)-9)))$
6445566	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7*(7*8)))^9)$	8812908	$12*(34+((5^6)^7*(7*8)-9)))$
6462540	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7*(7+8)))^9)$	8846855	$-1+((2^3)^4*5^6*7)*8*9$
6468048	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)-78)^9)$	8846857	$1+((2^3)^4*5^6*7)*8*9$
6468336	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)-8))^9)$	9690587	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6468615	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)-7+8))^9)$	9723072	$((-123-4)+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6468741	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)-8))^9)$	9731337	$-12-((34-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6468759	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)-7+8))^9)$	9731361	$12-((34-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6468885	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)+8))^9)$	9737389	$-12+((34+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6469164	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)+8))^9)$	9737413	$12+((34+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6469452	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)+78))^9)$	9745678	$((123+4)+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6474960	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)+8))^9)$	9778163	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$
6491934	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)+7*8))^9)$	10496628	$-12*(((34-((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$
6501042	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7+78))^9)$	10496727	$((-12*(34-((5^6)^7))^8)-9)$
7207308	$(123/4)*(((5^6)^7*(7+8))+9)$	10496745	$((-12*(34-((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$
7365816	$(-1-(2/3)^{-4}*5^6*7/8-9)$	10496844	$-12*(((34-((5^6)^7))^8)-9)$
7435409	$(-123+((4*(5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	10499484	$-12*(((34-((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$
7437377	$-123+(((4*(5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	10499583	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^7)*8))-9)$
7437623	$123+(((4*(5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	10499601	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^7)*8))+9)$
7439591	$(123+((4*(5^6)^7))^8)+9)$	10499700	$-12*(34-(((5^6)^7)*8)+9)$
7665160	$-12*(34+(((5^6)^7)-7^8))/9)$	10500399	$(12*(34+(((5^6)^7)*8))-9)$
7665976	$12*(34-(((5^6)^7)-7^8))/9)$	10500417	$(12*(34+(((5^6)^7)*8))+9)$
7863894	$(-1234+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10500516	$12*(34+(((5^6)^7)*8))+9)$
7865856	$((-1-123-4)+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10503156	$12*(((34+((5^6)^7))^8)-9)$
7870572	$((-123^4)+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10503255	$((12*(34+((5^6)^7))^8)-9)$
7872540	$-12-(((34-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10503273	$((12*(34+((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$
7872564	$12-(((34-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10503372	$12*(((34+((5^6)^7))^8)+9)$
7873857	$((-123-4)+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10780836	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7*(7+8))-9)$
7873929	$((-123+4)+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10781664	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7*(7+8))+9)$
7874181	$(-123+((4+((5^6)^7))^8))^9)$	10957644	$(-1234+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874589	$-123-(((4-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10964322	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874663	$-1-(2/3+4-5^6*7)*8*9)$	10965078	$((-12*34)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874665	$1-(2/3+4-5^6*7)*8*9)$	10967679	$((-123+4)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874682	$-12-((34-(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10968336	$((-12-34)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874706	$12-((34-(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10968432	$-12-((34-((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874835	$123-(((4-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10968456	$12-((34-((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874841	$-123-(((4-((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10968552	$((12-34)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7874913	$-123+((4+((5^6)^7))^8))^9)$	10968578	$-1-(23-4-5^6*7*8)*9)$
7874957	$-1-(2/3+4-5^6*7*8)*9)$	10968579	$-1*(23-4-5^6*7*8)*9)$
7874959	$1-(2/3+4-5^6*7*8)*9)$	10968580	$1-(23-4-5^6*7*8)*9)$
7875041	$-1+(2/3+4+5^6*7*8)*9)$	10968591	$-123-(((4-((5^6)^7))^8))^9)$
7875043	$1+(2/3+4+5^6*7*8)*9)$	10968909	$123+((4+((5^6)^7))^8))^9)$
7875087	$123-((4-(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10968920	$-1+(23-4+5^6*7*8)*9)$
7875159	$123+((4+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10968921	$1*(23-4+5^6*7*8)*9)$
7875165	$-123+(((4+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10968922	$1+(23-4+5^6*7*8)*9)$
7875294	$-12+((34+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10968948	$((-12+34)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7875318	$12+((34+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10969044	$-12+((34+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7875335	$-1+(2/3+4+5^6*7)*8*9)$	10969068	$12+((34+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7875337	$1+(2/3+4+5^6*7)*8*9)$	10969164	$((12+34)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7875411	$123+(((4+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	10969821	$((123-4)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7875819	$(123-((4-((5^6)^7))^8))^9)$	10972422	$((12*34)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7876071	$((123-4)+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10973178	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7876143	$((123+4)+(((5^6)^7)*8))^9)$	10979856	$(1234+((5^6)^7*8))^9)$
7877436	$-12+(((34+((5^6)^7))^8)*9)$	11108663	$-1-(2-3^4)*((5^6)^7+8)*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
11108665	$1 - (2 - 3^4) * (5^6 + 7 - 8) * 9$	12937908	$12 * (34 + ((5^6)^*(78-9)))$
11109365	$-1 - ((2 - 3^4) * 5^6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	12991444	$-1 * 2 / 3 * (4 - (5 + 6)^{7 - 8 + 9})$
11109367	$1 - ((2 - 3^4) * 5^6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	13005034	$(123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - 89)$
11109383	$-1 - ((2 - 3^4) * 5^6 + 7 - 8) * 9$	13007057	$(123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - (8 * 9))$
11109385	$1 - ((2 - 3^4) * 5^6 + 7 - 8) * 9$	13013602	$(123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - (8 + 9))$
11110085	$-1 - (2 - 3^4) * (5^6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	13014664	$((123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - 8)) - 9$
11110087	$1 - (2 - 3^4) * (5^6 - 7 + 8) * 9$	13014682	$((123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - 8)) + 9$
11156250	$(123 - 4) * 5^6 * (7 + 8 - 9)$	13016568	$((123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) + 8)) - 9$
11165202	$(123^{\wedge}((4 + 5) - 6)) * ((7 + 8) - 9)$	13016586	$((123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) + 8)) + 9$
11389824	$(-12 + (3/45)^{-6}) - 789$	13017648	$(123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) + 8) + 9$
11389833	$((-1 - 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 789$	13024193	$(123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) + (8 * 9))$
11389834	$((-1 * 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 789$	13026216	$(123 - 4) * (((5^6)^*7) + 89)$
11389838	$((1 * 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 789$	13441686	$-123 * ((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + 89)$
11389839	$((1 + 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 789$	13442670	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - 89)$
11389848	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 789$	13443777	$-123 * ((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + (8 * 9))$
11389990	$(-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - (7 * 89)$	13444761	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - (8 * 9))$
11390014	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - (7 * 89)$	13450542	$-123 * (((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + 8) + 9)$
11390531	$((-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 7) - 89$	13451526	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - (8 + 9))$
11390541	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - (7 + 89)$	13451640	$(-123 * ((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + 8)) - 9$
11390550	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - (78 + 9)$	13451658	$(-123 * ((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + 8)) + 9$
11390568	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 78 + 9$	13452510	$-123 * ((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + 8) + 9$
11390682	$((-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 78) - 9$	13452544	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) - 89$
11390700	$((-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 78) + 9$	13452561	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) - (8 * 9)$
11390709	$((-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 7) + 89$	13452616	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) - (8 + 9)$
11390719	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) - 7 + 89$	13452624	$(123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - 8)) - 9$
11391236	$(-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + (7 * 89)$	13452632	$((-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) + 8) - 9$
11391260	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + (7 * 89)$	13452634	$((-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) - 8) + 9$
11391402	$(-12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	13452642	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - 8) + 9$
11391411	$((-1 - 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	13452650	$((-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) + 8) + 9$
11391412	$((-1 * 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	13452705	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) + (8 * 9)$
11391416	$((1 * 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	13452722	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) + 89$
11391417	$((1 + 2) + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	13452756	$-123 * ((4 - ((5^6)^*7)) + 8) - 9$
11391426	$(12 + ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	13453494	$123 * (((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) + 8) - 9)$
11530758	$-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*(7 + 8 - 9)))$	13453528	$123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - 89$
11531742	$123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*(7 + 8 - 9)))$	13453545	$(123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7))) - (8 * 9)$
11586560	$((1 + (2/3)) * (4^5)) * 6789$	13453600	$(123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7))) - (8 + 9)$
11671865	$-1 + (2 + 3^4) * 5^6 + 7 - 8 * 9$	13453608	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7) + 8)) - 9$
11671867	$1 + (2 + 3^4) * 5^6 + 7 - 8 * 9$	13453616	$(123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7) + 8)) - 9$
11807964	$(-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^*7) + 8)) * 9$	13453618	$((123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7))) - 8) + 9$
11808756	$((-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^*7))) - 8) * 9$	13453626	$(-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7) + 8)) + 9$
11808900	$((-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^*7))) + 8) * 9$	13453634	$((123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7))) + 8) + 9$
11811228	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^*7) - 8) * 9)$	13453689	$123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7)) + (8 * 9)$
11812044	$12 * (34 + (((5^6)^*7) - 8) * 9)$	13453706	$(123 * (4 + ((5^6)^*7))) + 89$
11812956	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^*7) + 8) * 9)$	13453740	$123 * (((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) - 8) + 9)$
11813772	$12 * (34 + (((5^6)^*7) + 8) * 9)$	13454592	$(123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) + 8)) - 9$
11815308	$(12 * (34 + ((5^6)^*7) - 8)) * 9$	13454610	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7) + 8)) + 9$
11816100	$((12 * (34 + ((5^6)^*7))) - 8) * 9$	13454724	$-123 * (4 - (((5^6)^*7) + 8) + 9)$
11816244	$((12 * (34 + ((5^6)^*7))) + 8) * 9$	13455708	$123 * (((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) + 8) + 9)$
11817036	$(12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^*7)) + 8)) * 9$	13461489	$-123 * (4 - (((5^6)^*7) + (8 * 9)))$
11957896	$((-123 * (4 - ((5^6)^*7))) * 8) / 9$	13462473	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) + (8 * 9))$
11958388	$(123 * (4 + (((5^6)^*7) * 8))) / 9$	13463580	$-123 * (4 - (((5^6)^*7) + 89))$
12116668	$(-123 + ((4 * 5)^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	13464564	$123 * ((4 + ((5^6)^*7)) + 89)$
12116914	$(123 + ((4 * 5)^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	13490280	$(-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^*7) * 8))) * 9$
12187092	$-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^*(7 - (8 * 9))))$	13493544	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^*7) * 8) * 9))$
12187908	$12 * (34 + ((5^6)^*(7 * 8 + 9)))$	13493951	$-1 + (2^3 + 4) * (5^6 - 7) * 8 * 9$
12201983	$-1 - (2^3)^4 * (5 - 6 * 7 * 8) * 9$	13493953	$1 + (2^3 + 4) * (5^6 - 7) * 8 * 9$
12201985	$1 - (2^3)^4 * (5 - 6 * 7 * 8) * 9$	13494360	$12 * (34 + (((5^6)^*7) * 8) * 9)$
12213276	$((12 + 34) * ((5^6)^*7)) * (8 + 9)$	13499495	$-1 + (2^3 + 4) * 5^6 - 7 * 8 * 9$
12218631	$((12 + 34) * (5^6)) - 7 * (8 + 9)$	13499497	$1 + (2^3 + 4) * 5^6 - 7 * 8 * 9$
12218869	$((12 + 34) * (5^6)) + 7 * (8 + 9)$	13500503	$-1 + (2^3 + 4) * 5^6 + 7 * 8 * 9$
12327693	$((-12^3) / 4) + ((5^6)^*789)$	13500505	$1 + (2^3 + 4) * 5^6 + 7 * 8 * 9$
12328557	$((12^3) / 4) + ((5^6)^*789)$	13505640	$-12 * (34 - (((5^6)^*7) * 8) * 9))$
12417786	$((1 + 2) * (3^4)) * 5678 * 9$	13506047	$-1 + (2^3 + 4) * (5^6 + 7) * 8 * 9$
12476160	$(-1 + 2 * (3/4)^{-5}) / 6^{\wedge}(-7 + 8 - 9)$	13506049	$1 + (2^3 + 4) * (5^6 + 7) * 8 * 9$
12515001	$-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) * 5^6 - 7) * 89$	13506456	$12 * (34 + (((5^6)^*7) * 8) * 9)$
12515003	$1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) * 5^6 - 7) * 89$	13509720	$(12 * (34 + (((5^6)^*7) * 8))) * 9$
12596021	$-1 - (2 * 3^4 - 5 * (6^7 + 8)) * 9$	13704804	$(1234^{\wedge}((5^6) / (7 + 8))) * 9$
12596023	$1 - (2 * 3^4 - 5 * (6^7 + 8)) * 9$	13879322	$(123 + 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - 89)$
12598217	$-1 + (2 * 3^4 + 5 * (6^7 - 8)) * 9$	13881481	$(123 + 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - (8 * 9))$
12598219	$1 + (2 * 3^4 + 5 * (6^7 - 8)) * 9$	13889600	$((123 + 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - 8)) - 9$
12598939	$1 + (2 * 3^4 + 5 * (6^7 + 8)) * 9$	13889618	$((123 + 4) * (((5^6)^*7) - 8)) + 9$
12937092	$-12 * (34 - ((5^6)^*(78 - 9)))$	13890625	$((123 + 4) * (5^6)) / (7^{\wedge}(8 - 9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
13891632	$((123+4)*((5^6)^7)+8))-9$	16817913	$((123-4)*((5^6)+78))^9$
13891650	$((123+4)*((5^6)^7)+8))+9$	17210037	$-123*(4-(((5^6)-78)^9))$
13899769	$(123+4)*(((5^6)^7)+(8^9))$	17211021	$123*(4+(((5^6)-78)^9))$
13901928	$(123+4)*(((5^6)^7)+89)$	17234391	$-123*(4-(((5^6)-(7^8))^9))$
14000127	$-1+2^(3+4)*5^6*7-8+9$	17235375	$123*(4+(((5^6)-(7^8))^9))$
14128805	$((-123^4)^5)/(6-(78+9))$	17279778	$-123*(4-(((5^6)-(7+8))^9))$
14624484	$-12*(34-((5^6)^78))+9$	17280762	$123*(4+(((5^6)-(7+8))^9))$
14624583	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^78)))-9$	17296260	$123*(4+(((5^6)+7)-8)^9)$
14624601	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^78)))+9$	17298474	$123*(4+(((5^6)-7)+8)^9)$
14624700	$-12*(34-(((5^6)^78)+9))$	17312988	$-123*(4-(((5^6)+7)+8)^9)$
14625300	$12*((34+((5^6)^78))-9)$	17313972	$123*(4+(((5^6)+7)+8)^9)$
14625399	$(12*(34+((5^6)^78)))-9$	17358375	$-123*(4-(((5^6)+7^8))^9)$
14625417	$(12*(34+((5^6)^78)))+9$	17359359	$123*(4+(((5^6)+7^8))^9)$
14625516	$12*((34+((5^6)^78))+9)$	17382729	$-123*(4-(((5^6)+78)^9))$
14812092	$-12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+(8^9))))$	17383713	$123*(4+(((5^6)+78)^9))$
14812908	$12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+(8^9))))$	17770221	$(123+4)*5^6-78)^9$
14867265	$(123-4)*(((5^6)-7)^8))-9$	17795367	$((123+4)*((5^6)-(7^8)))^9$
14868327	$((123-4)*((5^6)-7))^8)-9$	17842230	$((123+4)*((5^6)-(7+8)))^9$
14868345	$((123-4)*((5^6)-7))^8)+9$	17851302	$((123+4)*((5^6)-7))-8)^9$
14869407	$(123-4)*(((5^6)-7)^8)+9$	17851446	$((123+4)*((5^6)-7))+8)^9$
14880593	$(123-4)*(((5^6)+7)^8))-9$	17858232	$((123+4)*((5^6)+7))-8)^9$
14881655	$((123-4)*((5^6)+7))^8)-9$	17858871	$((123+4)*((5^6)-(7^8))^9$
14881673	$((123-4)*((5^6)+7))^8)+9$	17859240	$((123+4)*5^6)-(7+8))^9$
14882735	$(123-4)*(((5^6)+7)^8)+9$	17859366	$((123+4)*5^6)+7)-8)^9$
14886936	$(123^((4+5)-6))^*(7-8)+9$	17859384	$((123+4)*5^6)-7)+8)^9$
15366513	$-123*(4-(((5^6)-7)^8))+9$	17859510	$((123+4)*5^6)+7)+8)^9$
15367497	$123*(4+(((5^6)-7)^8))-9$	17859879	$((123+4)*5^6)+7^8))^9$
15368727	$-123*(4-(((5^6)-7)^8)+9)$	17860518	$((123+4)*((5^6)-7)+8))^9$
15369711	$123*(4+(((5^6)-7)^8))+9$	17867304	$((123+4)*((5^6)+7))-8)^9$
15374508	$-123*(4-((5^6)^*(7-8+9)))$	17867448	$((123+4)*((5^6)+7))+8)^9$
15374592	$-12*(34+((5^6)^*(7-89)))$	17876520	$((123+4)*((5^6)+7)+8))^9$
15375408	$12*(34-((5^6)^*(7-89)))$	17923383	$((123+4)*((5^6)+7^8))^9$
15375492	$123*(4+((5^6)^*(7-8+9)))$	17948529	$(123+4)*5^6+78)^9$
15380289	$-123*(4-(((5^6)+7)^8))+9$	17998847	$-1+2^(3+4)*5^6+7-8)^9$
15381273	$123*(4+(((5^6)+7)^8))-9$	17998849	$1+2^(3+4)*5^6+7-8)^9$
15382503	$-123*(4-(((5^6)+7)^8)+9)$	17999592	$-12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+89)))$
15383487	$123*(4+(((5^6)+7)^8))+9$	17999990	$-1+(2^(3+4)*5^6+7-8)^9$
15835392	$-1+2*(3/4)^5*6^7+8-9$	17999992	$1+(2^(3+4)*5^6+7-8)^9$
15866745	$(123+4)*(((5^6)-7)^8))-9$	18000008	$-1+(2^(3+4)*5^6-7+8)^9$
15869031	$(123+4)*(((5^6)-7)^8)+9$	18000010	$1+(2^(3+4)*5^6-7+8)^9$
15880969	$(123+4)*(((5^6)+7)^8))-9$	18000408	$12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+89)))$
15883255	$(123+4)*(((5^6)+7)^8)+9$	18001151	$-1+2^(3+4)*5^6-7+8)^9$
16156250	$((-12+34)*5^6)^*(7^8)-9$	18001153	$1+2^(3+4)*5^6-7+8)^9$
16269819	$((-12+(34^5)/6)-(7^8))^9$	18040536	$((12*(34^5*(5^6)-7))/8))^9$
16269909	$((12-(34^5)/6)+(7^8))^9$	18608670	$(-123^((4+5)-6))^*(7-(8+9))$
16269945	$((12-(34^5)/6)-(7^8))^9$	19125000	$((123-4)*5^6)/7)^8)^9$
16270035	$((12+(34^5)/6)-(7^8))^9$	19218258	$-123*(4+((5^6)^*(7-(8+9))))$
16312092	$-12*(34-((5^6)^*(78+9)))$	19219242	$123*(4-(((5^6)^*(7-(8+9))))$
16312908	$12*(34+((5^6)^*(78+9)))$	19249802	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)^8)-9$
16650837	$(123-4)*((5^6)-78))^9$	19249991	$(((-12+34)*5^6)^7)^8)-9$
16655758	$-123*(4-((5^6)^78)/9)$	19250009	$(((-12+34)*5^6)^7)^8)+9$
16656742	$123*(4+((5^6)^78)/9)$	19250198	$(-12+34)*(((5^6)^7)^8)+9$
16674399	$((123-4)*5^6-7^8))^9$	19414133	$-1+((2^3)^4+5)^6*789$
16680023	$-1+(2^3+4)*5^6-7)^89$	19414135	$1+((2^3)^4+5)^6*789$
16680025	$1+(2^3+4)*5^6-7)^89$	19643018	$((-123/4)*((5^6)-(7^8)))/9$
16694975	$-1+(2^3+4)*5^6+7)^89$	20154293	$-1-(2^3*4^4-(5+6^7)^8)^9$
16694977	$1+(2^3+4)*5^6+7)^89$	20154295	$1-(2^3*4^4-(5+6^7)^8)^9$
16718310	$((123-4)*((5^6)-(7+8)))^9$	20156489	$-1+(2^3*4^4-(5-6^7)^8)^9$
16726806	$((123-4)*((5^6)-7))-8)^9$	20156491	$1+(2^3*4^4-(5-6^7)^8)^9$
16726950	$((123-4)*((5^6)-7))+8)^9$	20925888	$(-1-((23^4)^*(5-6^7)))/9$
16733304	$(123-4)*(((5^6)+7)-8))^9$	21365423	$-1+(23-4)*5^6-7)^8)^9$
16733871	$((123-4)*5^6)^*(7^8))^9$	21365425	$1+(23-4)*5^6-7)^8)^9$
16734240	$((123-4)*5^6)-(7+8))^9$	21654666	$((-12+34)*((5^6)^7)-8))^9$
16734366	$((123-4)*5^6)+7)-8))^9$	21656178	$(((-12+34)*5^6)^7)-8))^9$
16734384	$((123-4)*5^6)-7)+8))^9$	21656322	$(((-12+34)*5^6)^7)+8))^9$
16734510	$((123-4)*5^6)+7)+8))^9$	21657834	$((-12+34)*((5^6)^7)+8))^9$
16734879	$((123-4)*5^6)+7^8))^9$	22305564	$(-12*(34-((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$
16735446	$((123-4)*((5^6)-7)+8))^9$	22312092	$-12*(34-(((5^6)^7)^*(8+9)))$
16741800	$((123-4)*((5^6)+7))-8))^9$	22312908	$12*(34+(((5^6)^7)^*(8+9)))$
16741944	$((123-4)*((5^6)+7))+8))^9$	22319436	$(12*(34+((5^6)^7))^*(8+9))$
16750440	$((123-4)*((5^6)+7)+8))^9$	22779671	$-1+(2*((3/4)^5)^6-789))$
16794351	$((123-4)*((5^6)+7^8))^9$	22779672	$(1*2)*((3/4)^5)^6-789)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
33466290	$-12+((34*((5^6)^7)-8))^*9$	45334405	$1-2*3^4*(5-6^7+89)$
33466314	$12+((34*((5^6)^7)-8))^*9$	45348824	$1-2*3^4*(5-6^7)-8+9$
33466410	$(12+(34*((5^6)^7)-8))^*9$	45348965	$-1-2*3^4*(5-6^7-8/9)$
33471090	$(-12+(34*((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$	45348966	$-1*2*3^4*(5-6^7-8/9)$
33471186	$-12+((34*((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$	45348967	$1-2*3^4*(5-6^7-8/9)$
33471210	$12+((34*((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$	45350369	$-1+2*3^4*(5+6^7)-8*9$
33471306	$(12+(34*((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$	45350371	$1+2*3^4*(5+6^7)-8*9$
33719262	$((123+4)*((5^6)-7))^*(8+9)$	45350444	$1+2*3^4*(5+6^7)-8+9$
33734256	$((123+4)*((5^6)^7)-7)^*(8+9)$	45350513	$-1+2*3^4*(5+6^7)+8*9$
33734494	$((123+4)*((5^6)^7)+7)^*(8+9)$	45350515	$1+2*3^4*(5+6^7)+8*9$
33749488	$((123+4)*((5^6)^7)+7)^*(8+9)$	45414459	$(((-12-34)*(5^6))+7^8))^*9$
33781250	$((12+34)*5^6)^*(7^8-9)$	46114268	$-12*(345-((6*(7^8))/9))$
33883208	$-1-(2^7(3+4)*5^6-7^8)^*9$	46116368	$-12*((34^5)-((6*(7^8))/9))$
33883210	$1-(2^7(3+4)*5^6-7^8)^*9$	46117940	$-12*((34+5)-((6*(7^8))/9))$
34023834	$((-123-4)*5^6)+7^8))^*9$	46118060	$-12*(34-(5+((6*(7^8))/9)))$
34169508	$(1+2)*(((3/45)^6)-789)$	46118756	$12*(34-5)+((6*(7^8))/9)$
34174242	$(1+2)*(((3/45)^6)+789)$	46118876	$12*(34+5)+((6*(7^8))/9)$
34736184	$((123+4)/(5+6/7))^*8/9$	46120448	$12*(34^5)+((6*(7^8))/9)$
35148834	$((-123+4)*5^6)+7^8))^*9$	46122548	$12*(345+((6*(7^8))/9))$
36984273	$(-1-2)^*(34-((5^6)*789))$	46124508	$-123*(4-((5^6)*((7+8)+9)))$
36984351	$-12-(3*(4-((5^6)*789)))$	46125492	$123*(4+((5^6)*((7+8)+9)))$
36984399	$12+(3*(4+((5^6)*789)))$	46406250	$(((-12+34)*5^6)^*(7+8))^*9$
36984477	$(1+2)^*(34+((5^6)*789))$	46718750	$((12+34)*5^6)^*(7^8)+9$
38147771	$((123^4-5)/6)-((7+8)/9)$	46749294	$-1+(2*3^4+5)*6^7-8-9$
38147776	$((123^4+5)/6)+((7+8)/9)$	46749296	$1+(2*3^4+5)*6^7-8-9$
38926553	$(-12+(4*(5^6))^*7))^*89$	46749314	$1+(2*3^4+5)*6^7-8+9$
38948447	$(123+(4*(5^6))^*7))^*89$	48789459	$(((-12-34)*5^6))+7^8))^*9$
38987639	$((12*(34^5))/6)-((7^8)^*9)$	49898834	$((-123-4)*5^6))+7^8))^*9$
40249586	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7)^*8)-9$	50023834	$((-123+4)*5^6))+7^8))^*9$
40249991	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)^*8)-9$	50203124	$-1+(23+4)*5^6*7*(8+9)$
40250009	$((12+34)*((5^6)^7)^*8)+9$	50203126	$1+(23+4)*5^6*7*(8+9)$
40250414	$(12+34)*(((5^6)^7)^*8)+9$	51114763	$((12/34)^5)^*(6^7))-89$
40906250	$((-12+34)*5^6)^*(8+9)$	51114941	$((12/34)^5)^*(6^7))+89$
41437182	$-12+(34*((5^6)^7)+9)$	51127497	$((-123*(4^5))^6)+((7^8)^*9)$
41437206	$12+(34*((5^6)^7)+9)$	51164459	$((-12-34)*5^6))+7^8))^*9$
41437794	$-12+(34*((5^6)^7)+9)$	51320586	$-123-(((4*(5^6))-7^8))^*9)$
41437818	$12+(34*((5^6)^7)+9)$	51320708	$-1+((2-3)*4*5^6+7^8)^*9$
41506449	$-123+((4/5)^6)+((7^8)^*9))$	51320710	$1+((2-3)*4*5^6+7^8)^*9$
41506695	$123+((4/5)^6)+((7^8)^*9))$	51320832	$123-(((4*(5^6))-7^8))^*9)$
41554943	$-1+(2*3^4+5)/6^7-8+9$	51539459	$((12-34)*5^6))+7^8))^*9$
41554945	$1+(2*3^4+5)/6^7-8+9$	51726816	$((12+34)*((5^6)-7))^*8+9$
42550254	$-1+2*(3^4-5)*6^7-8-9$	51741350	$-1234-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
42550256	$1+2*(3^4-5)*6^7-8-9$	51742092	$(-123*4)-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
42550270	$-1+2*(3^4-5)*6^7+8-9$	51742176	$(-12*34)-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
42550274	$1+2*(3^4-5)*6^7+8+9$	51742465	$(-123+4)-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
42550288	$-1+2*(3^4-5)*6^7+8+9$	51742562	$12-(34+((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
42550290	$1+2*(3^4-5)*6^7+8+9$	51742606	$(-12+34)-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
42916254	$(((((123^4)+5)/6)+7)/8))^*9$	51742703	$123-(4+((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
43883208	$-1-2^7-3*(4^5)^6+7^8)^*9$	51742992	$(12*34)-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
43883209	$-1*2^7-3*(4^5)^6+7^8)^*9$	51743076	$(123*4)-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
43883210	$1-2^7-3*(4^5)^6+7^8)^*9$	51743818	$1234-(((5^6)-7^8))^*9)$
44353673	$-1*(23-4-5)^6+7^8)^*9$	51749496	$(((((12+34)*5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
44588688	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)-89)$	51750504	$(((((12+34)*5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
44595624	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)-(8^9))$	51756519	$(-123*((4^5)+6))+7^8))^*9$
44618064	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)-(8+9))$	51757251	$((-123*(4^5))-6)+((7^8)^*9)$
44621628	$12*((34*((5^6)^7)-8))-9$	51757263	$((-123*(4^5))+6)+((7^8)^*9)$
44621727	$((12*34)*((5^6)^7)-8)-9$	51757995	$(-123*(4^5)-6)+((7^8)^*9)$
44621745	$((12*34)*((5^6)^7)-8)+9$	51773184	$((12+34)*((5^6)+7))^*8+9$
44621844	$12*((34*((5^6)^7)-8))+9$	51846335	$-1-((2^3)^4-5+6-7^8)^*9$
44624592	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)+8)-9$	51846337	$1-((2^3)^4-5+6-7^8)^*9$
44625408	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)-8)+9$	51846353	$-1-((2^3)^4+5-6-7^8)^*9$
44628156	$12*((34*((5^6)^7)+8))-9$	51846355	$1-((2^3)^4+5-6-7^8)^*9$
44628255	$((12*34)*((5^6)^7)+8)-9$	51862217	$((-123*(4^5))/6)+((7^8)^*9)$
44628273	$((12*34)*((5^6)^7)+8)+9$	51870049	$((-1-234)^5)+((7^8)^*9)$
44628372	$12*((34*((5^6)^7)+8))+9$	51870161	$((1-234)^5)+((7^8)^*9)$
44631936	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)+8)+9$	51874730	$-1-((2*3^4-5)^*6-7^8)^*9$
44654376	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)+8+9))$	51874732	$1-((2*3^4-5)^*6-7^8)^*9$
44660808	$(123^(4+5)-6)^*(7^8+9)$	51875829	$(-123*(4+56))+((7^8)^*9)$
44661312	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)+89)$	51876813	$(123*(4-56))+((7^8)^*9)$
45277938	$((12+34)*(((5^6)^7)-8))^*9$	51877803	$(123-(4^5))^6+((7^8)^*9)$
45284562	$((12+34)*(((5^6)^7)+8))^*9$	51879027	$(-123*(4+(5^6)))+((7^8)^*9)$
45334403	$-1-2*3^4*(5-6^7+89)$	51879142	$-1-(2^3)^4+5*6+7^8)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
259416029	$(-12-34)+(5*(6+((7^8)^9)))$	357003672	$(12*34)*(((5^6)^7)*8)+9$
259416061	$(12+34)-(5*(6-((7^8)^9)))$	362250000	$(((12+34)*(5^6)^7)*8)^9$
259416097	$(-12+34)+(5*(6+((7^8)^9)))$	363182420	$-1+(2*(3-4)-5)*(6-7^8*9)$
259416121	$(12+34)+5*(6+((7^8)^9))$	363182422	$1+(2*(3-4)-5)*(6-7^8*9)$
259416142	$123+4-5*(6-7^8*9)$	363182504	$-1-(2*(3-4)-5)*(6+7^8*9)$
259416168	$123+(((4-5)+6)*(7^8)^9)$	363182506	$1-(2*(3-4)-5)*(6+7^8*9)$
259416483	$(12^*34)+(5*(6+((7^8)^9)))$	373079304	$((1+2)^(3*4)+5+6)*7^8*9$
259416507	$(123^*4)-(5*(6-((7^8)^9)))$	382952375	$-1+(2*(3^4-5)*6^7-8)^9$
259448697	$(-123*(4-((5^6)^*(7+8))))^9$	382952377	$1+(2*(3^4-5)*6^7-8)^9$
259452633	$-123*(4-((5^6)^*(7+8))^9)$	382952519	$-1+(2*(3^4-5)*6^7+8)^9$
259453617	$123*(4+((5^6)^*(7+8))^9)$	382952521	$1+(2*(3^4-5)*6^7+8)^9$
259457553	$(123*(4+((5^6)^*(7+8))))^9$	383999892	$1*2*(3*((4^5)^6-7-8)-9)$
266324069	$-123*(4-(((5+6)^7-8)/9))$	383999928	$1*2*(3*((4^5)^6-7-8)+9)$
266325053	$123*(4+(((5+6)^7-8)/9))$	384000105	$(-1+2/3*((4^5)^6+7+8))^9$
267890625	$(((123+4)*(5^6)^*(7+8))^9)$	401595624	$((12^*34)*((5^6)^7-8))^9$
269792718	$(12-(34/5))*(6+((7^8)^9))$	401654376	$((12^*34)*((5^6)^7+8))^9$
271218662	$(1-23)*(4-((5^6)^*789))$	419315628	$((1+2)^(3*4)+5+6)*789$
271218838	$(-1+23)*(4+((5^6)^*789))$	420731783	$-1+(2/3^(4-5)*6^7-8)^9$
280629225	$(123^4)-(((5^6)^-7^8)^*9)$	420731785	$1+(2/3^(4-5)*6^7-8)^9$
280910475	$(123^4)+(((5^6)^+7^8)^*9)$	420743735	$-1+(2*3^4+5)*6^7-8)^9$
283546782	$-1-(23*(4-((5^6)^*789)))$	420743737	$1+(2*3^4+5)*6^7-8)^9$
283546783	$(-1*23)*(4-((5^6)^*789))$	420755831	$-1+(2/3^(4-5)*6^7+8)^9$
283546784	$1-(23*(4-((5^6)^*789)))$	420755833	$1+(2/3^(4-5)*6^7+8)^9$
283546966	$-1+(23*(4+((5^6)^*789)))$	427523973	$-123-(((4/5)^6-7)^*(8^9))$
283546967	$(1*23)*(4+((5^6)^*789))$	427524219	$123-(((4/5)^6-7)^*(8^9))$
283546968	$1+(23*(4+((5^6)^*789)))$	430495572	$(123^4)*(((5^6)^7)^8)-9)$
283966653	$(-1+234)*(((5^6)^*78-9)$	430498893	$123*(((4*(5^6)^7)^8)-9)$
283970847	$(-1+234)*(((5^6)^*78+9)$	430501107	$123*(((4*(5^6)^7)^8)+9)$
285185393	$-1+(234*(((5^6)^*78-9)$	430504428	$(123^4)*(((5^6)^7)^8)+9)$
285185394	$(1*234)*(((5^6)^*78-9)$	435819636	$(((12^*34)/5)-6)*((7^8)+9)$
285185395	$1+(234*(((5^6)^*78-9)$	443812356	$(-12^*3)*(4-((5^6)^*789))$
285189605	$-1+(234*(((5^6)^*78+9)$	443812644	$(12^*3)*(4+((5^6)^*789))$
285189606	$(1*234)*(((5^6)^*78+9)$	447781250	$(((12+34)*5^6)^7)*89$
285189607	$1+(234*(((5^6)^*78+9)$	449141760	$(-1+2*(3/4)^(4-5)/6^(7-8-9))$
286404135	$(1+234)*(((5^6)^*78-9)$	460033596	$((((12/34)^(4-5))*6^7)-8)^9$
286408365	$(1+234)*(((5^6)^*78+9)$	460033740	$((((12/34)^(4-5))*6^7)+8)^9$
289207644	$1234*(((5^6)^*(7+8))-9)$	465683255	$-1-(2+3+4)*5^6-7^8*9$
289229856	$1234*(((5^6)^*(7+8))+9)$	465683257	$1-(2+3+4)*(5^6+7^8)^9$
295874904	$(-1-23)*(4-((5^6)^*789))$	466944777	$(-12+3)*(456-((7^8)^9))$
295875096	$(1+23)*(4+((5^6)^*789))$	466948704	$-123-((4+5)*6-((7^8)^9)))$
296156249	$-1+(23+4)/5^6-6^7*8^9$	466949058	$123+((4+5)*6+(7^8)^9)))$
296156251	$1+(23+4)/5^6-6^7*8^9$	466952985	$(12-3)*(456+(7^8)^9)$
299766844	$(-12*(34+5))*(6-((7^8)/9))$	468214505	$-1+(2+3+4)*(5^6+7^8)^9$
299772460	$(12*(34+5))*(6+((7^8)/9))$	468214507	$1+(2+3+4)*(5^6+7^8)^9$
301989765	$-123+((4^4/(5/6)^*(7+8))^9)$	472587730	$-123*((4^5)-(6*(7^8)/9))$
301990011	$123+((4^4/(5/6)^*(7+8))^9)$	472708147	$-123*(45-(6*(7^8)/9))$
311173302	$(-123*(4^5))+((6*(7^8))^9)$	472711222	$-123*((4^5)-(6*(7^8)/9))$
311298677	$-1-(2^4(-3(-4-5))-6*7^8)^9$	472712575	$-123*((4+5)-(6*(7^8)/9))$
311298679	$1-(2^4(-3(-4-5))-6*7^8)^9$	472713682	$(((-123*(4-5))^6*(7^8)/9)$
311299109	$-1-(2^4(3-(4-5))-6*7^8)^9$	472714789	$123*((4+5)+((6*(7^8)/9))$
311299399	$1+(2^4(3-(4-5))+6*7^8)^9$	472716142	$123*((4^5)+((6*(7^8)/9))$
311299829	$-1+(2^4(-3(-4-5))+6*7^8)^9$	472719217	$123*(45+(6*(7^8)/9))$
311299831	$1+(2^4(-3(-4-5))+6*7^8)^9$	472839634	$123*((4^5)+((6*(7^8)/9))$
311300756	$-1+(2*3^4+5+6*7^8)^9$	477071124	$(((-12+(34^5/6))^7-8)^9$
311300758	$1+(2*3^4+5+6*7^8)^9$	477071268	$(((-12+(34^5/6))^7+8)^9$
311336117	$-1+(2^4(3(-4-5))+6*7^8)^9$	477071754	$((((12-(34^5)/-6)^7-8)^9$
311336119	$1+(2^4(3(-4-5))+6*7^8)^9$	477071772	$(((-12+((34^5/6)^7)-8)^9$
311425206	$(123*((4^5))+((6*(7^8))^9)$	477071916	$(((-12+((34^5/6)^7)+8)^9$
323870466	$((-1+234)*((5^6)^-7))^89$	477071988	$((12+(((34^5/6)^7))-8)^9$
324160784	$((-1+234)*((5^6)^+7))^89$	477072132	$((12+(((34^5/6)^7))+8)^9$
324495681	$((-12+(34^5))^6)+((7^8)^9)$	477072150	$((((12-(-34^5)/6)^7)+8)^9$
324495825	$((12+(34^5))^6)+((7^8)^9)$	477072636	$((((12+((34^5/6)^7)-8)^9$
326650470	$((1+234)*((5^6)^-7))^89$	477072780	$((((12+((34^5/6)^7)+8)^9$
326943280	$((1+234)*((5^6)^+7))^89$	477325026	$(((-12-34)/5)*6-(7^8))^9$
331094596	$((1+2)^4(3^4)+5+6)^7*8^9$	477325578	$((12+34)/5)^6+(7^8)^9)$
332150613	$-12+(3^4*5)^(4-6-7+8+9)$	480468750	$(123*(4^5))/((6/(7+8))^9)$
334358458	$(123^4+5^6)^7*8^9/9$	484277076	$((123^4)*(((5^6)^7-8))^9$
351703791	$((123^4)/(5+(6/7)))^8)^9$	484303644	$(123*((4*(5^6)^7)-8))^9$
351703935	$((123^4)/(5+(6/7)))^8)^9$	484321356	$(123*((4*(5^6)^7)+8))^9$
352805850	$-12+((34/5)*6+((7^8)^9))$	484347924	$((123^4)*(((5^6)^7+8))^9$
352805874	$12+((34/5)*6+((7^8)^9))$	488302656	$(123^4)-(5*(6-((7^8)^9)))$
356996328	$(12^*34)*(((5^6)^7)^8)-9$	488302716	$(123^4)+(5*(6+((7^8)^9)))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1794607605	$-1+(2-(3-4)/5)*((6+7)^8+9)$		
1794607607	$1+(2-(3-4)/5)*((6+7)^8+9)$		
1815912303	$-12+(((34-5)+6)*(7^8))^9$		
1815912327	$12+(((34-5)+6)*(7^8))^9$		
1830218119	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7))^8-9$		
1830218137	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7))^8+9$		
1831968119	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7))^8-9$		
1831968137	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7))^8+9$		
1836675729	$(-123^4)*((5/(6-(7/8))))-9$		
1867779108	$(-12^3)*(456-((7^8)^9))$		
1867811940	$(12^3)*(456+((7^8)^9))$		
1881956826	$((123^4)/5)*((6^7)-(8/9))$		
1890852268	$(-123^4)*(5-((6*(7^8))/9))$		
1890857188	$(123^4)*(5+((6*(7^8))/9))$		
1908876089	$-1+(2^34+5^6-(7-8))/9$		
1908876091	$1+(2^34+5^6-(7-8))/9$		
1971561941	$-1-((2/(3-4))^5-6)^7*8^9$		
1971561943	$1-((2/(3-4))^5-6)^7*8^9$		
1988856345	$((12+34)^5/6)^7*(7^8)^9$		
2023444905	$-12-((34+5)^6-(7^8)^9)$		
2023444929	$12-((34+5)^6-(7^8)^9)$		
2023445028	$-123+(((45-6)*(7^8))^9)$		
2023445274	$123+(((45-6)*(7^8))^9)$		
2023445373	$-12+((34+5)^6+(7^8)^9)$		
2023445397	$12+((34+5)^6+(7^8)^9)$		
2025467426	$(-12-(34/(5+6)))*(7-(8^9))$		
2049011019	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2052104769	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2057870394	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2058854265	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2058855273	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2058995322	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2058995466	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2059962183	$((123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2059997355	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2060964072	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2060964216	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2061104265	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2061105273	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2062089144	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2067854769	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2070948519	$((123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$		
2092622763	$((12+((34^5)/6))^7*(7^8))^9$		
2113928871	$(1+(2/3-4^(5+6))^7*8)^9$		
2113928889	$(1-(2/3-4^(5+6))^7*8)^9$		
2127211323	$(-12-34+5)^6*(6-7^8)^9$		
2127211815	$(12+34-5)^6*(6+7^8)^9$		
2139349536	$((123-(4+5))^6*(6+7-8))/9$		

Supplement 2

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
24878	$98*7+6^5*(4+3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	144429	$-9*8-7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
41294	$((98-76)*((5^{\wedge}4)*3)+2))*1$	144474	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
51069	$(9*87)*(65-(4/(3-21)))$	144492	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
51652	$((987/6)*((5^{\wedge}4)+3))/2)-1$	144502	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
56955	$-9*((8-((7/6)*5432))+1)$	144506	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
56973	$-9*((8-((7/6)*5432))-1)$	144508	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
57262	$9+((8/(7*65432))^{\wedge}-1)$	145298	$(9+8+7/6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}3-2)+1$
57871	$-9-8-(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)/2+1$	145496	$-9-(8+7)*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
57899	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)/2-1$	145677	$-98*(76-((5^{\wedge}4)*((3/2)+1)))$
57901	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)/2+1$	146366	$(9-87)*(-6/5^{\wedge}-4-3)/2-1$
58061	$(-987+((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)))-1$	147026	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)/4-32+1$
59746	$-9-8-(-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)/2+1$	147088	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)/4+32-1$
59756	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)/2-1$	147094	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)/4+32+1$
63435	$(-9+(87/((6/54)^{\wedge}3)))+21$	147410	$9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4-3-2)-1$
63453	$(9+(87/((6/54)^{\wedge}3)))+21$	147412	$9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4-3-2)+1$
65290	$-9*8-(-7^{\wedge}6*5-4)/3^{\wedge}2+1$	147502	$9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4+3+2)+1$
71076	$-98+(76*((5^{\wedge}4)*3)/2)-1$	152033	$((98*76)-((5^{\wedge}4)/3))*21$
71300	$((98+(76*(5^{\wedge}4)*3))/2)+1$	152762	$(-9+(8/(7+6))^{\wedge}-5)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
72107	$(98*(7+((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)))-21$	154724	$9876*((5*((4/3)+2))-1)$
72149	$(98*(7+((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)))+21$	158086	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1$
72326	$(98+76)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^2)-1$	160313	$((-9+87*6)*5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1$
75519	$(-9-8-7)*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	160315	$((-9+87*6)*5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1$
75521	$(-9-8-7)*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	160783	$((98*76)+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))*21$
77917	$-98-(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/3^2-1$	161189	$((9*876)-((5^{\wedge}4)/3))*21$
78373	$-9*8-(-7^{\wedge}6-5*4)/3^2-1$	164095	$-9+(876*((5^{\wedge}4)/3)-21))$
82499	$((98-76)*((5^{\wedge}4)*3)^2)-1$	164113	$9+(876*((5^{\wedge}4)/3)-21))$
82750	$(987+6)/((5/4)^{\wedge}-3)-(2^{\wedge}-1))$	164599	$((9876*5)*((4/3)+2))-1$
84275	$-9+(8+7)*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)-1$	164601	$((9876*5)*((4/3)+2))+1$
84277	$-9+(8+7)*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	165937	$((9+87*6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$
84293	$9+(8+7)*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)-1$	166491	$-9*(876-((5^{\wedge}4)*32-1))$
84295	$9+(8+7)*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	167926	$-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(43-2)-1$
84426	$(-98*(76-((5^{\wedge}4)*3)/2)))-1$	169649	$9*87*(65*(4/3+2))-1$
89938	$9-8*(7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3+2)+1$	169651	$9*87*(65*(4/3+2))+1$
92983	$(-987+(6^{\wedge}(-5+(4*3)))/(2+1)$	169939	$((9*876)+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))*21$
95048	$(98/(((7/654)*3)^{\wedge}2))*1$	170093	$987*((((65*4)/3)^2)-1)$
95468	$9876*((((5*4)/3)+2)+1)$	170562	$((9-8)*7+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$
95598	$((98*(76+((5^{\wedge}4)*3)))/2)-1$	172107	$-9*((876-((5^{\wedge}4)*32))+1)$
99421	$98*((76+((5^{\wedge}4)*3)/2))+1$	173302	$-9+8*7*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
99605	$(9+((8*7)/6))*5432+1$	174476	$9876*((5*((4/3)+2))+1)$
104461	$(9-8)*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	176369	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3^2+1$
106759	$(98-7-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1$	176382	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4*3^2-1$
106761	$(98-7-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1$	176578	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4*3^2-1$
107261	$98+((7/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))*21)$	178976	$-987*((6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3))+21)$
107294	$(9+8*7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1$	180143	$(9+87)*6/5^{\wedge}-4+3/2-1$
107296	$(9+8*7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	184385	$(-9-8+7)*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
109167	$9+8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	184499	$9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)*(3+2)-1$
110000	$((98-76)*(5^{\wedge}4))*((3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	184930	$98*((((76/((5/4)-3))^{\wedge}2)+1)$
115081	$(9-8/7)*(6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)+21$	190820	$987*((6+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))-21)$
115280	$(9-8/7)*(6+5)^{\wedge}4+32-1$	191096	$(9+8)*(-7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1$
115808	$(987*6)*((5*(4+(3^{\wedge}-2)))-1)$	191098	$(9+8)*(-7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1$
116795	$987*((6*(5*4)-(3^{\wedge}-2)))-1$	191164	$(-9-8)*7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1$
118518	$98765/((4/3)-(2^{\wedge}-1))$	191378	$9*(-87-6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
119019	$-987+(6*((5^{\wedge}4)*32)+1)$	191402	$(9+8)*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3+2)-1$
120743	$987*((6*5)*(4+(3^{\wedge}-2)))-1$	191404	$(9+8)*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3+2)+1$
121072	$(987*6)*((5*(4-(3^{\wedge}-2)))+1)$	196012	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3+2-1$
121831	$(98-7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1$	196799	$(-9+(8+7-6)^{\wedge}5)*(4/3+2)-1$
125442	$9*(876+((5^{\wedge}4)-3)*21))$	196859	$(9+(8+7-6)^{\wedge}5)*(4/3+2)-1$
127395	$((-9/87)+6)*5*4321$	196861	$(9+(8+7-6)^{\wedge}5)*(4/3+2)+1$
129832	$(9+8)*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	198832	$(-9+876)*((5^{\wedge}4)/3)+21$
129834	$(9+8)*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	199700	$(-987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))-(2+1)$
130072	$(9+8)*7-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	199702	$((-987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))-2)+1$
137684	$-98-7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	199705	$((-987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))+2)*1$
137878	$98-7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	199706	$((-987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))+2)+1$
138000	$(9+8*7*6)*(5*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	199724	$(-987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))+21$
138564	$9*(87+((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)*21))$	199870	$-9-8*(7+6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
139415	$9*(8+7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1$	199888	$9-8*(7+6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
141816	$(9-8)*76*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1)$	199982	$-9+8*(7-6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
142591	$9*(8+76/5^{\wedge}-4/3+2)+1$	200157	$((9-87)*6)+((5^{\wedge}4)*321)$
143800	$(-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5-4/3))/(2+1)$	200638	$((-9+87)/6)+((5^{\wedge}4)*321)$
143806	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5-4/3))/(2+1)$	200667	$(9-8)*7*6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
144419	$-9*8-7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	200887	$-9+(876*((5^{\wedge}4)/3)+21))$
144427	$-9*8-7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	200905	$9+(876*((5^{\wedge}4)/3)+21))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
379790	$9-8+7^6-5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$	482552	$-98*(76-((5^4)^*(3^2-1)))$
380748	$((-9876+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	488843	$-9-87*(6-5^4*3^2)-1$
380750	$((-9876+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	488845	$-9-87*(6-5^4*3^2)+1$
383176	$((-98*76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	493500	$(987*6)/(((5/4)^-3)-(2^1-1))$
384702	$((-987*6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	495423	$(9-8-7)^6*5+4^3 \wedge 2-1$
384704	$((-987*6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	495425	$(9-8-7)^6*5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$
389631	$((-987-6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	500073	$((98*7)/((6/54)^3))-21$
389633	$((-987-6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	500589	$98*(7+6^5)-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
389643	$((-987+6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	500591	$98*(7+6^5)-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
389645	$((-987+6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	502604	$9-8*(-7^6-(5*4)^3)/2-1$
390450	$((-98-76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	502606	$9-8*(-7^6-(5*4)^3)/2+1$
390452	$((-98-76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	506987	$-9+(((8*7)/6)^*54321)$
390798	$((98+76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	507005	$9+(((8*7)/6)^*54321)$
390800	$((98+76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	512420	$(98-7)^*(6+5^4/3^2)-1$
391605	$((987-6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	512422	$(98-7)^*(6+5^4/3^2)+1$
391617	$((987+6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	512604	$(9*87)^*(654+((3/2)^-1))$
392093	$-9*8+(7^6*5+4)/3^2-1$	514690	$(9-8/7)^*(-6*5+4^3 \wedge 2-1)$
392095	$-9*8+(7^6*5+4)/3^2+1$	522874	$-9+(8*7^6*5-4)/3^2-1$
392146	$(-98+7^6*5^4)/3^2-1$	522876	$-9+(8*7^6*5-4)/3^2+1$
392174	$9-(-8-7^6*5+4)/3^2-1$	526906	$9*(-8+(7^6-543)/2)+1$
392176	$9-(-8-7^6*5+4)/3^2+1$	528524	$9*(8-(-7^6+5^4*3)/2)-1$
394216	$(-9-8)*(7-6^5)+4^3 \wedge 2-1$	528526	$9*(8-(-7^6+5^4*3)/2)+1$
394218	$(-9-8)*(7-6^5)+4^3 \wedge 2+1$	530453	$(-987+((6/54)^(-3^2)))-1$
396546	$((987*6)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	530454	$-987+((6/54)^(-3-(2+1)))$
398072	$((98*76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	530455	$(-987+((6/54)^(-3^2)))+1$
398074	$((98*76)+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	531199	$-9^((8+7)/6)+5+(5+4)^3 \wedge 2+1$
398419	$-987*((6-((5^4/3)^2)+1)$	532427	$(987+((6/54)^(-3^2)))-1$
399405	$((-987*(6-((5^4/3)^2)-1$	532428	$987+((6/54)^(-3-(2+1)))$
399406	$((-987*(6-((5^4/3)^2)+1$	532429	$(987+((6/54)^(-3^2)))+1$
399407	$((-987*(6-((5^4/3)^2)+1$	544958	$-9+(87*6)^(-5+4+3)^2-1$
400393	$-987*((6-((5^4/3)^2)-1)$	544960	$-9+(87*6)^(-5+4+3)^2+1$
400500	$(9876+(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$	554335	$(98+7)^*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
400502	$(9876+(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$	555360	$98*((76-(5/(4+3)))^2)-1$
403563	$(9^8-7+6)/5^4-3*(2+1)$	555457	$(98*((76-(5/(4+3)))^2))-1$
407769	$(987-6)*(((5^4/3)^2)-1)$	555458	$(98*((76-(5/(4+3)))^2))*1$
408749	$((((-987-6)*(5^4)/3)^2)-1$	555459	$(98*((76-(5/(4+3)))^2))+1$
408751	$((((-987-6)*(5^4)/3)^2)+1$	559708	$9-(87-6^5(-5+4^3))^2+1$
409731	$(987-6)*(((5^4/3)^2)+1)$	559850	$9-(8+7-6^5(-5+4^3))^2-1$
409966	$((((9^8)-76)/5)-43)/21$	559894	$-9+(8+7+6^5(-5+4^3))^2+1$
411500	$9876/(((5/4)^-3)^2)-1$	559910	$9+(8+7+6^5(-5+4^3))^2-1$
414743	$(987+6)*(((5^4/3)^2)+1)$	560054	$9+(87+6^5(-5+4^3))^2-1$
416480	$(9/(-8+((7^6-5^4+3)^2)))^-1$	570618	$9*((87/((6/54)^3))-21)$
417171	$(987*(6+((5^4/3)^2)))-1$	570786	$((9*87)/((6/54)^3))-21$
417173	$(987*(6+((5^4/3)^2)))+1$	570828	$((9*87)/((6/54)^3))+21$
418916	$(-987+(((6^5)/(4^3)^2))-1$	570996	$9*((87/((6/54)^3))+21)$
418918	$(-987+(((6^5)/(4^3)^2))+1$	584131	$-9-8+7^6*5-(4^3)^2-1$
420890	$(987+(((6^5)/(4^3)^2))-1$	584222	$9*8+7^6*5-(4^3)^2+1$
420892	$(987+(((6^5)/(4^3)^2))+1$	585118	$-9+8+(7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
422107	$987*((6+((5^4/3)^2)-1)$	585122	$9-8+(7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)+1$
423093	$((987*(6+((5^4/3)^2))-1$	585158	$(98*(76+((5^4/3)^2))^21$
423094	$((987*(6+((5^4/3)^2))*1$	587973	$-9+8+(7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
423095	$((987*(6+((5^4/3)^2))+1$	587991	$9+8+(7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
424081	$987*((6+((5^4/3)^2)+1)$	588499	$-9-8+(7^6+5^4)^*(3+2)+1$
438281	$(9-87)^*(6-5^4/3^2)-1$	591368	$-9+8+(7^6+5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
438283	$(9-87)^*(6-5^4/3^2)+1$	591372	$9-8+(7^6+5^4)^*(3+2)+1$
440575	$(-9+8^7-6)/((5/(4^3))^2-1)$	592323	$-9-8+7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1$
442584	$9*(8-(7-6-5)^4+3)^*(2+1)$	592339	$-9+8+7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1$
448767	$(9+8+7)^*6^5+4^3 \wedge 2-1$	619948	$98*(76+((5^4)^*(3^2+1)))$
448769	$(9+8+7)^*6^5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$	633338	$-98+(7+6)^5+4^3 \wedge 2-1$
456216	$(9*8)*(((7/6)^*5432)-1)$	633340	$-98+(7+6)^5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$
456360	$(9*8)*(((7/6)^*5432)+1)$	633364	$-9*8+(7+6)^5+4^3 \wedge 2-1$
457546	$-9+(8+7^6)^*5*((4/3)^2-1)$	633366	$-9*8+(7+6)^5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$
457564	$9+(8+7^6)^*5*((4/3)^2-1)$	633419	$-9-8+(7+6)^5+4^3 \wedge 2-1$
468074	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4-3)/2-1$	633421	$-9-8+(7+6)^5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$
468125	$((98/(7^6))^*(5^4))^*321$	634751	$9/8*(7+6)^*(5^4-4^3)^2-1$
470350	$-9+8*(7^6+5-4^3)/2-1$	652326	$(98+76)*(((5^4)^3)^2)-1$
470748	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)/2+1$	652499	$((((98+76)^*(5^4))^3)^2)-1$
470842	$9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)/2+1$	652501	$((((98+76)^*(5^4))^3)^2)+1$
471446	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)/2-1$	652674	$(98+76)*(((5^4)^3)^2)+1$
471448	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)/2+1$	660674	$9/8*((765+4/3)^2)-1$
471464	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)/2-1$	661724	$9/8*(7^6-(5+4))^*(3+2)-1$
471466	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)/2+1$	661726	$9/8*(7^6-(5+4))^*(3+2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
679043	$-9+8*7^6+5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	925805	$(-987/((6/((5^4-4)+3)))-2))-1$
679045	$-9+8*7^6+5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	925806	$(-987/((6/((5^4-4)+3)))-2))*1$
679051	$9+8*7^6-5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	925807	$(-987/((6/((5^4-4)+3)))-2))+1$
679053	$9+8*7^6-5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	926200	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4*3^2)+1$
681250	$((987-6)*(5^4))*((3^4-2)+1)$	938646	$-9+87*6^5+4^3\Delta^2-1$
689312	$(9+8)*7^6-5*4^3\Delta^2-1$	938648	$-9+87*6^5+4^3\Delta^2+1$
689314	$(9+8)*7^6-5*4^3\Delta^2+1$	969759	$(98-7)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2-1$
697590	$-9+8*7*6^5+4^3\Delta^2-1$	969761	$(98-7)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2+1$
697592	$-9+8*7*6^5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	977696	$-9+87*6*(5^4*3-2)-1$
702071	$-9*(8-(7^6-5^4)/(3/2))-1$	977698	$-9+87*6*(5^4*3-2)+1$
702073	$-9*(8-(7^6-5^4)/(3/2))+1$	986960	$(9-(8/7+6))*((5+4)^(3^2))-1$
702215	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)/(3/2))-1$	995885	$(9+(8^7)/6))*54321$
702217	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)/(3/2))+1$	996542	$9^((8+7)/6)*((5+4)^(3^2))-1$
717548	$(987*((6/54)^3)-2))-1$	996544	$9^((8+7)/6)*((5+4)^(3^2))+1$
717550	$(987*((6/54)^3)-2))+1$	999516	$(9+8)*(7^6+5-4^3)/2+1$
718497	$(9-8/7-6)*((5^4-3)^(2-1))$	1008639	$(9+87)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2-1$
719502	$(987/((6/54)^\Delta^3))-21$	1008641	$(9+87)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2+1$
719520	$(987/((6/54)^\Delta^3))-(2+1)$	1018874	$9876*((5^4)/(3^2))-1$
719521	$((987/((6/54)^\Delta^3))-2)*1$	1020474	$(98+7^6)*((5+4-3^4(-2+1)))$
719525	$((987/((6/54)^\Delta^3))+2)*1$	1024877	$98*(7+6^5)+4^3\Delta^2-1$
719526	$((987/((6/54)^\Delta^3))+2)+1$	1024879	$98*(7+6^5)+4^3\Delta^2+1$
719544	$(987/((6/54)^\Delta^3))+21$	1028398	$((9^((8+7)/6)))-5)*4321$
720599	$9/8*((7/(6-5))^\Delta-4^3)^\Delta-2-1$	1028749	$((9876*(5^4))/(3^2))-1$
721496	$(987*((6/54)^\Delta-3)+2))-1$	1028751	$((9876*(5^4))/(3^2))+1$
721498	$(987*((6/54)^\Delta-3)+2))+1$	1038626	$9876*((5^4)/(3^2))+1$
736273	$98*(7-(-6*5^4-3)^2)-1$	1047630	$(-9+8^7-6-5^4*3)/2-1$
736275	$98*(7-(-6*5^4-3)^2)+1$	1047632	$(-9+8^7-6-5^4*3)/2+1$
737860	$(9+8-7)^\Delta+5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	1048328	$-9^((8+7)/6)-5+4^\Delta(3^2+1)$
737862	$(9+8-7)^\Delta+5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	1051218	$(9^((8+7)/6))*((5+4321))$
766322	$98*(7/(6-5^4))^\Delta(-3+2-1)$	1055362	$(98+7^6)*((5+4-3^4(-2-1)))$
767583	$(9*8-7)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2-1$	1055969	$-9*(8-(7^6+(-5^4+3)/2))-1$
784297	$(-98+7^6*5^4)/3+2+1$	1055971	$-9*(8-(7^6+(-5^4+3)/2))+1$
784316	$-9-(8-7^6*5^4)/3+2-1$	1056113	$9*(8-(-7^6+5^4-3)/2))-1$
786263	$(9+87)/((6/543)^\Delta^2))-1$	1056115	$9*(8-(-7^6+5^4-3)/2))+1$
786264	$((9+87)/((6/543)^\Delta^2))*1$	1061567	$-9*(8-(7^6+5^4-3)/2))-1$
786265	$((9+87)/((6/543)^\Delta^2))+1$	1061569	$-9*(8-(7^6+5^4-3)/2))+1$
786360	$(9+87)*((6/543)^\Delta-2))+1$	1061711	$9*(8-(-7^6+(-5^4+3)/2))-1$
796619	$9*(8+7^6)-5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	1061713	$9*(8-(-7^6+(-5^4+3)/2))+1$
796621	$9*(-8+7^6)-5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	1071608	$((9^((8+7)/6))+5)*4321$
796629	$9*(8+7^6)+5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	1078623	$(98+7)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2-1$
796631	$9*(8+7^6)+5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	1078625	$(98+7)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2+1$
796763	$9*(8+7^6)-5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	1087500	$((98+76)*(5^4))*((3^2)+1)$
796765	$9*(8+7^6)-5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	1109388	$(987*6)*((5^4)/3)-21$
796773	$9*(8+7^6)+5-4^3\Delta^2-1$	1138800	$(9-8/7*6)*((5+4)^(3^2))-1$
796775	$9*(8+7^6)+5-4^3\Delta^2+1$	1153438	$((98-76)/5)*((4^4(3^2))+1)$
820001	$(-9+8+7^6)/(5^4-4/32)+1$	1155930	$9-8*(7^6+5-4^3\Delta^2)+1$
821107	$(-98+((7^6)-54)/3))*21$	1155990	$-9-8*(7^6-5-4^3\Delta^2)-1$
821863	$(-98+((7^6)+54)/3))*21$	1155992	$-9-8*(7^6-5-4^3\Delta^2)+1$
823000	$9876/(((5/4)^\Delta-3)-(2^\Delta-1))$	1156008	$9-8*(7^6-5-4^3\Delta^2)-1$
825223	$(98+((7^6)-54)/3))*21$	1156010	$9-8*(7^6-5-4^3\Delta^2)+1$
836847	$(-987+(6^4(-5+(4^3))))*(2+1)$	1157712	$(9+8^7(7-6))^\Delta-4^3\Delta^2-1$
850303	$(-9-8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2-1$	1157714	$(9+8^7(7-6))^\Delta-4^3\Delta^2+1$
850305	$(-9-8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1183167	$9^\Delta(-8-(-7-6))*((5^4+3^\Delta(-2-1)))$
850339	$-9+(-8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2-1$	1192972	$-98-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2-1$
850341	$-9+(-8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1192974	$-98-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2+1$
850357	$9+(-8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2-1$	1192998	$-9*8-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2-1$
850359	$9+(-8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1193000	$-9*8-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2+1$
850383	$(-9+8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2-1$	1193053	$-9-8-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2-1$
850385	$(-9+8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1193055	$-9-8-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2+1$
850421	$-9+(8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1193069	$-9+8-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2-1$
850439	$9+(8+7^6)*5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1193073	$9-8-7^6+5*4^3\Delta^2+1$
863200	$98*((7/(654+3))^\Delta-2))-1$	1204301	$((-98+((7^6)*5))^\Delta*43)/21$
863297	$(98/((7/(654+3))^\Delta^2))-1$	1204497	$(-98+((7^6)*5)^\Delta*43)/21$
863298	$(98/((7/(654+3))^\Delta^2))*1$	1219383	$(987-6)*(((5^4)-3)^2)-1$
863299	$(98/((7/(654+3))^\Delta^2))+1$	1221345	$(987-6)*(((5^4)-3)^2)+1$
863396	$98*((7/(654+3))^\Delta-2))+1$	1231155	$(987-6)*(((5^4)+3)^2)-1$
876093	$(9*8*(7+6))^\Delta(-5+4+3)-2-1$	1233117	$(987-6)*(((5^4)+3)^2)+1$
876099	$(9*8*(7+6))^\Delta(-5+4+3)+2+1$	1234299	$(987+6)*(((5^4)-3)^2)-1$
876449	$(9*8+7)*6^5+4^3\Delta^2+1$	1236285	$(987+6)*(((5^4)-3)^2)+1$
907564	$((-98+((7^6)*54))^3)/21$	1246215	$(987+6)*(((5^4)+3)^2)-1$
907592	$((98+((7^6)*54))^3)/21$	1248201	$(987+6)*(((5^4)+3)^2)+1$
918995	$(9-8/7)*(6*(5+3))^\Delta^2-1$	1262148	$(9+8-7)^\Delta+5+4^3\Delta^2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1619497	$9*8*(-7+6*5^4*3^2)+1$	1889341	$-98+7*(6^5+4^3^2)-1$
1631112	$((-9+8^7+6)-5)*((4/3)^2-1)$	1889422	$-9-8+7*(6^5+4^3^2)-1$
1631126	$((9+8^7+6)-5)*((4/3)^2-1)$	1889458	$9+8+7*(6^5+4^3^2)+1$
1658070	$(9^*8/7-6)*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	1904407	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4*3^2)-1$
1711952	$(9-8^7/6^*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$	1924559	$(9^(-8+7)+6)^*5^4^3^2-1$
1712411	$-9-87*(6-5-4)^3^2-1$	1924561	$(9^(-8+7)+6)^*5^4^3^2+1$
1712413	$-9-87*(6-5-4)^3^2+1$	1926535	$9*((8*(7-65)+4/3)^2-1)$
1712429	$9-87*(6-5-4)^3^2-1$	1926553	$9*((8*(7-65)+4/3)^2+1)$
1712431	$9-87*(6-5-4)^3^2+1$	1952341	$-9*87+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1764671	$(-9-8+7^6*5-4)*3^2+1$	1952343	$-9*87+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1764799	$(9+8+7^6*5+4)*3^2-1$	1952438	$-98*7+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1780477	$-98-7*(6^5-4^3^2)-1$	1952440	$-98*7+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1780479	$-98-7*(6^5-4^3^2)+1$	1952620	$-9*8^7+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1780578	$9-8-7*(6^5-4^3^2)+1$	1952622	$-9*8^7+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1808064	$(9*876)*(((5^4)/3)+21)$	1953019	$-98-7+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1811097	$9*((8*76)+((5^4)*321))$	1953021	$-98-7+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1827240	$9+8^7-6^5-4^3^2-1$	1953628	$9*8^7+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1827242	$9+8^7-6^5-4^3^2+1$	1953630	$9*8^7+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1834480	$-9*8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$	1953810	$98*7+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1834482	$-9*8-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$	1953812	$98*7+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1834535	$-9-8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$	1953907	$9*87+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
1834537	$-9-8-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$	1953909	$9*87+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
1834551	$-9+8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$	1960919	$(-9+(8+7^6)*5)*((4/3)+2)-1$
1834555	$9-8-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$	1960921	$(-9+(8+7^6)*5)*((4/3)+2)+1$
1834569	$9+8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$	1965199	$(9+8)*(-7^6(-6+5+4)+3)^2-1$
1834571	$9+8-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$	1965201	$(9+8)*(-7^6(-6+5+4)+3)^2+1$
1834624	$9*8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$	2027872	$9876*((5^4)/3)-(2+1)$
1834626	$9*8-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$	2030057	$9*(87*((6^5-4)/3+2))-1$
1834814	$9+8-7*(6^5-4^3^2)-1$	2030059	$9*(87*((6^5-4)/3+2))+1$
1834816	$9+8-7*(6^5-4^3^2)+1$	2035171	$(9+8)*7^6(-6+5+4)+3)^2-1$
1834858	$-9*8-7*(6+5-4^3^2)-1$	2035173	$(9+8)*7^6(-6+5+4)+3)^2+1$
1834860	$-9*8-7*(6+5-4^3^2)+1$	2037747	$(9876*((5^4)/3)-2))-1$
1834909	$-98+7^6(6-5)^4^3^2-1$	2037748	$(9876*((5^4)/3)-2))^*1$
1834911	$-98+7^6(6-5)^4^3^2+1$	2037749	$(9876*((5^4)/3)-2))+1$
1834913	$-9-8-7*(6+5-4^3^2)-1$	2052562	$9876*((5^4)/3)-(2^(-1))$
1834915	$-9-8-7*(6+5-4^3^2)+1$	2062438	$9876*((5^4)/3)+(2^(-1))$
1834928	$-9*8-7*(6-5-4^3^2)-1$	2077251	$(9876*((5^4)/3)+2))-1$
1834937	$-9*8+7^6(6-5)^4^3^2+1$	2077252	$(9876*((5^4)/3)+2))^*1$
1834949	$9+8-7*(6+5-4^3^2)+1$	2077253	$(9876*((5^4)/3)+2))+1$
1834983	$-9-8-7*(6-5-4^3^2)-1$	2085904	$-9+8^7-6*(5^4*3-2)-1$
1834985	$-9-8-7*(6-5-4^3^2)+1$	2085906	$-9+8^7-6*(5^4*3-2)+1$
1834986	$9+8^7-6^*5-4^3^2-1$	2087128	$9876*((5^4)/3+2)+1$
1834990	$-9-8+7^6(6-5)^4^3^2-1$	2095896	$-9+8^7-6*5^4/3+2+1$
1834992	$-9-8+7^6(6-5)^4^3^2+1$	2098408	$9+8^7+6*5^4/3-2-1$
1835004	$9*8-7*(6+5-4^3^2)+1$	2100182	$-9+8*(76*5+4^3^2)-1$
1835030	$-9+8^7+6*5-4^3^2+1$	2100184	$-9+8*(76*5+4^3^2)+1$
1835063	$-9+8^7+65-4^3^2-1$	2108404	$-9+8^7+6*(5^4*3+2)-1$
1835065	$-9+8^7+65-4^3^2+1$	2116612	$-98-(((7^6)-54)*(3-21))$
1835067	$-9-8+7*(6+5+4^3^2)-1$	2116808	$98-(((7^6)-54)*(3-21))$
1835220	$9-8+7*(6*5+4^3^2)+1$	2117600	$9*8*(7^6-5)/4+3^2-1$
1835445	$-9-8+7*(65+4^3^2)-1$	2117602	$9*8*(7^6-5)/4+3^2+1$
1835447	$-9-8+7*(65+4^3^2)+1$	2117668	$-9-8+7^6*5^4/3+2+1$
1839366	$((987-6)*(5^4))-3*(2+1)$	2117678	$-9+8+7^6*5^4/3-2-1$
1839384	$((987-6)*(5^4))+3*(2+1)$	2118556	$-98-(((7^6)+54)*(3-21))$
1849638	$-987/((6/(((5^4)-4)-3)^2))+1$	2118752	$98-(((7^6)+54)*(3-21))$
1850104	$9876*((5^4)/3)-21$	2201680	$(9-(-8/7+6))*((5+4)^(3*2))-1$
1850624	$(987/(((6+(5^4-4))/3)-2))-1$	2221183	$-9+8*(7^6+(5^4)^(3+2))-1$
1850626	$(987/(((6+(5^4-4))/3)-2))+1$	2239568	$9+8*(7+6^6(-5+4^3)+2)-1$
1851612	$-987/((6/(((5^4)-4)+3)^2))-1$	2239570	$9+8*(7+6^6(-5+4^3)+2)+1$
1852892	$9/8*(7^6-5)*(4^3+2)-1$	2251902	$-9+8*7^6+5*4^3^2-1$
1852894	$9/8*(7^6-5)*(4^3+2)+1$	2251904	$-9+8*7^6+5*4^3^2+1$
1861875	$((987+6)*(5^4))^3*(2-1)$	2264896	$9876*((5^4)/3)+21$
1861884	$((987+6)*(5^4))^3*(2+1)$	2277600	$(9*8/7-6)*((5+4)^(3*2))-1$
1864559	$-9*8*(7-6^5)*(4/3+2)-1$	2280402	$-9*((8765-(4^4(3^2))))+1$
1864561	$-9*8*(7-6^5)*(4/3+2)+1$	2280410	$(-9*(8765-(4^4(3^2))))-1$
1869335	$9*(-8-7*6^5+4^3^2)-1$	2280412	$(-9*(8765-(4^4(3^2))))+1$
1869337	$9*(-8-7*6^5+4^3^2)+1$	2280420	$-9*(8765-(4^4(3^2))+1)$
1869479	$9*(8-7*6^5+4^3^2)-1$	2285567	$9*8^6(-7+6+5)*(4^3-2)-1$
1869481	$9*(8-7*6^5+4^3^2)+1$	2285569	$9*8^6(-7+6+5)*(4^3-2)+1$
1875028	$9*8*(7/6+5^4(4+3))/(2+1)$	2342757	$-987+(6*((5^4(4^3/2))))-1$
1879137	$-9+(-8/7+6)*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	2342762	$(-987+(6*(5^4(4^3/2))))-1$
1879155	$9+(-8/7+6)*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	2342764	$(-987+(6*(5^4(4^3/2))))+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2342769	$-987+(6*((5^(4*(3/2))))+1))$	2822182	$-98+(((7^6)-54)*(3+21))$
2344731	$987+(6*((5^(4*(3/2))))-1))$	2822378	$98+(((7^6)-54)*(3+21))$
2344736	$(987+(6*(5^(4*(3/2)))))-1$	2822423	$9*8*((7^6-54)/3+2)-1$
2344738	$(987+(6*(5^(4*(3/2)))))+1$	2822425	$9*8*((7^6-54)/3+2)+1$
2344743	$987+(6*((5^(4*(3/2))))+1))$	2823368	$-9+8*((7^6-5-4)*3+2)+1$
2351366	$9*(-876-5+4^3*2)-1$	2823464	$9+8*(7^6-5)*(4-3+2)-1$
2351368	$9*(-876-5+4^3*2)+1$	2823466	$9+8*(7^6-5)*(4-3+2)+1$
2351456	$9*(-876+5+4^3*2)-1$	2823686	$-9+8*(7^6+5)*(4-3+2)-1$
2351458	$9*(-876+5+4^3*2)+1$	2823688	$-9+8*(7^6+5)*(4-3+2)+1$
2352267	$((-98+((7^6)*5))^4)-321$	2823704	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(4-3+2)-1$
2352338	$9*(-8-765+4^3*2)-1$	2823706	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(4-3+2)+1$
2352340	$9*(-8-765+4^3*2)+1$	2824727	$9*8*((7^6+54)/3-2)-1$
2352586	$(-98+7^6*5)^4-3+2-1$	2824729	$9*8*((7^6+54)/3-2)+1$
2352619	$(-98+7^6*5)^4+32-1$	2824774	$-98+(((7^6)+54)*(3+21))$
2352621	$(-98+7^6*5)^4+32+1$	2824970	$98+(((7^6)+54)*(3+21))$
2352661	$(-9*8+7^6*5)^4-32+1$	2825015	$9*8*((7^6+54)/3+2)-1$
2352688	$(-9*8+7^6*5)^4-3-2+1$	2825017	$9*8*((7^6+54)/3+2)+1$
2352943	$-9-(8-7^6*5)^4+3+2-1$	2847311	$(-9+87)^(6-5+4)*3^2-1$
2353017	$9-(8-7^6*5)^4-3-2+1$	2847313	$(-9+87)^(6-5+4)*3^2+1$
2353374	$(98+7^6*5)^4+3-2+1$	2849111	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4^3*2)-1$
2353693	$((98+((7^6)*5))^4)+321$	2849113	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4^3*2)+1$
2358512	$9*(-87^6(6-5)+4^3*2)-1$	2850820	$98*((((7^6)-5)/4)-321)$
2358514	$9*(-87^6(6-5)+4^3*2)+1$	2851065	$98*((((7^6)+5)/4)-321)$
2358944	$9*(8-7^6-5+4^3*2)-1$	2881957	$((98*((7^6)-5))/4)-321$
2358946	$9*(8-7^6-5+4^3*2)+1$	2882202	$((98*((7^6)+5))/4)-321$
2359034	$9*(8-7^6+5+4^3*2)-1$	2882586	$-987+((6+5)*(4^3*2))-1$
2359036	$9*(8-7^6+5+4^3*2)+1$	2882596	$(-987+((6+5)*(4^3*2))))-1$
2359061	$9*(-8-7-6-5+4^3*2)-1$	2882598	$(-987+((6+5)*(4^3*2))))+1$
2359063	$9*(-8-7-6-5+4^3*2)+1$	2882599	$((98*((7^6)-5))/4)+321$
2359160	$9*(-8-7^6(6-5)+4^3*2)-1$	2882608	$-987+((6+5)*(4^3*2))+1$
2359162	$9*(-8-7^6(6-5)+4^3*2)+1$	2882844	$((98*((7^6)+5))/4)+321$
2359556	$9*(-8+7^6-5+4^3*2)-1$	2884560	$987+((6+5)*((4^3*2))-1))$
2359558	$9*(-8+7^6-5+4^3*2)+1$	2884570	$(987+((6+5)*(4^3*2))))-1$
2359565	$9^8(8-7)*(6^5+4^3*2)-1$	2884572	$(987+((6+5)*(4^3*2))))+1$
2359567	$9^8(8-7)*(6^5+4^3*2)+1$	2884582	$987+((6+5)*((4^3*2))+1))$
2359646	$9*(-8+7^6+5+4^3*2)-1$	2887083	$((987-6)^(6-5+4+3))^*(2+1)$
2359648	$9*(-8+7^6+5+4^3*2)+1$	2898917	$((98-76)^5)/((4/3)^2)-1$
2359808	$9*(-8+(7+6)^5+4^3*2)-1$	2898919	$((98-76)^5)/((4/3)^2)+1$
2359810	$9*(-8+(7+6)^5+4^3*2)+1$	2913736	$98*((((7^6)-5)/4)+321)$
2366108	$9*(-8+765+4^3*2)-1$	2913981	$98*((((7^6)+5)/4)+321)$
2366110	$9*(-8+765+4^3*2)+1$	2922507	$(987^6(((6-5)+4)-3))^*(2+1)$
2419704	$9*8*((7^6(6-5+4)-3)^2-1)$	2930943	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4/3))^2-1$
2419848	$9*8*((7^6(6-5+4)-3)^2+1)$	2930945	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4/3))^2+1$
2420568	$9*8*((7^6(6-5+4)+3)^2-1)$	2958147	$((987+6)^(6-5+4+3))^*(2+1)$
2420712	$9*8*((7^6(6-5+4)+3)^2+1)$	2999815	$9*((8*(7+65)+4/3)^2-1)$
2428496	$9*(-87+6^5+4^3*2)-1$	2999833	$9*((8*(7+65)+4/3)^2+1)$
2428498	$9*(-87+6^5+4^3*2)+1$	3038294	$-9+8*(7^6-5+4^3*2)-1$
2428775	$9*(-8*7+6^5+4^3*2)-1$	3038296	$-9+8*(7^6-5+4^3*2)+1$
2428777	$9*(-8*7+6^5+4^3*2)+1$	3038374	$-9+8*(7^6+5+4^3*2)-1$
2438172	$9*((8765+(4^3*2)))-1$	3038376	$-9+8*(7^6+5+4^3*2)+1$
2438190	$9*((8765+(4^3*2)))+1$	3041969	$-98+7^6*543/21$
2444192	$(-9+(8/(7+6))^-5)^4*(3^2+1)$	3042050	$(-9-8)+(((7^6)*543)/21)$
2460342	$(9*(8+7))^6(-6+5+4)-32-1$	3042066	$(-9+8)+(((7^6)*543)/21)$
2460344	$(9*(8+7))^6(-6+5+4)-32+1$	3042068	$(9-8)+(((7^6)*543)/21)$
2460348	$(9*(8+7))^6(-6+5+4)-3^2(2+1)$	3042084	$(9+8)+(((7^6)*543)/21)$
2460406	$(9*(8+7))^6(-6+5+4)+32-1$	3042165	$98+7^6*543/21$
2460408	$(9*(8+7))^6(-6+5+4)+32+1$	3091188	$9876*((((5^4)+3)/2)-1)$
2470153	$-98+(((7^6)-(54/3))^2)$	3111595	$-98+(7^6)^5(-5-(4-3))-2-1$
2471105	$98+(((7^6)+(54/3))^2)$	3111601	$-98+(7^6)^5(-5-(4-3))+2+1$
2539475	$98*(-7+6^5*(4/3+2))+1$	3137259	$(-9+8*7^6-5)^*(4/3+2)-1$
2621447	$9*((8^7/6^5+4)/(3^2))+1$	3137261	$(-9+8*7^6-5)^*(4/3+2)+1$
2647142	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(4-3/2))-1$	3142928	$9*(8^7/6+(-5^4+3)/2)-1$
2647144	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(4-3/2))+1$	3142930	$9*(8^7/6+(-5^4+3)/2)+1$
2647214	$9/8*(7^6+5)^4*(3+2)-1$	3148526	$9*(8^7/6+(5^4-3)/2)-1$
2647216	$9/8*(7^6+5)^4*(3+2)+1$	3148528	$9*(8^7/6+(5^4-3)/2)+1$
2693120	$9^8+7-(6+5-4)^3*2-1$	3176189	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3-2)-1$
2693122	$9^8+7-(6+5-4)^3*2+1$	3176191	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3-2)+1$
2745344	$(98*((7^6)*5)+43)/21$	3176225	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3+2)-1$
2763441	$-9+(8/7+6)^*(5^4-3)^2-1$	3176227	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3+2)+1$
2792286	$((9/8)*((7^6)+543))^2-1$	3176371	$9*(8+(7^6-5-4)*3+2)+1$
2808666	$(-98/7)^*(6-((5^4)*321))$	3176405	$9*(-8+(7^6-5+4)*3-2)-1$
2808834	$(98/7)^*(6+((5^4)*321))$	3176407	$9*(-8+(7^6-5+4)*3-2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
22952678	$98^*(((7^6)-543)^2)-1$	25698148	$98^*(((76+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
22952874	$98^*(((7^6)-543)^2)+1$	25727254	$98^*(((76^5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$
23058883	$((98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5))/4)-321$	25727351	$(98^*(((76^5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))))-1$
23059525	$((98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5))/4)+321$	25727353	$(98^*(((76^5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))))+1$
23165534	$98^*(((7^6)+543)^2)-1$	25727450	$98^*(((76^5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
23165730	$98^*(((7^6)+543)^2)+1$	25764984	$98^*((765+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$
23294429	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-32))-1$	25765180	$98^*((765+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
23294431	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-32))+1$	25999323	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3^2)-1$
23652700	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^2-1$	25999325	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3^2)+1$
23652702	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^2+1$	26000493	$((9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3^2)-1$
24336527	$-9+(((8^*(7^6))^*543)/21)$	26000495	$((9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3^2)+1$
24336545	$9+(((8^*(7^6))^*543)/21)$	26007353	$9^{\wedge}8-7-65^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1$
24405760	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3))/2-1$	26007355	$9^{\wedge}8-7-65^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1$
24405762	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3))/2+1$	26007367	$9^{\wedge}8+7-65^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1$
24504585	$(98^*(((7/6)^*54)^{\wedge}3))-21$	26007369	$9^{\wedge}8+7-65^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1$
24504627	$(98^*(((7/6)^*54)^{\wedge}3))+21$	26302563	$((987^{\wedge}(6/(5+4)))^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
24928749	$98^*(7-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	26352246	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3^2)-1$
24928751	$98^*(7-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	26352248	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3^2)+1$
25411103	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	26451473	$98^*(-7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
25411105	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	26451475	$98^*(-7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
25412162	$-9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)/2-1$	26647996	$((9^{\wedge}8)^*(7+6))+543/21$
25412164	$-9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)/2+1$	26872006	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-43^2-1$
25412168	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	26872008	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-43^2+1$
25412170	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	26873827	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4-3^2-1$
25412177	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*54-3)/2-1$	26873885	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4+3^2+1$
25412179	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*54-3)/2+1$	26875704	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43^2-1$
25412198	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	26875706	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43^2+1$
25412200	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	27378531	$-9^*(8-(((7^6)^*543)/21))$
25412204	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)/2-1$	27378675	$9^*(8+(((7^6)^*543)/21))$
25412206	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)/2+1$	27529793	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^2))-1$
25412318	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	27529795	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^2))+1$
25412320	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	28235750	$-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3/2-1$
25517019	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4^*3)^2)-1$	28235752	$-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3/2+1$
25517021	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4^*3)^2)+1$	28619377	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25529760	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^2)-1$	28619379	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25529762	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^2)+1$	28661525	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25529904	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^2)-1$	28661527	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25529906	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^2)+1$	28697303	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25582053	$987^*(((6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3)+2))-1$	28697305	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25583039	$((987^*(6^{\wedge}5))^*(4/3)+2))-1$	28697673	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25583041	$((987^*(6^{\wedge}5))^*(4/3)+2))+1$	28697675	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25584027	$987^*(((6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3)+2))+1$	28697777	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7-6)^*54)/(3/2)-1$
25615044	$-98^*((765-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	28697799	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6-5-4))/(3/2)-1$
25615141	$(-98^*(765-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$	28697801	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6-5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25615143	$(-98^*(765-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	28697803	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6-5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25615240	$-98^*(765-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1))$	28697825	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25628943	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3+21$	28697827	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25652774	$-98^*((76^5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	28697829	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-5-4))/(3/2)+1$
25652871	$(-98^*((76^5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$	28697953	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25652873	$(-98^*((76^5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	28697955	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25652970	$-98^*((76^5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1))$	28698323	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25682076	$-98^*((76+5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	28698325	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25682173	$(-98^*((76+5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$	28734101	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25682175	$(-98^*((76+5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	28734103	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25682272	$-98^*((76+5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1))$	28776249	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$
25683055	$98^*(-7-65+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	28776251	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$
25683057	$98^*(-7-65+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	28822779	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3/2)-1$
25683153	$(-98^*(76-(5+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))))-1$	28822781	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3/2)+1$
25683155	$(-98^*(76-(5+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))))+1$	28835818	$(98-76)^*(5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))-1$
25683252	$-98^*(76-((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)))$	28835839	$((98-76)^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2))-1$
25690013	$-98^*((7-6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	28835841	$((98-76)^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1$
25690015	$-98^*((7-6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	28835862	$(98-76)^*(5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))+1$
25690209	$98^*((7-6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	28835950	$((98-76)^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1$
25690211	$98^*((7-6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	29164138	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^2-1$
25695795	$98^*(-7+65+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	29164140	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^2+1$
25695797	$98^*(-7+65+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	29381850	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
25696972	$98^*((76-5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))-1$	29646287	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)/2-1$
25697069	$(98^*((76-5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$	29646289	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)/2+1$
25697071	$(98^*((76-5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	29647534	$(98^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*54)-3))/21$
25697952	$98^*((76+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2)))-1$	29647562	$(98^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*54+3))/21$
25698049	$(98^*((76+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))-1$	29648807	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)/2-1$
25698051	$(98^*((76+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	29648809	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)/2+1$

Integer

Genuine CSR

140823795 (-98+((7^6)*(54+3)))*21
 140825755 -98+(((7^6)*(54+3))*21)
 140825951 98+(((7^6)*(54+3))*21)
 140827911 (98+((7^6)*(54+3)))*21
 147110928 (9+8)/7*((6^5+4+3)^2-1)
 148056254 -9^8+((7-6+5)*4)^(3^2)-1
 148056256 -9^8+((7-6+5)*4)^(3^2)+1
 148237667 -9*(8+7^6*5*(4-32))-1
 148237669 -9*(8+7^6*5*(4-32))+1
 148237811 9*(8-7^6*5*(4-32))-1
 148237813 9*(8-7^6*5*(4-32))+1
 150633998 9^8*(7-(6/54)^3)/2-1
 150634000 9^8*(7-(6/54)^3)/2+1
 150652096 (((9^8)-7)/6)-543)*21
 150652145 (((9^8)+7)/6)-543)*21
 150663477 (9^8-7-6)*(5+4*3)/2-1
 150663479 (9^8-7-6)*(5+4*3)/2+1
 150674902 (((9^8)-7)/6)+543)*21
 150674951 (((9^8)+7)/6)+543)*21
 151023438 (-98+(((7^6)-5)*4))*321
 151036278 (-98+(((7^6)+5)*4))*321
 151086354 98+(((7^6)-5)*4))*321
 151093255 9*(8^(-7-(-6-5))+4/3)^2-1)
 151093264 9*(8^(-7+6+5)+4/3)^2+1
 151093273 9*(8^(-7-(-6-5))+4/3)^2+1)
 151099194 (98+(((7^6)+5)*4))*321
 152470752 (-98+((7^6)*54))*321
 152475456 (98+((7^6)*54))*321
 153691424 9*(8+7)^6*(5^(-4+3))/2-1
 153691426 9*(8+7)^6*(5^(-4+3))/2+1
 154649330 -9^8*(76/54-3-2)-1
 154649332 -9^8*(76/54-3-2)+1
 155788134 (((9^8)*76)+(54/3))/21
 155788159 (((9^8)*76)+543)/21
 155885625 (((9*87)-6)*(5^4))*321
 156300003 ((987*(6+((5*4)/3)))^2)-1
 156300004 ((987*(6+((5*4)/3)))^2)*1
 156300005 ((987*(6+((5*4)/3)))^2)+1
 157672116 (9*876)*(((5^4)*32)-1)
 157687884 (9*876)*(((5^4)*32)+1)
 157767236 9*(-8+7^6*(5+(4*3)^2))-1
 157767238 9*(-8+7^6*(5+(4*3)^2))+1
 158293125 (((9*87)+6)*(5^4))*321
 159380502 -9-8*76*(5-4^3)^2-1
 159380504 -9-8*76*(5-4^3)^2+1
 159380520 9-8*76*(5-4^3)^2-1
 159380522 9-8*76*(5-4^3)^2+1
 159386582 -9+8*76*(5+4^3)^2-1
 159386584 -9+8*76*(5+4^3)^2+1
 161425154 (-9^8+7+6)*(5/4-3-2)-1
 161425156 (-9^8+7+6)*(5/4-3-2)+1
 162760984 (9^8+7*(6+5-4+3))/2-1
 162760986 (9^8+7*(6+5-4+3))/2+1
 164088871 (((9/(87*6))^5)/4)-321
 164089513 (((9/(87*6))^5)/4)+321
 164107541 9^8+7^6*(5+4^3+2))-1
 164107543 9^8+7^6*(5+4^3+2))+1
 169921865 -9+87*(6-5+4)^3^2-1
 169921867 -9+87*(6-5+4)^3^2+1
 169921883 9+87*(6-5+4)^3^2-1
 169921885 9+87*(6-5+4)^3^2+1
 171969155 (9^8-7*6^5)*4^(3-2)-1
 171969157 (9^8-7*6^5)*4^(3-2)+1
 172156268 ((9^8)-7654)*((3+2)-1)
 172182563 ((-9^8)*(7-(6+5)))-4321
 172186575 (9^8-7*(6+5))*4*(3-2)-1
 172186577 (9^8-7*(6+5))*4*(3-2)+1
 172187191 (9^8+7*(6+5))*4*(3-2)-1
 172187193 (9^8+7*(6+5))*4*(3-2)+1
 172191205 ((-9^8)*(7-(6+5)))+4321
 172217500 ((9^8)+7654)*((3+2)-1)
 173649851 9*(-8+7^6*(54^3+2))-1

Integer

Genuine CSR

173649853 9*(-8+7^6*(54^3+2))+1
 174120519 9*8/7^6-5*(4+3^2)-1
 174120521 9*8/7^6-5*(4+3^2)+1
 174849381 (-98+765)*((4^(3^2))-1)
 174850047 ((-98+765)*(4^(3^2)))-1
 174850049 ((-98+765)*(4^(3^2)))+1
 174850715 (-98+765)*((4^(3^2))+1)
 177782661 (9*(8*(7^6))-543))*21
 177884640 9*8*(7^6+5-4)^3*(2+1)
 177885936 9*8*(7^6+5-4)^3*(2+1)
 177987915 (9*(8*(7^6))+543))*21
 179523141 (((-9-8)^7+65)*((4/3)^2-1))
 179523169 (((-9-8)^7+6)-5)*((4/3)^2-1)
 180795006 (((9^8)-76)/5)-43)*21
 180796812 (((9^8)-76)/5)+43)*21
 184941467 9^8*(7-6/54)/3+2-1
 184941469 9^8*(7-6/54)/3+2+1
 186442599 (98-((7^6)*5))*4-321
 186473567 -98-(((7^6)*5)*(4-321))
 186473763 98-(((7^6)*5)*(4-321))
 186504731 (-98-((7^6)*5))*4-321
 186883604 9^8-7*(6*5)^4*(3+2)-1
 186883606 9^8-7*(6*5)^4*(3+2)+1
 189405238 (9^8-76)/5*(43-21)
 189724416 ((9^8)*((76/54)+3))-21
 189724458 (9^8)*((76/54)+3)+21
 189843719 (-9+(8+7)^6*5)*(4/3+2)-1
 189843721 (-9+(8+7)^6*5)*(4/3+2)+1
 190840836 (9+8+7)^6+5-4^3^2-1
 190840838 (9+8+7)^6+5-4^3^2+1
 191147775 (-98+((7^6)*5))*4+321
 191179527 -98+(((7^6)*5)*(4+321))
 191179723 98+(((7^6)*5)*(4+321))
 191211475 (98+((7^6)*5))*4+321
 191649927 (-98+((7^6)*543))*2+1
 191650515 (98+((7^6)*543))*2+1
 193180823 (9^8-7^6)*(5-(4-3)/2)-1
 193180825 (9^8-7^6)*(5-(4-3)/2)+1
 193706802 (((-9^8)+765)/4)*(3-21)
 193713687 (((-9^8)-765)/4)*(3-21)
 194239664 (9^8+7^6)*(5-(4-3)/2)-1
 194239666 (9^8+7^6)*(5-(4-3)/2)+1
 196941388 (-98+((7^6)*54))*32-1
 196944328 -98+(((7^6)*54)*(32-1))
 196944524 98+(((7^6)*54)*(32-1))
 196947464 (98+((7^6)*54))*32-1
 198003267 (9+8)*7^6*(5^4*(3+2)-1)
 199148552 9+(8/(7*6))^5*(5-4-3)^2-1
 200539297 -98+(765*((4^(3^2))-1))
 200539493 98+(765*((4^(3^2))-1))
 200540087 -9*8+765*4^3^2-1
 200540089 -9*8+765*4^3^2+1
 200540162 9-8+765*4^3^2+1
 200540827 -98+(765*((4^(3^2))+1))
 200541023 98+(765*((4^(3^2))+1))
 202003333 (9+8)*7^6*(5^4*(3+2)+1)
 207359895 -98-7+(6*5^4)^(3+2)-1
 207530778 98*(((7^6)*54)/3)-21
 207532815 (((98*(7^6))*54)/3)-21
 207532857 (((98*(7^6))*54)/3)+21
 207534894 98*(((7^6)*54)/3)+21
 209279225 (9^8-7^6)*(5-4^(-3/2))-1
 209279227 (9^8-7^6)*(5-4^(-3/2))+1
 209647284 (-98+((7^6)*54))*32+1
 209650420 -98+(((7^6)*54)*(32+1))
 209650616 98+(((7^6)*54)*(32+1))
 209653752 (98+((7^6)*54))*32+1
 211307030 (9^8-(7*6*5)^4)*-3^2-2-1
 211307032 (9^8-(7*6*5)^4)*-3^2+2-1
 212722224 9*((8*7-(6+5)^4)/3)^2-1
 212722226 9*((8*7-(6+5)^4)/3)^2+1
 214089742 ((9+8)^7*6-5)/(4*3-2^2-1)

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
237180523	$(-9*8^7\wedge 6-5)*(4-32)-1$	258280697	$(9\wedge 8+7)*6+5*(4\wedge 3+2)-1$
237180525	$(-9*8^7\wedge 6-5)*(4-32)+1$	258280699	$(9\wedge 8+7)*6+5*(4\wedge 3+2)+1$
237181643	$-9*(8^7\wedge 6+5)*(4-32)-1$	258284647	$((9\wedge 8)*((7-6)+5))+4321$
237181645	$-9*(8^7\wedge 6+5)*(4-32)+1$	258284916	$((9\wedge 8)+765)/4*(3+21)$
238085505	$9/8*(7-(-6\wedge(5+4)+3)*21)$	258422541	$(987-(6/5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
241061631	$(9\wedge 8-7+6)/(5/(-4+32))-1$	258472998	$((987-6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
241061633	$(9\wedge 8-7+6)/(5/(-4+32))+1$	258473983	$((987-6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
241695846	$(987-65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$	258473985	$((987-6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
241696767	$((987-65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1))$	258474970	$((987-6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
241696769	$(987-65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$	258670986	$-987*((65-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2)))+1)$
241697690	$(987-65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$	258671972	$(-987*(65-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
242121264	$((98*(7\wedge 6))-54/3)*21$	258671974	$(-987*(65-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
242122020	$((98*(7\wedge 6))+54/3)*21$	258672960	$-987*(65-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
242518329	$9/((87*(6-543))\wedge 2)\wedge -1$	258705531	$-987*((6*5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
247141711	$-9\wedge((8-7)*6)-(-5\wedge 4-3)\wedge(2+1)$	258706517	$(-987*((6*5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
247165834	$-9+(8/(7\wedge(6+5)+4-3))\wedge(-2+1)$	258706519	$(-987*((6*5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
247165852	$9+(8/(7\wedge(6+5)+4-3))\wedge(-2+1)$	258707505	$-987*((6*5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
247518570	$(9\wedge 8-7-6)*(5/4^3+2)-1$	258724284	$-987*((6+5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
247518572	$(9\wedge 8-7-6)*(5/4^3+2)+1$	258725270	$(-987*((6+5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
249600546	$(9-87)*(-6-(5^4)\wedge(3+2))-1$	258725272	$(-987*((6+5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
250870851	$(987-(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$	258726258	$-987*((6+5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
250871807	$((987-(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1))$	258734154	$-987*((6-(5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1)$
250871809	$((987-(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$	258735140	$(-987*(6-(5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2)))))-1$
250872765	$(987-(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$	258735142	$(-987*(6-(5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2)))))+1$
251060229	$-987*((6\wedge 5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$	258738102	$987*((6-5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
251061215	$(-987*((6\wedge 5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$	258745998	$987*((6+5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
251061217	$(-987*((6\wedge 5)-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$	258747972	$987*((6+5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
251062203	$-987*((6\wedge 5)-((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$	258764751	$987*((6*5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
252765128	$98/((76-(54\wedge 3))\wedge 2)\wedge -1$	258765737	$(987*((6*5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
252965916	$9\wedge((8-7)+6)*(54-3\wedge 2-1)$	258765739	$(987*((6*5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
253491357	$(-98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432-1$	258766725	$987*((6*5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
253533497	$-98+(((7\wedge 6)^5)*432-1)$	258799296	$987*((65+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
253533693	$98+(((7\wedge 6)^5)*432-1)$	258801270	$987*((65+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
253575833	$(98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432-1$	258997284	$((987+6)-5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
254003556	$((9+8)*7\wedge 6-5)*(4\wedge 3^2-1)$	258998271	$((987+6)-5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
254004826	$((9+8)*7\wedge 6+5)*(4\wedge 3^2-1)$	258998273	$((987+6)-5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
254028798	$9\wedge((8-7)+6)*(54+3\wedge 2-1)$	258999260	$((987+6)-5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
254079503	$((-98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432-1)$	259051689	$(987+(6/5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
254079504	$((-98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432)*1$	260303034	$(-987-6)*((5-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
254079505	$((-98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432)+1$	260305020	$(-987-6)*((5-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$
254164175	$((98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432)-1$	260312964	$(987+6)*((5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
254164176	$((98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432)*1$	260314950	$(987+6)*((5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
254164177	$((98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432)+1$	261618714	$((987+6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
254667651	$(-98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432+1$	261619711	$((987+6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
254709987	$-98+(((7\wedge 6)^5)*432+1)$	261619713	$((987+6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
254710183	$98+(((7\wedge 6)^5)*432+1)$	261620710	$((987+6)+5)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
254752519	$(98+((7\wedge 6)^5))*432+1$	262531854	$9\wedge((8-7)+6)*(54-3\wedge 2+1)$
255851568	$(987-(6+5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$	262933532	$(-9\wedge 8+(7*6)\wedge 5)*(4-3+2)-1$
255852543	$((987-(6+5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1))$	262933534	$(-9\wedge 8+(7*6)\wedge 5)*(4-3+2)+1$
255852545	$((987-(6+5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$	265142853	$(9+8/7-6)*((5^4)\wedge(3^2)-1)$
255853520	$(987-(6+5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$	266410053	$987*((6\wedge 5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
256686002	$9\wedge 8*((7-6)/-54+3)*2-1$	266411039	$(987*((6\wedge 5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
256686004	$9\wedge 8*((7-6)/-54+3)*2+1$	266411041	$(987*((6\wedge 5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$
257025328	$(987*6)*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2)-1$	266412027	$987*((6\wedge 5)+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
257030263	$987*((6*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2))-1)$	266599431	$(987+(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
257031249	$((987*6)*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2))-1$	266600447	$((987+(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1))$
257031250	$((987*6)*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2))*1$	266600449	$((987+(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$
257031251	$((987*6)*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2))+1$	266601465	$(987+(6*5))*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1)$
257032237	$987*((6*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2))+1)$	269041924	$(9\wedge 8-7-6)*(5/4+3+2)-1$
257037172	$(987*6)*(((5\wedge 4)/3)\wedge 2)+1$	269041926	$(9\wedge 8-7-6)*(5/4+3+2)+1$
257157378	$(-987+6)*((5-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$	271061727	$(9*(8/7\wedge 6-5)-4)*32-1$
257159340	$(-987+6)*((5-(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$	271061729	$(9*(8/7\wedge 6-5)-4)*32+1$
257167188	$(987-6)*((5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1))$	271061983	$(9*(8/7\wedge 6-5)+4)*32-1$
257169150	$(987-6)*((5+(4\wedge(3\wedge 2))+1))$	271061985	$(9*(8/7\wedge 6-5)+4)*32+1$
258003612	$((9+8)*7\wedge 6-5)*(4\wedge 3^2+1)$	271063304	$9+8*7\wedge 6*(5+4)*32-1$
258004902	$((9+8)*7\wedge 6+5)*(4\wedge 3^2+1)$	271063306	$9+8*7\wedge 6*(5+4)*32+1$
258275736	$((9\wedge 8)-765)/4*(3+21)$	271064863	$(9*(8/7\wedge 6+5)+4)*32-1$
258276005	$((9\wedge 8)*((7-6)+5))-4321$	271064865	$(9*(8/7\wedge 6+5)+4)*32+1$
258280037	$(9\wedge 8+7)*6-5*(4\wedge 3+2)-1$	274658121	$9/8*(-76+5\wedge(4^3)+2)+1$
258280039	$(9\wedge 8+7)*6-5*(4\wedge 3+2)+1$	275774436	$(987+65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))-1)$
258280613	$(9\wedge 8-7)*6+5*(4\wedge 3+2)-1$	275775487	$((987+65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))-1$
258280615	$(9\wedge 8-7)*6+5*(4\wedge 3+2)+1$	275775489	$((987+65)*((4\wedge(3\wedge 2))))+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
329321942	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1$	383828125	$((9*8+7)+6)^*5^{\wedge}(4/3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
329321944	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	384072195	$(9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*3+2+1$
330887789	$-9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1$	385539966	$-987^*((6-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1)$
330887791	$-9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	385540952	$(-987^*(6-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))-1$
330887834	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1$	385540954	$(-987^*(6-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$
330887836	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	385541940	$-987^*(6-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1))$
330887861	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1$	385551810	$987^*((6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1)$
330887863	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1$	385552796	$(987^*(6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))-1$
333606159	$((9^{\wedge}8)-765)/4)^*(32-1)$	385552798	$(987^*(6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$
335999265	$(98+7)^*(-6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	385553784	$987^*((6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1)$
339731883	$-9^*(8-(((7^{\wedge}6)-54)^*321))$	386479287	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
339732027	$9^*(8+(((7^{\wedge}6)-54)^*321))$	386479289	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
339856503	$(-98+((7^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4))^*321$	386479305	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
339919419	$(98+((7^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4))^*321$	386479307	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
340043895	$-9^*(8-(((7^{\wedge}6)+54)^*321))$	387302838	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
340044039	$9^*(8+(((7^{\wedge}6)+54)^*321))$	387302842	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
340946729	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3+2))-1$	387302856	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
340946731	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3+2))+1$	387302858	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
344312536	$((9^{\wedge}8)-7654)^*((3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	387302937	$98-7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
344369447	$((9^{\wedge}8)^*((7+6)-5))-4321$	387302939	$98-7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
344373663	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6)^*(5+4-3+2)-1$	387413603	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4+3+2)-1$
344373665	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6)^*(5+4-3+2)+1$	387413605	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4+3+2)+1$
344378089	$((9^{\wedge}8)^*((7+6)-5))+4321$	387417068	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
344435000	$((9^{\wedge}8)+7654)^*((3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	387417070	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5)^*(4+3+2)+1$
347298002	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43-2)-1$	387418598	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
347298004	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43-2)+1$	387418600	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(4+3+2)+1$
347299642	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43-2)-1$	387419484	$((9^{\wedge}8)-76)^*(5+4)-321$
347299644	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43-2)+1$	387419501	$(-987+((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))-1$
349360127	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1$	387419503	$(-987+((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
350578043	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*4*(3-2)-1$	387419851	$(9^{\wedge}8-76+5)^*(4+3+2)+1$
350578045	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*4*(3-2)+1$	387419966	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-65)^*(4+3+2)-1$
355129137	$((9^{\wedge}8)-765)/4)^*(32+1)$	387419968	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-65)^*(4+3+2)+1$
355147416	$(-9/8+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5-4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	387420065	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6-5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
355330152	$(-9/8+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	387420067	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6-5)^*(4+3+2)+1$
362796768	$9^*8^*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)/2+1)$	387420126	$((9^{\wedge}8)-76)^*(5+4)+321$
362797344	$9^*8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)/2-1)$	387420173	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
362797524	$9^*8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)/2+1)$	387420175	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2+1$
363505323	$((9^{\wedge}8)^*76)/(5+4))-321$	387420281	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6^*5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
363505965	$((9^{\wedge}8)^*76)/(5+4))+321$	387420299	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
363893775	$(9^{\wedge}8-8+7+6)-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$	387420301	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2+1$
363893777	$(9^{\wedge}8-8+7+6)-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$	387420316	$((-98-76)+((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
365897017	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6)^*(5^*4-3)/2-1$	387420662	$((98+76)+((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$
365897019	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6)^*(5^*4-3)/2+1$	387420677	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
365897068	$(9^{\wedge}8-7)^*(6+5-4+3/2)-1$	387420679	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2+1$
365897070	$(9^{\wedge}8-7)^*(6+5-4+3/2)+1$	387420803	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
365897136	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6)^*(5^*4-3)/2-1$	387420805	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2+1$
365897138	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6)^*(5^*4-3)/2+1$	387420852	$((9^{\wedge}8)+76)^*(5+4)-321$
368777822	$98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)-54)^*32)-1)$	387421010	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+65)^*(4+3+2)-1$
368778018	$98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)-54)^*32)+1)$	387421012	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+65)^*(4+3+2)+1$
369116510	$98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)+54)^*32)-1)$	387421127	$(9^{\wedge}8+76-5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
369116706	$98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)+54)^*32)+1)$	387421475	$(987+((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))-1$
373027200	$98^*((((76+((5^{\wedge}4)^*3))^{\wedge}2)-1)$	387421477	$(987+((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
373027297	$(98^*((76+((5^{\wedge}4)^*3))^{\wedge}2))-1$	387421494	$((9^{\wedge}8)+76)^*(5+4)+321$
373027299	$(98^*((76+((5^{\wedge}4)^*3))^{\wedge}2))+1$	387422378	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
373027396	$98^*((((76+((5^{\wedge}4)^*3))^{\wedge}2))+1)$	387422380	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(4+3+2)+1$
374837585	$9-8^{\wedge}7^*6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	387423908	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*5)^*(4+3+2)-1$
374837587	$9-8^{\wedge}7^*6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	387423910	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*5)^*(4+3+2)+1$
376029872	$9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	387538136	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
376029874	$9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	387538140	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
377487211	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7^*6-5)^*(4/3+2))+1$	387538154	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
378949760	$-9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	387538156	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
378949762	$-9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	387538235	$98+7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
381180734	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43+2)-1$	387538237	$98+7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
381180736	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43+2)+1$	387889632	$(987+6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
381182984	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43+2)-1$	387890624	$((987+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
381182986	$(9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43+2)+1$	387890626	$((987+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
382056830	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	387891618	$(987+6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
382056832	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	388361689	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
383202144	$(987-6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$	388361691	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
383203124	$((987-6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$	390491192	$((98^*76)/5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$
383203126	$((987-6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	392590718	$-9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5*(4/3+2)-1$
383204106	$(987-6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	392590720	$-9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5*(4/3+2)+1$

Supplement 3

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3376081	$-1-2^3*(4*(5^6+7)-8)^*9$	-3938679	$(-123-(((4*(5^6))^*7)+8))^*9$
-3442951	$(1-2*(3^4-5))^6/(7-8)+9$	-3938895	$(-123-(4*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$
-3499913	$123-(4*((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9$	-3983048	$(-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6-7+8)/9$
-3500087	$-123-(4*((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9$	-4029357	$-123*((4^{\wedge}((5-6)+7))^*8)-9$
-3500975	$((-123-((4*(5^6))^*7))^*8)+9$	-4031571	$-123*((4^{\wedge}((5-6)+7))^*8)+9$
-3500993	$((-123-((4*(5^6))^*7))^*8)-9$	-4062377	$123+((4*(5^6))^*(7-(8^*9)))$
-3511807	$1+(2*(-3^4+5))^6/(7-8)+9$	-4062499	$1-(2-3)^4*5^6*(7-8^*9)$
-3511809	$-1+(2*(-3^4+5))^6/(7-8)+9$	-4062501	$-1-(2-3)^4*5^6*(7-8^*9)$
-3581577	$(-1-2*(3^4-5))^6/(7-8)+9$	-4062623	$-123+((4*(5^6))^*(7-(8^*9)))$
-3633122	$((((-123^4)+5)+6)/7)-8)/9$	-4151671	$1-((23^4+5)/6+7)^*89$
-3715712	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-89)$	-4151673	$-1-((23^4+5)/6+7)^*89$
-3715736	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-89)$	-4218911	$1-2*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)^*9)$
-3716290	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-(8^*9))$	-4218913	$-1-2*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)^*9)$
-3716314	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-(8^*9))$	-4247778	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9$
-3718160	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-(8+9))$	-4247802	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9$
-3718184	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-(8+9))$	-4248390	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9$
-3718457	$(12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-4248414	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9$
-3718475	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-8)+9$	-4252198	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9$
-3718481	$(-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-4252222	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9$
-3718499	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-8)+9$	-4408884	$-12*((3^4)^*567)^*8)-9$
-3718704	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+8)-9$	-4409100	$-12*((3^4)^*567)^*8)+9$
-3718796	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)-8)+9$	-4463424	$((12*(3^4))^*56)^*(7-89)$
-3719001	$(12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-4496877	$(123-((4*(5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
-3719019	$12-((34*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-4498389	$(123-((4*(5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
-3719043	$-12-((34*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-4499091	$(-123-((4*(5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
-3719316	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+8)+9$	-4499397	$(123-((4*(5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
-3719340	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+8)+9$	-4499592	$12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+8)+9))$
-3721186	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+(8^*9))$	-4499864	$1+((2-34)^*5^6+7+8)^*9$
-3721210	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+(8^*9))$	-4499866	$-1+((2-34)^*5^6+7+8)^*9$
-3721764	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+89)$	-4499990	$1+((2-34)^*5^6-7+8)^*9$
-3721788	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)+89)$	-4500010	$-1+((2-34)^*5^6+7-8)^*9$
-3796172	$1-((23+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$	-4500408	$-12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+8)+9))$
-3796174	$-1-((23+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$	-4500503	$1-(2^3*4^*5^6+7^*8)^*9$
-3796370	$1-((23+4)^*5^6-7^*8)^*9$	-4500505	$-1-(2^3*4^*5^6+7^*8)^*9$
-3796372	$-1-((23+4)^*5^6-7^*8)^*9$	-4500603	$(-123-((4*(5^6)-7)^*8))^*9$
-3796631	$1-(23+4)^*(5^6+7-8)^*9$	-4500909	$(123-((4*(5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
-3796633	$-1-(23+4)^*(5^6+7-8)^*9$	-4501611	$(-123-((4*(5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
-3797117	$1-(23+4)^*(5^6-7+8)^*9$	-4503123	$(-123-((4*(5^6)+7)^*8))^*9$
-3797119	$-1-(23+4)^*(5^6-7+8)^*9$	-4505615	$1-2^3*(4^*5^6+78)^*9$
-3797378	$1-((23+4)^*5^6+7^*8)^*9$	-4505617	$-1-2^3*(4^*5^6+78)^*9$
-3797380	$-1-((23+4)^*5^6+7^*8)^*9$	-4515625	$(((-123+4)^*(5^6))/7)^*(8+9)$
-3797576	$1-((23+4)^*5^6+78)^*9$	-4717485	$(123-((4^{\wedge}(56/7))^*8))^*9$
-3797578	$-1-((23+4)^*5^6+78)^*9$	-4718469	$123-((4^{\wedge}(56/7))^*8)^*9$
-3825931	$1-(2+3/4)^*(5^6+7)^*89$	-4718715	$-123-((4^{\wedge}(56/7))^*8)^*9$
-3825933	$-1-(2+3/4)^*(5^6+7)^*89$	-4719699	$(-123-((4^{\wedge}(56/7))^*8))^*9$
-3906127	$123-((4^{\wedge}5)/((6/(7+8))^{\wedge}9))$	-4735584	$((-12*(3^4))^*56)^*(78+9)$
-3906373	$-123-((4^{\wedge}5)/((6/(7+8))^{\wedge}9))$	-4874841	$123-(4*((5^6)^*78)-9)$
-3917568	$(-12^{\wedge}3)^*(4*567)-(8/9)$	-4875159	$-123-(4*((5^6)^*78)+9)$
-3920640	$(-12^{\wedge}3)^*(4*567)+(8/9)$	-4937377	$123-((4*(5^6))^*(7+(8^*9)))$
-3936105	$(123-(4*((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-4937499	$1+(2-3)^4*5^6*(7+8^*9)$
-3936321	$((123-((4*(5^6))^*7))+8)^*9$	-4937501	$-1+(2-3)^4*5^6*(7+8^*9)$
-3936465	$(123-((4*(5^6))^*7)+8))^*9$	-4937623	$-123-((4*(5^6))^*(7+(8^*9)))$
-3936681	$(123-(4*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-4958696	$((-12*34)^*((5^6)^*7)+8)/9$
-3937089	$123-((4*((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-5027156	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)-89$
-3937305	$123-(((4*(5^6))^*7)-8)^*9$	-5027938	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)-(8^*9)$
-3937335	$-123-((4*((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-5030468	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)-(8+9)$
-3937427	$1+((2-3)^4*5^6*7+8)^*9$	-5030873	$((-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)-8)+9$
-3937429	$-1+((2-3)^4*5^6*7+8)^*9$	-5030891	$((-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)-8)-9$
-3937436	$1+(2-3-4^*5^6*7+8)^*9$	-5031161	$(((-12-34)^*(5^6))^*7)+89$
-3937438	$-1+(2-3-4^*5^6*7+8)^*9$	-5031178	$(((-12-34)^*(5^6))^*7)+(8^*9)$
-3937449	$123-(((4*(5^6))^*7)+8)^*9$	-5031204	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)+8)-9$
-3937498	$1-(2+34)^*5^6*7-8+9$	-5031296	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)-8)+9$
-3937551	$-123-(((4*(5^6))^*7)-8)^*9$	-5031322	$(((-12-34)^*(5^6))^*7)-(8^*9)$
-3937562	$1-(2-3+4^*5^6*7+8)^*9$	-5031339	$(((-12-34)^*(5^6))^*7)-89$
-3937564	$-1-(2-3+4^*5^6*7+8)^*9$	-5031609	$(((-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)+8))+9$
-3937571	$1+((2-3)^4*5^6*7-8)^*9$	-5031627	$(((-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)+8))-9$
-3937573	$-1+((2-3)^4*5^6*7-8)^*9$	-5032032	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)+8)+9$
-3937665	$123-((4*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-5034562	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)+(8^*9)$
-3937695	$-123-(((4*(5^6))^*7)+8)^*9$	-5035344	$(-12-34)^*((5^6)^*7)+89)$
-3937911	$-123-((4*((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-5037335	$1+2*(3^4-5-6^7+8)^*9$
-3938319	$(-123-(4*((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-5037337	$-1+2*(3^4-5-6^7+8)^*9$
-3938535	$((-123-((4*(5^6))^*7))+8)^*9$	-5037551	$1+(2*(3^4-5-6^7)-8)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-5037553	$-1+(2*(3^4-5-6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$	-7863894	$(1234-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5039048	$(1*(-2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$	-7865856	$((123+4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-5040143	$1-(2*(3^4-5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$	-7870572	$((123*4)-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5040145	$-1-(2*(3^4-5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$	-7872540	$12+(((34)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-5040359	$1-2*(3^4-5+6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$	-7872564	$-12+(((34)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-5040361	$-1-2*(3^4-5+6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$	-7873857	$((123+4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-5040467	$1-(2*(3^4+5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$	-7873929	$(123-(4+((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5040469	$-1-(2*(3^4+5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$	-7874181	$(123-((4+((5^6)*7))^8))^9$
-5040539	$1-2*(3^4+5+6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$	-7874589	$123+(((4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-5040541	$-1-2*(3^4+5+6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$	-7874663	$1+(2/3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7)*8^9$
-5044613	$1-(23-4)*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$	-7874665	$-1+(2/3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7)*8^9$
-5044615	$-1-(23-4)*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$	-7874682	$12+((34-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5062175	$1-(2+34)*(5^{\wedge}6+7-8)*9$	-7874706	$-12+((34-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5062177	$-1-(2+34)*(5^{\wedge}6+7-8)*9$	-7874835	$-123+(((4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-5062490	$1-((2+34)*5^{\wedge}6+7-8)*9$	-7874841	$123+((4-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5062492	$-1-((2+34)*5^{\wedge}6+7-8)*9$	-7874913	$123-((4+(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5062508	$1-((2+34)*5^{\wedge}6-7+8)*9$	-7874957	$1+(2/3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^9$
-5062510	$-1-((2+34)*5^{\wedge}6-7+8)*9$	-7874959	$-1+(2/3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^9$
-5062823	$1-(2+34)*(5^{\wedge}6-7+8)*9$	-7875041	$1-(2/3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^9$
-5062825	$-1-(2+34)*(5^{\wedge}6-7+8)*9$	-7875043	$-1-(2/3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^9$
-5156052	$(12-34)*(((5^6)*7+8))-9$	-7875087	$-123+((4-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5156448	$(12-34)*(((5^6)*7+8))+9$	-7875159	$-123-((4+(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5574453	$(-12*34)*(((5^6)*7/8)-9)$	-7875165	$123-(((4+((5^6)*7))^8)*9)$
-5578017	$-12*(((34*(5^6))^7/8)-9)$	-7875294	$12-((34+(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5578116	$((((-12*34)*(5^6))^7/8)+9)$	-7875318	$-12-((34+(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-5578134	$((((-12*34)*(5^6))^7/8)-9)$	-7875335	$1-(2/3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7)*8^9$
-5578233	$-12*(((34*(5^6))^7/8)+9)$	-7875337	$-1-(2/3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7)*8^9$
-5581797	$(-12*34)*(((5^6)*7/8)+9)$	-7875411	$-123-(((4+((5^6)*7))^8)*9)$
-5599530	$(12^{\wedge}3-34)*5/6^{\wedge}7-7/(8-9)$	-7875819	$(-123+((4-((5^6)*7))^8))^9$
-5686200	$(-1+(2/3)^{\wedge}4-4)*5*6^{\wedge}7*(8-9)$	-7876071	$((-123+4)-((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5694918	$(-1/2)*(((3/45)^{\wedge}6)-789)$	-7876143	$(-123-(4+((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5695707	$(-1/2)*(((3/45)^{\wedge}6)+789)$	-7877436	$12-(((34+((5^6)*7))^8)*9)$
-5747010	$(-12-34)*(((5^6)-7)*8)-9$	-7877460	$-12-(((34+((5^6)*7))^8)*9)$
-5747415	$((-12-34)*((5^6)-7))^8)+9$	-7879428	$((-123*4)-((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5747433	$((-12-34)*((5^6)-7))^8)-9$	-7884144	$((-123-(4+((5^6)*7))^8))^9$
-5747838	$(-12-34)*(((5^6)-7)*8)+9$	-7886106	$(-1234-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9$
-5752162	$(-12-34)*(((5^6)+7)*8)-9$	-7891847	$1-(234+5^{\wedge}6*7)*8^9$
-5752567	$((-12-34)*((5^6)+7))^8)+9$	-7891849	$-1-(234+5^{\wedge}6*7)*8^9$
-5752585	$((-12-34)*((5^6)+7))^8)-9$	-7968432	$12-(34*(((5^6)*7+8))-9)$
-5752990	$(-12-34)*(((5^6)+7)*8)+9$	-7968456	$-12-(34*(((5^6)*7+8))-9)$
-5841132	$(12-34)*((5^6)-7)*(8+9)$	-7969044	$12-(34*(((5^6)*7+8))+9)$
-5842160	$1-(2*3^4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-7969068	$-12-(34*(((5^6)*7+8))+9)$
-5842162	$-1-(2*3^4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-8036351	$1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6*7+8)^9$
-5843631	$((12-34)*(5^6)+7)*(8+9)$	-8036353	$-1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6*7+8)^9$
-5843869	$((12-34)*(5^6)-7)*(8+9)$	-8169906	$-123*(((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)-9$
-5845166	$1-(2*3^4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-8437377	$123-(((4*(5^6))^7+8))^9$
-5845168	$-1-(2*3^4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-8437623	$-123-(((4*(5^6))^7+8))^9$
-5846368	$(12-34)*((5^6)+7)*(8+9)$	-8485560	$(1+(2/3)^{\wedge}4-4)*5*6^{\wedge}7*(8-9)$
-5979276	$(-123*(((4*(5^6))^7+8))/9)$	-8644563	$(((-123*4)*((5^6)-7))/8)*9$
-5979604	$((-123*4)*((5^6)*7+8))/9$	-8652312	$(((-123*4)*((5^6)+7))/8)*9$
-6445566	$((-12-34)*((5^6)-(7*8))^9)$	-8812092	$12*(34-((5^6)*((7*8)-9)))$
-6462540	$((-12-34)*((5^6)-(7+8))^9)$	-8812908	$-12*(34+((5^6)*((7*8)-9)))$
-6468048	$(((-12-34)*(5^6)+78)*9)$	-8846855	$1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6-7)*8^9$
-6468336	$(((-12-34)*((5^6)+7)-8))^9$	-8846857	$-1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6-7)*8^9$
-6468615	$((((-12-34)*(5^6)+7)+8)*9)$	-9690587	$((123*4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6468741	$((((-12-34)*(5^6)-7)+8)*9)$	-9723072	$((123+4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6468759	$((((-12-34)*(5^6)+7)-8)*9)$	-9731337	$12+((34-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6468885	$(((-12-34)*(5^6))-7+8)*9$	-9731361	$-12+((34-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6469164	$(((-12-34)*((5^6)-7)+8))^9$	-9737389	$12-((34+((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6469452	$(((-12-34)*(5^6))-78)*9$	-9737413	$-12-((34+((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6474960	$(((-12-34)*((5^6)+7)+8))^9$	-9745678	$(-123-(4+((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6491934	$(((-12-34)*((5^6)+7+8))^9)$	-9778163	$((-123*4)-((5^6)*7))^8)*9$
-6501042	$(((-12-34)*((5^6)+78))^9)$	-10496628	$12*(((34-((5^6)*7))^8)+9)$
-6805944	$(1-(2/3)^{\wedge}4-4*5)*-6^{\wedge}7/(8-9)$	-10496727	$((12*(34-((5^6)*7))^8)+9)$
-7207308	$(-123/4)*(((5^6)*7+8))+9$	-10496745	$((12*(34-((5^6)*7))^8)-9)$
-7365816	$(1-(2/3)^{\wedge}4-4*5)*6^{\wedge}7/(8-9)$	-10496844	$12*(((34-((5^6)*7))^8)*9)$
-7435409	$(123-((4*(5^6))^7))^8)+9$	-10499484	$12*(34-(((5^6)*7)*8))+9$
-7437377	$123-(((4*(5^6))^7)*(8+9))$	-10499583	$(12*(34-(((5^6)*7)*8))^9)$
-7437623	$-123-(((4*(5^6))^7)*(8+9))$	-10499601	$(12*(34-(((5^6)*7)*8))-9)$
-7439591	$(-123-((4*(5^6))^7))^8)+9$	-10499700	$12*(34-(((5^6)*7)*8)+9)$
-7665160	$12*(34+(((5^6)-(7^{\wedge}8))/9))$	-10500399	$(-12*(34+(((5^6)*7)*8))+9)$
-7665976	$-12*(34-(((5^6)-(7^{\wedge}8))/9))$	-10500417	$(-12*(34+(((5^6)*7)*8))-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-10500516	$-12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7)^8) + 9)$	-11808900	$((12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7))) - 8)^9$
-10503156	$-12 * (((34 + ((5^6)^7))^8) - 9)$	-11811228	$12 * (34 - (((5^6)^7) - 8)^9)$
-10503255	$((-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7)))^8) + 9$	-11812044	$-12 * (34 + (((5^6)^7) - 8)^9)$
-10503273	$((-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7)))^8) - 9$	-11812956	$12 * (34 - (((5^6)^7) + 8)^9)$
-10503372	$-12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7))^8) + 9$	-11813772	$-12 * (34 + (((5^6)^7) + 8)^9)$
-10780836	$(-12 - 34) * (((5^6)^7 + 8) - 9)$	-11815308	$(-12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7) - 8)))^9$
-10781664	$(-12 - 34) * (((5^6)^7 + 8) + 9)$	-11816100	$((-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) + 8)^9$
-10957644	$(1234 - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-11816244	$((-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7))) - 8)^9$
-10964322	$((123^4) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-11817036	$(-12 * ((34 + ((5^6)^7) + 8)))^9$
-10965078	$((12^34) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-11957896	$((123^4 - (4 - ((5^6)^7)))^8)^9$
-10967679	$(123 - (4 + ((5^6)^7)))^9$	-11958388	$(-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7)^8))^9$
-10968336	$((12 + 34) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-12116668	$(123 - ((4^5)^6)) + ((7^8)^9)$
-10968432	$12 + ((34 - ((5^6)^7))^9)$	-12116914	$(-123 - ((4^5)^6)) + ((7^8)^9)$
-10968456	$-12 + ((34 - ((5^6)^7))^9)$	-12187092	$12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7) * (7 - (8^9)))$
-10968552	$((-12 + 34) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-12187908	$-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7) * ((7^8) + 9))$
-10968578	$1 + (23 - 4 - 5^6 * 78)^9$	-12201983	$1 + (2^3)^4 * (5 - 6 * 7^8)^9$
-10968579	$1 * (23 - 4 - 5^6 * 78)^9$	-12201985	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * (5 - 6 * 7^8)^9$
-10968580	$-1 + (23 - 4 - 5^6 * 78)^9$	-12213276	$((-12 - 34) * ((5^6) - 7))^8 * (8 + 9)$
-10968591	$123 + ((4 - ((5^6)^7))^9)$	-12218631	$(((-12 - 34) * (5^6) + 7))^8 * (8 + 9)$
-10968909	$-123 - ((4 + ((5^6)^7))^9)$	-12218869	$(((-12 - 34) * (5^6) - 7))^8 * (8 + 9)$
-10968920	$1 - (23 - 4 + 5^6 * 78)^9$	-12327693	$((12^3)^4) - ((5^6)^789)$
-10968921	$1 * (-23 + 4 - 5^6 * 78)^9$	-12328557	$((-12^3)^4) - ((5^6)^789)$
-10968922	$-1 - (23 - 4 + 5^6 * 78)^9$	-12417786	$(((-1 - 2) * (3^4))^5 * 678)^9$
-10968948	$(12 - (34 + ((5^6)^7)))^9$	-12476160	$(1 - 2 * (3/4)^{-5}) / 6^{(-7+8-9)}$
-10969044	$12 - ((34 + ((5^6)^7))^9)$	-12515001	$1 - ((2 + 3 + 4)^5 * 6^7 - 7)^8 * 9$
-10969068	$-12 - ((34 + ((5^6)^7))^9)$	-12515003	$-1 - ((2 + 3 + 4)^5 * 6^7 - 7)^8 * 9$
-10969164	$(-12 - (34 + ((5^6)^7)))^9$	-12596021	$1 + (2^3 * 4^5 - 5 * (6^7 + 8))^9$
-10969821	$((-123 + 4) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-12596023	$-1 + (2^3 * 4^5 - 5 * (6^7 + 8))^9$
-10972422	$((-12^34) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-12598217	$1 - (2^3 * 4^5 + 5 * (6^7 - 8))^9$
-10973178	$((-123^4) - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-12598219	$-1 - (2^3 * 4^5 + 5 * (6^7 - 8))^9$
-10979856	$(-1234 - ((5^6)^7))^9$	-12598939	$-1 - (2^3 * 4^5 + 5 * (6^7 + 8))^9$
-11108663	$1 + (2 - 3^4)^5 * (5^6 + 7 - 8)^9$	-12937092	$12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7 * (78 - 9)))$
-11108665	$-1 + (2 - 3^4)^5 * (5^6 + 7 - 8)^9$	-12937908	$-12 * (34 + ((5^6)^7 * (78 - 9)))$
-11109365	$1 + ((2 - 3^4)^5 * 5^6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-12991444	$1^2 / 3 * (4 - (5 + 6)^7 - 8 + 9)$
-11109367	$-1 + ((2 - 3^4)^5 * 5^6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-13005034	$(-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) - 89)$
-11109383	$1 + ((2 - 3^4)^5 * 5^6 + 7 - 8)^9$	-13007057	$(-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) - (8^9))$
-11109385	$-1 + ((2 - 3^4)^5 * 5^6 + 7 - 8)^9$	-13013602	$(-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) - (8 + 9))$
-11110085	$1 + (2 - 3^4)^5 * (5^6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-13014664	$((-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) - 8) + 9)$
-11110087	$-1 + (2 - 3^4)^5 * (5^6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-13014682	$((-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) - 8) - 9)$
-11156250	$((-123 + 4) * (5^6))^8 * ((7 + 8) - 9)$	-13016568	$((-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9)$
-11165202	$(-123^4 - ((4 + 5) - 6))^8 * ((7 + 8) - 9)$	-13016586	$((-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9)$
-11389824	$(12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	-13017648	$(-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9$
-11389833	$((1 + 2) - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	-13024193	$(-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) + (8^9))$
-11389834	$((1^2) - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	-13026216	$(-123 + 4) * (((5^6)^7) + 89)$
-11389838	$(-1 * (2 + ((3/45)^{-6}))) + 789$	-13441686	$123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 89)$
-11389839	$(-1 - (2 + ((3/45)^{-6}))) + 789$	-13442670	$-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - 89)$
-11389848	$(-12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 789$	-13443777	$123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + (8^9))$
-11389990	$(12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + (7^89)$	-13444761	$-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - (8^9))$
-11390014	$(-12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + (7^89)$	-13450542	$123 * (((4 - ((5^6)^7)) + 8) + 9)$
-11390531	$(12 - ((3/45)^{-6} + 7)) + 89$	-13451526	$-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - (8 + 9))$
-11390541	$((-12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 7) + 89$	-13451640	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9)$
-11390550	$((-12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 78) + 9$	-13451658	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9)$
-11390568	$((-12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 78) - 9$	-13452510	$123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9$
-11390682	$(12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 78) + 9)) + 9$	-13452544	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 89)$
-11390700	$12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 78) + 9)$	-13452561	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 8^9)$
-11390709	$12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 7) + 89)$	-13452616	$((123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9) - 123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 9)$
-11390719	$((-12 - ((3/45)^{-6})) + 7) - 89$	-13452624	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) - 8) + 9)$
-11391236	$12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 7) + 89)$	-13452632	$((123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9) - 123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 9)$
-11391260	$-12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 7) + 89)$	-13452634	$((123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9) - 123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 9)$
-11391402	$12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 789))$	-13452642	$(-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 9)$
-11391411	$(1 + 2) - (((3/45)^{-6} + 789))$	-13452650	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 8 + 9)$
-11391412	$(1^2) - (((3/45)^{-6} + 789))$	-13452705	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 8^9)$
-11391416	$-1 * (2 + ((3/45)^{-6} + 789))$	-13452722	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) - 8) - 89)$
-11391417	$-1 - (2 + ((3/45)^{-6} + 789))$	-13452756	$123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9$
-11391426	$-12 - (((3/45)^{-6} + 789))$	-13453494	$-123 * (((4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9) - 123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 89)$
-11530758	$123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7 * ((7 + 8) - 9)))$	-13453528	$(-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 89)$
-11531742	$-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7 * ((7 + 8) - 9)))$	-13453545	$(-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 8^9)$
-11586560	$((-1 - (2/3)) * (4^5))^6 * 789$	-13453600	$((-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9) - 123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9)$
-11671865	$1 - ((2 + 3^4)^5 * 5^6 + 7 - 8)^9$	-13453608	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9)$
-11671867	$-1 - ((2 + 3^4)^5 * 5^6 + 7 - 8)^9$	-13453616	$((-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9) - 123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9)$
-11807964	$(12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7) + 8))^9$	-13453618	$((-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9) - 123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9)$
-11808756	$((12 * (34 - ((5^6)^7) + 8))^8)^9$	-13453626	$(123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-13453634	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^7)))-(8+9)$	-15880969	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)+7)*8)-9$
-13453689	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^7)))-(8*9)$	-15883255	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)+7)*8)+9$
-13453706	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^7)))-89$	-16156250	$((12-34)*(5^6))*((7*8)-9)$
-13453740	$-123*((4+((5^6)^7))-8)+9$	-16269819	$((12-((34^5)/6))+7^8)*9$
-13454592	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^7)+8))+9$	-16269909	$((12-(34^5)/6)+7^8)*9$
-13454610	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^7)+8))-9$	-16269945	$((-12-(34^5)/6)+(7^8))*9$
-13454724	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+8)+9)$	-16270035	$((-12-((34^5)/6))+7^8)*9$
-13455708	$-123*((4+((5^6)^7))+8)+9$	-16312092	$12*(34-((5^6)^*(78+9)))$
-13461489	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+(8*9)))$	-16312908	$-12*(34+((5^6)^*(78+9)))$
-13462473	$-123*((4+((5^6)^7))+8*9)$	-16650837	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-78))*9$
-13463580	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+89))$	-16655758	$123*(4-(((5^6)^78)/9))$
-13464564	$-123*((4+((5^6)^7))+89)$	-16656742	$-123*(4+(((5^6)^78)/9))$
-13490280	$(12*(34-(((5^6)^7)+8*9)))*9$	-16674399	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-(7*8)))*9$
-13493544	$12*(34-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-16680023	$1-(2^3+4)*((5^6-7)*89)$
-13493951	$1-(2^3+4)*((5^6-7)*8*9)$	-16680025	$-1-(2^3+4)*((5^6-7)*89)$
-13493953	$-1-(2^3+4)*((5^6-7)*8*9)$	-16694975	$1-(2^3+4)*((5^6+7)*89)$
-13494360	$-12*(34+(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-16694977	$-1-(2^3+4)*((5^6+7)*89)$
-13499495	$1-((2^3+4)*5^6-7)*8*9$	-16718310	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-(7+8)))*9$
-13499497	$-1-((2^3+4)*5^6-7)*8*9$	-16726806	$(((-123+4)*((5^6)-7))+8)*9$
-13500503	$1-((2^3+4)*5^6+7)*8*9$	-16726950	$(((-123+4)*((5^6)-7))-8)*9$
-13500505	$-1-((2^3+4)*5^6+7)*8*9$	-16733304	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7)-8)*9$
-13505640	$12*(34-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-16733871	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7*8))*9$
-13506047	$1-(2^3+4)*((5^6+7)*8*9)$	-16734240	$(((-123+4)*((5^6)+7)+8)*9$
-13506049	$-1-(2^3+4)*((5^6+7)*8*9)$	-16734366	$(((-123+4)*((5^6)-7)+8)*9$
-13506456	$-12*(34+(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-16734384	$(((-123+4)*((5^6)+7)-8)*9$
-13509720	$(-12*(34+(((5^6)^7)+8*9)))*9$	-16734510	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-7)+8)*9$
-13704804	$(-1234^((5^6)/(7+8)))*9$	-16734879	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-(7*8))*9$
-13879322	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)-89)$	-16735446	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-7)+8)*9$
-13881481	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)-(8*9))$	-16741800	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7))+8)*9$
-13889600	$((-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)-8))+9$	-16741944	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7))-8)*9$
-13889618	$((-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)-8))-9$	-16750440	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7)+8)*9$
-13890625	$((123+4)*((5^6)^7)*8-9)$	-16794351	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+(7*8)))*9$
-13891632	$((-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)+8))+9$	-16817913	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+78))*9$
-13891650	$((-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)+8))-9$	-17210037	$123*(4-(((5^6)-78)*9))$
-13899769	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)+(8*9))$	-17211021	$-123*(4+(((5^6)-78)*9))$
-13901928	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)+89)$	-17234391	$123*(4-(((5^6)-(7*8)*9))$
-14000127	$1-2^(3+4)*((5^6+7-8)+9)$	-17235375	$-123*(4+(((5^6)-(7*8)*9))$
-14128805	$(123^4)*5/(6-(78+9))$	-17279778	$123*(4-(((5^6)-(7+8)*9))$
-14624484	$12*(34-(((5^6)^78)+9))$	-17280762	$-123*(4+(((5^6)-(7+8)*9))$
-14624583	$(12*(34-(((5^6)^78)+9)))+9$	-17296260	$-123*(4+(((5^6)+7)-8)*9)$
-14624601	$(12*(34-(((5^6)^78)+9))-9$	-17298474	$-123*(4+(((5^6)-7)+8)*9)$
-14624700	$12*(34-(((5^6)^78)+9))$	-17312988	$123*(4-(((5^6)+7)+8)*9)$
-14625300	$-12*(34+((5^6)^78)-9)$	-17313972	$-123*(4+(((5^6)+7)+8)*9)$
-14625399	$(-12*(34+((5^6)^78))+9)$	-17358375	$123*(4-(((5^6)+7*8)*9))$
-14625417	$(-12*(34+((5^6)^78))-9)$	-17359359	$-123*(4+(((5^6)+7*8)*9))$
-14625516	$-12*(34+((5^6)^78))+9$	-17382729	$123*(4-(((5^6)+78)*9))$
-14812092	$12*(34-(((5^6)^7+(7+8*9))))$	-17383713	$-123*(4+(((5^6)+78)*9))$
-14812908	$-12*(34+((5^6)^7+(7+8*9)))$	-17770221	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-78))*9$
-14867265	$(-123+4)*(((5^6)-7)*8)-9$	-17795367	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-(7*8)))*9$
-14868327	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-7))*8+9$	-17842230	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-(7+8)))*9$
-14868345	$((-123+4)*((5^6)-7))*8-9$	-17851302	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-7))+8)*9$
-14869407	$(-123+4)*(((5^6)-7)*8)+9$	-17851446	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-7))-8)*9$
-14880593	$(-123+4)*(((5^6)+7)*8)-9$	-17858232	$((-123-4)*((5^6)+7)-8)*9$
-14881655	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7))*8+9$	-17858871	$((-123-4)*((5^6)+7*8))*9$
-14881673	$((-123+4)*((5^6)+7))*8-9$	-17859240	$(((-123-4)*((5^6)+7)+8)*9$
-14882735	$(-123+4)*(((5^6)+7)*8)+9$	-17859366	$(((-123-4)*((5^6)-7)+8)*9$
-14886936	$(-123^((4+5)-6))*((7-8)+9)$	-17859384	$(((-123-4)*((5^6)+7)-8)*9$
-15366513	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-17859510	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-7)+8)*9$
-15367497	$-123*((4+(((5^6)^7)+8*9))-9)$	-17859879	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-(7*8))*9$
-15368727	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-17860518	$((-123-4)*((5^6)-7)+8)*9$
-15369711	$-123*((4+(((5^6)^7)+8*9))+9)$	-17867304	$(((-123-4)*((5^6)+7))+8)*9$
-15374508	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-17867448	$((-123-4)*((5^6)+7))-8)*9$
-15374592	$12*(34+((5^6)^7-89))$	-17876520	$((-123-4)*((5^6)+7)+8)*9$
-15375408	$-12*(34-((5^6)^7-89))$	-17923383	$((-123-4)*((5^6)+(7*8)))*9$
-15375492	$-123*(4+((5^6)^7-89))$	-17948529	$((-123-4)*((5^6)+78))*9$
-15380289	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-17998847	$1-2^(3+4)*((5^6+7-8)*9$
-15381273	$-123*((4+(((5^6)^7)+8*9))-9)$	-17998849	$-1-2^(3+4)*((5^6+7-8)*9$
-15382503	$123*(4-(((5^6)^7)+8*9))$	-17999592	$12*(34-(((5^6)^7+89)))$
-15383487	$-123*((4+(((5^6)^7)+8*9))+9)$	-17999990	$1-(2^3+4)*5^6+7-8)*9$
-15383532	$(-1-2*(3/4)^-5)/6^(7+8-9)$	-17999992	$-1-(2^3+4)*5^6+7-8)*9$
-15866745	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)+8*9)-9$	-18000008	$1-(2^3+4)*5^6+7+8)*9$
-15869031	$(-123-4)*(((5^6)^7)+8*9)+9$	-18000010	$-1-(2^3+4)*5^6+7+8)*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-18000408	$-12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+89)))$	-25192637	$1+2*(3^4-(5^6*7-8))^*9$
-18001151	$1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)*(5^6-7+8)^*9$	-25192639	$-1+2*(3^4-(5^6*7-8))^*9$
-18001153	$-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)*(5^6-7+8)^*9$	-25192709	$1+(2*(3^4-5^6*7)+8)^*9$
-18040536	$((-12*(34^{\wedge}((5+6)-7)))/8)^*9$	-25192711	$-1+(2*(3^4-5^6*7)+8)^*9$
-18608670	$(123^{\wedge}((4+5)-6))^*(7-(8+9))$	-25195769	$1-(2*(3^4+5^6*7)+8)^*9$
-19125000	$(((-123+4)*(5^6))/7)^*8)^*9$	-25195771	$-1-(2*(3^4+5^6*7)+8)^*9$
-19218258	$123*(4+((5^6)^*(7-(8+9))))$	-25195841	$1+2*(-3^4-(5^6*7+8))^*9$
-19219242	$-123*(4-((5^6)^*(7-(8+9))))$	-25195843	$-1+2*(-3^4-(5^6*7+8))^*9$
-19249802	$(12-34)*(((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9$	-25308828	$(12*(34-((5^6)^*(7+8))))^*9$
-19249991	$((((12-34)*(5^6))^*7)^*8)+9$	-25312092	$12*(34-(((5^6)^*(7+8))^*9))$
-19250009	$((((12-34)*(5^6))^*7)^*8)-9$	-25312908	$-12*(34+(((5^6)^*(7+8))^*9))$
-19250198	$(12-34)*(((5^6)^*7)^*8)+9$	-25316172	$(-12*(34+((5^6)^*(7+8))))^*9$
-19414133	$1-((2^{\wedge}3)^4+5)^6*789$	-25431799	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^*(7+8)))/9$
-19414135	$-1-((2^{\wedge}3)^4+5)^6*789$	-25431838	$(((-123^4)-5)+((6+7)^*8))/9$
-19643018	$((123/4)*(5^6)-(7^8))/9$	-25431860	$(((-123^4)+5)-((6+7)^*8))/9$
-20154293	$1+(2*3^4-(5+6^7)^*8)^*9$	-25431899	$((-123^4)-((5^6)^*(7+8)))/9$
-20154295	$-1+(2*3^4-(5+6^7)^*8)^*9$	-25463638	$(1-234)*(((5^6)^*7)-89)$
-20156489	$1-(2*3^4-(5-6^7)^*8)^*9$	-25484286	$((1-234)^*(5^6)^*7)+89$
-20156491	$-1-(2*3^4-(5-6^7)^*8)^*9$	-25484464	$((1-234)^*(5^6)^*7)-89$
-20925888	$(1+((23^4)^*(5-678)))/9$	-25505112	$(1-234)*(((5^6)^*7)+89)$
-21365423	$1-(23-4)*(5^6-7)^*8^9$	-25509432	$(1-2/3*((4+5)^6+7))^*8^9$
-21365425	$-1-(23-4)*(5^6-7)^*8^9$	-25509504	$-1*2/3*((4+5)^6+7)^*8^9$
-21654666	$((12-34)*(((5^6)^*7)-8))^*9$	-25509576	$(-1-2/3*((4+5)^6+7))^*8^9$
-21656178	$((((12-34)*(5^6))^*7)+8)^*9$	-25572923	$1-(234)*(((5^6)^*7)-89)$
-21656322	$((((12-34)*(5^6))^*7)-8)^*9$	-25572924	$(-1*234)*(((5^6)^*7)-89)$
-21657834	$((12-34)*(((5^6)^*7)+8))^*9$	-25572925	$-1-(234)*(((5^6)^*7)-89)$
-22305564	$(12*(34-((5^6)^*7))^*(8+9))$	-25614575	$1-(234)*(((5^6)^*7)+89)$
-22312092	$12*(34-((5^6)^*7)^*(8+9))$	-25614576	$(-1*234)*(((5^6)^*7)+89)$
-22312908	$-12*(34+(((5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)))$	-25614577	$-1-(234)*(((5^6)^*7)+89)$
-22319436	$(-12*(34+((5^6)^*7)))^*(8+9)$	-25682210	$(-1-234)*(((5^6)^*7)-89)$
-22779671	$1-(2*((3/45)^{\wedge}6)-789)$	-25703036	$(((-1-234)^*(5^6)^*7)+89)$
-22779672	$(-1*2)*(((3/45)^{\wedge}6)-789)$	-25703214	$(((-1-234)^*(5^6)^*7)-89)$
-22779673	$-1-(2*((3/45)^{\wedge}6)-789)$	-25724040	$(-1-234)*(((5^6)^*7)+89)$
-22780460	$(1-2/((3/45)^6))^*789$	-25871291	$1+2^{\wedge}-3*4*(5^6-7^8)^*9$
-22780461	$((-1*2)/((3/45)^6))+789$	-25871293	$-1+2^{\wedge}-3*4*(5^6-7^8)^*9$
-22780462	$(-1-(2/((3/45)^6)))+789$	-26011916	$1-2^{\wedge}-3*4*(5^6+7^8)^*9$
-22782038	$1-((2/((3/45)^6))+789)$	-26011918	$-1-2^{\wedge}-3*4*(5^6+7^8)^*9$
-22782039	$-1*((2/((3/45)^6))+789)$	-26410037	$1-(23-4)*((5^6)^*7)^*89$
-22782040	$-1-((2/((3/45)^6))+789)$	-26410039	$-1-(23-4)*(5^6-7)^*89$
-22782827	$1-(2*((3/45)^{\wedge}6)+789)$	-26422497	$1-((23-4)^*5^6+7)^*89$
-22782828	$(-1*2)*(((3/45)^{\wedge}6)+789)$	-26422499	$-1-((23-4)^*5^6+7)^*89$
-22782829	$-1-(2*((3/45)^{\wedge}6)+789)$	-26578052	$1-(23+4)^*5^6*7-8)^*9$
-23042788	$(12^*3)^*(456-((7^8)/9))$	-26578054	$-1-((23+4)^*5^6*7-8)^*9$
-23075620	$(-12^*3)^*(456+((7^8)/9))$	-26578196	$1-((23+4)^*5^6*7+8)^*9$
-23156078	$1-(23-4)^*(5^6*78-9)$	-26578198	$-1-((23+4)^*5^6*7+8)^*9$
-23156079	$1*(-23+4)^*(5^6*78-9)$	-26812302	$(12-34)*(((5^6)^*78)-9)$
-23156080	$-1-(23-4)^*(5^6*78-9)$	-26812698	$(12-34)*(((5^6)^*78)+9)$
-23156420	$1-(23-4)^*(5^6*78+9)$	-27156250	$((12-34)^*(5^6))^*(7+(8^9))$
-23156421	$1*(23-4)^*(-5^6*78-9)$	-27551073	$(1+2/3)*((4^5)^6-7)-8^9$
-23156422	$-1-(23-4)^*(5^6*78+9)$	-27889554	$(-123+4)*(((5^6)^*(7+8))-9)$
-23624990	$1-(23+4)^*5^6*7^*8+9$	-27891696	$(-123+4)*(((5^6)^*(7+8))+9)$
-23624992	$-1-(23+4)^*5^6*7^*8+9$	-27913005	$((123^4)^5)/((6-(7^8))+9)$
-23640625	$(((-123+4)^*(5^6))/7)^*89$	-28610813	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^*(7+8)))/8)+9$
-23914782	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4)^*-5+6-7+8)^*9$	-28610822	$((((123^4)^*(5-6))-7)/8)+9$
-23914908	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4)^*-5-6+7-8)^*9$	-28610824	$((((-123^4)-(5^6))+7)/8)+9$
-24054036	$12+((34^5)/(6-(7+(8/9))))$	-28610827	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^*(7+8)))/8)+9$
-24054060	$-12+((34^5)/(6-(7+(8/9))))$	-28610831	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^*(7+8)))/8)-9$
-24137496	$1-((2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7))-8^*9)$	-28610840	$((((123^4)^*(5-6))-7)/8)-9$
-24137642	$-1-((2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7))+8^*9)$	-28610842	$((((-123^4)-(5^6))+7)/8)-9$
-24375008	$1-(2+3)^4*5^6*78-9$	-28610845	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^*(7+8)))/8)-9$
-24375010	$-1-(2+3)^4*5^6*78-9$	-28624493	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^*(7+8)))/8)+9$
-24656181	$1+(2*(34-((5^6)^*789)))$	-28624511	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^*(7+8)))/8)-9$
-24656182	$(1*2)^*(34-((5^6)^*789))$	-28826526	$123*(4-((5^6)^*(7+8)))+9$
-24656183	$-1+(2*(34-((5^6)^*789)))$	-28827510	$-123*(4+((5^6)^*(7+8)))-9$
-24656317	$1-(2*(34+((5^6)^*789)))$	-28827624	$(123*(4-((5^6)^*(7+8))))+9$
-24656318	$(-1*2)^*(34+((5^6)^*789))$	-28827642	$(123*(4-((5^6)^*(7+8))))-9$
-24656319	$-1-(2*(34+((5^6)^*789)))$	-28828608	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^*(7+8))))+9$
-24738912	$((12-34)*((5^6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	-28828626	$(-123*(4+((5^6)^*(7+8))))-9$
-24749496	$((((12-34)^*(5^6))^*7)^*8)^*9$	-28828740	$123*(4-(((5^6)^*(7+8))^*9))$
-24750504	$((((12-34)^*(5^6))^*7)-7)^*8^*9$	-28829724	$-123*((4+((5^6)^*(7+8))^*9))$
-24761088	$((12-34)*((5^6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	-29749682	$12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9$
-24811560	$((-123^4)^5)/((6-(7^8))^*9)$	-29749706	$-12-(34*((5^6)^*7)^*8)-9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-29750294	$12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$	-41437818	$-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$
-29750318	$-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$	-41506449	$123 - ((4/5) * (6 + ((7^8)^9)))$
-29764482	$(-123 - 4) * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9$	-41506695	$-123 - ((4/5) * (6 + ((7^8)^9)))$
-29766768	$(-123 - 4) * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9)$	-41554943	$1 - (2 * 3^4 + 5) / 6^7 - 8 / 9$
-30529374	$(123^4) + (5 * (6 - ((7^8)^9)))$	-41554945	$-1 - (2 * 3^4 + 5) / 6^7 - 8 / 9$
-30529434	$(123^4) - (5 * (6 + ((7^8)^9)))$	-42550254	$1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5) * 6^7 + 8 - 9$
-30580044	$((12 - 34) * ((5^6)^7))^89$	-42550256	$-1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5) * 6^7 + 8 - 9$
-30607456	$((12 - 34) * ((5^6)^7))^89$	-42550270	$1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5) * 6^7 - 8 - 9$
-31491144	$((123 - ((4 * (5^6)^7))^8) * 9)$	-42550274	$-1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5) * 6^7 + 8 - 9$
-31498893	$(123 - ((4 * (5^6)^7))^8) * 9$	-42550288	$1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5) * 6^7 - 8 - 9$
-31499990	$1 - (2 + 34) * 5^6 * 7^8 + 9$	-42550290	$-1 - 2 * (3^4 - 5) * 6^7 - 8 - 9$
-31501107	$(-123 - (((4 * (5^6)^7)^8))^9$	-42916254	$(((((-123^4) - 5) / 6) - 7) / 8))^9$
-31508856	$((-123 - ((4 * (5^6)^7))^8))^9$	-43883208	$1 + 2^{\wedge} - 3 * (4 * 5) / 6^7 - 8 + 9$
-31595214	$((-123 + 4) * ((5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-43883209	$1 + 2^{\wedge} - 3 * (4 * 5) / 6^7 - 8 + 9$
-31609256	$(((-123 + 4) * (5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-43883210	$-1 + 2^{\wedge} - 3 * (4 * 5) / 6^7 - 8 + 9$
-31609494	$(((-123 + 4) * (5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-44588688	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 - 9)$
-31623536	$((-123 + 4) * ((5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-44595624	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 - (8 * 9))$
-31768362	$(-1 + 2 * (3/4)^5) / 6^7 - 8 - 9$	-44618064	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 - (8 + 9))$
-32478625	$(-1 - 2/3) * (4 - (5 + 6)^7) * (8 - 9)$	-44621628	$-12 * ((34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9))$
-32602059	$((1 - 234) * ((5^6)^7))^89$	-44621727	$((-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8) + 9)$
-32656746	$123 * (4 - (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$	-44621745	$((-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9)$
-32657730	$-123 * (4 + (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$	-44621844	$-12 * ((34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) + 9))$
-32686020	$123 * (4 - (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$	-44624592	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 - 9)$
-32687004	$-123 * (4 + (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9))$	-44625408	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9)$
-32764923	$(((-1234) * (5^6)^7))^89$	-44628156	$-12 * ((34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9))$
-32766327	$(((-1234) * (5^6)^7))^89$	-44628255	$((-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8) + 9)$
-32881905	$((-1234) * ((5^6)^7))^89$	-44628273	$((-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9)$
-32929191	$((1 - 234) * ((5^6)^7))^89$	-44628372	$-12 * ((34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) + 9))$
-33046173	$(((-1234) * (5^6)^7))^89$	-44631936	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9)$
-33047577	$(((-1234) * (5^6)^7))^89$	-44654376	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 8 * 9)$
-33211845	$((-1234) * ((5^6)^7))^89$	-44660808	$(-123^{\wedge}((4+5) - 6)) * ((7+8)^9)$
-33466194	$(12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8)))^9$	-44661312	$(-12 * 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8 + 9)$
-33466290	$12 - ((34 * (((5^6)^7)^8))^9)$	-45277938	$((-12 - 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8))^9$
-33466314	$-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8))^9$	-45284562	$((-12 - 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8))^9$
-33466410	$(-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8)))^9$	-45334403	$1 + 2 * 3^4 * (5 - 6^7 + 89)$
-33471090	$(12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8)))^9$	-45334405	$-1 + 2 * 3^4 * (5 - 6^7 + 89)$
-33471186	$12 - ((34 * (((5^6)^7)^8))^9)$	-45348820	$1 + 2 * 3^4 * (5 - 6^7) - 8 + 9$
-33471210	$-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8))^9$	-45348965	$1 + 2 * 3^4 * (5 - 6^7 - 8) - 9$
-33471306	$(-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8)))^9$	-45348966	$1 * 2 * 3^4 * (5 - 6^7 - 8 / 9)$
-33719262	$((-123 - 4) * ((5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-45348967	$-1 + 2 * 3^4 * (5 - 6^7 - 8 / 9)$
-33734256	$(((-123 - 4) * (5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-45350369	$1 - 2 * 3^4 * (5 + 6^7) + 8 * 9$
-33734494	$(((-123 - 4) * (5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-45350371	$-1 - 2 * 3^4 * (5 + 6^7) + 8 * 9$
-33749488	$((-123 - 4) * ((5^6)^7))^8 + 9$	-45350440	$1 - 2 * 3^4 * (5 + 6^7) - 8 + 9$
-33781250	$((-12 - 34) * (5^6)^7) * ((7^8)^9) - 9$	-45350513	$1 - 2 * 3^4 * (5 + 6^7) - 8 * 9$
-33883208	$1 + (2^{\wedge}(3+4) * 5^6 - 7^8) * 9$	-45350515	$-1 - 2 * 3^4 * (5 + 6^7) - 8 * 9$
-33883210	$-1 + (2^{\wedge}(3+4) * 5^6 - 7^8) * 9$	-45414459	$((12 + 34) * (5^6) - (7^8))^9$
-34023834	$((123 + 4) * (5^6)^7) - (7^8))^9$	-46114268	$12 * (345 - ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-34169508	$(-1 - 2) * ((3/4)^5)^6 - (7^8) / 9$	-46116368	$12 * ((34 * 5) - ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-34174242	$(-1 - 2) * ((3/4)^5)^6 + 789$	-46117940	$12 * ((34 + 5) - ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-34736184	$((-123^4) / (5 + (6/7)))^8) * 9$	-46118060	$12 * (34 - (5 + ((6 * (7^8))^9)))$
-35148834	$((123 - 4) * (5^6)^7) - (7^8))^9$	-46118756	$-12 * ((34 - 5) + ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-36984273	$(1 + 2) * (34 - ((5^6)^7) * 89)$	-46118876	$-12 * ((34 + 5) + ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-36984351	$12 + (3 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) * 89))$	-46120448	$-12 * ((34 * 5) + ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-36984399	$-12 - (3 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) * 89))$	-46122548	$-12 * (345 + ((6 * (7^8))^9)) / 9$
-36984477	$(-1 - 2) * (34 + ((5^6)^7) * 89)$	-46124508	$123 * (4 - ((5^6)^7) * ((7^8)^9))$
-38147771	$((-123^4 + 5) / 6) + ((7^8)^9) / 9$	-46125492	$-123 * (4 + ((5^6)^7) * ((7^8)^9))$
-38147776	$((-123^4 - 5) / 6) - ((7^8)^9) / 9$	-46406250	$((12 - 34) * (5^6)^7) * ((7^8)^9) * 9$
-38926553	$(123 - ((4 * (5^6)^7))^8) * 89$	-46718750	$(12 + 34) * (5^6)^7 * (7 - (8 * 9))$
-38948447	$(-123 - ((4 * (5^6)^7))^8) * 89$	-46749310	$1 - (2 * 3^4 + 5) * 6^7 - 8 + 9$
-38987639	$((-12 * (34^5)) / 6) + ((7^8)^9) * 9$	-46749328	$1 - (2 * 3^4 + 5) * 6^7 - 8 - 9$
-40249586	$(-12 - 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9$	-46749330	$-1 - (2 * 3^4 + 5) * 6^7 - 8 - 9$
-40249991	$(((-12 - 34) * (5^6)^7))^8 * 9 + 9$	-48789459	$(((-12 + 34) * (5^6)^7) - (7^8))^9$
-40250009	$(((-12 - 34) * (5^6)^7))^8 * 9 - 9$	-49898834	$((123 + 4) * (5^6)^7) - ((7^8)^9)$
-40250414	$(-12 - 34) * (((5^6)^7)^8) + 9$	-50023834	$((123 - 4) * (5^6)^7) - ((7^8)^9)$
-40333126	$1 + (2^{\wedge}3) / 4^5 - (6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-50203124	$1 - (23 + 4) * 5^6 * 7^8 + 9$
-40333128	$-1 + (2^{\wedge}3) / 4^5 - (6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-50203126	$-1 - (23 + 4) * 5^6 * 7^8 + 9$
-40374086	$1 - (2^{\wedge}3) / 4^5 - (6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-51114763	$(((-12/34)^{\wedge} - 5) * (6^7))^8 + 89$
-40374088	$-1 - (2^{\wedge}3) / 4^5 - (6 - 7 + 8)^9$	-51114941	$(((-12/34)^{\wedge} - 5) * (6^7))^8 - 89$
-40906250	$((12 - 34) * (5^6)^7) * 8 + 9$	-51127497	$((123 * (4^5))^6) - ((7^8)^9)$
-41437182	$12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9)$	-51164459	$((12 + 34) * (5^6)^7) - ((7^8)^9)$
-41437206	$-12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) - 9)$	-51320586	$123 + ((4 * (5^6)^7) - (7^8))^9$
-41437794	$12 - (34 * (((5^6)^7)^8) + 9)$	-51320708	$1 - ((2 - 3) * 4 * 5^6 + 7^8)^9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-51320710	$-1 - ((-2-3)^4 * 5^6 + 7^8) * 9$	-51904201	$((-123 * (4^5)) / 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51320832	$-123 + (((4 * (5^6)) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-51920063	$1 - ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6 + 7^8) * 9$
-51539459	$((-12+34) * (5^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-51920065	$-1 - ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6 + 7^8) * 9$
-51726816	$(((-12-34) * ((5^6) - 7)) * 8) * 9$	-51920081	$1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6 + 7^8) * 9$
-51741350	$1234 + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-51920083	$-1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6 + 7^8) * 9$
-51742092	$(123 * 4) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52008423	$(-123 * ((4^5) - 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51742176	$(12 * 34) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52009155	$((-123 * (4^5)) + 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51742465	$(123 - 4) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52009167	$(-123 * (4^5)) - (6 + ((7^8) * 9))$
-51742562	$(-12 + 34) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52009899	$(-123 * ((4^5) + 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51742606	$(12 - 34) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52022600	$1234 - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51742703	$(-123 + 4) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52023342	$(123 * 4) - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51742992	$(-12 * 34) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52023426	$(12 * 34) - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51743076	$(-123 * 4) + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52023715	$123 - (4 + (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9))$
-51743818	$-1234 + (((5^6) - (7^8)) * 9)$	-52023812	$(-12 + 34) - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51749496	$((((-12-34) * (5^6)) + 7) * 8) * 9$	-52023856	$12 - (34 + (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9))$
-51750504	$((((-12-34) * (5^6)) - 7) * 8) * 9$	-52023953	$(-123 + 4) - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51756519	$(123 * ((4^5) + 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-52024242	$(-12 * 34) - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51757251	$((123 * (4^5)) + 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-52024326	$(-123 * 4) - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51757263	$(123 * (4^5)) - (6 + ((7^8) * 9))$	-52025068	$-1234 - (((5^6) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51757995	$(123 * ((4^5) - 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-52226959	$((12 - 34) * (5^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51773184	$(((-12-34) * ((5^6) + 7)) * 8) * 9$	-52445586	$123 - ((4 * (5^6)) + (7^8)) * 9$
-51846335	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6 - 7^8) * 9$	-52445708	$1 + ((2 - 3)^4 * 5^6 - 7^8) * 9$
-51846337	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6 - 7^8) * 9$	-52445710	$-1 + ((2 - 3)^4 * 5^6 - 7^8) * 9$
-51846353	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6 - 7^8) * 9$	-52445832	$-123 - (((4 * (5^6)) + (7^8)) * 9)$
-51846355	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6 - 7^8) * 9$	-52601959	$((-12 - 34) * (5^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51862217	$(123 * (4^5)) / 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-52638921	$((-123 * (4^5)) * 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51870049	$((1 + 234) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-52784475	$(1 - ((2 / (3^4))^5)) * 6789$
-51870161	$((-1 + 234) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-52791263	$1 - ((2 / (3^4))^5) * 6789$
-51874730	$1 + ((2 * 3^4 - 5) * 6 - 7^8) * 9$	-52791265	$-1 - ((2 / (3^4))^5) * 6789$
-51874732	$-1 + ((2 * 3^4 - 5) * 6 - 7^8) * 9$	-52798053	$(-1 - ((2 / (3^4))^5)) * 6789$
-51875829	$(123 * (4 + 56)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53036105	$((12 + 34) / 5) * (6 - (7^8)) + 9$
-51876813	$(-123 * (4 - 56)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53036123	$((12 + 34) / 5) * (6 - (7^8)) - 9$
-51877803	$((-123 + (4^5)) * 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53742584	$((-123 + 4) * (5^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51879027	$(123 * (4 + (5 * 6))) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53768712	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) - 89)$
-51879084	$-1 + (2^3)^4 + 5 * 6 - 7^8 * 9$	-53777076	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) - (8 * 9))$
-51879399	$((123 + 4) * 5) * 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53801553	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) - 89)$
-51879639	$((123 - 4) * 5) * 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53803644	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) - (8 * 9))$
-51880011	$(123 * (4^5) + 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53804136	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) - (8 + 9))$
-51880633	$((12 + 34) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53807457	$-123 * (4 * (((5^6) * 7) - 8)) - 9$
-51881097	$(12 * ((34 * 5) + 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53808555	$((-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) - 8)) + 9$
-51881241	$(12 * ((34 * 5) - 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53808573	$((-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) - 8)) - 9$
-51881487	$((123 / 4) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53809671	$-123 * (4 * (((5^6) * 7) - 8)) + 9$
-51881737	$-1 + (2 * (3^4 + 5 / 6) - 7^8) * 9$	-53810409	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) - (8 + 9))$
-51881977	$((-12 + 34) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53811507	$(-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) - 8)) + 9$
-51882117	$((12 + (34 * 5)) * 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53811525	$(-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) - 8)) - 9$
-51882348	$(-123 * (4 - (5 + 6))) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53812008	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) + 8) - 9$
-51882568	$((123 + 4) * 5) + 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53812377	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) + 8) - 9$
-51882608	$((123 - 4) * 5) + 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53812623	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) - 8) + 9$
-51882620	$(123 - 4) * 5 - (6 + ((7^8) * 9))$	-53812992	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) - 8) + 9$
-51883798	$((-123 + 4) * 5) + 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53813475	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) + 8) + 9$
-51883810	$((-123 + 4) * 5) - (6 + ((7^8) * 9))$	-53813493	$(-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) + 8)) - 9$
-51883850	$((-123 - 4) * 5) - (6 + ((7^8) * 9))$	-53814591	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) + 8) + 9$
-51884070	$(123 * (4 - (5 + 6))) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53815329	$-123 * (4 * (((5^6) * 7) + 8)) + 9$
-51884301	$((-12 - (34 * 5)) * 6) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53816427	$((-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) + 8)) + 9$
-51884441	$(12 - 34) * 56 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53816445	$((-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) + 8)) - 9$
-51884681	$1 - (2 * (3^4 + 5 / 6) + 7^8) * 9$	-53817543	$-123 * (4 * (((5^6) * 7) + 8)) + 9$
-51884931	$((-123 / 4) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53820864	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) + 8) + 9$
-51885177	$(-12 * ((34 * 5) - 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53821356	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) + (8 * 9))$
-51885321	$(-12 * ((34 * 5) + 6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53823447	$-123 * (((4 * (5^6)) * 7) + 89)$
-51885785	$((-12 - 34) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53847924	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) + (8 * 9))$
-51886407	$(123 * (4 - (5 * 6))) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53856288	$(-123 * 4) * (((5^6) * 7) + 89)$
-51886779	$((-123 + 4) * 5) * 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-53867584	$((-123 - 4) * (5^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51887019	$((-123 - 4) * 5) * 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-54113064	$(((((12 - 34)^5) / 6) * 7) + 8) * 9$
-51887276	$-1 - (2^3)^4 + 5 * 6 - 7^8 * 9$	-54113208	$(((((12 - 34)^5) / 6) * 7) - 8) * 9$
-51887391	$(-123 * (4 + (5 * 6))) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-54976959	$((12 - 34) * (5^6)) - ((7^8) * 9)$
-51888615	$(123 - (4^5)) * 6 - ((7^8) * 9)$	-55491279	$1 + 2 * ((3^4 + 5) * 6 - 7^8 * 9)$
-51889605	$(123 * (4 - 56)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-55491280	$1 + 2 * ((3^4 + 5) * 6 - 7^8 * 9)$
-51890589	$(-123 * (4 + 56)) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-55491281	$-1 + 2 * ((3^4 + 5) * 6 - 7^8 * 9)$
-51891686	$1 - ((2 * 3^4 - 5) * 6 + 7^8) * 9$	-56062086	$(-12 - 34) * (((5^6) * 7) - 8) - 9$
-51891688	$-1 - ((2 * 3^4 - 5) * 6 + 7^8) * 9$	-56062914	$(-12 - 34) * (((5^6) * 7) + 8) + 9$
-51896257	$((1 - 234) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-56781250	$((-12 - 34) * (5^6)) * (7 + (8 * 9))$
-51896369	$((-1 - 234) * 56) - ((7^8) * 9)$	-56824467	$(1 - 2^3)^4 - (4 + 5 + 6) * (78 - 9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-112294325	$(1 - (2+34)^5) * ((6/7-8)+9)$	-134210713	$1 + (2^3 \wedge 4 + 5) * 6^7 - 8^9$
-115308072	$(-123^4) * (((5^6)^*(7+8))-9)$	-134224743	$-1 - (2^3 \wedge 4 + 5) * 6^7 - 8^9$
-115316928	$(-123^4) * (((5^6)^*(7+8))+9)$	-134238206	$1 - (2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 + 7 - 8^9$
-115883086	$123 - (((4^5)^6) + ((7^8)^9))$	-134238210	$-1 - (2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 - 7 - 8^9$
-115883332	$-123 - (((4^5)^6) + ((7^8)^9))$	-134246392	$1 - ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6) * 7 - 8^9$
-116776188	$(12^*(34 - ((5^6)^7))) * 89$	-134246394	$-1 - ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6) * 7 - 8^9$
-116812092	$12^*(34 - ((5^6)^7) * 89)$	-134246406	$1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6) * 7 - 8^9$
-116812908	$-12^*(34 + ((5^6)^7) * 89)$	-134246408	$-1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6) * 7 - 8^9$
-116848812	$(-12^*(34 + ((5^6)^7))) * 89$	-134483353	$(((-123+4)^*(5^6))/7) - (8^9)$
-117132057	$((-123+4) * ((5^6)^7 - 8)) * 9$	-134545852	$1 - (2 - 3 + 4) * 5^6 * 7 - 8^9$
-117140553	$((((-123+4)^*(5^6)^7) + 8) * 9$	-134545854	$-1 - (2 - 3 + 4) * 5^6 * 7 - 8^9$
-117140697	$((((-123+4)^*(5^6)^7) - 8) * 9$	-134858924	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) - 89)$
-117149193	$((-123+4) * (((5^6)^7) + 8)) * 9$	-134879902	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) - (8^9))$
-120036237	$(12 - (((34^5)/6) + (7^8))) * 9$	-134947772	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) - (8+9))$
-120036327	$((12 - (34^5)/6) - (7^8)) * 9$	-134958869	$(-1234 * (((5^6)^7) - 8)) + 9$
-120036363	$((-12 - (34^5)/6) - (7^8)) * 9$	-134958887	$(-1234 * (((5^6)^7) - 8)) - 9$
-120036453	$(-12 - (((34^5)/6) + (7^8))) * 9$	-134967516	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) + 8) - 9$
-120764111	$(123^4 + ((5^6)^7)) - (8^9)$	-134969984	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) - 8) + 9$
-120765095	$(-123^4 - ((5^6)^7)) - (8^9)$	-134978613	$(-1234 * (((5^6)^7) + 8)) + 9$
-120859375	$((123 - 4) * (5^6)) * (7 - (8^9))$	-134978631	$(-1234 * (((5^6)^7) + 8)) - 9$
-120932448	$-1^2 * (3 + 45 + 6^{\wedge}(-7 + 8 + 9))$	-134989728	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) + 8) + 9$
-120932595	$1^* (-2 - (3^4)^{-5}) / 6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 - 9)$	-135078576	$-1234 * (((5^6)^7) + 89)$
-121064841	$(123^*(4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8)) * 9$	-135529820	$(12^*(34 - ((5^6)^7))) - (8^9)$
-121068777	$123^*(4 - (((5^6)^7) - 8) * 9)$	-135530636	$(-12^*(34 + ((5^6)^7))) - (8^9)$
-121069761	$-123^*(4 + (((5^6)^7) - 8) * 9)$	-135624319	$1 - (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^{\wedge}7 - 8^9$
-121073625	$((123^*(4 - ((5^6)^7))) + 8) * 9$	-135624321	$-1 - (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^{\wedge}7 - 8^9$
-121073697	$(-123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7) - 8)) * 9$	-136623978	$((12 - 34) * (5^6)^7) - (8^9)$
-121073769	$((123^*(4 - ((5^6)^7))) - 8) * 9$	-136678032	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 789$
-121082481	$((-123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7))) + 8) * 9$	-136680024	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - (7^*89)$
-121082553	$(-123^*(4 - ((5^6)^7) + 8)) * 9$	-136686348	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - (7 + 89)$
-121082625	$((-123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7))) - 8) * 9$	-136686456	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - (78 + 9)$
-121086489	$123^*(4 - (((5^6)^7) + 8) * 9)$	-136686516	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + 7 - 89$
-121087473	$-123^*(4 + (((5^6)^7) + 8) * 9)$	-136686555	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 78) + 9$
-121091409	$(-123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7) + 8)) * 9$	-136686573	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - (78) - 9$
-121202103	$((123 - 4) * (5^6)^7) - (8^9)$	-136686711	$(-12 / ((3/45)^6)) + 789$
-124921383	$123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7) - (8^9))$	-136686877	$(-12 / ((3/45)^6)) + (7^*89)$
-124922367	$-123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7) - (7^*8) + 9)$	-136687327	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 7) + 89$
-125006481	$((-123 - 4) * ((5^6)^7 - 8)) * 9$	-136687404	$((-12 / ((3/45)^6)) + 7) + 89$
-125015553	$((((-123 - 4) * (5^6)^7) + 8) * 9$	-136687413	$((-12 / ((3/45)^6)) + 78) + 9$
-125015697	$((((-123 - 4) * (5^6)^7) - 8) * 9$	-136687418	$((-12 / ((3/45)^6)) - 7) + 89$
-125024769	$((-123 - 4) * ((5^6)^7) + 8) * 9$	-136687431	$((-12 / ((3/45)^6)) + 78) - 9$
-125186687	$1 - (2^3 \wedge 4 + 5) * 6^{\wedge}7 * 89$	-136687495	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 7) + 89$
-125186689	$-1 - (2^3 \wedge 4 + 5) * 6^{\wedge}7 * 89$	-136687505	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 7)) - 89$
-128984375	$((123 + 4) * (5^6)) * (7 - (8^9))$	-136687569	$((-12 / ((3/45)^6)) - 78) + 9$
-129186478	$((123 + 4) * (5^6)^7) - (8^9)$	-136687582	$((-12 / ((3/45)^6)) + 7) - 89$
-131621328	$(12^*(34 - ((5^6)^7 * 8))) * 9$	-136687587	$-12 / ((3/45)^6) - (78 + 9)$
-131624592	$12^*(34 - ((5^6)^7 * 8) * 9)$	-136687596	$(-12 / ((3/45)^6)) - (7 + 89)$
-131625408	$-12^*(34 + ((5^6)^7 * 8) * 9)$	-136687673	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + 7)) - 89$
-131628672	$(-12^*(34 + ((5^6)^7 * 8))) * 9$	-136688123	$(-12 / ((3/45)^6)) - (7^*89)$
-131811478	$((-12 + 34) * (5^6)^7) - (8^9)$	-136688289	$-12 / ((3/45)^6) - 789$
-132608883	$123^*(4 - ((5^6)^7 * 8) - 9))$	-136688427	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + 78)) + 9$
-132609867	$-123^*(4 + ((5^6)^7 * 8) - 9))$	-136688445	$(-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + 78)) - 9$
-132811135	$1 + (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^{\wedge}7 - 8^9$	-136688484	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 7) + 89$
-132811137	$-1 + (2/3^4 + 5) * 6^{\wedge}7 - 8^9$	-136688544	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + 78) + 9$
-132904820	$(12^*(34 + ((5^6)^7))) - (8^9)$	-136688652	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + 7) + 89$
-132905636	$(-12^*(34 - ((5^6)^7))) - (8^9)$	-136694976	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) + (7^*89))$
-133815024	$((-123 + 4) * ((5^6) - 7)) * 8 * 9$	-136696968	$-12^*((3/45)^{\wedge}6) - 6) + 789$
-133874496	$((((-123 + 4) * (5^6)) * 5) * 7) * 8 * 9$	-138312516	$123^*(4 - (((5^6) - 7) * 8) * 9))$
-133875504	$((((-123 + 4) * (5^6)) - 7) * 8) * 9$	-138313500	$-123^*(4 + (((5^6) - 7) * 8) * 9))$
-133889602	$1 + (2 - 3 + 4) * 5^6 * 7 - 8^9$	-138436500	$123^*(4 - (((5^6) + 7) * 8) * 9))$
-133889604	$-1 + (2 - 3 + 4) * 5^6 * 7 - 8^9$	-138437484	$-123^*(4 + (((5^6) + 7) * 8) * 9))$
-133934976	$((-123 + 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) * 8 * 9$	-139031931	$(1 - (2^{\wedge}(3^4) * 5)) * 6789$
-133952103	$((123 - 4) * (5^6)) / 7 - (8^9)$	-139045509	$(-1 - (2^{\wedge}(3^4) * 5)) * 6789$
-133982433	$((-123^4) / ((5/6) + (7/8))) - 9$	-139219767	$-1^*(23 - 4 + 5)^6 + 7^8 * 9$
-134171093	$1 + (23^4 + 5) / 6 - 7 - 8^9$	-139248978	$((-12 - 34) * (5^6)^7) - (8^9)$
-134171095	$-1 + (23^4 + 5) / 6 - 7 - 8^9$	-141814121	$(-123/45) * (6 + ((7^8)^9))$
-134189048	$1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6) * 7 - 8^9$	-142754057	$((-12^*(34^5)/6) - (7^8)^9)$
-134189050	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 - 5 + 6) * 7 - 8^9$	-142810992	$((-123 - 4) * ((5^6) - 7)) * 8 * 9$
-134189062	$1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6) * 7 - 8^9$	-142874496	$((((-123 - 4) * (5^6)) + 7) * 8) * 9$
-134189064	$-1 + ((2^3)^4 + 5 - 6) * 7 - 8^9$	-142875504	$((((-123 - 4) * (5^6)) - 7) * 8) * 9$
-134197246	$1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 - 6 + 7 - 8^9$	-142939008	$((-123 - 4) * ((5^6) + 7)) * 8 * 9$
-134197250	$-1 + (2^3)^4 * 5 + 6 - 7 - 8^9$	-143115452	$1 - ((2^3)^4 - 5) * (6^{\wedge}7 / 8 - 9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1425203085	$(((-123^4)-5)^6)-((7^8)^9)$	-2023445028	$123-(((45-6)^*(7^8))^9)$
-1451523973	$123-(((4/5)^{-6}+7)^*(8^9))$	-2023445274	$-123-(((45-6)^*(7^8))^9)$
-1451524219	$-123-(((4/5)^{-6}+7)^*(8^9))$	-2023445373	$12-((34+5)^*(6+((7^8)^9)))$
-1470024243	$12-(((34^5)/6)^*(7^8))^9$	-2023445397	$-12-((34+5)^*(6+((7^8)^9)))$
-1470024267	$-12-(((34^5)/6)^*(7^8))^9$	-2025467426	$(12+(34/(5+6)))^*(7-(8^9))$
-1490365293	$-123*((4^5)^6)-((7^8)^9)$	-2049011019	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))^9$
-1498848260	$(((-1-2345)+6)^*(7^8))/9$	-2052104769	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^7)^8)^9$
-1503926394	$-1234*((5^6)^78)-9$	-2057870394	$((-123^4)+((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9$
-1503948606	$-1234*((5^6)^78)+9$	-2058854265	$((-123^4)+((5^6)+7)^8)^9$
-1504612875	$12+((34-5)^*(6-((7^8)^9)))$	-2058855273	$((-123^4)+((5^6)-7)^8)^9$
-1504612899	$-12+((34-5)^*(6-((7^8)^9)))$	-2058995322	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))+8)^9$
-1504613223	$12-((34-5)^*(6+((7^8)^9)))$	-2058995466	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))-8)^9$
-1504613247	$-12-((34-5)^*(6+((7^8)^9)))$	-2059962183	$((-123^4)+((5^6)+7)/8)^9$
-1516358883	$123*(4-((5^6)^789))$	-2059997355	$((-123^4)-((5^6)+7)/8)^9$
-1516359867	$-123*(4+((5^6)^789))$	-2060964072	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^7))+8)^9$
-1537734363	$12-(3/45)^{((-6+7)-8)^9}$	-2060964216	$((-123^4)-((5^6)^7)+8)^9$
-1537734373	$1^*2-(3/45)^{(-6+7-8)^9}$	-2061104265	$((-123^4)-((5^6)-7)^8)^9$
-1537734377	$-1^*2-(3/45)^{(-6+7-8)^9}$	-2061105273	$((-123^4)-((5^6)+7)^8)^9$
-1537734387	$-12-(3/45)^{((-6+7)-8)^9}$	-2062089144	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^*(7+8)))^9$
-1568023832	$(12^*34)^*(5-((6^*(7^8))/9))$	-2067854769	$((-123^4)-((5^6)^7)^8)^9$
-1568027912	$(-12^*34)^*(5+((6^*(7^8))/9))$	-2070948519	$((-123^4)-((5^6)^78))^9$
-1579555474	$(((-123^4)^5)-6)^*(7^8)/9$	-2092622763	$((-12-(34^5)/6)^*(7^8))^9$
-1594928208	$(123/4)^*((5^6)-((7^8)^9))$	-2113928871	$(1+(2/3-4^5+6))^*7^8)^9$
-1595408646	$(-123/4)^*((5-6)+((7^8)^9))$	-2113928889	$(-1+(2/3-4^5+6))^*7^8)^9$
-1595409015	$(-123/4)^*((5+6)+((7^8)^9))$	-2127211323	$((12+34)-5)^*(6-((7^8)^9))$
-1599963136	$-1^*(2^3)^4*(5/((6-7)^8)-9)$	-2127211815	$((-12-34)+5)^*(6+((7^8)^9))$
-1609299828	$12^*((34+((5^6)^7))-((8^9)))$	-2139349536	$(((-123+4)+5)^{((6+7)-8)}/9)$
-1609300644	$-12^*((34-((5^6)^7))+((8^9)))$		
-1610061612	$12^*((3^4)^567)-((8^9))$		
-1611163860	$-12^*((3^4)^567)+((8^9))$		
-1611924828	$12^*(34-(((5^6)^7)+((8^9))))$		
-1611925644	$-12^*((34+((5^6)^7))+((8^9)))$		
-1670420001	$-1-2^*(34^5)^{(-6-7+8+9)}$		
-1737904896	$(1-(2/34)^{(-5+6-7)})^8)^9$		
-1737904956	$12-(((34^{((5-6)+7)})/8)^9)$		
-1737904980	$-12-(((34^{((5-6)+7)})/8)^9)$		
-1737905040	$(1+(2/34)^{(-5+6-7)})^8)^9$		
-1764028074	$12+(34^*((5^6)-((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764028098	$-12+(34^*((5^6)-((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764028720	$12+(34^*((5+6)-((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764028743	$(12+(34^*((5/6)-((7^8)^9)))^9$		
-1764028744	$-12+(34^*((5+6)-((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764028959	$(-12+(34^*((5/6)-((7^8)^9)))^9$		
-1764028983	$123-(((4+(5^6))^*(7^8))^9)$		
-1764029229	$-123-(((4+(5^6))^*(7^8))^9)$		
-1764029253	$(12-(34^*((5/6)+((7^8)^9)))^9$		
-1764029468	$12-(34^*((5+6)+((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764029469	$(-12-(34^*((5/6)+((7^8)^9)))^9$		
-1764029492	$-12-(34^*((5+6)+((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764030114	$12-(34^*((5^6)+((7^8)^9)))$		
-1764030138	$-12-(34^*((5^6)+((7^8)^9)))$		
-1794607605	$1+(-2-(-3+4)/5)^*(6+7)^8+9$		
-1794607607	$-1+(-2-(-3+4)/5)^*(6+7)^8+9$		
-1815912303	$12-(((34-5)+6)^*(7^8))^9$		
-1815912327	$-12-(((34-5)+6)^*(7^8))^9$		
-1830218119	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))^8)+9$		
-1830218137	$(((-123^4)+((5^6)^7))^8)-9$		
-1831968119	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^7))^8)+9$		
-1831968137	$(((-123^4)-((5^6)^7))^8)-9$		
-1836675729	$(123^4)^*(5/((6-(7/8))-9))$		
-1867779108	$(12^*3)^*(456-((7^8)^9))$		
-1867811940	$(-12^*3)^*(456+((7^8)^9))$		
-1881956826	$((-123^4)/5)^*((6^7)-(8/9))$		
-1890852268	$(123^4)^*(5-((6^*(7^8))/9))$		
-1890857188	$(-123^4)^*(5+((6^*(7^8))/9))$		
-1908876089	$1-(2^3+5^6-(7-8))/9$		
-1908876091	$-1-(2^3+5^6-(7-8))/9$		
-1971561941	$1+((2/(3-4))^5-6)^*7^8)^9$		
-1971561943	$-1+((2/(3-4))^5-6)^*7^8)^9$		
-1988856345	$((((-12-34)^5)/6)^*(7^8))^9$		
-2023444905	$12+((34+5)^*(6-((7^8)^9)))$		
-2023444929	$-12+((34+5)^*(6-((7^8)^9)))$		

Supplement 4

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-16571	$-9*(8-7*6+5^4*3)-2*1$	-134524	$(-9^8+7-6)/5^4-3-2-1$
-23948	$(-9+8-76)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-137684	$98+7*(6-5-4)^3-2-1$
-25300	$-9*((8+7-6)*5^4-3)/2-1$	-137878	$-98+7*(6-5-4)^3+2+1$
-28922	$(-9-8-76)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-138000	$(-9-8*7*6)*(5^4)^{(3-2+1)}$
-28924	$(-9-8-76)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-138564	$-9*(87+((6/54)^{-3})^{*21})$
-41294	$((-98+76)*((5^4)*3)+2))^*1$	-139415	$(98+7+6)*(-5^4-3)^*2+1$
-43280	$-9-8-((7-6-5^4)/3)^2+1$	-141816	$(9-8)*76*(-5^4+3)^*(2+1)$
-45328	$9-8*(7^6+5^4/3^2)-1$	-142591	$-9*(8+76/5^4-4/3+2)-1$
-51069	$(-9*87)*(65-(4/(3-21)))$	-143800	$(9+(8+7^6)*(-5+4/3))/(2+1)$
-51652	$((-987/6)*((5^4)+3))/2+1$	-143806	$(9+(8+7^6)*(-5-4/3))/(-2-1)$
-53384	$-9*8+(-7-6)*(5+4^{3*2})+1$	-144474	$9+8+7^6+5-4^3-2-1$
-56955	$9*((8-((7/6)*5432))+1)$	-144482	$9+8+7^6-5-4^3-2+1$
-56973	$9*(8-(((7/6)*5432)+1))$	-144484	$9+8+7^6-5-4^3-2-1$
-57262	$-9-((8/(7*65432)))^{\wedge}-1)$	-144561	$-9*8+7^6+5-4^3+2+1$
-57871	$9+8-(7^6-5^4*3)/2-1$	-144563	$-9*8+7^6+5-4^3+2-1$
-57899	$-9-(8+7^6-5^4*3)/2+1$	-145298	$(9+8+7^6)*((-5^4)^3+2)-1$
-57901	$-9-(8+7^6-5^4*3)/2-1$	-145677	$98*(76-((5^4)*((3/2)+1)))$
-57935	$(-98-7^6+5^4*3)/2+1$	-146366	$(9-87)^*(6/5^4-4+3)/2+1$
-57937	$(-98-7^6+5^4*3)/2-1$	-147088	$(9+8-7^6*5)/4-32+1$
-58061	$(987-((6/54)^{-3-2})))+1$	-147410	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*4+3+2)+1$
-59756	$9-(8+7^6+5^4*3)/2+1$	-147412	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*4+3+2)-1$
-63435	$9-((87/((6/54)^3))+21)$	-147502	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*4+3+2)-1$
-63453	$-9-((87/((6/54)^3))+21)$	-152033	$((-98*76)+((5^4)/3))^*21$
-71076	$98-(76*((5^4)*3)/2)-1)$	-152762	$(9+(8/(-7-6))^{\wedge}-5)^*4^{(3^2-1)}$
-71287	$(-9*8-76*5^4*3)/2-1$	-154724	$-9876*((5*((4/3)+2))-1)$
-71300	$((-98-((76*(5^4))^3))/2)-1$	-158086	$9-8*(7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1$
-72107	$(-98*(7+((6/54)^{-3})))^{*21}$	-160243	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5^4)^{(3+2-1)}$
-72149	$(-98*(7+((6/54)^{-3})))^{-21}$	-160313	$((9-87*6)*5^4-3)/2+1$
-72326	$(-98-76)*(((5^4)/3)^*2)-1$	-160315	$((9-87*6)*5^4-3)/2-1$
-82499	$(((-98+76)*(5^4))^3)^*2+1$	-160783	$((-98*76)-((5^4)/3))^*21$
-82750	$(-987-6)/(((5/4)^{-3})-(2^{\wedge}-1))$	-161189	$((-9*876)+((5^4)/3))^*21$
-83508	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4-3^2)^* -1$	-164095	$9-(876*((5^4)/3)-21))$
-83515	$((98-76-5)^4-3^2)/-1$	-164113	$-9-(876*((5^4)/3)-21))$
-84275	$9+(8+7)*(6-5^4*3^2)+1$	-164722	$(-9*8-7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))/(3+2)+1$
-84277	$9+(8+7)*(6-5^4*3^2)-1$	-165937	$((-9-87*6)*5^4+3)/2-1$
-84293	$-9+(8+7)*(6-5^4*3^2)+1$	-166491	$9*(876-((5^4)* (32-1)))$
-84295	$-9+(8+7)*(6-5^4*3^2)-1$	-167926	$9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
-84426	$(98*(76-(((5^4)*3)/2))+1$	-169939	$((-9*876)-((5^4)/3))^*21$
-85850	$-9*(-8-(7-6*5^4)/3)^2-1$	-170093	$-987*((((65^4)/3)^*2)-1)$
-89938	$-9+8*(7-6*5^4*3+2)-1$	-170562	$(((-9+8)*7-6)^*5^4+3)^*21$
-92983	$(987-(6^{\wedge}(-5+(4^3))))/(2+1)$	-172107	$9*((876-((5^4)*32))+1)$
-95048	$(-98/(((7/654)*3)^2))^*1$	-173302	$9-8*7^6+5^4+3^2+1$
-95468	$-9876*((((5^4)/3)+2)+1)$	-174476	$-9876*((5*((4/3)+2))+1)$
-95598	$((-98*(76+((5^4)*3)))/2)+1$	-176369	$98+(-7^6+5)/4^3*2-1$
-99421	$-98*((76+(((5^4)*3)/2))+1)$	-176382	$98+(-7^6-5)/4^3*2+1$
-99605	$(-9-((8*7)/6))^*(5432+1)$	-176578	$-98+(-7^6-5)/4^3*2+1$
-100011	$(-9-(8-7)^6)^{\wedge}5-4^3+2-1$	-178976	$987*((6-((5^4)/3))+21)$
-102338	$9*(8-(7-6))- (5^4+3)^2-1$	-180066	$-9-8*(7+6*5^4*3^2)-1$
-104461	$(-9+8)*7^6+(5^4+3)^*21$	-180143	$(9+87)^*(-6/5^4-4-3)/2+1$
-106399	$9*8*76*5*(-4+3^2-2)+1$	-184385	$(9+8-7)^6+5-4^3-2-1$
-107261	$-98-((7/((6/54)^3))^*21)$	-184499	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-107294	$(9+8*7*6)*(-5^4+3)/2+1$	-184930	$-98*((76/((5/4)-3))^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-107296	$(9+8*7*6)*(-5^4+3)/2-1$	-190020	$-9-8*(76*5^4+3)/2+1$
-109167	$-9-8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^3-2-1$	-190820	$-987*((6+((5^4)/3))-21)$
-109220	$-9*8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^3+2+1$	-191003	$(-98*((76+((5^4)*3))-2))-1$
-109246	$-98-(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^3+2+1$	-191096	$(9+8)^*(7-6*5^4*3+2)+1$
-110000	$((-98+76)*(5^4))^*(3^2)-1$	-191098	$(9+8)^*(7-6*5^4*3+2)-1$
-115081	$(-9+8/7)*(6+5)^4+3-21$	-191164	$(9+8)^*(7-6*5^4*3-2)+1$
-115280	$(-9+8/7)*(6+5)^4+32-1$	-191378	$9*(87+6^{\wedge}5)-4^3-2-1$
-115808	$(-987*6)^*(5*(4+(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$	-191402	$(9+8)^*(-7-6*5^4*3-2)+1$
-116795	$-987*((6*((5^4)-(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-191404	$(9+8)^*(-7-6*5^4*3-2)-1$
-118518	$-98765/((4/3)-(2^{\wedge}-1))$	-195982	$98-(7^6+5+4)/3+2+1$
-119019	$987-(6*((5^4)*32)+1)$	-196012	$9*8-(7^6+5+4)/3-2+1$
-119545	$(-9+8)*7^6-5^4*3-21$	-196799	$(9+(-8-7+6)^5)*(4/3+2)+1$
-120743	$-987*((6*5)^*(4+(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$	-198832	$(9-876)*((5^4)/3)+21$
-121072	$(-987*6)^*(5*(4-(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-199700	$((987*(6-((5^4)/3)))+2)+1$
-121831	$(98-7+6)*(-5^4-3)^*2+1$	-199702	$((987*(6-((5^4)/3)))+2)-1$
-125442	$-9*(876+((5^4)-3)^*21))$	-199705	$((987*(6-((5^4)/3)))-2)^*1$
-127395	$((9/87-6)^5)*4321$	-199706	$(987*(6-((5^4)/3)))- (2+1)$
-129832	$(9+8)*(7+6^{\wedge}5)-4^3+2+1$	-199724	$(987*(6-((5^4)/3)))-21$
-129834	$(9+8)*(7+6^{\wedge}5)-4^3+2-1$	-199888	$-9+8*(7+6^{\wedge}5)-4^3+2+1$
-130837	$(-9+8)*7^6-(5^4+3)^*21$	-199982	$9-8*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^3+2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-200157	$((-9+87)*6)-((5^4)*321)$	-254250	$(9+8)*7+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-200638	$((9-87)/6)-((5^4)*321)$	-254276	$98-7+6^5-4^3*2+1$
-200667	$(9-8)*-7*6-5^4*321$	-254278	$98-7+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-200887	$9-(876*((5^4)/3)+21))$	-254291	$-9+87+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-200905	$-9-(876*((5^4)/3)+21))$	-254357	$9+8-7+6^5-4^3*2+1$
-201171	$((-98+7)*6)-((5^4)*321)$	-254363	$-9+8+7+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-202636	$-9*(8+7+6*5^4*3^2)-1$	-254391	$-9-8-7+6^5-4^3*2+1$
-202960	$(-9-876)*((5^4)/3)+21))$	-254393	$-9-8-7+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-203085	$9+(8+7-6)^5-4^3*2+1$	-254458	$-98+7+6^5-4^3*2+1$
-203105	$-9+(8+7-6)^5-4^3*2-1$	-254460	$-98+7+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-203896	$(-987-6)*((5^4)/3)-(2+1))$	-254472	$-98-7+6^5-4^3*2+1$
-204396	$(((-987+6)*(5^4))/3)-21$	-254700	$((98*76)-(5+(4^(3^2))))+1$
-204888	$((-987-6)*((5^4)/3)-2)))+1$	-255026	$-9*((8^7+6/54)*3)^2-1$
-205619	$(((-987/6)*(5^4))+3)*2)^1$	-255152	$-9*87+6^5-4^3*2-1$
-206670	$9/8*(7/6*(-54^3+2)-1)$	-255962	$-987*((65*4)-((3/2)^-1))$
-206854	$(((-987-6)*(5^4))/3)+21$	-256226	$((987*6)-(5+(4^(3^2))))+1$
-206896	$(((-987-6)*(5^4))/3)-21$	-256666	$9*8*76+5-4^3*2+1$
-207294	$9+8*(7-6^5*(4/3+2))+1$	-256668	$9*8*76+5-4^3*2-1$
-207296	$9+8*(7-6^5*(4/3+2))-1$	-256676	$9*8*76-5-4^3*2+1$
-207406	$9-8*(7+6^5*(4/3+2))+1$	-256678	$9*8*76-5-4^3*2-1$
-209055	$((-9-((8^7)/6))*543)*21$	-257008	$(9*8+7)*65-4^3*2+1$
-211481	$(98*7-6)*(-5^4+3)/2-1$	-257033	$9*8*(76-5)-4^3*2-1$
-211526	$(-987*(6+((5^4)/3)))+21$	-257278	$-987*((65*4)+((3/2)^-1))$
-211544	$((-987*(6+((5^4)/3)))+2)+1$	-257440	$9*87*6+5-4^3*2+1$
-211546	$((-987*(6+((5^4)/3)))+2)-1$	-257442	$9*87*6+5-4^3*2-1$
-211549	$((-987*(6+((5^4)/3)))-2)*1$	-257450	$9*87*6-5-4^3*2+1$
-211568	$(-987*(6+((5^4)/3)))-21$	-257452	$9*87*6-5-4^3*2-1$
-212499	$(-9*8*7-6)*5^4/(3/2)+1$	-258198	$(9*87+6)*5-4^3*2+1$
-212501	$(-9*8*7-6)*5^4/(3/2)-1$	-258200	$(9*87+6)*5-4^3*2-1$
-212651	$9*(8-76*(5^4-3)/2)+1$	-258512	$-9+8*7*65-4^3*2+1$
-212653	$9*(8-76*(5^4-3)/2)-1$	-258514	$-9+8*7*65-4^3*2-1$
-212795	$-9*(8+76*(5^4-3)/2)+1$	-258683	$(98*7+6)*5-4^3*2+1$
-212797	$-9*(8+76*(5^4-3)/2)-1$	-258685	$(98*7+6)*5-4^3*2-1$
-212884	$(98+((7^6)*(5-43)))/21$	-259124	$9*8*7*6-5-4^3*2+1$
-215489	$(-9+8+7)*6^5-4^3*2-1$	-259126	$9*8*7*6-5-4^3*2-1$
-215492	$(9-8-7)^6-5-4^3*2+1$	-259148	$(-9+8*76)*5-4^3*2+1$
-217289	$(-98*7-6)*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-259150	$(-9+8*76)*5-4^3*2-1$
-218370	$(-98-76)*(((5^4)+3)*2)-1$	-259593	$(9*8*7+6)*5-4^3*2+1$
-220430	$987*(6-(((5^4)/3)+21))$	-259595	$(9*8*7+6)*5-4^3*2-1$
-222278	$-98*((7^6)*54+(3/21))$	-260290	$((9-8+7)^6-5-4^3*2)^-1$
-223340	$((-98*7)-(6/5))*(4+321)$	-261186	$(987-((6^5)+(4^(3^2))))+1$
-223769	$(9-8)*7*(-6^5*(4+3^2)+1)$	-261188	$987-(((6^5)+(4^(3^2))))+1$
-223872	$(9+8)*(-7*(6+5^4*3)-2)+1$	-261221	$(987-(65+(4^(3^2))))+1$
-227728	$(-987-6)*(((5^4)/3)+21)$	-261223	$987-((65+(4^(3^2))))+1$
-232160	$(-9/(8^7-6^5+4^3))^(-2+1)$	-261395	$-9-8+765-4^3*2+1$
-232274	$-987*((6+((5^4)/3))+21)$	-261397	$-9-8+765-4^3*2-1$
-234956	$9+8-(7^6-54*3)*2+1$	-261476	$((-98+765)-(4^(3^2))))+1$
-234958	$9+8-(7^6-54*3)*2-1$	-261478	$(-98+765)-((4^(3^2))+1)$
-234959	$9*((-8*7-6^5)*(4/3+2))+1$	-261531	$9+8*76-5-4^3*2+1$
-234961	$9*((-8*7-6^5)*(4/3+2))-1$	-261533	$9+8*76-5-4^3*2-1$
-235640	$-9-8-(7^6+54*3)*2-1$	-261584	$-9+8*(76-5)-4^3*2+1$
-238525	$-987*((6*((5+(4/3))^2))+1)$	-261586	$-9+8*(76-5)-4^3*2-1$
-240008	$(-9/(8*((7+(6^5)^4/3)+2)))^(-1)$	-261638	$9*8*7+6-5-4^3*2+1$
-241646	$(9*87-6)*(-5^4+3)/2+1$	-261664	$(9*8+7)*6+5-4^3*2+1$
-241648	$(9*87-6)*(-5^4+3)/2-1$	-261687	$9-8+7*65-4^3*2+1$
-242810	$((-9*87+6)/5^4-4+3)/2+1$	-261712	$9*8*(7-6+5)-4^3*2*1$
-242812	$((-9*87+6)/5^4-4+3)/2-1$	-261716	$9+(8+76)*5-4^3*2-1$
-243460	$(-987*6)*(((5+(4/3))^2)+1)$	-261738	$9*(8+7-6)*5-4^3*2+1$
-249899	$((-98*765)*((4/3)+2))+1$	-261740	$9*(8+7-6)*5-4^3*2-1$
-249901	$((-98*765)*((4/3)+2))-1$	-261750	$(9*8-7)*6+5-4^3*2-1$
-249970	$98-(((7/6)*5^4)^3)+21$	-261755	$(-9+8+7)*65-4^3*2-1$
-250124	$(-98-(((7/6)*5^4)^3))+21$	-261785	$(-9+87-6)*5-4^3*2-1$
-250821	$(9*87)*((6/(5+4))-321)$	-261803	$9+8*7*6-5-4^3*2+1$
-251286	$((987*(6+5))-(4^(3^2))))+1$	-261805	$9+8*7*6-5-4^3*2-1$
-252012	$-9-(8+(7+6)*(-5+43))^2+1$	-261811	$-9+8*7*6+5-4^3*2+1$
-252014	$-9-(8+(7+6)*(-5+43))^2-1$	-261821	$-9+8*7*6-5-4^3*2+1$
-252272	$(9876-(5+(4^(3^2))))+1$	-261835	$-9*8+76*5-4^3*2+1$
-252274	$9876-((5+(4^(3^2))))+1$	-261878	$(-9+8*7+6)*5-4^3*2+1$
-253164	$(-9/(876*((54-3)^2)))^(-1)$	-261920	$9*(-8+7+6)*5-4^3*2-1$
-253387	$((-9+8765)-(4^(3^2))))+1$	-261932	$9-8+7*6*5-4^3*2+1$
-253389	$(-9+8765)-((4^(3^2))+1)$	-261952	$-9-8+7*6*5-4^3*2-1$
-253681	$98*7+6^5-4^3*2+1$	-262002	$-9+87+65-4^3*2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-262031	$-9+8*7+65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-268274	$-9-8*765-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-262255	$((-98+76)*5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$	-268932	$(987-((6^5)+4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
-262283	$9*8-7*6*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-268934	$987-(((6^5)+4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
-262315	$-98-7-65-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-269122	$(-987*6)*(((5*4)/3)^2)+1$
-262329	$(-9-8)*7-65-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-269588	$((-98*76)+5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$
-262336	$9+8-7*6*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-269828	$98-7-6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-262348	$(9-8*7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-269840	$9*8+7-6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-262352	$9-8-7*6*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-269854	$9+8*7-6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-262402	$-9-(8+7*6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-269915	$-9+8+7-6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-262427	$98-(((76*5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-269931	$-9-8+7-6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-262453	$9*8-76*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-269945	$-9-8-7-6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-262483	$-9-8*7*6+5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-270917	$(-9-(8765+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
-262506	$9+8-76*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-271527	$(-9-8/7+6)*5+4^{\wedge}(3^2-1)$
-262526	$9+8-7*65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-273002	$(-987*(6+5))-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$
-262550	$9*(-8-7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-276560	$((-9-876)*5^4+3)/2+1$
-262570	$(-98+7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-276562	$((-9-876)*5^4+3)/2-1$
-262612	$(-9*8-7)*6+5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-278163	$9*((8*7-6^5)*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-262614	$(-9*8-7)*6+5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-278959	$-9-(8-7+6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-262640	$(-98-7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-278961	$-9-(8-7+6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-262646	$-9*8*7+6-5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-279520	$(-9+8)/(7-6*5)^{\wedge}-4+321$
-262651	$9-8*7*6+5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-280162	$(-9+8)/(7-6*5)^{\wedge}-4-321$
-262660	$-9*8*7-6-5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-283986	$((-9*8765)*4)/((3^{\wedge}-2)+1)$
-262694	$(-98+7)*6-5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-285621	$98-(((7^6)*54-3))/21$
-262708	$((-9-8)*7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-285817	$-98-(((7^6)*54-3))/21$
-262767	$-9-8*76-5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-286224	$-9*((8+7)*6-5^4)/3^{\wedge}2+1$
-262793	$(-9-8+7)*65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-290268	$9*(8-7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-262795	$(-9-8+7)*65-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-290270	$9*(8-7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-262812	$98-((765+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-294020	$98-(7^6*5-4-3)/2+1$
-262838	$9*8-765-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-294022	$98-(7^6*5-4-3)/2-1$
-262894	$-98*7-65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-294062	$9*8+(-7^6-5)*4-3/2+1$
-262915	$-9*87+6+5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-294176	$(-98-7^6*5-4-3)/2-1$
-262917	$-9*87+6+5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-294190	$-9*8-(7^6*5-4-3)/2+1$
-262939	$-9*87-6-5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-294234	$-98-(7^6+5)*4-3/2-1$
-262982	$-9*8-765-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-297223	$9*8*(7-6^5)+4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-262993	$-9*87-65-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-305090	$(((-987+6)*((5^4)-3))/2)+1$
-263015	$((-98-76)*5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$	-308273	$(-987/6)*(((5^4)*3-2))+1$
-263017	$9-876-5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-308437	$(((-987/6)*5^4)*3)+(2^{\wedge}-1)$
-263023	$-9-876+5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-308438	$(((-987/6)*5^4)*3)-(2^{\wedge}-1)$
-263025	$-9-876+5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-308795	$((9-8-7)^6-5+4^3 \wedge 2)*-1$
-263033	$-9-876-5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-308801	$(9-8-7)^6-5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-263065	$((-987+65)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-308824	$(((-987-6)*((5^4)-3))/2)-1$
-263067	$(-987+65)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$	-310310	$((((-987-6)*5^4)+3)/2)+1$
-263090	$-9*(8+7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-310312	$((((-987-6)*5^4)+3)/2)-1$
-263100	$((-987+(6*5))-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-311523	$((-987*6*5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$
-263162	$-987-(((6*5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-312052	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)/3+2+1$
-263195	$(-987-(65+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-313040	$-9*8*7*65-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-263199	$((-987*6)*(((5*4)/3)^2))+1$	-313587	$987-((6/5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1))$
-263201	$((-987*6)*(((5*4)/3)^2))-1$	-314654	$9+8*7*(6-5^4*3^2)+1$
-263998	$((9-8+7)^6+5+4^3 \wedge 2)*-1$	-314656	$9+8*7*(6-5^4*3^2)-1$
-264800	$(-9-87*6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-315561	$-987-((6/5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1))$
-265138	$(9-8*76)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-316477	$98-7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-265228	$(-9-8*76)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-316479	$98-7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-265279	$-9+(8-7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-316558	$9+8-7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-265543	$(-98*7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-316560	$9+8-7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-265545	$(-98*7+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-316574	$9-8-7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-265774	$9-8*7*65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-316578	$-9+8-7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-266028	$(-9*87+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-318274	$(-9+8)*7^6-5^4*321$
-266030	$(-9*87+6)*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-318942	$(-987*6)*54-(3/21))$
-266368	$(-9*8+7)*65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-321183	$9-(8+7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-266514	$9-876*5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-321185	$9-(8+7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-266516	$9-876*5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-321201	$-9-(8+7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-267050	$((-987+6)*5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$	-321203	$-9-(8+7-6)^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-267108	$(((-987-6)*5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-321551	$9*8*7*(6-5^4/3^2)+1$
-267110	$((-987-6)*5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$	-321553	$9*8*7*(6-5^4/3^2)-1$
-267278	$(-9*8-7)*65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-323381	$-9/8*7*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-267791	$9-8*7*65-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-324286	$9+8*(7-6^5)-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-268058	$(-98+7)*65-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-324353	$(-9+8-7)*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-268060	$-98*7*6+5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$	-324398	$9-8*(7+6^5)-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-268062	$((-987*6)+5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$	-324400	$9-8*(7+6^5)-4^3 \wedge 2-1$
-268070	$((-987*6)-(5+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-325323	$(-9/8-7)*6^5-4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-268072	$(-987*6)-((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^2))))+1$	-326015	$(9+8-7^6)*5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$
-268256	$9-8*765-4^3 \wedge 2-1$	-326051	$9+(8-7^6)*5+4^3 \wedge 2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-326053	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-396546	$((-987*6)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-326069	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-398072	$((-98*76)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-326071	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-398074	$(-98*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-326076	$(-98-76)^{*}(((5^{\wedge}4)^{*}3)-2)+1$	-398419	$987*((6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3))^*2)+1$
-326117	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-399405	$((987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))^*2)+1$
-326119	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-399406	$((987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))^*2)^*1$
-326131	$9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-399407	$((987*(6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))^*2)-1$
-326133	$9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-399423	$-9*((8-7+6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-326149	$-9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-399425	$-9*((8-7+6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-326187	$(-9-8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-400393	$987*((6-((5^{\wedge}4)/3))^*2)-1$
-328328	$-9*(8-(76-5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-400500	$(-9876-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-328330	$-9*(8-(76-5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-400502	$-9876-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-331769	$(9-8)^{*}7+(6-54)^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$	-403563	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/5*4^{\wedge}3*-2-1$
-332129	$-9^{\wedge}8(8-7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-405935	$-9*8*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-332500	$(-9+8)^{*}76*5^{\wedge}4/3*21$	-405937	$-9*8*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-332910	$9*(87-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-407769	$(-987+6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)-1$
-332912	$9*(87-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-408749	$((((-987+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)+1$
-335953	$(9+8)^{*}(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1$	-408751	$((((-987+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)-1$
-335955	$(9+8)^{*}(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1$	-409731	$(-987+6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)+1$
-338681	$(9-8*7*6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-409966	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+43)/21$
-338695	$(-9-8*7*6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-411500	$-9876/(((5/4)^{-3})^*2)-1$
-339903	$(-9-8+7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-414743	$(-987-6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)+1$
-339905	$(-9-8+7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-415727	$-9*8*(76^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)+1$
-339982	$(9+8)^{*}(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*32)+1$	-415729	$-9*8*(76^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)-1$
-339984	$(9+8)^{*}(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*32)-1$	-416480	$(9/(8+((7*6-5)^{\wedge}4+3)^*-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-341291	$(9+8)^{*}(-76-5^{\wedge}4*32)+1$	-417171	$(-987*(6+(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)))^*1$
-341293	$(9+8)^{*}(-76-5^{\wedge}4*32)-1$	-417173	$(-987*(6+(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^*2)))^*-1$
-344383	$(9-87)^{*}6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-417315	$-9*((8+7+6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-344385	$(9-87)^{*}6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-417317	$-9*((8+7+6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-346491	$9*(876-(((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^*21))$	-418916	$(987-(((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2))+1$
-351672	$-9*8*(7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4/3-2)-1$	-418918	$987-(((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1$
-353924	$9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-420890	$(-987-(((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2))+1$
-353926	$9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-420892	$-987-(((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1$
-354068	$-9*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-421202	$-9*(-8-((7-6)^*5)^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-354070	$-9*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-422107	$-987*((6+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))^*2)-1$
-354478	$98-(((7^{\wedge}6)+543)^*(2+1))$	-423093	$((-987*(6+((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))^*2)+1$
-354674	$-98-(((7^{\wedge}6)+543)^*(2+1))$	-423094	$((-987*(6+((5^{\wedge}4)/3)))^*2)^*1$
-354680	$9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-423095	$((-987*(6+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))^*2)-1$
-354682	$9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-424081	$-987*((6+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))^*2)+1$
-355554	$(-98765*4)/((3^{\wedge}-2)+1)$	-440575	$(9-8^{\wedge}7+6)/((5/(4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-362259	$-9*(876+(((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^*21))$	-442143	$9-8/7*((6-5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-364817	$-9*(8+7+6-5^{\wedge}4)/3^{\wedge}2-1$	-448767	$(-9-8-7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-366014	$(9+8*7)^{*}(-6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-448769	$(-9-8-7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-369518	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-456216	$(-9*8)*(((7/6)^*5432)-1)$
-369520	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-456360	$(-9*8)*(((7/6)^*5432)+1)$
-369536	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-457546	$9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-369538	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-457564	$-9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^{*}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-378792	$-9-(8+7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-458328	$-9*(8-(76+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-378794	$-9-(8+7)^{*}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-458330	$-9*(8-(76+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-379770	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-468074	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$
-379772	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-468125	$((-98/(7*6))^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*321$
-379780	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-470350	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
-379782	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-470444	$-9-(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
-379786	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-470748	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3)/2-1$
-379796	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-470842	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1$
-380748	$(9876-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-471446	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
-380750	$9876-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-471448	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3)/2-1$
-383176	$((98*76)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-471464	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
-384702	$((987*6)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-471466	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3)/2-1$
-384704	$(987*6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-482552	$98*(76-((5^{\wedge}4)^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)))$
-389631	$((987+6)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-488843	$9+87*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-389633	$(987+6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-488845	$9+87*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-389643	$(987-(6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-493500	$(-987*6)/(((5/4)^{-3})-(2^{\wedge}-1))$
-389645	$987-((6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-500073	$((-98*7)/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))+21$
-390450	$((98+76)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-500589	$98*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-390452	$(98+76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-500591	$98*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-390798	$(-98-(76+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-502604	$-9+8*(-7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1$
-390800	$-98-((76+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-502606	$-9+8*(-7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)/2-1$
-391605	$((-987+6)-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$	-502680	$-9*((8+76+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-391617	$(-987-(6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-502682	$-9*((8+76+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-392174	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)/3^*2+1$	-506987	$9-(((8*7)/6)^*54321)$
-392176	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)/3^*2-1$	-507005	$-9-(((8*7)/6)^*54321)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-509836	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+ (5^{\wedge}4321)$	-587973	$9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-512604	$(-9^{\wedge}87)^{\wedge}(654+((3/2)^{\wedge}-1))$	-587991	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-514690	$(9-8/7)^{\wedge}(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-588499	$9+8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-515523	$-9^{\wedge}((87+6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-589994	$(98+7)^{\wedge}(6-5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-515525	$-9^{\wedge}((87+6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-591297	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-520038	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+ (543^{\wedge}21)$	-591299	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-522874	$9+(-8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+4)/3^{\wedge}2+1$	-591368	$9-8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-522876	$9+(-8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+4)/3^{\wedge}2-1$	-591372	$-9+8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-526008	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+5432)+1$	-591443	$-9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-526010	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+5432)-1$	-592339	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-526906	$9^{\wedge}(8+(-7^{\wedge}6+543)/2)-1$	-592343	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-527115	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+5)+4321$	-592357	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-527125	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))-5)+4321$	-608228	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}76^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
-527350	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-614662	$((98+7^{\wedge}6)/5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-528524	$9^{\wedge}(-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}43)/2)+1$	-619948	$-98^{\wedge}(76+((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}((3^{\wedge}2)+1)))$
-528526	$9^{\wedge}(-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}43)/2)-1$	-633338	$98-(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-530453	$(987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge}+1$	-633340	$98-(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-530454	$987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-(2+1)))$	-633419	$9+8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-530455	$987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-633421	$9+8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-530821	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3+2)^{\wedge}-1$	-633435	$9-8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-530822	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3+2)^{\wedge}-1$	-634751	$-9/8^{\wedge}(7+6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-530877	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+543)+21$	-652326	$(-98-76)^{\wedge}(((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-530919	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+543)-21$	-652499	$(((-98-76)^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4))^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-531066	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+54)+321$	-652501	$(((-98-76)^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4))^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-531111	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-652674	$(-98-76)^{\wedge}(((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-531119	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-660674	$-9/8^{\wedge}((765+4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-531174	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))-54)+321$	-661724	$-9/8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4))^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-531683	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-661726	$-9/8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4))^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-531685	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-661769	$-9/8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-531708	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+54)-321$	-666635	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-5)-43)/(-2-1)$
-531763	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$	-679043	$9-8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-531771	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-679045	$9-8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-531816	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))- (54+321)$	-681250	$((-987+6)^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4))^{\wedge}((3^{\wedge}-2)+1)$
-531963	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))-543)+21$	-689312	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-532005	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))- (543+21)$	-689314	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-532427	$(-987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge}+1$	-697590	$9-8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-532428	$-987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-(2+1)))$	-697592	$9-8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-532429	$-987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-702071	$9^{\wedge}(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/(3/2))+1$
-535441	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)^{\wedge}-1$	-702073	$9^{\wedge}(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/(3/2))-1$
-535542	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-702215	$9^{\wedge}(-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/(3/2))+1$
-535757	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))+5)-4321$	-702217	$9^{\wedge}(-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/(3/2))-1$
-535767	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))- (5+4321))$	-711827	$(9-87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^{\wedge}3/2+1$
-536872	$((-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))-5432)+1$	-711829	$(9-87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^{\wedge}3/2-1$
-536874	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))- (5432+1)$	-717548	$(-987^{\wedge}(((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)-2))+1$
-538813	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^{\wedge}((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-717550	$(-987^{\wedge}(((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)-2))-1$
-542844	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))- (543^{\wedge}21)$	-718497	$(-9+8/7+6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-544958	$9+(87^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	-719502	$(-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))+21$
-544960	$9+(87^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	-719520	$((-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))+2)+1$
-544976	$-9+(87^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	-719521	$((-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))+2)^{\wedge}1$
-544978	$-9+(87^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	-719525	$((-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))-2)^{\wedge}1$
-553046	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))- (5^{\wedge}4321)$	-719526	$(-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))- (2+1)$
-554335	$(-98-7)^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-719544	$(-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))- 21$
-555360	$-98^{\wedge}(((76-(5/(4+3)))^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-720599	$-9/8^{\wedge}(((7/(6-5))^{\wedge}-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-555457	$(-98^{\wedge}(((76-(5/(4+3)))^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-721496	$(-987^{\wedge}(((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)+2))+1$
-555458	$(-98^{\wedge}(((76-(5/(4+3)))^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}1)$	-721498	$(-987^{\wedge}(((6/54)^{\wedge}-3)+2))-1$
-555459	$(-98^{\wedge}(((76-(5/(4+3)))^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-732735	$-9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4/3)))^{\wedge}2+1$
-559850	$-9+(8+7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-732737	$-9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4/3)))^{\wedge}2-1$
-559894	$9-(8+7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-736273	$98^{\wedge}(-7-(6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-559910	$-9-(8+7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-736275	$98^{\wedge}(-7-(6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-570618	$-9^{\wedge}((87/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))-21)$	-737861	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-570786	$((-9^{\wedge}87)/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))+21$	-766322	$-98^{\wedge}(7/((6-5^{\wedge}4))^{\wedge}(-3+2-1))$
-570828	$((-9^{\wedge}87)/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))-21$	-767583	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7)^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-570996	$-9^{\wedge}((87/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))+21)$	-784328	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4)/3-2+1$
-584151	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-786263	$((-9-87)/((6/543)^{\wedge}2))+1$
-584165	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-786264	$((-9-87)/((6/543)^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}1$
-584167	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-786265	$((-9-87)/((6/543)^{\wedge}2))-1$
-584222	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-786360	$(-9-87)^{\wedge}(((6/543)^{\wedge}-2)+1)$
-585047	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	-793584	$9^{\wedge}(-8-7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-585049	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	-793586	$9^{\wedge}(-8-7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-585102	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	-796619	$9^{\wedge}(8-7^{\wedge}6)+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-585158	$(-98^{\wedge}(76+((5^{\wedge}4)/3))^{\wedge}21)$	-796621	$9^{\wedge}(8-7^{\wedge}6)+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-585762	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^{\wedge}6))-54321$	-796629	$9^{\wedge}(8-7^{\wedge}6)-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-796631	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6)-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1028751	$((-9876*(5^{\wedge}4))/(3^{\wedge}2))-1$
-796763	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1038626	$-9876*((5^{\wedge}4)/(3^{\wedge}2))+1$
-796765	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1049522	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1$
-796773	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1051218	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6))*(5+4321)$
-796775	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1055362	$(98+7^{\wedge}6)*(-5-4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-820001	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6)/(5^{\wedge}-4/32)-1$	-1055969	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2))+1$
-821107	$(98-(((7^{\wedge}6)-54)/3))^*21$	-1055971	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2))-1$
-821511	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1056113	$9*(-8-(7^{\wedge}6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2))+1$
-821513	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1056115	$9*(-8-(7^{\wedge}6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2))-1$
-821863	$(98-(((7^{\wedge}6)+54)/3))^*21$	-1061567	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2))+1$
-823000	$-9876/(((5/4)^{\wedge}-3)-(2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1061569	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2))-1$
-825223	$(-98-(((7^{\wedge}6)-54)/3))^*21$	-1061711	$9*(-8-(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2))+1$
-836847	$(987-(6^{\wedge}(-5+(4^{\wedge}3))))*(2+1)$	-1061713	$9*(-8-(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2))-1$
-846399	$-9*(8*(7*6-(5-4/3)))^{\wedge}2+1$	-1071608	$((-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6))-5)*4321$
-846401	$-9*(8*(7*6-(5-4/3)))^{\wedge}2-1$	-1078623	$(-98-7)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-850339	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1078625	$(-98-7)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-850341	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1087500	$((-98-76)*(5^{\wedge}4))*(3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-850357	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1109388	$(-987*6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)-21)$
-850359	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1138800	$(-9+8/7*6)*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-850393	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1153438	$((-98+76)/5)*((4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-850421	$9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1155910	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-850439	$-9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1155912	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-850473	$(-9-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1155990	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-850475	$(-9-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1155992	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-859950	$(9-8)^*7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-1156008	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-863200	$-98*((7/(654+3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	-1156010	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-863297	$(-98/((7/(654+3))^{\wedge}2))+1$	-1157712	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(7-6))^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-863298	$(-98/((7/(654+3))^{\wedge}2))^*1$	-1157714	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(7-6))^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-863299	$(-98/((7/(654+3))^{\wedge}2))-1$	-1183167	$9^{\wedge}(-8-(-7-6))*(-5*4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-863396	$-98*((7/(654+3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	-1185916	$((98-(7+6)*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$
-876449	$(-9*8-7)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1185927	$((98-(7+6)*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-907564	$(98-((7^{\wedge}6)^*54))^*3/21$	-1192972	$98+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-907592	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)^*54))^*3)/21$	-1192974	$98+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-918995	$(-9+8/7)^*((6*(54+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1192998	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-925805	$(987/((6/((5^{\wedge}-4)+3))-2))+1$	-1193000	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-925806	$(987/((6/((5^{\wedge}-4)+3))-2))^*1$	-1193053	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-925807	$(987/((6/((5^{\wedge}-4)+3))-2))-1$	-1193055	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-933700	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3/2)+1$	-1193069	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-938646	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1193073	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-938648	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1198351	$9+8/7*(6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-938664	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1203321	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-938666	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1203323	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-969759	$(-98+7)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1203331	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-969761	$(-98+7)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1203333	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-977696	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-2)+1$	-1204301	$((98-((7^{\wedge}6)^*5))^*43)/21$
-977698	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-2)-1$	-1204497	$(98-(((7^{\wedge}6)^*5)^*43))/21$
-986960	$(-9-(-8/7-6))*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-1209575	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-995885	$(-9-((8*7)/6))^*54321$	-1209995	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}(6-5+4)-3/2)+1$
-996542	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-1209997	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}(6-5+4)-3/2)-1$
-996544	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-1219383	$(-987+6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*2)-1$
-998146	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-1221345	$(-987+6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*2)+1$
-998971	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))^*-1$	-1231155	$(-987+6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*2)-1$
-999670	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2))^*-1$	-1233117	$(-987+6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*2)+1$
-999862	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2))^*-1$	-1234299	$(-987-6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*2)-1$
-999939	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-1236285	$(-987-6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*2)+1$
-999948	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5*4-32)^*-1$	-1246215	$(-987-6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*2)-1$
-999951	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-54+3+2)^*-1$	-1248201	$(-987-6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*2)+1$
-999964	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5-43+2)^*-1$	-1262149	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-1000036	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5+43-2)^*-1$	-1299611	$(9+8*7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1000052	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5*4+32)^*-1$	-1300839	$9876-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$
-1000061	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3+2)^*-1$	-1300849	$9876-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$
-1000065	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5*(4+3^{\wedge}2))/-1$	-1302835	$9*876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-1000330	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5*(4^{\wedge}3+2))^*-1$	-1302837	$9*876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-1001019	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))^*-1$	-1303267	$(98*76)-(5*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1))$
-1008639	$(-9-87)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1303271	$((98*76)-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$
-1008641	$(-9-87)^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1303273	$(98*76)-((5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$
-1018874	$-9876*((5^{\wedge}4)/(3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-1303277	$(98*76)-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$
-1020474	$(98+7^{\wedge}6)*(-5-4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-1304793	$(987*6)-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$
-1024877	$98*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1304797	$((987*6)-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$
-1024879	$98*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1304799	$(987*6)-((5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$
-1028398	$((-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6))+5)^*4321$	-1304803	$(987*6)-(5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$
-1028749	$((-9876*(5^{\wedge}4))/(3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-1305247	$9*8*76-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1305249	$9*8*76-5*4^3*2-1$	-1320919	$9*(8-7^6)-5-4^3*2-1$
-1306021	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1321051	$-9*(8+7^6)+5-4^3*2+1$
-1306023	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1321053	$-9*(8+7^6)+5-4^3*2-1$
-1306605	$98*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1321061	$-9*(8+7^6)-5-4^3*2+1$
-1307695	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1321063	$-9*(8+7^6)-5-4^3*2-1$
-1307697	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1323494	$-9/8*(7^6-5)*(4*3-2)+1$
-1309722	$(987+6)-(5*((4^3*2))-1))$	-1323496	$-9/8*(7^6-5)*(4*3-2)-1$
-1309732	$(987+6)-(5*((4^3*2))+1))$	-1331874	$9-((87/((6/54)^3))^*21)$
-1309734	$987-(6+(5*((4^3*2))-1)))$	-1331892	$-9-((87/((6/54)^3))^*21)$
-1309738	$(987-(6+(5*((4^3*2)))))+1$	-1332072	$(-9-(87/((6/54)^3))^*21)$
-1309740	$987-((6+(5*((4^3*2))))+1)$	-1332410	$(9+(8/(7+6))^5)^{-4^3*2-1}$
-1309744	$987-(6+(5*((4^3*2))+1)))$	-1333295	$((9+8)*(-7^6+5)+4)/(3/2)+1$
-1309930	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1333297	$((9+8)*(-7^6+5)+4)/(3/2)-1$
-1309932	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1333631	$(9-(8-7-6)*5)^{4-3-2}*^{-1}$
-1309942	$9*8*7-6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1345071	$(-9^8+7*(6+5^4))/32+1$
-1309944	$9*8*7-6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1358112	$(-987*6)*(((5^4)/3)+21)$
-1310027	$98*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1393119	$((-98+7)/((6/54)^3))^*21$
-1310029	$98*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1413288	$(((-9*8)/7)^*6543)^*21$
-1310039	$98*7-6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1419999	$(-9*8+7-6)^5*4^3*2+1$
-1310041	$98*7-6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1428270	$98-7^6-5*4^3*2+1$
-1310102	$9+8*76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1428272	$98-7^6-5*4^3*2-1$
-1310104	$9+8*76-5*4^3*2-1$	-1428296	$9*8-7^6-5*4^3*2+1$
-1310188	$9+8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1428298	$9*8-7^6-5*4^3*2-1$
-1310190	$9+8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1428351	$9+8-7^6-5*4^3*2+1$
-1310209	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1428353	$9+8-7^6-5*4^3*2-1$
-1310374	$9*8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1428367	$9-8-7^6-5*4^3*2+1$
-1310376	$9+8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1438059	$-987*(((6/54)^{-3})^2)-1$
-1310541	$(98+76)-(5*((4^3*2))-1))$	-1439045	$((-987/((6/54)^3))^*2)+1$
-1310551	$(98+76)-(5*((4^3*2))+1))$	-1439047	$((-987/((6/54)^3))^*2)-1$
-1310571	$9*8*76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1439063	$9*8*(7+6-5^4*32)+1$
-1310581	$98+7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1439065	$9*8*(7+6-5^4*32)-1$
-1310629	$9+8*7-6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1440033	$-987*(((6/54)^{-3})^2)+1$
-1310631	$9+8*7-6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1440071	$-9*8*(7-6+5^4*32)+1$
-1310637	$98*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1440073	$-9*8*(7-6+5^4*32)-1$
-1310642	$9-8+76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1451510	$9-8*7*6^5*(4/3+2)+1$
-1310650	$9+8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1451512	$9-8*7*6^5*(4/3+2)-1$
-1310663	$98-7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1451528	$-9-8*7*6^5*(4/3+2)+1$
-1310668	$-9+8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1451530	$-9-8*7*6^5*(4/3+2)-1$
-1310778	$9+8-76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1476936	$(-9*876)*(((5^4)/3)-21)$
-1310794	$9-8-76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1567503	$-9*(8*(7/6+54-3))^2+1$
-1310809	$-9-87+6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1567505	$-9*(8*(7/6+54-3))^2-1$
-1310811	$-9-87+6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1571841	$987+(6*((5-(4^3*2))))+1$
-1310869	$-9*8-76-5*4^3*2-1$	-1571846	$(987+(6*(5-(4^3*2))))+1$
-1310889	$-98-(76+(5*((4^3*2))-1)))$	-1571848	$(987+(6*(5-(4^3*2))))-1$
-1310899	$-98-(76+(5*((4^3*2))+1)))$	-1571853	$987+(6*(5-((4^3*2))+1)))$
-1311046	$9-8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1571901	$987-(6*((5+(4^3*2))))-1$
-1311048	$9-8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1571906	$(987-(6*(5+(4^3*2))))+1$
-1311232	$9-8*7*6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1571908	$987-((6*(5+(4^3*2))))+1$
-1311234	$9-8*7*6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1571913	$987-(6*((5+(4^3*2))))+1$
-1311318	$9-8*76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1572742	$98-7+6*(5-4^3*2)+1$
-1311320	$9-8*76-5*4^3*2-1$	-1572802	$98-7-6*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-1311411	$-98*7-6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1572804	$98-7-6*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-1311413	$-98*7-6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1572817	$-9+8*7-6*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-1311508	$-9*8*7-6-5*4^3*2+1$	-1572911	$9-8*7+6*(5-4^3*2)+1$
-1311510	$-9*8*7-6-5*4^3*2-1$	-1572929	$-9-8*7+6*(5-4^3*2)+1$
-1311586	$9-8*76-5*4^3*2+1$	-1572931	$-9-8*7+6*(5-4^3*2)-1$
-1311588	$9-8*76-5*4^3*2-1$	-1572938	$-98-7+6*(5-4^3*2)+1$
-1311696	$(-987+6)-(5*((4^3*2))-1))$	-1572940	$-98-7+6*(5-4^3*2)-1$
-1311706	$(-987+6)-(5*((4^3*2))+1))$	-1572971	$9-8*7-6*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-1311708	$-987-(6+(5*((4^3*2))-1)))$	-1572986	$-98+7-6*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-1311718	$-987-(6+(5*((4^3*2))+1)))$	-1572989	$-9-8*7-6*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-1316637	$(-98*76)-(5*((4^3*2))-1))$	-1572991	$-9-8*7-6*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-1316647	$(-98*76)-(5*((4^3*2))+1))$	-1572998	$-98-7-6*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-1318163	$(-98*76)-(5*((4^3*2))-1))$	-1573000	$-98-7-6*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-1318173	$(-98*76)-(5*((4^3*2))+1))$	-1573397	$-9*8*7-6*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-1319733	$(-9*(8+7)/6)^*(5432-1)$	-1573399	$-9*8*7-6*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-1320219	$(-9*(8+7)/6)^*(5432+1)$	-1573815	$-987+(6*((5-(4^3*2))))+1$
-1320591	$-98*76-(5*((4^3*2))-1))$	-1573820	$(-987+(6*(5-(4^3*2))))+1$
-1320601	$-98*76-(5*((4^3*2))+1))$	-1573822	$(-987+(6*(5-(4^3*2))))-1$
-1320907	$9*(8-7^6)+5-4^3*2+1$	-1573827	$-987+(6*(5-((4^3*2))))+1$
-1320909	$9*(8-7^6)+5-4^3*2-1$	-1573875	$-987-(6*((5+(4^3*2))))-1$
-1320917	$9*(8-7^6)-5-4^3*2+1$	-1573880	$(-987-(6*(5+(4^3*2))))+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2201680	$(-9 - (8/7-6))^*((5+4)^{(3*2)}-1)$	-2420712	$9*8*((-7^(6-5+4)-3)^2-1)$
-2205685	$-98*(7+6*5^4*3^2)+1$	-2428496	$9*(87-6^45-4^43^2)+1$
-2205687	$-98*(7+6*5^4*3^2)-1$	-2428498	$9*(87-6^45-4^43^2)-1$
-2239406	$9+8*(7-6^4(-5+4^3)+2)+1$	-2428775	$9*(8^7-6^45-4^43^2)+1$
-2239408	$9+8*(7-6^4(-5+4^3)+2)-1$	-2428777	$9*(8^7-6^45-4^43^2)-1$
-2251902	$9-8*7^46-5*4^43^2+1$	-2429783	$-9*(8^7+6^45+4^43^2)+1$
-2251904	$9-8*7^46-5*4^43^2-1$	-2429785	$-9*(8^7+6^45+4^43^2)-1$
-2251920	$-9-8*7^46-5*4^43^2+1$	-2438172	$-9*((8765+(4^4(3^2))))-1$
-2251922	$-9-8*7^46-5*4^43^2-1$	-2438190	$-9*((8765+(4^4(3^2))))+1$
-2264896	$-9876*((5^4)/3)+21$	-2444192	$(9+(8/(-7-6))^-5)^4(3^2+1)$
-2277600	$(-9*8/7+6)^*((5+4)^{(3*2)}-1)$	-2460342	$(-9*(8+7))^(-6+5+4)+32+1$
-2280402	$9*((8765-(4^4(3^2))))+1$	-2460344	$(-9*(8+7))^(-6+5+4)+32-1$
-2280410	$(9*(8765-(4^4(3^2))))+1$	-2460371	$(9*(-8-7))^(-6+5+4)+3+2-1$
-2280412	$(9*(8765-(4^4(3^2))))-1$	-2460379	$(9*(-8-7))^(-6+5+4)-3-2+1$
-2280420	$9*(8765-((4^4(3^2))+1))$	-2460406	$(-9*(8+7))^(-6+5+4)-32+1$
-2285567	$-9*8^4(-7+6+5)^*(4^43^2-2)+1$	-2460408	$(-9*(8+7))^(-6+5+4)-32-1$
-2285569	$-9*8^4(-7+6+5)^*(4^43^2-2)-1$	-2470153	$98-((7^46)-(5/4/3))^*21$
-2342757	$987-6*((5^4(4^4(3/2))))-1$	-2471105	$-98-(((7^46)+(5/4/3))^*21)$
-2342762	$(987-(6*(5^4(4^4(3/2)))))+1$	-2480055	$-9^8*7/6^45*4^43^2+1$
-2342764	$987-((6*(5^4(4^4(3/2))))+1)$	-2480061	$-9^8*7/6^45*4^43^2-1$
-2342769	$987-(6*(5^4(4^4(3/2))))+1$	-2539475	$98*(7-6^45*(4/3+2))-1$
-2344731	$-987-6*((5^4(4^4(3/2))))-1$	-2540845	$-98*(7+6^45*(4/3+2))+1$
-2344736	$(-987-(6*(5^4(4^4(3/2)))))+1$	-2540847	$-98*(7+6^45*(4/3+2))-1$
-2344738	$-987-((6*(5^4(4^4(3/2))))+1)$	-2545144	$(9/(8-((76-5)^4)^3))^(-2+1)$
-2344743	$-987-(6*((5^4(4^4(3/2))))+1)$	-2621433	$9*((8^47/6^5+5)/4/(3^2))+1$
-2351456	$9*(876-5-4^43^2)+1$	-2621447	$9*((8^47/6^5+5)/4/(-3^2))-1$
-2351458	$9*(876-5-4^43^2)-1$	-2647214	$9/8*(7^46+5)^4*(-3-2)+1$
-2352267	$((98-((7^46)^5))^4)+321$	-2647216	$9/8*(7^46+5)^4*(-3-2)-1$
-2352586	$(98-7^46*5)^4+3-2+1$	-2693106	$-9^8+7+(6+5-4)^43^2+1$
-2352619	$(98-7^46*5)^4-32+1$	-2693108	$-9^8+7+(6+5-4)^43^2-1$
-2352621	$(98-7^46*5)^4-32-1$	-2745344	$(-98*((7^46)^5+43))/21$
-2352688	$(9*8-7^46*5)^4+3+2-1$	-2792286	$((-9/8)*((7^46)+543))^*21$
-2352943	$9-(-8+7^46*5)^4-3-2+1$	-2808666	$(98/7)^6(6-((5^4)^321))$
-2353299	$(-9*8-7^46*5)^4-32+1$	-2808834	$(-98/7)^6(6+((5^4)^321))$
-2353374	$(-98-7^46*5)^4-3+2-1$	-2822182	$98-(((7^46)-54)^*(3+21))$
-2353693	$((-98-((7^46)^5))^4)-321$	-2822378	$-98-(((7^46)-54)^*(3+21))$
-2358512	$9*(87^4(6-5)-4^43^2)+1$	-2823368	$9-8*((7^46-5-4)^3+2)-1$
-2358514	$9*(87^4(6-5)-4^43^2)-1$	-2823446	$9-8*(7^46-5)^4*(4-3+2)+1$
-2358944	$-9*(8-7*6-5+4^43^2)+1$	-2823448	$9-8*(7^46-5)^4*(4-3+2)-1$
-2358946	$-9*(8-7*6-5+4^43^2)-1$	-2823464	$-9-8*(7^46-5)^4*(4-3+2)+1$
-2359034	$-9*(8-7*6+5+4^43^2)+1$	-2823466	$-9-8*(7^46-5)^4*(4-3+2)-1$
-2359036	$-9*(8-7*6+5+4^43^2)-1$	-2823784	$-9-8*((7^46+5+4)^3-2)+1$
-2359061	$9*(8+7+6+5-4^43^2)+1$	-2824774	$98-(((7^46)+54)^*(3+21))$
-2359063	$9*(8+7+6+5-4^43^2)-1$	-2824970	$-98-(((7^46)+54)^*(3+21))$
-2359160	$9*(8+7^4(6-5)-4^43^2)+1$	-2825759	$((9-8^7+6)^4(5-4+3)-2)^*-1$
-2359162	$9*(8+7^4(6-5)-4^43^2)-1$	-2847613	$9-((8+7)^46-5)/4+32+1$
-2359221	$9-8^47+65-4^43^2+1$	-2847615	$9-((8+7)^46-5)/4+32-1$
-2359430	$-9*(8+7^4(6-5)+4^43^2)+1$	-2847622	$9-((8+7)^46-5)/4+3+21$
-2359432	$-9*(8+7^4(6-5)+4^43^2)-1$	-2849111	$9*(8-7^46^45-4^43^2)+1$
-2359556	$9*(8-7^46+5-4^43^2)+1$	-2849113	$9*(8-7^46^45-4^43^2)-1$
-2359558	$9*(8-7^46+5-4^43^2)-1$	-2850820	$-98*((((7^46)-5)/4)-321)$
-2359565	$9^4(8-7)^*(-6^5-4^43^2)+1$	-2851065	$-98*((((7^46)+5)/4)-321)$
-2359567	$9^4(8-7)^*(-6^5-4^43^2)-1$	-2881957	$((-98*((7^46)-5))/4)+321$
-2359646	$9*(8-7^46-5-4^43^2)+1$	-2882202	$((-98*((7^46)+5))/4)+321$
-2359648	$9*(8-7^46-5-4^43^2)-1$	-2882586	$987-((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2)))-1$
-2359808	$9*(8+(-7-6)^5-4^43^2)+1$	-2882596	$(987-((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$
-2359810	$9*(8+(-7-6)^5-4^43^2)-1$	-2882598	$987-(((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$
-2360078	$-9*(87^4(6-5)+4^43^2)+1$	-2882599	$((-98*((7^46)-5))/4)-321$
-2360080	$-9*(87^4(6-5)+4^43^2)-1$	-2882608	$987-((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2))+1)$
-2366108	$9*(8-765-4^43^2)+1$	-2882844	$((-98*((7^46)+5))/4)-321$
-2366110	$9*(8-765-4^43^2)-1$	-2884560	$-987-(((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2)))-1)$
-2366252	$-9*(8+765+4^43^2)+1$	-2884570	$(-987-((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$
-2366254	$-9*(8+765+4^43^2)-1$	-2884572	$-987-(((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$
-2367062	$9-8^47-6^45-4^43^2+1$	-2884582	$-987-((6+5)^*(4^4(3^2))+1)$
-2367064	$9-8^47-6^45-4^43^2-1$	-2887083	$((987-6)^4((-5+4)^3))^(-2-1)$
-2367082	$-9-8^47-6^45-4^43^2-1$	-2889917	$((((-98+76)^45)/((4/3)^2))+1)$
-2367224	$-9*(876+5+4^43^2)+1$	-2889919	$((((-98+76)^45)/((4/3)^2))-1)$
-2367226	$-9*(876+5+4^43^2)-1$	-2913736	$-98*((((7^46)-5)/4)+321)$
-2376567	$((-9+8)/(7-6))^*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	-2913981	$-98*((((7^46)+5)/4)+321)$
-2419704	$-9*8*((7^4(6-5+4)-3)^2-1)$	-2922507	$(-987^4((6-5+4)^3))^*(2+1)$
-2419848	$9*8*((-7^4(6-5+4)+3)^2-1)$	-2958147	$((987+6)^4((-5+4)^3))^*(-2-1)$
-2420568	$-9*8*((7^4(6-5+4)+3)^2-1)$	-2999815	$-9*((8*(7+65)+4/3)^2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2999833	$-9 * ((8 * (7 + 65) + 4 / 3) ^ 2 + 1)$	-3494149	$-987 - (((6 - ((5^4) * 3))^2) + 1)$
-3038294	$9 - 8 * (7^6 - 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$	-3529079	$9 * (8 - 7^6 + 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) + 1$
-3038296	$9 - 8 * (7^6 - 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$	-3529081	$9 * (8 - 7^6 + 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) - 1$
-3038312	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 - 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$	-3529379	$9 * (8 - 7^6 - 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) + 1$
-3038314	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 - 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$	-3529381	$9 * (8 - 7^6 - 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) - 1$
-3041969	$98 - 7^6 * 543 / 21$	-3529444	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * 5^4 * 3 - 2) + 1$
-3042050	$(9 + 8) - (((7^6) * 543) / 21)$	-3529466	$9 + (-8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3) / 2 - 1$
-3042066	$9 - (8 + (((7^6) * 543) / 21))$	-3529472	$-9 + 8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3 / 2 - 1$
-3042068	$(-9 + 8) - (((7^6) * 543) / 21)$	-3529474	$-9 + (8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3) / 2 + 1$
-3042084	$-9 - (8 + (((7^6) * 543) / 21))$	-3529486	$-9 - 8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3 / 2 + 1$
-3042165	$-98 - 7^6 * 543 / 21$	-3529488	$-9 - 8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3 / 2 - 1$
-3084479	$(-9 - 8) * 7^6 * 5 * (4 / 3 + 2) + 1$	-3529496	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 * 5^4 * 3 + 2) - 1$
-3084481	$(-9 - 8) * 7^6 * 5 * (4 / 3 + 2) - 1$	-3529541	$-9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3 / 2 + 1$
-3091188	$-9876 * (((5^4) + 3) / 2) - 1$	-3529543	$-9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3 / 2 - 1$
-3111791	$-98 - (7^6) ^ (5 - 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$	-3529567	$-98 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3 / 2 + 1$
-3137319	$(-9 - 8 * 7^6 + 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) + 1$	-3529859	$9 * (-8 - 7^6 - 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) + 1$
-3137321	$(-9 - 8 * 7^6 + 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) - 1$	-3529861	$9 * (-8 - 7^6 - 5) * (4 / 3 + 2) - 1$
-3142928	$9 * (-8^7 / 6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2) + 1$	-3539173	$(987 - ((6 + ((5^4) * 3))^2)) + 1$
-3142930	$9 * (-8^7 / 6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2) - 1$	-3537174	$(987 - ((6 + ((5^4) * 3))^2)) * 1$
-3148526	$-9 * (8^7 / 6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2) + 1$	-3537175	$987 - (((6 + ((5^4) * 3))^2) + 1)$
-3148528	$-9 * (8^7 / 6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2) - 1$	-3539147	$(-987 - ((6 + ((5^4) * 3))^2)) + 1$
-3175010	$9 * (8 - (7^6 - 54) * 3 - 2) + 1$	-3539148	$(-987 - ((6 + ((5^4) * 3))^2)) * 1$
-3175012	$9 * (8 - (7^6 - 54) * 3 - 2) - 1$	-3539149	$-987 - (((6 + ((5^4) * 3))^2) + 1)$
-3175118	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * 3 - 2) + 1$	-3587142	$((-9^8) + 765) / (4 * 3) + 21$
-3175120	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * 3 - 2) - 1$	-3587184	$((-9^8) + 765) / (4 * 3) - 21$
-3176189	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) + 1$	-3645347	$98 - (((7^6) - 54) * (32 - 1))$
-3176191	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3645543	$-98 - (((7^6) - 54) * (32 - 1))$
-3176225	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) + 1$	-3648695	$98 - (((7^6) + 54) * (32 - 1))$
-3176227	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) - 1$	-3648891	$-98 - (((7^6) + 54) * (32 - 1))$
-3176371	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3651912	$-9 * (8 + 7 - 6 + 5^4 + 3) ^ 2 - 1$
-3176405	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) + 1$	-3669976	$9 - 8^7 + 6 * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$
-3176407	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3669978	$9 - 8^7 + 6 * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$
-3176461	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 - 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3669994	$-9 - 8^7 + 6 * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$
-3176585	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * 3 + 2) + 1$	-3670001	$98 / 7 * (6 - 5 - 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$
-3176587	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3670003	$98 / 7 * (6 - 5 - 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$
-3176639	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) + 1$	-3670029	$-98 / 7 * (6 - 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$
-3176641	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3670031	$-98 / 7 * (6 - 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$
-3176819	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) + 1$	-3670038	$9 - 8^7 - 6 * (5 + 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$
-3176821	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) - 1$	-3670169	$-98 / 7 * (6 + 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$
-3176855	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) + 1$	-3670171	$-98 / 7 * (6 + 5 + 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$
-3176857	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 + 2) - 1$	-3677769	$(-987 + 6) * (((5^4) * 3) ^ 2) - 1$
-3177926	$9 * (8 - (7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) + 1$	-3678749	$((((-987 + 6) * (5^4) * 3) ^ 2) + 1$
-3177928	$9 * (8 - (7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) - 1$	-3678751	$((((-987 + 6) * (5^4) * 3) ^ 2) - 1$
-3178034	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) + 1$	-3679731	$(-987 + 6) * (((5^4) * 3) ^ 2) + 1$
-3178036	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * 3 - 2) - 1$	-3680899	$9 - 8^7 / 6 * ((5^4 + 3) ^ 2 - 1)$
-3232478	$9 - 8 * (7 + 6) ^ 5 - 4^3 * 2 + 1$	-3680917	$-9 - 8^7 / 6 * ((5^4 + 3) ^ 2 - 1)$
-3232480	$9 - 8 * (7 + 6) ^ 5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1$	-3705713	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 5) * (4 + 3) / 2) + 1$
-3294034	$-9 + 8 + (7^6 - 5) * (4 - 32) - 1$	-3705715	$9 * (8 + (-7^6 + 5) * (4 + 3) / 2) - 1$
-3294294	$9 + 8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 - 32) + 1$	-3706172	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 + 3) / 2) + 1$
-3294296	$9 + 8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 - 32) - 1$	-3706174	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 + 3) / 2) - 1$
-3294310	$9 - 8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 - 32) + 1$	-3722757	$(-987 - 6) * (((5^4) * 3) ^ 2) - 1$
-3310752	$(-9 - 8) * 7^6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 + 1$	-3723749	$((((-987 - 6) * (5^4) * 3) ^ 2) + 1$
-3310754	$(-9 - 8) * 7^6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 - 1$	-3723751	$((((-987 - 6) * (5^4) * 3) ^ 2) - 1$
-3312472	$-9 * 8 - (7 * 65^4) ^ (3 - 2 + 1)$	-3724743	$(-987 - 6) * (((5^4) * 3) ^ 2) + 1$
-3356234	$-9 - (8 * ((7 - 65) * 4 + 3))^2 - 1$	-3724899	$-9 * ((8^7 - 6^5) / (4 * 3))^2 + 1$
-3363555	$-9 * (8 * (76 + 5 / (4^3)))^2 + 1$	-3724901	$-9 * ((8^7 - 6^5) / (4 * 3))^2 - 1$
-3363557	$-9 * (8 * (76 + 5 / (4^3)))^2 - 1$	-3748017	$9 * 8 + 7 - ((6 + 5)^4) ^ (3 + 2) - 1$
-3407789	$9 + 8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$	-3748091	$((98 / 7 + 6 * 5) ^ 4 - 3 - 2) / -1$
-3407791	$9 + 8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$	-3764926	$9 - 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3 - 2) + 1$
-3407805	$9 - 8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$	-3764930	$-9 - 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3 - 2) - 1$
-3407809	$-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$	-3764938	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 + 5) * 4 ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3407856	$9 - 8^7 + 6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 + 1$	-3779031	$98 + 7 - (6^5 - 5^4) ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3407858	$9 - 8^7 + 6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 - 1$	-3779045	$98 - 7 - (6^5 - 5^4) ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3407868	$9 - 8^7 - 6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 + 1$	-3779058	$-9 + 87 - (6^5 - 5^4) ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3407870	$9 - 8^7 - 6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 - 1$	-3779214	$9 - 87 - (6^5 - 5^4) ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3407935	$9 - 8 + (-7 - 6) * (5 + 4^3) ^ 2 + 1$	-3779227	$-98 + 7 - (6^5 - 5^4) ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3407939	$-9 + 8 + (-7 - 6) * (5 + 4^3) ^ 2 - 1$	-3779241	$-98 - 7 - (6^5 - 5^4) ^ (3 - 2) - 1$
-3492173	$(987 - ((6 - ((5^4) * 3))^2)) + 1$	-3794850	$(9 * (8 + 7) ^ 6 / (5^4 - 4 - 3)) ^ (-2 + 1)$
-3492174	$(987 - ((6 - ((5^4) * 3))^2)) * 1$	-3806302	$(98 - ((76 + ((5^4) * 3))^2)) + 1$
-3492175	$987 - (((6 - ((5^4) * 3))^2) + 1)$	-3806304	$98 - (((76 + ((5^4) * 3))^2) + 1)$
-3494147	$(-987 - ((6 - ((5^4) * 3))^2)) + 1$	-3806498	$(-98 - ((76 + ((5^4) * 3))^2)) + 1$
-3494148	$(-987 - ((6 - ((5^4) * 3))^2)) * 1$	-3806500	$-98 - (((76 + ((5^4) * 3))^2) + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-5333022	$9*(8 - ((7^6)^5) + 4321))$	-6990319	$(-9-8^7+65)*(4/3+2)+1$
-5333166	$-9*((8+((7^6)^5))+4321)$	-6990321	$(-9-8^7+65)*(4/3+2)-1$
-5372800	$-98*(7^6-(5^4)^3)/2+1$	-6990439	$(9-8^7+6+5)*(4/3+2)+1$
-5372802	$-98*(7^6-(5^4)^3)/2-1$	-6990441	$(9-8^7+6+5)*(4/3+2)-1$
-5415775	$(((-98+76)^5)-(4^(3^2)))+1$	-6990481	$(9-8^7-6+5)*(4/3+2)-1$
-5415777	$((-98+76)^5)-(4^(3^2))+1$	-6990499	$(-9-8^7+6+5)*(4/3+2)+1$
-5423104	$(9+(8-76)^5)/4^(-3*2-1)$	-7084204	$(9-(8/7)^(-6^5))*-4^(3^2+1)$
-5437500	$(9+8-7)^6*(5+4/3)^(-2-1)$	-7174469	$(-9^8-7)/6-5^*4/3^*2-1$
-5556708	$9*(8-7^6)^5-4^3^2+1$	-7176490	$98+7^6*(5-4^3-2)+1$
-5556710	$9*(8-7^6)^5-4^3^2-1$	-7176492	$98+7^6*(5-4^3-2)-1$
-5576411	$((98/7)^6-5^(4+3+2))*-1$	-7176686	$-98+7^6*(5-4^3-2)+1$
-5670231	$(-9+8)^7*(6^5)^4+32+1$	-7176688	$-98+7^6*(5-4^3-2)-1$
-5738096	$-98*((7^6-543)/2)-1$	-7267387	$((98/7)^6-5-4^3^2)*-1$
-5738292	$-98*((7^6-543)/2)+1$	-7294530	$9+8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3-2)+1$
-5764523	$(98*(7^6+5)+4^3)/2+1$	-7294532	$9+8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3-2)-1$
-5764525	$(98*(7^6+5)+4^3)/2-1$	-7294546	$9-8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3-2)+1$
-5764549	$(98*(7^6+5)+4^3)/2+1$	-7294550	$-9+8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3-2)-1$
-5764551	$(98*(7^6+5)+4^3)/2-1$	-7361046	$(-987^6)*(((5^4)-3)^2)-1$
-5764561	$(98*(7^6+5)-4^3)/2+1$	-7365981	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)-3)^2)-1$
-5764563	$(98*(7^6+5)-4^3)/2-1$	-7367955	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)-3)^2)+1$
-5764587	$(98*(7^6+5)-4^3)/2+1$	-7372890	$(-987^6)*(((5^4)-3)^2)+1$
-5764589	$(98*(7^6+5)-4^3)/2-1$	-7395591	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)-3)^2)-1$
-5765013	$(-98*(7^6+5)+4^3)/2+1$	-7397565	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)-3)^2)+1$
-5765015	$(-98*(7^6+5)+4^3)/2-1$	-7398390	$9-(8*(7^(-6+5+4)+3))^2+1$
-5765077	$(-98*(7^6+5)-4^3)/2+1$	-7398392	$9-(8*(7^(-6+5+4)+3))^2-1$
-5765079	$(-98*(7^6+5)-4^3)/2-1$	-7398408	$-9-(8*(7^(-6+5+4)+3))^2+1$
-5767036	$(98-76)*((5-(4^(3^2)))+1)$	-7398410	$-9-(8*(7^(-6+5+4)+3))^2-1$
-5767080	$(98-76)*((5-(4^(3^2)))+1)$	-7406427	$(98-((7^6-54)^3))^21$
-5767256	$(-98+76)*((5+4^(3^2))-1)$	-7407435	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)+3)^2)-1$
-5788124	$(98+7)^6*(-6+5+4)^*(-3-2)+1$	-7409409	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)+3)^2)+1$
-5788126	$(98+7)^6*(-6+5+4)^*(-3-2)-1$	-7410543	$(-98-((7^6-54)^3))^21$
-5791310	$-98*((7^6+543)/2)-1$	-7413231	$(98-((7^6+54)^3))^21$
-5791506	$-98*((7^6+543)/2)+1$	-7417347	$(-98-((7^6+54)^3))^21$
-5823449	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^*(4+3/2))+1$	-7432110	$(-987^6)*(((5^4)+3)^2)-1$
-5823451	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^*(4+3/2))-1$	-7437045	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)+3)^2)-1$
-5825450	$(-9-8^7-6+5)^*(4/3)^2+1$	-7439019	$-987^6*((6*(5^4)+3)^2)+1$
-5942859	$((-9+8/7)+6)^*(5^4)^{(3+2)+1}$	-7443954	$(-987^6)*(((5^4)+3)^2)+1$
-5999843	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-7450804	$(98/7)^6-5^4^3/2)*-1$
-5999845	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	-7525259	$-9/8*((7-(6^5+4)/3)^2-1)$
-6029294	$9-(-8-(7-6^5)^4)^3^2+1$	-7525435	$((98/7)^6-5-4^(3^2))^*-1$
-6029296	$9-(-8-(7-6^5)^4)^3^2-1$	-7529206	$((98/7)^6-5*(4^3+2))^*-1$
-6111386	$9*(-8^7^6+5+4^3^2)+1$	-7529220	$-9+8-(7^6-5)^4^3-2-1$
-6111388	$9*(-8^7^6+5+4^3^2)-1$	-7529397	$((98/7)^6-(5+(4^3)^2))^*-1$
-6111476	$9*(-8^7^6-5+4^3^2)+1$	-7529411	$((98/7)^6-5^4/(3+2))^*-1$
-6111478	$9*(-8^7^6-5+4^3^2)-1$	-7529495	$((98/7)^6-5-4-32)^*-1$
-6131250	$((-987+6)^*(5^4))^*(3^2)+1$	-7529500	$((98/7)^6+5-4+3)^*-1$
-6149506	$((-9^8)/7)-((6-543)/21)$	-7529572	$((98/7)^6-5+4+3)^*-1$
-6149625	$((-9^8)/7)-((654^3)/21)$	-7529576	$((98/7)^6-5+4+3)^*-1$
-6162828	$987*(6-((5^4)^*(3^2)+1))$	-7529588	$((98/7)^6+5^4+32)^*-1$
-6174672	$-987*(6+((5^4)^*(3^2)+1))$	-7529594	$((98/7)^6+5^4*(3-2)^*-1$
-6206250	$((-987-6)^*(5^4))^*(3^2)+1$	-7529597	$((98/7)^6-5+4^3+2)^*-1$
-6218816	$((98/7)^6-5^4^3^2)^*-1$	-7529617	$((98/7)^6-5+4^3+2)^*-1$
-6230015	$-9*((8*(7-6)+5)^4)^3^2+1$	-7529636	$((98/7)^6+5^4*(3+2))^*-1$
-6230017	$-9*((8*(7-6)+5)^4)^3^2-1$	-7529674	$((98/7)^6+(5+4^3)^2)^*-1$
-6336141	$98-((7^6)^*(54-(3/21)))$	-7529675	$((98/7)^6-5+(4^3)^2)^*-1$
-6336337	$-98-((7^6)^*(54-(3/21)))$	-7529824	$((98/7)^6+(5+4)^3)^2)^*-1$
-6369755	$98-((7^6)^*(54+(3/21)))$	-7529852	$9-8-(7^6+5)^4^3+2+1$
-6369951	$-98-((7^6)^*(54+(3/21)))$	-7529866	$((98/7)^6+5*(4^3+2))^*-1$
-6529016	$(-9-(-8/7-6))^*(5^4)^3^2-1$	-7530167	$((98/7)^6+5^4+3^2)^*-1$
-6581055	$(-9/8-7)^*(6^5)^4-3-21$	-7530622	$((98/7)^6+(543^2))^*-1$
-6832995	$-9*((87^6*5+4)/3)^2+1$	-7531264	$((98/7)^6+(54^3)^2)^*-1$
-6832997	$-9*((87^6*5+4)/3)^2-1$	-7531696	$((98/7)^6+(5^4)^3)^*-1$
-6851250	$(((-98-76)^*(5^4))^3)^21$	-7533627	$((98/7)^6-5+4^3)^2)^*-1$
-6906195	$-9*((876^6)((-5+4)+3))-21$	-7533637	$((98/7)^6+5+4^3)^2)^*-1$
-6906573	$-9*((876^6)((-5+4)+3))+21$	-7536902	$-9/8*((7-6^5+4)/3)^2-1$
-6916900	$((9+8-7)^*(65^4+3))^2)^*-1$	-7591355	$-9/8*((7-(6^5-4)/-3)^2-1)$
-6941287	$9-8+7^6*(5-4^3)+2+1$	-7606949	$-9/8*((7-(6^5+4)/-3)^2-1)$
-6941295	$-9+8+7^6*(5-4^3)-2-1$	-7615335	$(98-((7^6)/5))^*(4+321)$
-6975052	$(-98^76)^*(5^4)^3/2-1$	-7647183	$9-8-7^6*5*(4+3^2)+1$
-6989948	$(-98^76)^*(5^4)^3/2+1$	-7647201	$-9-8-7^6*5*(4+3^2)+1$
-6990259	$(9-8^7+65)^*(4/3+2)+1$	-7647203	$-9-8-7^6*5*(4+3^2)-1$
-6990261	$(9-8^7+65)^*(4/3+2)-1$	-7661814	$9-(8*(7^(-6+5+4)+3))^2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7661816	$9 - (8*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-8609004	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+4)+321$
-7661832	$-9 - (8*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-8609012	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)-4)+321$
-7661834	$-9 - (8*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-8609265	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+43)+21$
-7679035	$(-98 - ((7^{\wedge}6)/5)) * (4+321)$	-8609307	$(-9^{\wedge}8+76)/5+43-21$
-7686397	$(98*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4/3-2)+1$	-8609309	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7-6)/5+4+32-1$
-7686399	$(98*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4/3-2)-1$	-8609351	$(-9^{\wedge}8+76)/5-43+21$
-7717695	$98*(-7*6*5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1$	-8609364	$(-9^{\wedge}8+76)/5-4-32+1$
-7717697	$98*(-7*6*5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1$	-8609366	$(-9^{\wedge}8+76)/5-4-32-1$
-7743840	$(-9-8)/7*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-8609393	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)-(43+21)$
-7764431	$9*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$	-8609646	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+4)-321$
-7764433	$9*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$	-8609654	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)-(4+321)$
-7764575	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$	-8610232	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)-(43*21)$
-7764577	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$	-8610613	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)-(4*321)$
-7764905	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)*2)+1$	-8613650	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)-4321$
-7764907	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)*2)-1$	-8613665	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+7)-6)/5)-4321$
-7830029	$(-9/87/((6*5)^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-8628553	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-(7^{\wedge}6))/5)+4321$
-7863303	$987-((6*5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$	-8637195	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-(7^{\wedge}6))/5)-4321$
-7863327	$987-(6*((5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$	-8643599	$-9*(8-(76-5)*4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-7863339	$987-(6*((5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-8643601	$-9*(8-(76-5)*4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-7863363	$987-((6*5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-8653584	$(-9+8)/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7864228	$98-7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-8823602	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4/3+2)))$
-7864335	$-98/7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-8823604	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4/3+2)))-1$
-7864366	$9-8*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-8823746	$9*(-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4/3+2)))+1$
-7864368	$9-8*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-8823748	$9*(-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4/3+2)))-1$
-7864397	$9-87-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-8910224	$-9*(8+7)*(65+4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-7864415	$-9-87-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-8910226	$-9*(8+7)*(65+4/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-7864417	$-9-87-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-8941225	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-7865005	$-98*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-8941227	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-7865007	$-98*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-8941251	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-7865102	$-9*87-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-8941253	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-7865104	$-9*87-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-8941306	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-7865277	$-987-((6*5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$	-8941308	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-7865301	$-987-(6*((5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$	-8941322	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-7865313	$-987-(6*((5*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-8941326	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-7865337	$-987-((6*5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-8941340	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-7890475	$(((-9-8+7)*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3*2)*-1$	-8941342	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-7890487	$(((-9-8+7)*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)*-1$	-8941395	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-7958303	$((9/8)-(7/6))^{\wedge}5+4321$	-8941397	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-7966945	$((9/8)-(7/6))^{\wedge}5-4321$	-8941421	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2+1$
-8020223	$-9*(8*(-7+(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-8941423	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*2-1$
-8020225	$-9*(8*(-7+(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-9122646	$((-98-76)/5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-8117777	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2+1$	-9248874	$-9876*(((5^{\wedge}4)*3)/2)-1$
-8117785	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2-1$	-9268626	$-9876*(((5^{\wedge}4)*3)/2)+1$
-8131648	$98*((7^{\wedge}6)-((5^{\wedge}4)*321))$	-9409473	$(98-(((7^{\wedge}6)-5)/4))*321$
-8159223	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-9440833	$98-(((7^{\wedge}6)-5)/4)*321$
-8159241	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-9441029	$-98-(((7^{\wedge}6)-5)/4)*321$
-8199521	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)-765)*4)+3)/21$	-9472389	$(-98-(((7^{\wedge}6)-5)/4))*321$
-8208578	$-9*8*7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-9482661	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))*-1$
-8208580	$-9*8*7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-9529559	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-8226918	$9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-9529561	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-8235331	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+2)+1$	-9529577	$9*(8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-8235333	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+2)-1$	-9529579	$9*(8+(-7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-8235357	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+2)+1$	-9641024	$-9*(8*7*6+5+4)*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-8288154	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-9641026	$-9*(8*7*6+5+4)*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-8448335	$9*8*(-7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-9647217	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(-5/4+3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-8448337	$9*8*(-7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-9647219	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(-5/4+3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-8467928	$9*(-8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-9699310	$9-(-8-(-7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-8467930	$9*(-8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-9699312	$9-(-8-(-7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-8473526	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-9699326	$9-(-8-(-7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-8473528	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-9699330	$-9-(-8-(-7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-8493119	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-9765506	$(9+8)*7-(6-5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-8493121	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-9765744	$(-9-8)*7-(6-5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-8542929	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)*(2+1)$	-9920658	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}2+1$
-8543001	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)*(2+1)$	-9926708	$(-9-8)*(((7^{\wedge}6)*5)-4321)$
-8593728	$(-98+76)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))-1)$	-9997039	$((-9-8)/7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2)+1$
-8593749	$((-98+76)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))+1)$	-9997041	$((-9-8)/7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2)-1$
-8593751	$((-98+76)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))-1)$	-9998437	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-8593772	$((-98+76)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))+1)$	-9999399	$(9+8)*(-7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(3+2)+1$
-8605008	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+4321$	-9999401	$(9+8)*(-7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(3+2)-1$
-8605023	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+7)-6)/5)+4321$	-9999739	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-8608045	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+(4*321)$	-9999741	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-8608426	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)+(43*21)$	-10000119	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*5+43+2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-10000121	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5+43+2-1$	-11010256	$9-8-7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-10000122	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5+43^{\wedge}(2-1)$	-11074210	$(-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*((5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-10000130	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5+4+32-1$	-11083023	$-987^*((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)-21$
-10000153	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3^{\wedge}(2-1)$	-11090919	$-987^*((6^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)-2))-1$
-10000159	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5+4+3-2+1$	-11092893	$-987^*((6^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)-2))+1$
-10000171	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-4-3+2-1$	-11100789	$-987^*((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)-(2+1)$
-10000177	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^*3^{\wedge}(2-1)$	-11102763	$-987^*((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)-2+1$
-10000189	$((9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-11104737	$-987^*((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)+2-1$
-10000191	$((9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-11114607	$-987^*((6^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)+2))-1$
-10000208	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-43^{\wedge}(2-1)$	-11121516	$(-987^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)+2+1$
-10000209	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-43-2+1$	-11124477	$-987^*((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)+21$
-10000211	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-43-2-1$	-11138549	$9^*((8+(-7-6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3+2))+1$
-10000609	$((9+8)^*(-7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)^*(3+2)+1$	-11138551	$9^*((8+(-7-6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3+2))-1$
-10000611	$((9+8)^*(-7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)^*(3+2)-1$	-11139029	$-9^*((8+7+6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3+2)+1$
-10001893	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-11139031	$-9^*((8+7+6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3+2)-1$
-10003289	$((-9-8)/7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+2)+1$	-11156259	$-9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*(2+1)$
-10003291	$((-9-8)/7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+2)-1$	-11197447	$(-9+8)^*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-10027768	$(9+8-7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11228112	$(-987^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)+21$
-10027770	$(9+8-7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11267452	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-10073622	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*5)+4321$	-11267454	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-10076975	$9^*8^*7^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1$	-11294205	$98-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43)^*2+1$
-10079672	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-11294306	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43)^*2-1$
-10199999	$(-9^*8^*7-6)/(5^{\wedge}4-3/32)+1$	-11294320	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43)^*2+1$
-10200001	$(-9^*8^*7-6)/(5^{\wedge}4-3/32)-1$	-11316175	$((-9+8)^*((7-65)^{\wedge}4))+321$
-10218881	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11316817	$(-9+8)^*((7-65)^{\wedge}4)+321$
-10218883	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11344750	$(-9-(8+7+6)^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-10223576	$9-(8^{\wedge}7-6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11370375	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)^{\wedge}2^*-1$
-10223578	$9-(8^{\wedge}7-6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11390394	$-9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-10223636	$9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11390874	$-9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-10223638	$9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11451455	$-9^*((8-76^*5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-10614586	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)/4+32+1$	-11451457	$-9^*((8-76^*5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-10747882	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7-6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11625009	$-9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*(2+1)$
-10747884	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7-6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11707022	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*((5+4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-10747918	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11751768	$9^*8^*7^*((-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3-2+1)$
-10747920	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11762856	$-9^*8^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3-2+1)$
-10747924	$9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11764803	$98-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*(3+2)-1$
-10747926	$9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11764890	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4-3/2)+1$
-10747942	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-11764892	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4-3/2)-1$
-10747944	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-11764971	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*(3+2)+1$
-10759735	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)/4-3/2+1$	-11764973	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*(3+2)-1$
-10759745	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)/4-3^*2-1$	-11764997	$-98-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*(3+2)+1$
-10761168	$((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4+321$	-11791740	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-10761339	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)+5)/4+321$	-11791742	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-10761377	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-76)+5)/4+321$	-11796488	$-9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)^*(43+2)+1$
-10761426	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)+(3^*21)$	-11796490	$-9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)^*(43+2)-1$
-10761465	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)+3+21$	-11986947	$((-9^*87)/((6/5^{\wedge}4)^3))^*21$
-10761471	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)-3+21$	-12000099	$98-7^{\wedge}6^*(54-3)^*2+1$
-10761473	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-(7^*65))/4)+321$	-12000101	$98-7^{\wedge}6^*(54-3)^*2-1$
-10761507	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)+3-21$	-12000214	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54-3)^*2+1$
-10761513	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)-(3+21)$	-12000216	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54-3)^*2-1$
-10761552	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)-(3^*21)$	-12003518	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-10761810	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)-321$	-12003520	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-10761825	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)/4-32+1$	-12117359	$((9+8-76)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)-2)^*-1$
-10761827	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)/4-32-1$	-12117363	$((9+8-76)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)+2)^*-1$
-10761981	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)+5)/4-321$	-12183776	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)+1$
-10762019	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-76)+5)/4-321$	-12183778	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)-1$
-10762115	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-(7^*65))/4)-321$	-12275868	$-9876^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
-10763623	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7-6^{\wedge}5)/4-3/2+1$	-12295620	$-9876^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
-10763633	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7-6^{\wedge}5)/4-3^*2-1$	-12299087	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+7)^*6)-543/21$
-10832967	$9^*(87-((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*321))$	-12299091	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-7)^*6)-543/21$
-10834533	$-9^*(87+((6^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*321))$	-12320763	$9-8^{\wedge}7^*6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-11009739	$98+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12320765	$9-8^{\wedge}7^*6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-11009741	$98+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12320771	$-9-8^{\wedge}7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-11009820	$9+8+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12320773	$-9-8^{\wedge}7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-11009822	$9+8+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12320816	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-11009836	$9+8+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12320818	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-11009935	$-98+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12394380	$-9876^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
-11009937	$-98+7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12414132	$-9876^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
-11010159	$98-7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12419972	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)+1$
-11010161	$98-7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12419974	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)-1$
-11010240	$9+8-7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12583321	$-9-8^{\wedge}7^*6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
-11010242	$9+8-7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12701335	$9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-12701337	$9 - (8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-15058441	$-9 - (8/(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-12742921	$-9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6 - (5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2 - 1)$	-15109983	$(-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}3))^*21$
-12845041	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-15116184	$9*8*((7 - (-6 - 5))^{\wedge}4 - 3)^* - 2 - 1$
-12845043	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-15326496	$(-9/(876*(54^{\wedge}3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-12845051	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-15496821	$(-9^{\wedge}8 + 7 - (6+5))/(4/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-12845053	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-15542853	$9 + (8/7 - 6)^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1$
-12939234	$(98 - ((7^{\wedge}6)^*5))^*(43 - 21)$	-15542871	$-9 + (8/7 - 6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
-12941292	$98 - (((7^{\wedge}6)^*5)^*(43 - 21))$	-15623952	$-98*((7/(65^*43))^{\wedge} - 2) - 1$
-12941488	$-98 - (((7^{\wedge}6)^*5)^*(43 - 21))$	-15624049	$(-98/((7/(65^*43))^{\wedge}2))^*1$
-12943546	$(-98 - ((7^{\wedge}6)^*5))^*(43 - 21)$	-15624050	$(-98/((7/(65^*43))^{\wedge}2))^*1$
-13213225	$((9+8)^*(7*6*5+4) - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-15624051	$(-98/((7/(65^*43))^{\wedge}2)) - 1$
-13257147	$((-9 - 8/7) + 6)^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1$	-15624148	$-98*((7/(65^*43))^{\wedge} - 2) + 1$
-13278735	$-9*(8^*7*65+4)/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-15660058	$(-9/(87*((6^*5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)^*2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-13278737	$-9*(8^*7*65+4)/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-15689751	$-9*((8^{\wedge}7)/6)^*5 - 4321$
-13411887	$98 - 7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)^*2 + 1$	-15767529	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7/6)^*5 + 4321$
-13411889	$98 - 7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)^*2 - 1$	-15824928	$((-98+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)))^*3)^*21$
-13411988	$-9+8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)^*2 - 1$	-16142489	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76 - 5)/(4/3^* - 2) + 1$
-13412002	$-9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)^*2 + 1$	-16142491	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76 - 5)/(4/3^* - 2) - 1$
-13412004	$-9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)^*2 - 1$	-16142546	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 76 - 5)/(4/3^* - 2) + 1$
-13613639	$(9 + (-8 - 7 - 6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3+2) + 1$	-16142548	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 76 - 5)/(4/3^* - 2) - 1$
-13613641	$(9 + (-8 - 7 - 6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3+2) - 1$	-16235544	$9+8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2 + 1$
-13696681	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7 + 65)/(43 - 21)$	-16235546	$9+8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2 - 1$
-13764275	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(-4 - 3^{\wedge}2))^*1$	-16235560	$9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2 + 1$
-13764277	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(-4 - 3^{\wedge}2))^* - 1$	-16235564	$-9+8 - 7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2 - 1$
-13765004	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^*1$	-16336907	$9 - (8/((7^*6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
-13765006	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^* - 1$	-16336925	$-9 - (8/((7^*6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
-13765589	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}2))^*1$	-16353213	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - (4^*3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-13765591	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}2))^* - 1$	-16554375	$((-987+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*(3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-13830960	$-9*(8+(7 - 6/5^{\wedge} - 4)/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-16592769	$-9^{\wedge}8 + 7/(6^{\wedge} - 5^*4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$
-13830962	$-9*(8+(7 - 6/5^{\wedge} - 4)/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-16711743	$-9*((-8 + (-7 - (6 - 5))^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-13882509	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2 + 1$	-16711745	$-9*((-8 + (-7 - (6 - 5))^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-13882511	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2 - 1$	-16752650	$-9+8 - ((7+6 - 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 * 1$
-13882564	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2 + 1$	-16756875	$((-987 - 6)^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*(3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-13882566	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2 - 1$	-16796155	$(-9/((8+7)^*(6^{\wedge}(5+4) - 3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-13882653	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2 + 1$	-16834609	$(9*(8+7*65) - 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-13882655	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2 - 1$	-16941482	$-9 - 8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3+2) - 1$
-13935288	$-9*(-8+(7+6/5^{\wedge} - 4)/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-17038308	$987 - (65*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1))$
-13935290	$-9*(-8+(7+6/5^{\wedge} - 4)/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-17038438	$987 - (65*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1))$
-13950006	$-98*((76*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3) - 2))^* - 1$	-17038576	$9*87 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-13950202	$-98*((76*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3) - 2))^* + 1$	-17038578	$9*87 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-13979798	$-98*((76*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3) + 2))^* - 1$	-17038673	$98*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-13979994	$-98*((76*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3) + 2))^* + 1$	-17038675	$98*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-13980122	$-9+8 - (7+6*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3))^{\wedge}2 * 1$	-17038855	$9*8*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14190288	$-9*(8+(-7+6/5^{\wedge} - 4)/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-17038857	$9*8*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14190290	$-9*(8+(-7+6/5^{\wedge} - 4)/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-17039268	$98 - 7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14250626	$-9+8 - (7+6*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 * 1$	-17039270	$98 - 7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14347360	$((-9^{\wedge}8) + (7^*654))/3 + 21$	-17039280	$9*8+7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14347402	$((-9^{\wedge}8) + (7^*654))/3 - 21$	-17039283	$-9+8+7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14347560	$((-9^{\wedge}8) + (76^*54))/3 - 21$	-17039294	$9+8*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14347866	$((-9^{\wedge}8) + (765^*4))/3 + 21$	-17039296	$9+8*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14347908	$((-9^{\wedge}8) + (765^*4))/3 - 21$	-17039345	$98/7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14348857	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6+5) + (4+3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-17039347	$98/7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14349906	$((-9^{\wedge}8) - (765^*4))/3 + 21$	-17039349	$9+8 - 7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14349948	$((-9^{\wedge}8) - (765^*4))/3 - 21$	-17039371	$-9 - 8+7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14350254	$((-9^{\wedge}8) - (76^*54))/3 + 21$	-17039406	$9 - 8*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14350412	$((-9^{\wedge}8) - (7^*654))/3 + 21$	-17039408	$9 - 8*7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14350454	$((-9^{\wedge}8) - (7^*654))/3 - 21$	-17039437	$9 - 87 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-14407956	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7+6)^*(5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-17039440	$-9*8 - 7 - 65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-14439528	$(9*8)^*(76 - ((5^{\wedge}4)^*321))$	-17040282	$-987 - (65*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1))$
-14450472	$(-9*8)^*(76 + ((5^{\wedge}4)^*321))$	-17040412	$-987 - (65*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1))$
-14564728	$(-9 - (8/7 - 6))^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-17076815	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3)/2 + 1$
-14625632	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-17076817	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3)/2 - 1$
-14676414	$9+8*7*(65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-17076833	$-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3)/2 + 1$
-14676416	$9+8*7*(65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-17076835	$-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3)/2 - 1$
-14676432	$-9+8*7*(65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-17293661	$(98*((-7^{\wedge}6+5)+4))^*3/2 + 1$
-14676434	$-9+8*7*(65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-17293663	$(98*((-7^{\wedge}6+5)+4))^*3/2 - 1$
-14683694	$9 - 8*7*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-17295131	$(-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4))^*3/2 + 1$
-14683696	$9 - 8*7*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-17295133	$(-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4))^*3/2 - 1$
-14734496	$9*(8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-17295143	$(-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5) - 4))^*3/2 + 1$
-14755608	$9*8*7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)^* - 2 - 1$	-17295145	$(-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5) - 4))^*3/2 - 1$
-14948064	$(-9*876)^*((5^{\wedge}4)^*3) + 21$	-17301473	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-15046650	$-9*((8 - 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-17301535	$-9*8^{\wedge}7 - 6*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-17339133	$(9-876)*(((5^4)^*32)-1)$	-19427122	$(987*((6-(5+4))^(3^2)))-1$
-17340867	$(9-876)*(((5^4)^*32)+1)$	-19428108	$987*((6-(5+4))^(3^2))-1$
-17516887	$-9^8+7^8*(5^4+3)+1$	-19619019	$(-987+6)*(((5^4)^*32)-1)$
-17516889	$-9^8+7^8*(5^4+3)-1$	-19620981	$(-987+6)*(((5^4)^*32)+1)$
-17529703	$-9+8-7^8*(5+(4^3)^2)-1$	-19859007	$(-987-6)*(((5^4)^*32)-1)$
-17529798	$-98-7^8*(5+(4^3)^2)+1$	-19860993	$(-987-6)*(((5^4)^*32)+1)$
-17529800	$-98-7^8*(5+(4^3)^2)-1$	-19877989	$9+(-8+7^6)^5*((4/3)^{-2}-1)$
-17563638	$9+(-8^7-6-5)^4*3^2+1$	-19878007	$-9+(-8+7^6)^5*((4/3)^{-2}-1)$
-17563640	$9+(-8^7-6-5)^4*3^2-1$	-19922390	$98+(76*((5-(4^4(3^2))))+1)$
-17563641	$-9^*8^7+6+5^4*3^2+1$	-19922465	$(98+(76*(5-(4^4(3^2)))))+1$
-17563643	$-9^*8^7+6+5^4*3^2-1$	-19922467	$(98+(76*(5-(4^4(3^2)))))-1$
-17563656	$-9+(-8^7-6-5)^4*3^2+1$	-19922542	$98+(76*(5-((4^4(3^2))+1)))$
-17563658	$-9+(-8^7-6-5)^4*3^2-1$	-19922562	$9-8+76*(5-4^4*3^2)+1$
-17699115	$(-9-876)*(((5^4)^*32)-1)$	-19922580	$-9-8+76*(5-4^4*3^2)+1$
-17700885	$(-9-876)*(((5^4)^*32)+1)$	-19922582	$-9-8+76*(5-4^4*3^2)-1$
-17999495	$((9+8)*(-7^8+5)+4)/3^{\wedge}-2+1$	-19922586	$-98+(76*((5-(4^4(3^2))))+1)$
-17999497	$((9+8)*(-7^8+5)+4)/3^{\wedge}-2-1$	-19922661	$(-98+(76*(5-(4^4(3^2)))))+1$
-18000143	$((-9-8)*(7^8-(5-4))/3^{\wedge}-2+1$	-19922663	$(-98+(76*(5-(4^4(3^2)))))-1$
-18000145	$((-9-8)*(7^8-(5-4))/3^{\wedge}-2-1$	-19922738	$-98+(76*(5-((4^4(3^2))+1)))$
-18000341	$((9+8)^7*7^8+5)^*(-4-3-2)+1$	-19923150	$98-(76*((5+(4^4(3^2))))-1)$
-18000343	$((9+8)^7*7^8+5)^*(-4-3-2)-1$	-19923225	$(98-(76*(5+(4^4(3^2)))))+1$
-18000449	$(9+8)*(-7^8-(5-4))/3^{\wedge}-2+1$	-19923227	$98-((76*(5+(4^4(3^2))))+1)$
-18000451	$(9+8)*(-7^8-(5-4))/3^{\wedge}-2-1$	-19923302	$98-(76*((5+(4^4(3^2))+1)))$
-18001026	$((9+8)^7*(7^8+5)-4)/-3^{\wedge}-2*1$	-19923322	$9-8-76*(5+4^4*3^2)+1$
-18001098	$((9+8)^7*(7^8+5)+4)/-3^{\wedge}-2*1$	-19923340	$-9-8-76*(5+4^4*3^2)+1$
-18512562	$-9876*((5^4)^*3)-(2^{\wedge}-1)$	-19923342	$-9-8-76*(5+4^4*3^2)-1$
-18522438	$-9876*((5^4)^*3)+(2^{\wedge}-1)$	-19923346	$-98-(76*((5+(4^4(3^2))))-1)$
-18541385	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)/2+1$	-19923421	$(-98-(76*(5+(4^4(3^2)))))+1$
-18541387	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-19923423	$-98-((76*(5+(4^4(3^2))))+1)$
-18604447	$-9^*8^7+6^5+4^4*3^2+1$	-19923498	$-98-(76*((5+(4^4(3^2))+1)))$
-18604449	$-9^*8^7+6^5+4^4*3^2-1$	-20089233	$9*(8/7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))-1)$
-18612055	$98-(((76-5)^*(4^4(3^2)))-1)$	-20117906	$9*(8+7^8*(5-4^3*2))+1$
-18612127	$98-(((76-5)^*(4^4(3^2)))+1)$	-20117908	$9*(8+7^8*(5-4^3*2))-1$
-18612158	$-9^*8^7+6+5+4^4*3^2+1$	-20185081	$-9^*8^7+6-5^4*3^2+1$
-18612160	$-9^*8^7+6+5+4^4*3^2-1$	-20185083	$-9^*8^7+6-5^4*3^2-1$
-18612193	$-9^*8^7+6^5+4^4*3^2+1$	-20308357	$(-9^8+7+(6^5)^4*3)/2^*1$
-18612195	$-9^*8^7+6^5+4^4*3^2-1$	-20308364	$(-9^8-7+(6^5)^4*3)/2^*1$
-18612197	$98-(((76-5)^*(4^4(3^2)))+1)$	-20447201	$-9^*8^7+6*(5-4^4*3^2)+1$
-18612212	$-9^*8^7+6+5+4^4*3^2+1$	-20447203	$-9^*8^7+6*(5-4^4*3^2)-1$
-18612214	$-9^*8^7+6+5+4^4*3^2-1$	-20447261	$-9^*8^7-6*(5+4^4*3^2)+1$
-18612251	$-98-((76-5)^*(4^4(3^2)))-1)$	-20447263	$-9^*8^7-6*(5+4^4*3^2)-1$
-18612321	$(-98-((76-5)^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$	-20709375	$(-9^*8-7^{\wedge}(6-5))^4*3^2+1$
-18612393	$-98-((76-5)^*(4^4(3^2)))+1)$	-20709377	$(-9^*8-7^{\wedge}(6-5))^4*3^2-1$
-18619999	$-9^*8^7-6^5+4^4*3^2+1$	-21177719	$-9^*8*(7^8+5)^*(4-3/2)+1$
-18620001	$-9^*8^7-6^5+4^4*3^2-1$	-21177721	$-9^*8*(7^8+5)^*(4-3/2)-1$
-18671867	$-9*(8^7-6^5*4^3*2)+1$	-21233485	$98-((76+5)^*(4^4(3^2)))-1)$
-18671869	$-9*(8^7-6^5*4^3*2)-1$	-21233843	$-98-((76+5)^*(4^4(3^2))+1)$
-18697220	$9*(8^7-(6-5-4)^3*2)+1$	-21249901	$(9^8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))/-2+1$
-18697222	$9*(8^7-(6-5-4)^3*2)-1$	-21249903	$(9^8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))/-2-1$
-18714374	$-9^*8^7-6+(5^4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-21249944	$(9^8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))/-2*1$
-18823758	$9-8*(7^8*5^4-3^2)+1$	-21294371	$98-(((7^8)^5*543)/(2+1))$
-18823782	$9-8*(7^8*5^4-3^2)+1$	-21294567	$-98-(((7^8)^5*543)/(2+1))$
-18823898	$-9-8*(7^8*5^4+3^2)-1$	-21318560	$(9+(8/(7+6))^{\wedge}-5)^4-4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-18823922	$-9-8*(7^8*5^4+3^2)-1$	-21388357	$(-9^8+7+(6^5)^4/3)/2^*1$
-18851867	$-9^*8^7+6^5*4^3*2+1$	-21388364	$(-9^8-7+(6^5)^4/3)/2^*1$
-18851869	$-9^*8^7+6^5*4^3*2-1$	-21444621	$(9^8-7-6-5^4)/-2+1$
-18872498	$-9^*8^7-6+5^4*3+2-1$	-21444623	$(9^8-7-6-5^4)/-2-1$
-18876238	$-9^*8^7+6-5^4*3-2+1$	-21444627	$(9^8-7+6-5^4)/-2+1$
-18929447	$-9^*8*(765+4^4*3^2)+1$	-21444630	$(9^8+7-6-5^4)/-2-1$
-18929449	$-9^*8*(765+4^4*3^2)-1$	-21464532	$(-9^8+7^8+5+4-3)/2+1$
-19051514	$-9*(8^7-(6-5-4)^3*2)+1$	-21464540	$(-9^8+7^8-5-4+3)/2-1$
-19051516	$-9*(8^7-(6-5-4)^3*2)-1$	-21484259	$(-9^8+7+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1$
-19059115	$9*(8-7^8*5^4)/3-2+1$	-21484261	$(-9^8+7+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1$
-19059161	$-9*(8+7^8*5^4)/3+2-1$	-21493835	$9^8*(7-(6+(5+4)^{-3}))/-2+1$
-19076867	$9*(8^7-6^5*4^3*2)+1$	-21493837	$9^8*(7-(6+(5+4)^{-3}))/-2-1$
-19076869	$9*(8^7-6^5*4^3*2)-1$	-21499357	$(9^8-7-6*(5^4)^3)/-2*1$
-19136500	$-9^*8^7+6+5-4^4*3^2+1$	-21499364	$(9^8+7-6*(5^4)^3)/-2*1$
-19136502	$-9^*8^7+6+5-4^4*3^2-1$	-21500028	$(9^8-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4-3))/-2+1$
-19398655	$(-9^{\wedge}(8-7)-65)^4*3^2+1$	-21500030	$(9^8-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4-3))/-2-1$
-19398657	$(-9^{\wedge}(8-7)-65)^4*3^2-1$	-21503452	$(9^8+7^8-5^4)/-2+1$
-19426134	$987*((6-(5+4))^(3^2))+1$	-21503454	$(9^8+7^8-5^4)/-2-1$
-19427120	$(987*((6-(5+4))^(3^2)))+1$	-21511687	$(-9^8+7+(6^5+4)^3)/2^*1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-21511694	$(-9^8-7+(6^5+4)^3)/2^*1$	-23861020	$(-98+7)^*(65+4^3^2)-1$
-21511699	$(-9^8+7+(6^5-4)^3)/2^*1$	-24137541	$((9+8)^(7-6+5)+4-32)^*-1$
-21511706	$(-9^8-7+(6^5-4)^3)/2^*1$	-24137597	$((9+8)^(7-6+5)-4+32)^*-1$
-21521705	$(9^8-7*(6+5)^43)/-2^*1$	-24138593	$((9+8)^(7-6+5)+4^(3+2))^*-1$
-21522159	$(-9^8+7*(6+5-4)^3)/2+1$	-24336527	$9-(((8*(7^6))^543)/21)$
-21522161	$(-9^8+7*(6+5-4)^3)/2-1$	-24336545	$-9-(((8*(7^6))^543)/21)$
-21522386	$(-9^8+76+5^4*3)/2-1$	-24353414	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4-32))+1$
-21522708	$(9^8-7-6^(5-4+3))/-2+1$	-24353416	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4-32))-1$
-21522717	$(9^8+7-6^(5-4+3))/-2-1$	-24504585	$(-98*((7/6)^54)^3)+21$
-21523300	$(-9^8+(7*6-5+4)^3)/2-1$	-24504627	$(-98*((7/6)^54)^3)-21$
-21523307	$(9^8-7*(6-5+4)^3)/-2+1$	-24504803	$98*((-7/(6/54))^3-2)-1$
-21523414	$(9^8+7*(6-5+4)^3)/-2-1$	-24609410	$(-9+8)^7*(6+(5^4*3)^2-1)$
-21523421	$(9^8+7*(6-5+4)^3)/-2+1$	-24928749	$-98*(7-6^5+4^3^2)+1$
-21524004	$(9^8-7+6^(5-4+3))/-2+1$	-24928751	$-98*(7-6^5+4^3^2)-1$
-21524335	$(-9^8-76-5^4*3)/2+1$	-25172063	$(9+87)^*(-65-4^3^2)+1$
-21524560	$(-9^8-7*(6+5-4)^3)/2+1$	-25172065	$(9+87)^*(-65-4^3^2)-1$
-21524562	$(-9^8-7*(6+5-4)^3)/2-1$	-25411360	$((-9+8)^*(76-5)^4)+321$
-21525015	$(9^8+7*(6+5)^43)/-2+1$	-25412002	$(-9+8)^*((76-5)^4)+321$
-21525017	$(9^8+7*(6+5)^43)/-2-1$	-25412048	$9*(8^7^6-5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-21535015	$(9^8-7+(6^5-4)^3)/-2^*1$	-25412050	$9*(8^7^6-5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-21535022	$(9^8+7+(6^5-4)^3)/-2^*1$	-25412162	$9-8*(7^6*54-3)/2+1$
-21535026	$(9^8-7+(6^5+4)^3)/-2+1$	-25412164	$9-8*(7^6*54-3)/2-1$
-21535034	$(9^8+7+(6^5+4)^3)/-2^*1$	-25412168	$(9*8^7^6-5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-21546684	$(9^8-7+6^(5+4-3))/-2+1$	-25412170	$(9*8^7^6-5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-21546686	$(9^8-7+6^(5+4-3))/-2-1$	-25412188	$9-8*(7^6*54+3)/2-1$
-21547357	$(9^8-7+6*(5*4)^3)/-2^*1$	-25412189	$(-9-8*7^6*54-3)/2+1$
-21547363	$(9^8+7+6*(5*4)^3)/-2+1$	-25412191	$(-9-8*7^6*54-3)/2-1$
-21547365	$(9^8+7+6*(5*4)^3)/-2-1$	-25412198	$(9*8^7^6+5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-21552884	$9^8*(7-(6-(5+4)^-3))/-2+1$	-25412200	$(9*8^7^6+5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-21552886	$9^8*(7-(6-(5+4)^-3))/-2-1$	-25412204	$-9-8*(7^6*54+3)/2+1$
-21562384	$(-9^8+76-5^4(4+3))/2+1$	-25412206	$-9-8*(7^6*54+3)/2-1$
-21562386	$(-9^8+76-5^4(4+3))/2-1$	-25413263	$9*8*(7^6+5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-21582181	$(-9^8-7^6+5+4-3)/2+1$	-25413265	$9*8*(7^6+5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-21582189	$(-9^8-7^6-5-4+3)/2-1$	-25582053	$-987*((6^5)^*((4/3)+2))-1$
-21602085	$(9^8-7-6+54^3)/-2+1$	-25583039	$((-987*(6^5))^*((4/3)+2))+1$
-21602087	$(9^8-7-6+54^3)/-2-1$	-25583041	$((-987*(6^5))^*((4/3)+2))-1$
-21602091	$(9^8-7+6+54^3)/-2+1$	-25584027	$-987*((6^5)^*((4/3)+2))+1$
-21602094	$(9^8+7-6+54^3)/-2-1$	-25615044	$98*((765-(4^3^2))+1)$
-21648383	$(-9^8-(7/6^5)^4^3)/2+1$	-25615141	$(98*(765-(4^3^2))))+1$
-21648385	$(-9^8-(7/6^5)^4^3)/2-1$	-25615143	$(98*(765-(4^3^2))))-1$
-21658356	$(9^8-7+(6^5)^4/3)/-2+1$	-25615240	$98*(765-(4^3^2))+1$
-21658358	$(9^8-7+(6^5)^4/3)/-2-1$	-25628943	$9*((8+7)^6-5)/-4-3-21$
-21658364	$(9^8+7+(6^5)^4/3)/-2^*1$	-25652774	$98*((76^5)-(4^3^2))+1$
-21660916	$(9^8+7^6+54^3)/-2+1$	-25652871	$(98*((76^5)-(4^3^2))))+1$
-21660918	$(9^8+7^6+54^3)/-2-1$	-25652873	$(98*((76^5)-(4^3^2))))-1$
-21705606	$(-98+(76/5))*((4^3^2))+1$	-25652970	$98*((76^5)-((4^3^2))+1)$
-21796776	$(9^8-7*(6-5^(4+3)))/-2+1$	-25674488	$-9*((8^7+6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-21796778	$(9^8-7*(6-5^(4+3)))/-2-1$	-25674490	$-9*((8^7+6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-21796819	$(9^8+7*(6+5^(4+3)))/-2^*1$	-25682076	$98*((76+5)-(4^3^2))+1$
-22132962	$9*(8-(((7^6)-543)^21))$	-25682173	$(98*((76+5)-(4^3^2))))+1$
-22133106	$-9*(8+(((7^6)-543)^21))$	-25682175	$(98*((76+5)-(4^3^2))))-1$
-22206513	$-987*((((6*(5^4))^3)^2)-1)$	-25682272	$98*((76+5)-((4^3^2))+1)$
-22208487	$-987*((((6*(5^4))^3)^2)+1)$	-25683153	$(98*(76-(5+(4^3^2))))+1$
-22213422	$(-987*6)*(((5^4)^3)^2)+1$	-25683155	$(98*(76-(5+(4^3^2))))-1$
-22338216	$9*(8-(((7^6)+543)^21))$	-25683252	$98*(76-((5+(4^3^2))+1))$
-22338360	$-9*(8+(((7^6)+543)^21))$	-25690013	$98*((7-6)^5-4^3^2)+1$
-22738357	$(9^8-7+(6^5)^4^3)/-2^*1$	-25690015	$98*((7-6)^5-4^3^2)-1$
-22738363	$(9^8+7+(6^5)^4^3)/-2+1$	-25690209	$98*((-7+6)^5-4^3^2)+1$
-22738365	$(9^8+7+(6^5)^4^3)/-2-1$	-25690211	$98*((-7+6)^5-4^3^2)-1$
-22937599	$(-98-7)/6*5^4^3^2+1$	-25695795	$98*(7-65-4^3^2)+1$
-22937601	$(-98-7)/6*5^4^3^2-1$	-25695797	$98*(7-65-4^3^2)-1$
-22952678	$-98*((((7^6)-543)^2)-1)$	-25696972	$-98*((76-5)+(4^3^2))-1$
-22952874	$-98*((((7^6)-543)^2)+1)$	-25697069	$(-98*((76-5)+(4^3^2))))+1$
-23058883	$((-98^((7+6)+5))/4)+321$	-25697071	$(-98*((76-5)+(4^3^2))))-1$
-23059525	$((-98^((7+6)+5))/4)-321$	-25697167	$-98*(7+65+4^3^2)+1$
-23124156	$(-98-76*(5-4^3^2))+1$	-25697169	$-98*(7+65+4^3^2)-1$
-23124158	$-98-76*(5-4^3^2)-1$	-25697952	$-98*((76+5)+(4^3^2))-1$
-23165534	$-98*((((7^6)+543)^2)-1)$	-25698049	$(-98*((76+5)+(4^3^2))))+1$
-23165730	$-98*((((7^6)+543)^2)+1)$	-25698051	$(-98*((76+5)+(4^3^2))))-1$
-23652700	$-9^8(8+7+6)^5+4^3^2+1$	-25698148	$-98*((76+5)+(4^3^2))+1$
-23652702	$-9^8(8+7+6)^5+4^3^2-1$	-25727254	$-98*((76^5)+(4^3^2))-1$
-23861018	$(-98+7)^*(65+4^3^2)+1$	-25727351	$(-98*((76^5)+(4^3^2))))+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-25727353	$(-98^*((76^5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-30115848	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*32+1$
-25727450	$-98^*((76^5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-30115850	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*32-1$
-25764984	$-98^*((765+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-30117898	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*32-1$
-25765180	$-98^*((765+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-30118294	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4^{\wedge}-3^*2)+1$
-25882770	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/2)+1$	-30118296	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4^{\wedge}-3^*2)-1$
-25882772	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/2)-1$	-30118312	$-9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4^{\wedge}-3^*2)+1$
-26302563	$((-987^{\wedge}(6/(5+4)))^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-30118314	$-9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4^{\wedge}-3^*2)-1$
-26451473	$98^*(7-6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-30118390	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*32+1$
-26451475	$98^*(7-6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-30118408	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*32+1$
-26470951	$-9^*8^*(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-30118410	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*32-1$
-26647996	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*(7+6))-543/21$	-30118474	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^*32-1$
-26874288	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+432)^*-1$	-30120456	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*32+1$
-27000831	$(-98^{\wedge}(7-6)-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-30120458	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*32-1$
-27000833	$(-98^{\wedge}(7-6)-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-30366254	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+2)+1$
-27378531	$9^*(8-(((7^{\wedge}6)^*543)/21))$	-30366256	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+2)-1$
-27378675	$-9^*(8+(((7^{\wedge}6)^*543)/21))$	-30601552	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2)+1$
-27428571	$-9/(8+7+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2))-1$	-30601554	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2)-1$
-27529937	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^*2))+1$	-31058329	$(98^*76-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2*-1$
-27529939	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^*2))-1$	-31072148	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)+1$
-27531944	$(-98-7)^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-31072150	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)-1$
-27531946	$(-98-7)^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-31189797	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*2)+1$
-28235750	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3/2+1$	-31189799	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*2)-1$
-28235752	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3/2-1$	-31190852	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6)+((5^{\wedge}4)^*321))$
-28619377	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-31457729	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5)^*(4+3^*2)+1$
-28619379	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-31457731	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5)^*(4+3^*2)-1$
-28661525	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-31640623	$((9-8-76)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)-2)^*-1$
-28661527	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-31640627	$((9-8-76)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)+2)^*-1$
-28697303	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-32000518	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^*3)^*2+1$
-28697305	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-32000520	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^*3)^*2-1$
-28697673	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-32284446	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)^*3)+21$
-28697675	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-32284488	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)^*3)-21$
-28697799	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-5-4))/(3/2)+1$	-32823998	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4-32))+1$
-28697801	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6-5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-32824000	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4-32))-1$
-28697803	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6-5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-32824142	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4-32))+1$
-28697825	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-32824144	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4-32))-1$
-28697827	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-33480462	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)^*6)/54)+321$
-28697829	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6-5-4))/(3/2)-1$	-33480814	$-9^{\wedge}8^*7^*6/54-32+1$
-28697851	$(-9^{\wedge}8-(7-6)^*54)/(3/2)-1$	-33481104	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)^*6)/54)-321$
-28697953	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-33881480	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+32)+1$
-28697955	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-33881482	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+32)-1$
-28698323	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-33882812	$9^*((-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-28698325	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-33883046	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3-2)+1$
-28734101	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-33883048	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3-2)-1$
-28734103	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-33884351	$9^*8^*(-7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3-2)+1$
-28776249	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-2)+1$	-33884353	$9^*8^*(-7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3-2)-1$
-28776251	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-2)-1$	-34138125	$((9-876)^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)^*21$
-28825229	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3/2)+1$	-34248671	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1$
-28825231	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3/2)-1$	-34248673	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)-1$
-28835818	$(-98+76)^*((5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-34398224	$-9^*((8^*7+6^{\wedge}5)/4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-28835839	$(((-98+76)^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-34398226	$-9^*((8^*7+6^{\wedge}5)/4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-28835841	$(((-98+76)^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$	-34436995	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)^*4)+321$
-28835862	$(-98+76)^*((5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-34437378	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7-6)/5^*4-3+2-1$
-28835950	$((-98+76)^*5)^*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-34437637	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)/5)^*4)-321$
-29646287	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(-4-3)/2+1$	-34570872	$-98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)-54)^*3)-21)$
-29646289	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(-4-3)/2-1$	-34574988	$-98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)-54)^*3)+21)$
-29647534	$(-98^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*54-3))/21$	-34587177	$((-98^*(7^{\wedge}6))+543)^*(2+1)$
-29647562	$(-98^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*54+3))/21$	-34588707	$98^*((-7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*3-2)+1$
-29674814	$(-98-(76/5))^*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-34588709	$98^*((-7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*3-2)-1$
-29687326	$98-(76^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1))$	-34590435	$((-98^*(7^{\wedge}6))-543)^*(2+1)$
-29687401	$(98-(76^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) +1$	-34602624	$-98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)+54)^*3)-21)$
-29687403	$98-((76^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) +1$	-34606740	$-98^*((((7^{\wedge}6)+54)^*3)+21)$
-29687478	$98-(76^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) +1$	-34811290	$-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*(4+3)^*2+1$
-29687522	$-98-(76^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) -1$	-34811292	$-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*(4+3)^*2-1$
-29687597	$(-98-(76^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) +1$	-34846875	$(((-9-876)^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*3)^*21$
-29687599	$-98-((76^*(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) +1$	-34941680	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4+32))+1$
-29687674	$-98-(76^*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))) +1$	-34941682	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4+32))-1$
-29692500	$(((-9^*8)-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4))^*321$	-35070086	$((987^*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3))^*2)^*-1$
-29778009	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^*2)+1$	-35182393	$-9^{\wedge}8+7+6*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-29778011	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^*2)-1$	-35182395	$-9^{\wedge}8+7+6*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-29895658	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-2)+1$	-35282216	$-9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-29895660	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-2)-1$	-35282218	$-9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-29986571	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7)+65)^{\wedge}4-3-2)/-1$	-35283599	$-9^*(87+(6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-35283601	$-9*(87+(6+5^4)*3)^2-1$	-38288600	$-98*((76+(5^(4^4(3/2)))))-1$
-35765198	$98-((7^6)^*(5^4-321))$	-38288697	$(-98*(76+(5^(4^4(3/2)))))+1$
-35765394	$-98-((7^6)^*(5^4-321))$	-38288699	$(-98*(76+(5^(4^4(3/2)))))-1$
-35913727	$-9*8^7-65*4^3^2+1$	-38288796	$-98*((76+(5^(4^4(3/2)))))+1$
-35913729	$-9*8^7-65*4^3^2-1$	-38626875	$(((-987+6)*(5^4))^3)*21$
-36000665	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)*2)+1$	-38824172	$-9+8-7^6*5*(4^3+2)-1$
-36000667	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)*2)-1$	-38824186	$-9-8-7^6*5*(4^3+2)+1$
-36471192	$-9+8-7^6*5*(4^3-2)-1$	-38824188	$-9-8-7^6*5*(4^3+2)-1$
-36471261	$-9*8-7^6*5*(4^3-2)+1$	-38857203	$987*(6-((5^4)^3)*21))$
-36471263	$-9*8-7^6*5*(4^3-2)-1$	-38869047	$-987*(6+(((5^4)^3)*21))$
-36471287	$-98-7^6*5*(4^3-2)+1$	-39046654	$-9^8+7^6*(5^4-3)^2+1$
-36471289	$-98-7^6*5*(4^3-2)-1$	-39046656	$-9^8+7^6*(5^4-3)^2-1$
-36492282	$-9^8(-8+7+6)*(5^4-3^2-1)$	-39099375	$(((-987-6)*(5^4))^3)*21$
-36558360	$(98-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-39282112	$-9^8+7^6*5*(4^3+2)+1$
-36558362	$(98-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-39282114	$-9^8+7^6*5*(4^3+2)-1$
-36566446	$(9^8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-40000559	$((-9-8)^7*7^6+5)^4*(3+2)+1$
-36566448	$(9^8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-40000561	$((-9-8)^7*7^6+5)^4*(3+2)-1$
-36576025	$-9^8+7^6*(5+4+3-2)+1$	-40163129	$-9^8+7+(6+5)^4*4^3^2+1$
-36576027	$-9^8+7^6*(5+4+3-2)-1$	-40163131	$-9^8+7+(6+5)^4*4^3^2-1$
-36583551	$(9+8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-40163143	$-9^8-7+(6+5)^4*4^3^2+1$
-36583553	$(9+8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-40163145	$-9^8-7+(6+5)^4*4^3^2-1$
-36586341	$9+(8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-40352823	$9*87-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36586343	$9+(8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-40352825	$9*87-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$
-36586359	$-9+(8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-40352920	$98*7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36586361	$-9+(8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-40352922	$98*7-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$
-36588527	$(9-8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-40353102	$9*8*7+(-6-5+4)^3^2+1$
-36588529	$(9-8-7^6)^*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-40353104	$9*8*7+(-6-5+4)^3^2-1$
-36589149	$(9-8+7^6)^*(5^4+3)/2+1$	-40353501	$98+7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36589151	$(9-8+7^6)^*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-40353503	$98+7-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$
-36594125	$(9+8+7^6)^*(5^4+3)/2+1$	-40353515	$98-7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36594127	$(9+8+7^6)^*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-40353517	$98-7-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$
-36619316	$(98+7^6)^*(5^4+3)/2+1$	-40353527	$9*8+7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36619318	$(98+7^6)^*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-40353653	$9-8*7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36728475	$9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)+2+1$	-40353655	$9-8*7-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$
-36728477	$9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)+2-1$	-40354110	$-9*8*7+(-6-5+4)^3^2+1$
-36811323	$-9^8+7^6*(54-3+2)+1$	-40354112	$-9*8*7+(-6-5+4)^3^2-1$
-36811325	$-9^8+7^6*(54-3+2)-1$	-40824203	$(98/7)^6*(-5-(4/3)^(-2-1))$
-36899063	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4-3^2-2)+1$	-41093588	$-9^8+7+(6-5+4)^3^2+1$
-36899065	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4-3^2-2)-1$	-41093590	$-9^8+7+(6-5+4)^3^2-1$
-36912185	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3^2-2)+1$	-41211719	$-9^8-7*(6-5-4)^3^2+1$
-36912187	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3^2-2)-1$	-41211721	$-9^8-7*(6-5-4)^3^2-1$
-36964673	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3-2)+1$	-41211789	$-9^8-7*(6+5-4)^3^2+1$
-36964675	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3-2)-1$	-41211791	$-9^8-7*(6+5-4)^3^2-1$
-37082769	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)+2+1$	-41212167	$-9^8-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$
-37082771	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)+2-1$	-41212169	$-9^8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$
-37082773	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)-2+1$	-41473879	$-9^8+7-6*(5-4)^3^2+1$
-37082775	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)-2-1$	-41473881	$-9^8+7-6*(5-4)^3^2-1$
-37164270	$-9^8+7^6*(5+4+3+2)+1$	-41517283	$-9^8+7^6*(5+4^4(3/2))+1$
-37164272	$-9^8+7^6*(5+4+3+2)-1$	-41517285	$-9^8+7^6*(5+4^4(3/2))-1$
-37385535	$(98/7)^6*5+4^3^2+1$	-41618351	$-9^8+7^6*5^4*4^3^2+1$
-37385537	$(98/7)^6*5+4^3^2-1$	-41618353	$-9^8+7^6*5^4*4^3^2-1$
-37641408	$(98-((7^6)^5))^*(43+21)$	-41735987	$-9^8+7+6+5^4*4^3^2+1$
-37653952	$(-98-((7^6)^5))^*(43+21)$	-41735989	$-9^8+7+6+5^4*4^3^2-1$
-37665881	$(9^8+7^6)^*(5/4-3)/2-1$	-41736042	$-9^8-7*6+5^4*4^3^2+1$
-37758811	$98-(((7^6)^5)-(5^4))^321$	-41736044	$-9^8-7*6+5^4*4^3^2-1$
-37759007	$-98-(((7^6)^5)-(5^4))^321$	-41752581	$-9^8+7^6*(5^4-3^2)+1$
-37771651	$98-(((7^6)^5)+(5^4))^321$	-41752583	$-9^8+7^6*(5^4-3^2)-1$
-37771847	$-98-(((7^6)^5)+(5^4))^321$	-41806842	$((-9-8)^*(7^6-543))^21$
-37909823	$(98/7)^6*5-4^3^2+1$	-41811967	$(((-987/6)+5)^*(4^4(3^2)))+1$
-37909825	$(98/7)^6*5-4^3^2-1$	-41811969	$(((-987/6)+5)^*(4^4(3^2)))-1$
-38118268	$-9+(8-7^6*5^4*3)^2+1$	-41997291	$((-9-8)^7*7^6+5^4*3)^21$
-38118270	$-9+(8-7^6*5^4*3)^2-1$	-42004095	$((-9-8)^7*7^6+5^4*3)^21$
-38118300	$-9-(8+7^6*5^4*3)^2+1$	-42042528	$(-9*8)^*((7^6)^5)-4321$
-38118302	$-9-(8+7^6*5^4*3)^2-1$	-42194544	$((-9-8)^*(7^6+543))^21$
-38256445	$9+8^7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$	-42314751	$-9*((8*(7^6)^5)-4321)$
-38256447	$9+8^7-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$	-42350399	$9*8*(-7^6*5+4+3+2)+1$
-38256463	$-9+8^7-(6+5-4)^3^2+1$	-42350401	$9*8*(-7^6*5+4+3+2)-1$
-38256465	$-9+8^7-(6+5-4)^3^2-1$	-42353369	$(9*8*7^6-54)^*(-3-2)+1$
-38273704	$98*((76-(5^4(4^4(3/2)))))+1$	-42353371	$(9*8*7^6-54)^*(-3-2)-1$
-38273801	$(98*(76-(5^4(4^4(3/2)))))+1$	-42353394	$(-9*(8/7^6-6-5)+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-38273803	$(98*(76-(5^4(4^4(3/2)))))-1$	-42353396	$(-9*(8/7^6-6-5)+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-38273900	$98*(76-((5^4(4^4(3/2))))+1)$	-42353711	$9*8*(-7^6*5+4-3-2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-42353713	$9^*8^*(-7^w6^*5+4-3-2)-1$	-43123675	$(-987/6)^*((5+(4^w(3^w2))))+1$
-42353844	$(9^*(-8/7^w-6-5)+4)^*(3+2)+1$	-43125156	$-9^w8+(7^w6+5)^*(4/3-2)+1$
-42353846	$(9^*(-8/7^w-6-5)+4)^*(3+2)-1$	-43125158	$-9^w8+(7^w6+5)^*(4/3-2)-1$
-42353884	$(9^*(-8/7^w-6-5)-4)^*(3+2)+1$	-43187345	$-9^w8-(7^*6^*(5+4)-3)^w2+1$
-42353886	$(9^*(-8/7^w-6-5)-4)^*(3+2)-1$	-43187347	$-9^w8-(7^*6^*(5+4)-3)^w2-1$
-42353891	$9^*(-8^*7^w6^*5+4-32)+1$	-43223121	$-9^w8-(7^*(6+54))^w(3-2+1)$
-42353893	$9^*(-8^*7^w6^*5+4-32)-1$	-43301081	$-9^w8+7+6^w5-4^w3^w2+1$
-42355439	$9^*8^*(7^w6+5)^*(4-3^w2)+1$	-43301083	$-9^w8+7+6^w5-4^w3^w2-1$
-42355441	$9^*8^*(7^w6+5)^*(4-3^w2)-1$	-43308846	$-9^w8+7+6+5-4^w3^w2+1$
-42356069	$-9^*(8^*7^w6+54)^*(3+2)+1$	-43308848	$-9^w8+7+6+5-4^w3^w2-1$
-42356071	$-9^*(8^*7^w6+54)^*(3+2)-1$	-43308856	$-9^w8+7+6-5-4^w3^w2+1$
-42356879	$-9^*8^*(7^w6^*5+43+2)+1$	-43308929	$-9^w8-(7+6)^*5-4^w3^w2+1$
-42356881	$-9^*8^*(7^w6^*5+43+2)-1$	-43308931	$-9^w8-(7+6)^*5-4^w3^w2-1$
-42392529	$-9^*((8^*(7^w6))^*5)+4321$	-43399652	$-9^w8+(-7^w6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-42413283	$-9^w8+(7+6)^w5+4^w3^w2+1$	-43399654	$-9^w8+(-7^w6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-42413285	$-9^w8+(7+6)^w5+4^w3^w2-1$	-43399682	$-9^w8+(-7^w6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-42450749	$9-8^w7-(6+5-4)^w3^w2+1$	-43399684	$-9^w8+(-7^w6-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-42450751	$9-8^w7-(6+5-4)^w3^w2-1$	-43440695	$((9-8^w7)+6)^*5^*(4+3/21)$
-42474176	$-9^*((8+7^w6)^*(5+4/3)^w2)+1$	-43822252	$(9^w8+(-7^*6)^w5+4+3)/2^*1$
-42474178	$-9^*((8+7^w6)^*(5+4/3)^w2)-1$	-43822255	$(9^w8+(-7^*6)^w5+4-3)/2^*1$
-42577144	$(-987+6)^*((((5^w4)/3)^w2)-1)$	-43822256	$(9^w8+(-7^*6)^w5-4+3)/2^*1$
-42579106	$(-987+6)^*((((5^w4)/3)^w2)+1)$	-43822259	$(9^w8+(-7^*6)^w5-4-3)/2^*1$
-42664752	$(-9^*8)^*((((7^w6)^*5)+4321)$	-44040821	$-9^*(8^w7/6+5)^*(4^*3+2)+1$
-42693788	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-44040823	$-9^*(8^w7/6+5)^*(4^*3+2)-1$
-42693790	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	-44302167	$((-98-76)+5)^*(4^w(3^w2))-1$
-42776793	$-9^w8+7+6^w5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44302505	$((-98-76)+5)^*(4^w(3^w2))+1$
-42776795	$-9^w8+7+6^w5+4^w3^w2-1$	-44340859	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(5^*4-3^w2)+1$
-42783811	$-9^w8+765+4^w3^w2+1$	-44340861	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(5^*4-3^w2)-1$
-42783813	$-9^w8+765+4^w3^w2-1$	-44357427	$-9^w8+7+6-5^*4^w3^w2+1$
-42784558	$-9^w8+7+6+5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44357429	$-9^w8+7+6-5^*4^w3^w2-1$
-42784560	$-9^w8+7+6+5+4^w3^w2-1$	-44433407	$(((-987/6)-5)^*(4^w(3^w2))))+1$
-42784568	$-9^w8+7+6-5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44433409	$(((-987/6)-5)^*(4^w(3^w2))))-1$
-42784580	$-9^w8+7-6-5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44469264	$(98-((7^w6)^*54)/3)^*21$
-42784599	$-9^w8+7-6^*5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44470636	$((98-((7^w6)^*54)/3))^*21$
-42784601	$-9^w8+7-6^*5+4^w3^w2-1$	-44472008	$((-98-((7^w6)^*54)/3))^*21$
-42792345	$-9^w8+7-6^w5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44473380	$(-98-((7^w6)^*54)/3)^*21$
-42792347	$-9^w8+7-6^w5+4^w3^w2-1$	-44576157	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(5+4^w(3/2))+1$
-42902220	$-9^w8-7^w6+5+4^w3^w2+1$	-44576159	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(5+4^w(3/2))-1$
-42902222	$-9^w8-7^w6+5+4^w3^w2-1$	-44881735	$-9^w8-7^*(6-5+4^w3^w2)+1$
-42906095	$-9^w8+(7^*6^*(5+4)-3)^w2+1$	-44881737	$-9^w8-7^*(6-5+4^w3^w2)-1$
-42906097	$-9^w8+(7^*6^*(5+4)-3)^w2-1$	-44999838	$-9^w8+7-(6-5+4)^w3^w2+1$
-42968284	$-9^w8+(7^w6+5)^*(-4/3+2)+1$	-44999840	$-9^w8+7-(6-5+4)^w3^w2-1$
-42968286	$-9^w8+(7^w6+5)^*(-4/3+2)-1$	-45324846	$-9^w8^*((7-(6/5+4))^w(-3-2))+1$
-42987866	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5+4^w3)/2+1$	-45612012	$(98+76)^*((5-(4^w(3^w2))))+1$
-42987927	$-9^w8+(7^w6+5-4^w3)/2-1$	-45612360	$(98+76)^*(5-((4^w(3^w2))))+1$
-43017303	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5)/4+3^*2+1$	-45613752	$(-98-76)^*((5+(4^w(3^w2))))-1$
-43017307	$-9^w8+(7^w6+5)/4+3/2-1$	-45613925	$((-98-76)^*(5+(4^w(3^w2))))+1$
-43017317	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5)/4-3^*2-1$	-45613927	$((-98-76)^*(5+(4^w(3^w2))))-1$
-43023084	$-9^w8+76^*(5^w4-3)/2+1$	-45614100	$(-98-76)^*((5+(4^w(3^w2))))+1$
-43023086	$-9^w8+76^*(5^w4-3)/2-1$	-45930297	$-9^w8+7+(-6-5)^*4^w3^w2+1$
-43026958	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5^w(4+3))/2+1$	-45930299	$-9^w8+7+(-6-5)^*4^w3^w2-1$
-43026960	$-9^w8+(7^w6-5^w(4+3))/2-1$	-45930311	$-9^w8-7+(-6-5)^*4^w3^w2+1$
-43033539	$-9^w8+7^*(6+5^w4^*3+2)+1$	-45930313	$-9^w8-7+(-6-5)^*4^w3^w2-1$
-43033541	$-9^w8+7^*(6+5^w4^*3+2)-1$	-46118392	$(-98^*7^w6+5)^*4-3-2+1$
-43033651	$-9^w8-7^*(6-5^w4^*3+2)+1$	-46118424	$(-98^*7^w6-5)^*4+3+2-1$
-43033653	$-9^w8-7^*(6-5^w4^*3+2)-1$	-46335248	$-9^*(8^*(76-5)^*4-3)^w2+1$
-43042677	$-9^w8-(7+6)^*(-5^w4+3)/2+1$	-46335250	$-9^*(8^*(76-5)^*4-3)^w2-1$
-43044629	$-9^w8+7/((6+5)^w4+3))^w(-2+1)$	-46590983	$9^*8^*(7^w6+5)^*(-4-3/2)+1$
-43050765	$-9^w8-(7+6)^*(5^w4-3)/2-1$	-46590985	$9^*8^*(7^w6+5)^*(-4-3/2)-1$
-43059789	$-9^w8+7^*(6-5^w4^*3+2)+1$	-46811328	$-9^w8-(7^w6-5)/(4^w-3^*2)+1$
-43059791	$-9^w8+7^*(6-5^w4^*3+2)-1$	-46811330	$-9^w8-(7^w6-5)/(4^w-3^*2)-1$
-43059901	$-9^w8-7^*(6+5^w4^*3+2)+1$	-46923597	$(-98-(76+5))^*((4^w(3^w2)))-1$
-43059903	$-9^w8-7^*(6+5^w4^*3+2)-1$	-46923955	$(-98-(76+5))^*((4^w(3^w2)))+1$
-43066482	$-9^w8-(7^w6-5^w(4+3))/2+1$	-47399733	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(5+4^w3/2)+1$
-43066484	$-9^w8-(7^w6-5^w(4+3))/2-1$	-47399735	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(5+4^w3/2)-1$
-43070356	$-9^w8-76^*(5^w4-3)/2+1$	-48093759	$-9+(8+7)^w6^*(-5+(4/3)^w2-1)$
-43070358	$-9^w8-76^*(5^w4-3)/2-1$	-48941992	$-9-8^*7^w6^*(5^*4+32)+1$
-43105515	$-9^w8-(7^w6+5-4^w3)/2+1$	-48941994	$-9-8^*7^w6^*(5^*4+32)-1$
-43105576	$-9^w8-(7^w6-5+4^w3)/2-1$	-48967897	$(9/(8+(-765+4)^w3))^w(-2+1)$
-43121701	$(987/6)^*((5-(4^w(3^w2))))+1$	-49282117	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(54-3+2)+1$
-43122030	$(987/6)^*((5-(4^w(3^w2))))+1$	-49282119	$-9^w8-7^w6^*(54-3+2)-1$
-43123346	$(-987/6)^*((5+(4^w(3^w2))))-1$	-50340648	$-9^w8-(7^w6-5)^*(4^w3-2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-50340650	$-9^8 \cdot (7^8 - 5) \cdot (4^3 - 2) - 1$	-58216891	$-9 \cdot ((8 - (7654/3))^2) - 1$
-50823935	$9^8 \cdot (-7^8 + 5 - 4) \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-58216909	$-9 \cdot ((8 - (7654/3))^2) + 1$
-50823937	$9^8 \cdot (-7^8 + 5 - 4) \cdot 3^2 - 1$	-58280376	$-987 \cdot ((6/54)^{\wedge(-3-2)}) - 1$
-50824310	$9 - 8 \cdot (7^8 \cdot 54 - 3^2) + 1$	-58281362	$(-987 / ((6/54)^{\wedge(3+2)})) + 1$
-50824312	$9 - 8 \cdot (7^8 \cdot 54 - 3^2) - 1$	-58281364	$(-987 / ((6/54)^{\wedge(3+2)})) - 1$
-50824330	$-9 - 8 \cdot (7^8 \cdot 54 - 3^2) - 1$	-58282350	$-987 \cdot ((6/54)^{\wedge(-3-2)}) + 1$
-50824388	$-9 - 8 \cdot (7^8 \cdot 54 + 3/2) + 1$	-58319352	$9^8 \cdot (7 - ((6^5)^{\wedge 4 - 3 + 2}) + 1)$
-50824424	$-9 - 8 \cdot (7^8 \cdot 54 + 3^2) + 1$	-58320360	$9^8 \cdot (-7 - ((6^5)^{\wedge 4 - 3 + 2}) + 1)$
-50824426	$-9 - 8 \cdot (7^8 \cdot 54 + 3^2) - 1$	-58429673	$(9^8 - (7^6)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot (-4/3 + 2) + 1$
-50824799	$-9^8 \cdot (7^8 + 5 - 4) \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-58429675	$(9^8 - (7^6)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot (-4/3 + 2) - 1$
-50824801	$-9^8 \cdot (7^8 + 5 - 4) \cdot 3^2 - 1$	-58583635	$9 \cdot (8 - ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2})) + 1$
-51227664	$(-9 - 8) / 7^6 \cdot ((5^{\wedge 4} \cdot 3)^{\wedge 2 - 1})$	-58583643	$(9 \cdot (8 - ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2}))) + 1$
-51282150	$-9^8 - 7^8 \cdot 5 \cdot (4 + 3)^2 + 1$	-58583645	$(9 \cdot (8 - ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2}))) - 1$
-51282152	$-9^8 - 7^8 \cdot 5 \cdot (4 + 3)^2 - 1$	-58583653	$9 \cdot (8 - ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2})) + 1$
-51432849	$((-987 + 6) / 5) \cdot ((4^{\wedge(3^2)}) + 1)$	-58583779	$-9 \cdot (8 + ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2})) - 1$
-52061997	$((-987 - 6) / 5) \cdot ((4^{\wedge(3^2)}) + 1)$	-58583787	$(-9 \cdot (8 + ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2}))) + 1$
-52236146	$9 - 8 \cdot 7^8 \cdot (54 + 3/2) + 1$	-58583789	$(-9 \cdot (8 + ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2}))) - 1$
-52236148	$9 - 8 \cdot 7^8 \cdot (54 + 3/2) - 1$	-58583797	$-9 \cdot (8 + ((7654/3)^{\wedge 2})) + 1$
-52236164	$-9 - 8 \cdot 7^8 \cdot (54 + 3/2) + 1$	-58720213	$(9 - 8^{\wedge 7} \cdot 6) \cdot (5^4 / 3 - 2) + 1$
-52236166	$-9 - 8 \cdot 7^8 \cdot (54 + 3/2) - 1$	-58720215	$(9 - 8^{\wedge 7} \cdot 6) \cdot (5^4 / 3 - 2) - 1$
-53661339	$(9^8 - 7^8) \cdot 5 / 4 \cdot (-3 + 2) + 1$	-58720297	$(9 + 8^{\wedge 7} \cdot 6) \cdot (-5^4 / 3 + 2) + 1$
-53661341	$(9^8 - 7^8) \cdot 5 / 4 \cdot (-3 + 2) - 1$	-58720299	$(9 + 8^{\wedge 7} \cdot 6) \cdot (-5^4 / 3 + 2) - 1$
-53747585	$((9^8)^{\wedge(-7 + 6 + 5)} \cdot 4^3) \cdot (-2) - 1$	-58951675	$-9 \cdot ((8 + (7654/3))^2) - 1$
-53747839	$((9^8)^{\wedge(-7 + 6 + 5)} \cdot 4^3) \cdot (-2) + 1$	-58951693	$-9 \cdot ((8 + (7654/3))^2) + 1$
-54434884	$((98 \cdot (76 - (5 / (4 + 3))))^{\wedge 2}) \cdot (-1)$	-59189250	$(9^8 + 7) \cdot ((6 - 5) / 4 - 3) / 2 + 1$
-55050167	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2} + 1$	-59189252	$(9^8 + 7) \cdot ((6 - 5) / 4 - 3) / 2 - 1$
-55050169	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2} - 1$	-59293152	$-9^8 \cdot (7^{\wedge(6 + 5 - 4)} \cdot 3^{\wedge(2 + 1)})$
-55050222	$9 + 8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2} + 1$	-59294727	$-9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge(6 + 5 - 4)} \cdot 3 - 2) - 1$
-55050224	$9 + 8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2} - 1$	-59294745	$9^8 \cdot (-8^{\wedge(6 + 5 - 4)} \cdot 3 - 2) - 1$
-55050238	$9 - 8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2} + 1$	-59295447	$-9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge(6 + 5 - 4)} \cdot 3 + 2) - 1$
-55050242	$-9 + 8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2} - 1$	-59295465	$9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge(-7^{\wedge(6 + 5 - 4)} \cdot 3 - 2) - 1})$
-55345761	$(-9^8 + 7 - (-6 - 5)) / ((4/3)^{\wedge 2 - 1})$	-59297040	$9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge(-7^{\wedge(6 + 5 - 4)} \cdot 3^{\wedge(2 + 1)})})$
-55345779	$(-9^8 - 7 - (-6 - 5)) / ((4/3)^{\wedge 2 - 1})$	-59923080	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1$
-55472706	$((98 \cdot 76)^{\wedge(-5 + 4 + 3)} + 2) \cdot (-1)$	-59923082	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1$
-56864187	$(-9^{\wedge((87 - 65) / 4)}) \cdot 321$	-60162039	$9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge 7} \cdot (-6 + 5^4 / 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-57059692	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 - 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) + 1$	-60162057	$-9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge 7} \cdot (6 - 5^4 / 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-57059694	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 - 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) - 1$	-60170930	$9^{\wedge(-8 + 7 + 6)} \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge(3 + 2)}) + 1$
-57059836	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 - 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) + 1$	-60170932	$9^{\wedge(-8 + 7 + 6)} \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge(3 + 2)}) - 1$
-57059838	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 - 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) - 1$	-60264168	$-9^8 \cdot (8 - (7 + 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1$
-57174453	$9^8 \cdot ((8 - ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) + 321)) + 321$	-60264170	$-9^8 \cdot (8 - (7 + 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1$
-57174597	$-9^8 \cdot ((8 + ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) - 321))$	-60326288	$-9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge(7 + 6 + 5)} \cdot 4 - 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1$
-57174983	$9/8 \cdot (-7^8 + 5) \cdot 432 + 1$	-60326290	$-9^8 \cdot (8^{\wedge(7 + 6 + 5)} \cdot 4 - 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1$
-57174985	$9/8 \cdot (-7^8 + 5) \cdot 432 - 1$	-60353864	$9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge 3} + 2)) + 1$
-57177021	$(9^8 \cdot (8 - ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}))) + 321$	-60353866	$9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge 3} + 2)) - 1$
-57177165	$(-9^8 \cdot (8 + ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}))) + 321$	-60354008	$9^8 \cdot (-8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge 3} + 2)) + 1$
-57177476	$9^8 \cdot (-8 - 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 - 2) + 1$	-60354010	$9^8 \cdot (-8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge 3} + 2)) - 1$
-57177478	$9^8 \cdot (-8 - 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 - 2) - 1$	-60583953	$(((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) + 321$
-57177663	$(9^8 \cdot (8 - ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}))) - 321$	-60584211	$(((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) + (3^2 \cdot 21)$
-57177807	$(-9^8 \cdot (8 + ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}))) - 321$	-60584250	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) + 3) + 21$
-57180231	$9^8 \cdot (8 - ((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) + 321) + 1$	-60584256	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) - 3) + 21$
-57180375	$-9^8 \cdot ((8 + ((7^8)^{\wedge 5})) + 321)$	-60584272	$-9^8 \cdot 76 / 54 + 3 - 2 + 1$
-57215259	$9 - (8 + 7)^{\wedge 6} \cdot 5 - 4^{\wedge 3} \cdot 2 + 1$	-60584276	$-9^8 \cdot 76 / 54 - 3 + 2 - 1$
-57215261	$9 - (8 + 7)^{\wedge 6} \cdot 5 - 4^{\wedge 3} \cdot 2 - 1$	-60584292	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) + 3) - 21$
-57294990	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 + 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) + 1$	-60584298	$(((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) - (3 + 21)$
-57294992	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 + 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) - 1$	-60584337	$(((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) - (3^2 \cdot 21)$
-57295134	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 + 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) + 1$	-60584595	$(((-9^8)^{\wedge 76}) / 54) - 321$
-57295136	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (54 + 3^{\wedge 2} - 2)) - 1$	-60668520	$-9^8 \cdot (8 - (7 - 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1$
-57394587	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 765}) + 765) \cdot 4) / 3 + 21$	-60668522	$-9^8 \cdot (8 - (7 - 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1$
-57394629	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 765}) + 765) \cdot 4) / 3 - 21$	-61011720	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + (7 + 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1$
-57396627	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 765}) - 765) \cdot 4) / 3 + 21$	-61011722	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + (7 + 6^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1$
-57396669	$((((-9^8)^{\wedge 765}) - 765) \cdot 4) / 3 - 21$	-62157458	$((9^8 \cdot 76)^{\wedge(-5 + 4 + 3)} + 2) \cdot (-1)$
-57522178	$-98 \cdot (((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot 5) - (4 \cdot 321)$	-62783497	$-9 - 8^{\wedge 7} \cdot (6^5 - 4^{\wedge(-3 + 2 - 1)})$
-57643775	$(-98 \cdot (((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot 5) - 43) + 21$	-62912609	$9^8 \cdot ((-8^{\wedge 7} + 65) \cdot (4/3 + 2)) + 1$
-57643817	$(-98 \cdot (((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot 5) - 43) - 21$	-62912611	$9^8 \cdot ((-8^{\wedge 7} + 65) \cdot (4/3 + 2)) - 1$
-57646637	$98 \cdot (-7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 + 2) + 1$	-62913659	$9^8 \cdot (-8^{\wedge 7} / 6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge(3 + 2)} + 1$
-57646639	$98 \cdot (-7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 + 2) - 1$	-62913661	$9^8 \cdot (-8^{\wedge 7} / 6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge(3 + 2)} - 1$
-57647991	$-98 \cdot 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (3 + 2) - 1$	-63415505	$98 \cdot (7^8 + 5) \cdot (-4 - 3/2) + 1$
-57648029	$-98 \cdot 7^8 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (3 + 2) + 1$	-63415507	$98 \cdot (7^8 + 5) \cdot (-4 - 3/2) - 1$
-57648107	$98 \cdot (-7^8 \cdot 5^4 - 3 - 2) + 1$	-63651825	$((-9 - 8) / ((765^4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge 2}))^{\wedge - 1}$
-57652203	$(-98 \cdot (((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot 5) + 43) + 21$	-64001215	$((-9 - 8) \cdot 7^8 \cdot 5 - 5) / (4^{\wedge(-3 + 2)} + 1)$
-57652245	$(-98 \cdot (((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot 5) + 43) - 21$	-64001217	$((-9 - 8) \cdot 7^8 \cdot 5 - 5) / (4^{\wedge(-3 + 2)} - 1)$
-57773842	$-98 \cdot (((7^8)^{\wedge 5}) \cdot 5) + (4 \cdot 321)$	-64001599	$(-9 - 8) \cdot (7^8 + 5 - 4) \cdot 3^2 + 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-64001601	$(-9-8) \cdot (7^{\wedge}6+5-4) \cdot 32-1$	-73648373	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)-1$
-64257648	$(-987/6) \cdot ((5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot (3/2))))-1)$	-73924326	$(98-(76 \cdot 5)) \cdot ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$
-64257977	$(-987/6) \cdot ((5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot (3/2))))+1)$	-73924607	$((98-(76 \cdot 5)) \cdot (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
-65609998	$((9+87-6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)-2) \cdot -1$	-73924609	$((98-(76 \cdot 5)) \cdot (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$
-65610002	$((9+87-6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)+2) \cdot -1$	-73924890	$(98-(76 \cdot 5)) \cdot ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
-65645423	$-9 \cdot (8+(7^{\wedge}6-5) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3-2))+1$	-74118967	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3+2)+1$
-65645425	$-9 \cdot (8+(7^{\wedge}6-5) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3-2))-1$	-74118969	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3+2)-1$
-67968576	$(-98-76) \cdot ((5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot (3/2))))-1)$	-74236420	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-67968749	$((-98-76) \cdot (5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot (3/2))))+1$	-74236422	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-67968751	$((-98-76) \cdot (5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot (3/2))))-1$	-74236446	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-67968924	$(-98-76) \cdot ((5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot (3/2))))+1$	-74236448	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-68123627	$-9/8 \cdot ((7+6^{\wedge}5-4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-74236501	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-68555868	$((9^{\wedge}8) \cdot ((76/54)-3))+21$	-74236503	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-68555910	$((9^{\wedge}8) \cdot ((76/54)-3))-21$	-74236517	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-68574956	$((98-7 \cdot (6-5))^{\wedge}4-3-2) \cdot -1$	-74236590	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-68824736	$-9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4+3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-74236592	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-68824738	$-9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4+3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-74236616	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-69765855	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-32)+1$	-74236618	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-69765859	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-32)-1$	-74589367	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-69765873	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-32)+1$	-74589369	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-69765875	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-32)-1$	-74589393	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-69765954	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-32)+1$	-74589395	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-69765956	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-32)-1$	-74589448	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-69880463	$9 \cdot (8-(7^{\wedge}6-5) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3+2))+1$	-74589450	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-69880465	$9 \cdot (8-(7^{\wedge}6-5) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3+2))-1$	-74589464	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-71530582	$9+8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5-43) \cdot 2+1$	-74589537	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-71530584	$9+8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5-43) \cdot 2-1$	-74589539	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-71530600	$-9+8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5-43) \cdot 2+1$	-74589563	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)+1$
-71530602	$-9+8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5-43) \cdot 2-1$	-74589565	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3 \cdot 2)-1$
-71744464	$(9^{\wedge}8-7 \cdot 6) \cdot (-5+4/3+2)+1$	-75177638	$9 \cdot (8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4 \cdot 3+2))+1$
-71744466	$(9^{\wedge}8-7 \cdot 6) \cdot (-5+4/3+2)-1$	-75177640	$9 \cdot (8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4 \cdot 3+2))-1$
-71744604	$(9^{\wedge}8+7 \cdot 6) \cdot (-5+4/3+2)+1$	-75331457	$((((-9^{\wedge}8) \cdot 7)-65)/4)+321$
-71744606	$(9^{\wedge}8+7 \cdot 6) \cdot (-5+4/3+2)-1$	-75331738	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6) \cdot (-5/4 \cdot 3+2)+1$
-71958528	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (6+5 \cdot ((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-75331740	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6) \cdot (-5/4 \cdot 3+2)-1$
-72471685	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-75332099	$((((-9^{\wedge}8) \cdot 7)-65)/4)-321$
-72471687	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-76236479	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4)-3+2+1$
-72471711	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-76236481	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4)-3+2-1$
-72471713	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-76236623	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4)-3+2+1$
-72471782	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-76236625	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4)-3+2-1$
-72471855	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-77295320	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-72471857	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-77295322	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-72471881	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-77295464	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-72471883	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-77295466	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-72824632	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-78014099	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4 \cdot (3+2))+1$
-72824634	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-78014101	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4 \cdot (3+2))-1$
-72824658	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-78199735	$-9^{\wedge}8-((7 \cdot (6+5))^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-72824660	$9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-78199789	$-9^{\wedge}8-((7 \cdot (6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-72824713	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-79883662	$9-((8/((7^{\wedge}6) \cdot 5432))^{\wedge}2)-1$
-72824715	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-79883680	$9-((8/((7^{\wedge}6) \cdot 5432))^{\wedge}2)-1$
-72824729	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-80471987	$9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5-43) \cdot 2)+1$
-72824802	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-80471989	$9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5-43) \cdot 2)-1$
-72824804	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-80615304	$(9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4)) \cdot (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-72824828	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-80929698	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 \cdot 4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-72824830	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-80929700	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 \cdot 4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-72942281	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3-2)+1$	-81870890	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-72942283	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3-2)-1$	-81870892	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-72942451	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3-2)+1$	-82589597	$-9/8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3+2)+1$
-72942453	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3-2)-1$	-82589599	$-9/8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3+2)-1$
-72942477	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3-2)+1$	-82721954	$-9/8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-72942479	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3-2)-1$	-83400320	$-9^{\wedge}8+7-(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3+2+1$
-73413047	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3+2)+1$	-83400322	$-9^{\wedge}8+7-(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3+2-1$
-73413049	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3+2)-1$	-83886052	$9+(-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4) \cdot (3+2)-1$
-73413073	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3+2)+1$	-83886108	$-9+(-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4) \cdot (3+2)+1$
-73413075	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4-3+2)-1$	-84710879	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4) \cdot (4 \cdot 3-2)+1$
-73433088	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (6-5 \cdot (4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-84710881	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4) \cdot (4 \cdot 3-2)-1$
-73648175	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)+1$	-85441983	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5)) \cdot (-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-73648177	$98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)-1$	-85609025	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5)) \cdot (-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-73648256	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)+1$	-85621698	$-98/((7/6543)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}2-1$
-73648258	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)-1$	-85648462	$9-8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-73648345	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)+1$	-85648464	$9-8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5+4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-73648347	$-9 \cdot 8-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)-1$	-86472014	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5/4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2+1$
-73648371	$-98-7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4+3-2)+1$	-86472016	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5/4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-86868973	$(9^8 + (7^6)^5 - 4 \cdot 3) / -2 \cdot 1$	-102512827	$-9 \cdot ((8+7)^6 - (5^4 - 3) / 2) - 1$
-86868976	$(9^8 + (7^6)^5 - 4 + 3) / -2 \cdot 1$	-102518423	$-9 \cdot ((8+7)^6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2) + 1$
-86868977	$(9^8 + (7^6)^5 + 4 - 3) / -2 \cdot 1$	-102518425	$-9 \cdot ((8+7)^6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2) - 1$
-86868979	$(9^8 + (7^6)^5 + 4 + 3) / -2 + 1$	-102679649	$9 \cdot (8+7)^6 \cdot (-5^4 - 4 - 3 + 2) + 1$
-86868981	$(9^8 + (7^6)^5 + 4 + 3) / -2 - 1$	-102679651	$9 \cdot (8+7)^6 \cdot (-5^4 - 4 - 3 + 2) - 1$
-86918329	$(9 \cdot 8^7 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^2 - 1$	-102920625	$((9 - (87 \cdot 6)) \cdot (5^4))^2 \cdot 321$
-88454024	$-9 \cdot ((8+7) \cdot (6 - 5 \cdot 43))^2 + 1$	-103734960	$-98 \cdot (((7^6)^5 \cdot (5+4)) - 321)$
-88454026	$-9 \cdot ((8+7) \cdot (6 - 5 \cdot 43))^2 - 1$	-103797876	$-98 \cdot (((7^6)^5 \cdot (5+4)) + 321)$
-88529279	$((98 - 7 + 6)^5 - (5 - 4 + 3) - 2)^2 - 1$	-104001715	$(-9 - 8)^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4 + 32) + 1$
-88529283	$((98 - 7 + 6)^5 - (5 - 4 + 3) + 2)^2 - 1$	-104001717	$(-9 - 8)^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4 + 32) - 1$
-90001484	$(-9 - 8) / 7^6 - 6 \cdot (54 - 3^2) + 1$	-104857651	$9 - (8^7 + 6 / 5) \cdot ((4 + 3)^2 + 1)$
-90001486	$(-9 - 8) / 7^6 - 6 \cdot (54 - 3^2) - 1$	-104857669	$-9 - (8^7 + 6 / 5) \cdot ((4 + 3)^2 + 1)$
-90354422	$9 - 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5 + 43)^2 + 1$	-105884099	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (-4 + 3 / 2) + 1$
-90354424	$9 - 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5 + 43)^2 - 1$	-105884101	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (-4 + 3 / 2) - 1$
-92236495	$(-98 \cdot ((7 + 6) - (5 + 4))) + 321$	-105884171	$-9 \cdot (8^7 + 6^5 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (3 + 2)) + 1$
-92237137	$(-98 \cdot ((7 + 6) - (5 + 4))) - 321$	-105884173	$-9 \cdot (8^7 + 6^5 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (3 + 2)) - 1$
-93881844	$(98 + ((7^6)^5 \cdot (5 - 43))) \cdot 21$	-106531875	$((-9 - (87 \cdot 6)) \cdot (5^4))^2 \cdot 321$
-93883804	$98 + (((7^6)^5 \cdot (5 - 43))^2 \cdot 21)$	-107295878	$9 - 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (54 + 3)^2 + 1$
-93884000	$-98 + (((7^6)^5 \cdot (5 - 43))^2 \cdot 21)$	-107295880	$9 - 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (54 + 3)^2 - 1$
-93885960	$(-98 + ((7^6)^5 \cdot (5 - 43))) \cdot 21$	-107322679	$(9^8 - 7^6) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-93892500	$((9 - 87)^6 \cdot (5^4))^2 \cdot 321$	-107322681	$(9^8 - 7^6) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-94109665	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 + 6)^5 \cdot 5 + 4 \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-107597344	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-94109667	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 + 6)^5 \cdot 5 + 4 \cdot 3^2 - 1$	-107597346	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-94633953	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 + 6)^5 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-107597379	$(-9^8 - 7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-94633955	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 + 6)^5 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 3^2 - 1$	-107597381	$(-9^8 - 7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-94634013	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 - 6)^5 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-107616599	$(9^8 - 76 - 5) \cdot (-4 + 3 / 2) + 1$
-94634015	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 - 6)^5 \cdot 5 - 4 \cdot 3^2 - 1$	-107616601	$(9^8 - 76 - 5) \cdot (-4 + 3 / 2) - 1$
-96001574	$9 - 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (54 - 3)^2 + 1$	-107616609	$(-9^8 + 7^6 \cdot (6 + 5)) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-96001576	$9 - 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (54 - 3)^2 - 1$	-107616611	$(-9^8 + 7^6 \cdot (6 + 5)) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-96354602	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (5 + 43^2)) + 1$	-107616744	$(-9^8 - 7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-96354604	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (5 + 43^2)) - 1$	-107616746	$(-9^8 - 7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-96855092	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6) \cdot (5 / 4 + 3 - 2) + 1$	-107616769	$(9^8 - 7 - 6) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-98392464	$(9^8 - 7 - (6 + 5)) / ((4 / 3)^2 - 2 - 1)$	-107616791	$(-9^8 / (7 - 6) + 5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-98392496	$(9^8 + 7 - (6 + 5)) / ((4 / 3)^2 - 2 - 1)$	-107616814	$(-9^8 / (7 - 6) - 5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-99614242	$98 - ((76^5)^2 \cdot ((4^4 \cdot (3^2) - 1)))$	-107616836	$(9^8 + 7 + 6) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-99614438	$-98 - ((76^5)^2 \cdot ((4^4 \cdot (3^2) - 1)))$	-107616894	$(-9^8 - 7^6 + 5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-99614546	$98 - (76^5 \cdot ((5^4 \cdot (4^4 \cdot (3^2) - 1))))$	-107616896	$(-9^8 - 7^6 + 5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-99614698	$98 - (76^5 \cdot ((5^4 \cdot (4^4 \cdot (3^2) + 1))))$	-107616994	$(-9^8 - 7^6 \cdot (6 + 5)) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-99614718	$9 - 8 - 76^5 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-107616996	$(-9^8 - 7^6 \cdot (6 + 5)) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-99614742	$-98 - (76^5 \cdot ((5^4 \cdot (4^4 \cdot (3^2) - 1))))$	-107636224	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-99614791	$-9^8 - 76^5 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 3^2 + 1$	-107636226	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-99614793	$-9^8 - 76^5 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 3^2 - 1$	-107636259	$(-9^8 - 7 - 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-99614894	$-98 - (76^5 \cdot ((5^4 \cdot (4^4 \cdot (3^2) + 1))))$	-107636261	$(-9^8 - 7 - 6^5) \cdot (4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-99615002	$98 - ((76^5)^2 \cdot ((4^4 \cdot (3^2) + 1)))$	-107910924	$(9^8 + 7^6) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-99615198	$-98 - ((76^5)^2 \cdot ((4^4 \cdot (3^2) + 1)))$	-107910926	$(9^8 + 7^6) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-99999995	$((98 / 7 + 6)^5)^4 - 3 - 2)^2 - 1$	-107996325	$(-9 - 8) \cdot (((7^6)^5 \cdot 54) - 321)$
-100440168	$(((-9^8) \cdot 7) + 6543) / (2 + 1)$	-108001780	$(-9 - 8)^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 + 3 - 2 + 1$
-100442110	$((((-9^8) \cdot 7) + 654) / 3) + 21$	-108001784	$(-9 - 8)^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3 + 2 - 1$
-100442152	$((((-9^8) \cdot 7) + 654) / 3) - 21$	-108001853	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (54 - 3)^2) + 1$
-100442250	$((-9^8 + 7^6) \cdot (5 - 4 / 3^2) + 1)$	-108001855	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (54 - 3)^2) - 1$
-100442252	$(-9^8 + 7^6) \cdot (5 - 4 / 3^2) - 1$	-108007239	$(-9 - 8) \cdot (((7^6)^5 \cdot 54) + 321)$
-100442306	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6^5 \cdot 4) / 3 + 2 + 1$	-108243214	$((9 + 8 + 7 + 6)^5 - (5 - 4 + 3) - 2)^2 - 1$
-100442308	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6^5 \cdot 4) / 3 + 2 - 1$	-108243218	$((9 + 8 + 7 + 6)^5 - (5 - 4 + 3) + 2)^2 - 1$
-100442341	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4) / 3 + 2 + 1$	-108909360	$(-9 + 8) \cdot (7^6)^5 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (4 / 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-100442343	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4) / 3 + 2 - 1$	-109541250	$(((-9 + 7) \cdot 6)^5 \cdot (5^4))^2 \cdot 321$
-100442355	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4) / 3 - 2 + 1$	-110114783	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot (7^6 - 5) \cdot (-4 - 3^2) + 1$
-100442357	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4) / 3 - 2 - 1$	-110114785	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot (7^6 - 5) \cdot (-4 - 3^2) - 1$
-100442390	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6^5 \cdot 4) / 3 - 2 + 1$	-110118878	$9 \cdot (-8^7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 + 3^2) + 1$
-100442392	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6^5 \cdot 4) / 3 - 2 - 1$	-110118880	$9 \cdot (-8^7 + 6^5) \cdot (4 + 3^2) - 1$
-100442446	$(-9^8 - 7^6) \cdot (5 - 4 / 3^2) + 1$	-110119528	$(-9^8 + 7^6 - 5) \cdot (4 + 3^2) + 1$
-100442448	$(-9^8 - 7^6) \cdot (5 - 4 / 3^2) - 1$	-110119530	$(-9^8 + 7^6 - 5) \cdot (4 + 3^2) - 1$
-100442546	$((((-9^8) \cdot 7) - 654) / 3) + 21$	-110124143	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot (7^6 + 5) \cdot (-4 - 3^2) + 1$
-100442588	$((((-9^8) \cdot 7) - 654) / 3) - 21$	-110124145	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot (7^6 + 5) \cdot (-4 - 3^2) - 1$
-100444530	$(((-9^8) \cdot 7) - 6543) / (2 + 1)$	-110481407	$(9 \cdot 8)^{\wedge} ((-7 + 6) + 5) \cdot (-4 - 3^{\wedge} - 2) + 1$
-100784790	$(9 \cdot 87 + 6^{\wedge} (5 + 4))^2 \cdot (-3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-110481409	$(9 \cdot 8)^{\wedge} ((-7 + 6) + 5) \cdot (-4 - 3^{\wedge} - 2) - 1$
-101648638	$98 + (-7^6) \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot ((4 / 3)^2 - 1)$	-110691373	$((((-9^8) + 76) \cdot 5)^2 \cdot 5) / 21$
-101648663	$9 \cdot (8 - 7^6 \cdot (5 + 43))^2 + 1$	-110886866	$9 \cdot (-8^7 + 6^5 + 5 + 4^3 \cdot 3^2) + 1$
-101648665	$9 \cdot (8 - 7^6 \cdot (5 + 43))^2 - 1$	-110886868	$9 \cdot (-8^7 + 6^5 + 5 + 4^3 \cdot 3^2) - 1$
-101648680	$(9^8 - (7^6)^5) \cdot ((4 / 3)^2 - 1)$	-111295856	$98 - ((7^6)^5 \cdot ((5^4) + 321))$
-101648792	$(-9 \cdot 8 - (7^6)^5) \cdot ((4 / 3)^2 - 1)$	-111296052	$-98 - ((7^6)^5 \cdot ((5^4) + 321))$
-101648834	$-98 + (-7^6) \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot ((4 / 3)^2 - 1)$	-111602609	$-9^8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 3^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$
-102512825	$-9 \cdot ((8 + 7)^6 - (5^4 - 3) / 2) + 1$	-111602611	$-9^8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-112550876	$((98^{7-6}+5)^{4-3-2})^*-1$	-128787232	$(-9^{8+7^6-5})^*(4-3+2)-1$
-112984058	$-9^*8^{7^6+5+4^3^2+1}$	-128976866	$(9^8-7^*6^6)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-112984060	$-9^*8^{7^6+5+4^3^2-1}$	-128976868	$(9^8-7^*6^6)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-113243408	$9^*(-8^{7^6+(5^4-3)/2})+1$	-129002760	$(((-9^8)/7)+6543)^*21$
-113243410	$9^*(-8^{7^6+(5^4-3)/2})-1$	-129016359	$(((-9^8)+(76*543))^*(2+1))$
-113249006	$-9^*(8^{7^6+(5^4-3)/2})+1$	-129041478	$(((-9^8)+(765*43))^*(2+1))$
-113249008	$-9^*(8^{7^6+(5^4-3)/2})-1$	-129071745	$(((-9^8)/7)+(6*543))^*21$
-113295360	$-9^*8^{7^6*((5+43)^{-2+1})}$	-129081468	$(((-9^8)/7)+(65*43))^*21$
-113632083	$-9^*(8^{7^6+(5*(4+3))^{(2+1)}})$	-129098961	$(((-9^8)/7)+(654*3))^*21$
-114353064	$(-98+((7^6)^{54}))^*(3-21)$	-129116813	$(-9^{8+7+6^6})^*(4-3+2)+1$
-114356592	$(98+((7^6)^{54}))^*(3-21)$	-129116815	$(-9^{8+7+6^6})^*(4-3+2)-1$
-115560000	$(((-9-87)^6)^*(5^4))^*321$	-129116855	$(-9^8-7+6^6)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-118434078	$(-987^6)^*((5^4)^*32)-1$	-129116857	$(-9^8-7+6^6)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-118445922	$(-987^6)^*((5^4)^*32)+1$	-129117192	$(((-9^8)+7654+3)^*(2+1))$
-118585151	$9^*8^*(7^6-5)^*(-4^3-2)+1$	-129117210	$(((-9^8)+7654)-3)^*(2+1)$
-118585153	$9^*8^*(7^6-5)^*(-4^3-2)-1$	-129120513	$(((-9^8)+7)+6543)^*(2+1)$
-118588134	$(98-((7^6)^*(5+43)))^*21$	-129120555	$(((-9^8)-7)+6543)^*(2+1)$
-118590094	$98-(((7^6)^*(5+43))^*21)$	-129126366	$((((-9^8)/7)+654+3)^*21)$
-118590290	$-98-(((7^6)^*(5+43))^*21)$	-129126492	$((((-9^8)/7)+654)-3)^*21$
-118592250	$(-98-((7^6)^*(5+43)))^*21$	-129128634	$((((-9^8)/7)+6)+543)^*21$
-118857141	$(-9+8/7+6)^*((5^4)^{(3^2)}-1)$	-129128886	$((((-9^8)/7)-6)+543)^*21$
-119275518	$9-8-7^*65^*4^3^2+1$	-129132509	$((-9^8)+(7654/3))^*(2+1)$
-119275591	$-9^*8-7^*65^*4^3^2+1$	-129135585	$(((-9^8)/7)+(654/3))^*21$
-119275593	$-9^*8-7^*65^*4^3^2-1$	-129137739	$(((-9^8)+765)+43)^*(2+1)$
-119714263	$(9^8-7^6(6+5-4+3))/2+1$	-129137867	$(-9^8+765)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-119714265	$(9^8-7^6(6+5-4+3))/2-1$	-129137869	$(-9^8+765)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-120005043	$((-9^8)^*((76/54)^3))+21$	-129137895	$((((-9^8)/7)+65)+43)^*21$
-120005085	$((-9^8)^*((76/54)^3))-21$	-129137997	$(((-9^8)+765)-43)^*(2+1)$
-120174375	$((9-(8^*76))^*(5^4))^*321$	-129139022	$(9^8-76^*5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-120707801	$9^*(8-7^6*(54+3)^2)+1$	-129139024	$(9^8-76^*5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-120707803	$9^*(8-7^6*(54+3)^2)-1$	-129139701	$((((-9^8)/7)+65)-43)^*21$
-121060722	$98-7^6*(5+4^3(3+2))+1$	-129139967	$(-9^8+(7+6)^5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-121060724	$98-7^6*(5+4^3(3+2))-1$	-129139969	$(-9^8+(7+6)^5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-121060805	$98-7^6*(5+4^3(3+2))-1$	-129140021	$(-9^8+7^*6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-122011486	$9-8+(7^6-5^4(4^3))/2+1$	-129140023	$(-9^8+7^*6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-122011490	$-9+8+(7^6-5^4(4^3))/2-1$	-129140051	$(-9^8+7^*6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-122070147	$((987/6)-((5^4(4^3))/2))+1$	-129140053	$(-9^8+7^*6-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-122070191	$9^8((8+7)/6)-5^4(4^3)/2^*1$	-129140273	$(-9^8-7^*6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-122070433	$9^8((8+7)/6)+5^4(4^3)/-2+1$	-129140275	$(-9^8-7^*6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-122070435	$9^8((8+7)/6)+5^4(4^3)/-2-1$	-129140303	$(-9^8-7^*6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-122070478	$(-987/6)-((5^4(4^3))/2)+1$	-129140305	$(-9^8-7^*6-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-123785625	$((-9-(8^*76))^*(5^4))^*321$	-129140357	$(9^8+(7+6)^5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-124002355	$((9+8)/7^6-6+5)^*(-4^3+2)+1$	-129140359	$(9^8+(7+6)^5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-124002357	$((9+8)/7^6-6+5)^*(-4^3+2)-1$	-129140625	$((((-9^8)/7)-65)+43)^*21$
-124497346	$-9^8-(76^*5/4)^{(3+2-1)}$	-129141302	$(9^8+76^*5)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-125304354	$(-98-(76^*5))^*(4^4(3^2))-1$	-129141304	$(9^8+76^*5)^*(-4+3-2)-1$
-125304831	$((-98-(76^*5))^*(4^4(3^2)))+1$	-129142329	$(((-9^8)-765)+43)^*(2+1)$
-125304833	$((-98-(76^*5))^*(4^4(3^2)))-1$	-129142431	$(((-9^8)/7)-(65+43))^*21$
-125305310	$(-98-(76^*5))^*(4^4(3^2))+1$	-129142457	$(-9^8-765)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-126000021	$98-((7^6)^*(54-3))^*21$	-129142459	$(-9^8-765)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-126001981	$98-(((7^6)^*(54-3))^*21)$	-129142587	$((-9^8)-(765+43))^*(2+1)$
-126002177	$-98-(((7^6)^*(54-3))^*21)$	-129144741	$(((-9^8)/7)-(654/3))^*21$
-126004137	$(-98-((7^6)^*(54-3))^*21)$	-129147817	$((-9^8)-(7654/3))^*(2+1)$
-126393750	$(((-98-7)^6)^*(5^4))^*321$	-129151440	$((((-9^8)/7)+6)-543)^*21$
-127102976	$((9+8+7)^6-(5^4)^{(3^2)})^*-1$	-129151692	$(((-9^8)/7)-(6+543))^*21$
-128024031	$(9^*-8^*7)^{(-6+5+4)+32+1}$	-129153834	$((((-9^8)/7)-654)+3)^*21$
-128024033	$(9^*-8^*7)^{(-6+5+4)+32-1}$	-129153960	$((((-9^8)/7)-(654+3))^*21)$
-128024095	$(9^*-8^*7)^{(-6+5+4)-32+1}$	-129159771	$(((-9^8)+7)-6543)^*(2+1)$
-128024097	$(9^*-8^*7)^{(-6+5+4)-32-1}$	-129159813	$((-9^8)-(7+6543))^*(2+1)$
-128442622	$98^*(76-(5^*(4^4(3^2))-1)))$	-129163116	$(((-9^8)-7654)+3)^*(2+1)$
-128443014	$98^*(76-(5^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$	-129163134	$((-9^8)-(7654+3))^*(2+1)$
-128443111	$(98^*(76-(5^*(4^4(3^2)))))+1$	-129163469	$(-9^8+7-6^6)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-128443113	$(98^*(76-(5^*(4^4(3^2)))))-1$	-129163471	$(-9^8+7-6^6)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-128443210	$98^*(76-((5^*(4^4(3^2))))+1)$	-129163511	$(-9^8-7-6^6)^*(4-3+2)+1$
-128443602	$98^*(76-((5^*(4^4(3^2))))+1)$	-129163513	$(-9^8-7-6^6)^*(4-3+2)-1$
-128457518	$-98^*(76+(5^*(4^4(3^2))-1)))$	-129181365	$((((-9^8)/7)-(654*3))^*21)$
-128457910	$-98^*(76+(5^*(4^4(3^2))))-1$	-129208581	$(((-9^8)/7)-(6*543))^*21$
-128458106	$-98^*(76+(5^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$	-129238848	$((-9^8)-(765^*43))^*(2+1)$
-128458498	$-98^*(76+(5^*(4^4(3^2))))+1$	-129263967	$((-9^8)-(76^*543))^*(2+1)$
-128787200	$(-9^8+7^6+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-129277566	$(((-9^8)/7)-6543)^*21$
-128787202	$(-9^8+7^6+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	-129303458	$(9^8+7^*6^6)^*(-4+3-2)+1$
-128787230	$(-9^8+7^6-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-129303460	$(9^8+7^*6^6)^*(-4+3-2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-129493094	$(-9^8-7^8+5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-157672116	$(-9*876)*(((5^4)*32)-1)$
-129493096	$(-9^8-7^8+5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	-157687884	$(-9*876)*(((5^4)*32)+1)$
-129493124	$(-9^8-7^8-5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-158293125	$(((-9*87)-6)^*(5^4))^*321$
-129493126	$(-9^8-7^8-5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	-159380502	$9+8*76*(5-4^3+2)+1$
-130237514	$-9*(8-7^8*(5-4^3+2))+1$	-159380504	$9+8*76*(5-4^3+2)-1$
-130237516	$-9*(8-7^8*(5-4^3+2))-1$	-159380520	$-9+8*76*(5-4^3+2)+1$
-130429086	$9-8-(7^6)^5+4^3+2+1$	-159380522	$-9+8*76*(5-4^3+2)-1$
-130625696	$(9-8)*(-7^6)^5+4^3+2-1$	-159386582	$9-8*76*(5+4^3+2)+1$
-130953374	$9-8-(7^6)^5-4^3+2+1$	-159386584	$9-8*76*(5+4^3+2)-1$
-132001847	$((-9-8)/7^8-6+5)^*(4^3+2)+1$	-161425154	$(9^8-7-6)^*(5/4-3-2)+1$
-132001849	$((-9-8)/7^8-6+5)^*(4^3+2)-1$	-161425156	$(9^8-7-6)^*(5/4-3-2)-1$
-133239827	$((((-9^8)+7)^*65)+43)/21$	-162760407	$(9/(87-6*5^4(4^3)))^(-2+1)$
-134369259	$((9^8)^(-7+6+5)-4)^*(-3-2)+1$	-164088871	$(((-9/(87*6))^(-5)/4)+321$
-134369261	$((9^8)^(-7+6+5)-4)^*(-3-2)-1$	-164089513	$(((-9/(87*6))^(-5)/4)-321$
-134369299	$((9^8)^(-7+6+5)+4)^*(-3-2)+1$	-164107541	$-9^8-7^8*(5+4^3+2)+1$
-134369301	$((9^8)^(-7+6+5)+4)^*(-3-2)-1$	-164107543	$-9^8-7^8*(5+4^3+2)-1$
-136577608	$(-9-8^7)^*65-4^3+2+1$	-168896011	$((9+(8+7+6)^5)^4-3-2)^*-1$
-136577610	$(-9-8^7)^*65-4^3+2-1$	-168896022	$((9-(8-(7+6)^5)^4+3^2)^*-1$
-136836548	$9+8^7*6*(5-4^3+2)+1$	-169414199	$-9*8*(7^8*5^4*3-2)+1$
-136836550	$9+8^7*6*(5-4^3+2)-1$	-169414201	$-9*8*(7^8*5^4*3-2)-1$
-136836566	$-9+8^7*6*(5-4^3+2)+1$	-169414631	$-9*8*(7^8*5^4+3-2)+1$
-136836568	$-9+8^7*6*(5-4^3+2)-1$	-169414633	$-9*8*(7^8*5^4+3-2)-1$
-136841768	$9-8^7*6*(5+4^3+2)+1$	-171969155	$(-9^8+7^8*6^5)^*4^3+2+1$
-136841770	$9-8^7*6*(5+4^3+2)-1$	-171969157	$(-9^8+7^8*6^5)^*4^3+2-1$
-140624495	$9*8*(7+(-6+5-4)^3+2)+1$	-172156268	$((-9^8)+7654)^*(3+2)-1$
-140624497	$9*8*(7+(-6+5-4)^3+2)-1$	-172182563	$(9^8)^*(7-(6+5))^+4321$
-140823795	$(98-((7^8)^*(54+3)))^*21$	-172187191	$(9^8+7^8*(6+5))^*4^3+2+1$
-140825755	$98-(((7^8)^*(54+3))^*21)$	-172187193	$(9^8+7^8*(6+5))^*4^3+2-1$
-140825951	$-98-(((7^8)^*(54+3))^*21)$	-172191205	$((9^8)^*(7-(6+5)))-4321$
-140827911	$(-98-((7^8)^*(54+3)))^*21$	-172217500	$((-9^8)-7654)^*(3+2)-1$
-146120129	$-9*(8+7^8*(5+4^3)^2)+1$	-172404611	$(-9^8-7^8*6^5)^*4^3+2+1$
-146120131	$-9*(8+7^8*(5+4^3)^2)-1$	-172404613	$(-9^8-7^8*6^5)^*4^3+2-1$
-146410006	$((98-76)^5)^4+3^2)^*-1$	-174120519	$-9*8/7^8-6*5^4(4+3^2)+1$
-147178970	$-9*(8-7^8*(5-(4^3)^2)+1)$	-174120521	$-9*8/7^8-6*5^4(4+3^2)-1$
-147178972	$-9*(8-7^8*(5-(4^3)^2))-1$	-174849381	$(98-765)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-148237667	$9*(8+7^8*5^4(4-32))+1$	-174850047	$((98-765)^*(4^3+2))+1$
-148237669	$9*(8+7^8*5^4(4-32))-1$	-174850049	$((98-765)^*(4^3+2))-1$
-150251751	$(9^8-7^8)^*(5-4^3)/2+1$	-174850715	$(98-765)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-150251753	$(9^8-7^8)^*(5-4^3)/2-1$	-177782661	$(-9*(8*(7^8))-543)^*21$
-150652096	$((((-9^8)+7)/6)+543)^*21$	-177884640	$-9*8*(7^8(6+5-4)-3)^*(2+1)$
-150652145	$((((-9^8)-7)/6)+543)^*21$	-177885936	$9*8*(7^8(6+5-4)-3)^*(2+1)$
-150663477	$(9^8-7-6)^*(5-4^3)/2+1$	-177987915	$(-9*(8*(7^8))+543)^*21$
-150663479	$(9^8-7-6)^*(5-4^3)/2-1$	-179523141	$((9+8)^8-65)^*(4/3)^(-2-1)$
-150663568	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4^3)/2+1$	-179523169	$((9+8)^8-6)^*(4/3)^(-2-1)$
-150663570	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4^3)/2-1$	-180795006	$((((-9^8)+76)/5)+43)^*21$
-150674902	$((((-9^8)+7)/6)-543)^*21$	-180796812	$((((-9^8)+76)/5)-43)^*21$
-150674951	$((((-9^8)-7)/6)-543)^*21$	-184941467	$-9^8*((7-6/54)/3+2)+1$
-151023438	$(98-(((7^8)^5)^4))^*321$	-184941469	$-9^8*((7-6/54)/3+2)-1$
-151036278	$(98-(((7^8)^5)^4))^*321$	-185606790	$(-9^8-7^8)/(5/43^2)+1$
-151075294	$(9^8+7^8)^*(5-4^3)/2+1$	-185606792	$(-9^8-7^8)/(5/43^2)-1$
-151075296	$(9^8+7^8)^*(5-4^3)/2-1$	-186442599	$(-98+((7^8)^5))^*(4-321)$
-151086354	$(-98-(((7^8)^5)^4))^*321$	-186473567	$98+(((7^8)^5)^*(4-321))$
-151093255	$-9*((8^8-(-7-(-6-5)))/4+3)^2-1$	-186473763	$-98+(((7^8)^5)^*(4-321))$
-151093264	$-9*(8^8-(-7+6+5)+4/3)^2+1$	-186504731	$(98+((7^8)^5))^*(4-321)$
-151093273	$-9*(8^8-(-7-(-6-5)))/4+3)^2+1$	-188130113	$-9^8*((7+6/54)/3+2)+1$
-151099194	$(-98-(((7^8)^5)^4))^*321$	-188130115	$-9^8*((7+6/54)/3+2)-1$
-151511480	$-9*(8^8-(-7+6+5)+4+3)^2+1$	-189405238	$(9^8-76)/-5*(43+21)$
-151511482	$-9*(8^8-(-7+6+5)+4+3)^2-1$	-189724416	$((-9^8)^*(76/54+3))^+21$
-152470752	$(98-((7^8)^54))^*(3+21)$	-189724458	$((-9^8)^*(76/54+3))-21$
-152475456	$(-98-((7^8)^54))^*(3+21)$	-189843719	$(9+(8+7)^8*5)^*(4/3+2)+1$
-153691424	$9*(8+7)^8*(5^4-4-3)/2+1$	-189843721	$(9+(8+7)^8*5)^*(4/3+2)-1$
-153691426	$9*(8+7)^8*(5^4-4-3)/2-1$	-189843779	$(9+(8+7)^8*5)^*(4/3-2)+1$
-154355496	$-9-8*7^8*(54^3+2)+1$	-189843781	$(9+(8+7)^8*5)^*(4/3-2)-1$
-154355498	$-9-8*7^8*(54^3+2)-1$	-190840837	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$
-154649330	$9^8*(76/54-3-2)+1$	-191101122	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$
-154649332	$9^8*(76/54-3-2)-1$	-191102345	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$
-155788134	$(((-9^8)^*76)-(54/3))/21$	-191102357	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$
-155788159	$(((-9^8)^*76)-543)/21$	-191102646	$((9+8+7)^8+5*(4^3+2))^*-1$
-155885625	$(((-9*87)+6)^*(5^4))^*321$	-191102837	$((9+8+7)^8+5-(4^3)^2)^*-1$
-156300004	$((987*(6+(5^4)/3))^2)^*-1$	-191102915	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$
-157493438	$9^8-765*4^3+2+1$	-191102931	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$
-157493440	$9^8-765*4^3+2-1$	-191102940	$((9+8+7)^8+5-4^3+2)^*-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-191103012	$((9+8+7)^6-5+43-2)^*-1$	-215078226	$(-9^8-(7-6^8)^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-191103025	$((9+8+7)^6+54-3-2)^*-1$	-215229074	$((-9^8)+(7^6))^5+4321$
-191103037	$((9+8+7)^6-5+4^3+2)^*-1$	-215229494	$((-9^8)-(7^6))^5+4321$
-191103306	$((9+8+7)^6+5*(4^3+2))^*-1$	-215229759	$(-9^8+7^6+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-191103607	$((9+8+7)^6+5^4+3^2)^*-1$	-215229761	$(-9^8+7^6+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-191106976	$((9+8+7)^6+(5^4)^3/2)^*-1$	-215230299	$(-9^8+7+654)^*(3+2)+1$
-191147775	$(98-((7^6)^5))^*(4+321)$	-215230301	$(-9^8+7+654)^*(3+2)-1$
-191179527	$98-(((7^6)^5)^*(4+321))$	-215230414	$(-9^8+7+6+5^4)^*(3+2)+1$
-191179723	$-98-(((7^6)^5)^*(4+321))$	-215230416	$(-9^8+7+6+5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-191211475	$(-98-((7^6)^5))^*(4+321)$	-215231189	$(9^8-7*(65+4))^*(-3-2)+1$
-191649927	$(98-((7^6)^543))^*(2+1)$	-215231191	$(9^8-7*(65+4))^*(-3-2)-1$
-191650515	$(-98-((7^6)^543))^*(2+1)$	-215231504	$(9^8-7*(6+54))^*(-3-2)+1$
-193180823	$(9^8-7^6)^*(-5+(4-3)/2)+1$	-215231506	$(9^8-7*(6+54))^*(-3-2)-1$
-193180825	$(9^8-7^6)^*(-5+(4-3)/2)-1$	-215232574	$(-9^8+7^6+5-4)^*(3+2)+1$
-193706802	$((9^8-765)/4)^*(3-21)$	-215232694	$(-9^8+7*(6+5^4))^*(3+2)+1$
-193713687	$((9^8+765)/4)^*(3-21)$	-215232696	$(-9^8+7*(6+5^4))^*(3+2)-1$
-194239664	$(9^8+7^6)^*(-5+(4-3)/2)+1$	-215232954	$(-9^8+76+54)^*(3+2)+1$
-194239666	$(9^8+7^6)^*(-5+(4-3)/2)-1$	-215232956	$(-9^8+76+54)^*(3+2)-1$
-196608007	$(-9+8)^*7-6/(5/4^3-3)^{(-2-1)}$	-215233144	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(3+2)+1$
-196941388	$(98-((7^6)^54))^*(32-1)$	-215233146	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-196944328	$98-(((7^6)^54)^*(32-1))$	-215233206	$(-9^8+76)^5+4*(3+2)-1$
-196944524	$-98-(((7^6)^54)^*(32-1))$	-215233264	$(-9^8+7+65-4)^*(3+2)+1$
-196947464	$(-98-((7^6)^54))^*(32-1)$	-215233279	$(9^8-(7+6)^5)^*(4-3^2)+1$
-198003267	$(-9-8)^*7^6*(5^4*(3+2)-1)$	-215233281	$(9^8-(7+6)^5)^*(4-3^2)-1$
-200539297	$98-(765*((4^3)^2)-1)$	-215233302	$(-9^8+76/5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-200539493	$-98-(765*((4^3)^2)-1)$	-215233334	$(-9^8-7+65-4)^*(3+2)+1$
-200540087	$9^8-765*4^3+2+1$	-215233336	$(-9^8-7+65-4)^*(3+2)-1$
-200540089	$9^8-765*4^3-2-1$	-215233479	$(-9^8+7+6)^5+4^3-2-1$
-200540158	$9-8-765*4^3+2+1$	-215233488	$(9^8-(7-6/5)^4)^*(-3-2)+1$
-200540827	$98-(765*((4^3)^2)+1)$	-215233501	$(-9^8-7*(6-5-4))^*(3+2)-1$
-200541023	$-98-(765*((4^3)^2)+1)$	-215233722	$(-9^8-(7-6/5)^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-202003333	$(9+8)^*7^6*(5^4*(3+2)-1)$	-215233731	$(-9^8-7-6)^5-4^3+2+1$
-204204952	$98+(-7^6)^5*((4/3)^{-2+1})$	-215233809	$(-9^8+7+6-54)^*(3+2)+1$
-204238654	$9-8^*7^6*(5^4+3+2)+1$	-215233811	$(-9^8+7+6-54)^*(3+2)-1$
-204238656	$9-8^*7^6*(5^4+3+2)-1$	-215233874	$(-9^8+7-65+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-204238672	$-9-8^*7^6*(5^4+3+2)+1$	-215233876	$(-9^8+7-65+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-204238674	$-9-8^*7^6*(5^4+3+2)-1$	-215233911	$(-9^8-7-6*(5+4))^*(3+2)-1$
-207359922	$-9+87-(6^5*4)^3(3+2-1)$	-215233929	$(9^8+(7+6)^5)^*(4-3^2)+1$
-207359993	$(9-8)^*7-(6^5*4)^3(3+2-1)$	-215233931	$(9^8+(7+6)^5)^*(4-3^2)-1$
-207360091	$-9+87-(6^5*4)^3(3+2-1)$	-215233946	$(-9^8-7-65+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-207360096	$-9-87-(6^5*4)^3(3+2-1)$	-215234004	$(-9^8-76)^5-4*(3+2)+1$
-207360105	$-9-87-(6^5*4)^3(3+2-1)$	-215234064	$(9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(-3-2)+1$
-207530778	$-98*(((7^6)^54)/3)-21$	-215234066	$(9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(-3-2)-1$
-207532815	$((-98*(7^6)^54)/3)+21$	-215234129	$(-9^8-7*(6+5+4))^*(3+2)+1$
-207532857	$((-98*(7^6)^54)/3)-21$	-215234131	$(-9^8-7*(6+5+4))^*(3+2)-1$
-207534894	$-98*(((7^6)^54)/3)+21$	-215234514	$(-9^8-7*(6+5^4))^*(3+2)+1$
-209279225	$(9^8-7^6)^*(-5+4^3(-3/2))+1$	-215234516	$(-9^8-7*(6+5^4))^*(3+2)-1$
-209279227	$(9^8-7^6)^*(-5+4^3(-3/2))-1$	-215234636	$(-9^8-7^6+5+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-209647284	$(98-((7^6)^54))^*(32+1)$	-215235704	$(9^8+7*(6+54))^*(-3-2)+1$
-209650420	$98-(((7^6)^54)^*(32+1))$	-215235706	$(9^8+7*(6+54))^*(-3-2)-1$
-209650616	$-98-(((7^6)^54)^*(32+1))$	-215236019	$(9^8+7*(65+4))^*(-3-2)+1$
-209653752	$(-98-((7^6)^54))^*(32+1)$	-215236021	$(9^8+7*(65+4))^*(-3-2)-1$
-212635449	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^*(5^4*3^2)+1$	-215236664	$(-9^8+7+6-5^4)^*(3+2)+1$
-214357893	$(987-((6+5)^4(4^3/2)))^3+1$	-215236666	$(-9^8+7+6-5^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-214357895	$987-(((6+5)^4(4^3/2)))^3+1$	-215237716	$((-9^8)+(7^6))^5-4321$
-214359867	$(-987-((6+5)^4(4^3/2)))^3+1$	-215238136	$((-9^8)-(7^6))^5-4321$
-214359869	$-987-(((6+5)^4(4^3/2)))^3+1$	-215388984	$(9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(-3-2)+1$
-214645341	$(-9^8+7^6)^5+4*(3+2)-1$	-215388986	$(9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(-3-2)-1$
-214645379	$(-9^8+7^6)^5-4*(3+2)+1$	-215389089	$(-9^8+7-6^5+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-214961304	$(-9^8+7*(6^5+4))^*(3+2)+1$	-215389091	$(-9^8+7-6^5+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-214961306	$(-9^8+7*(6^5+4))^*(3+2)-1$	-215389264	$(-9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*(3+2)+1$
-214961424	$(-9^8+7^6+5+4)^*(3+2)+1$	-215389266	$(-9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*(3+2)-1$
-214961426	$(-9^8+7^6+5+4)^*(3+2)-1$	-215495748	$-9^8(7-6)^5-4^3+2+1$
-214961584	$(-9^8+7*(6^5-4))^*(3+2)+1$	-215495750	$-9^8(7-6)^5-4^3+2-1$
-214961586	$(-9^8+7*(6^5-4))^*(3+2)-1$	-215505624	$(-9^8-7*(6^5-4))^*(3+2)+1$
-214971460	$-9^8(7-6)^5+4^3+2+1$	-215505626	$(-9^8-7*(6^5-4))^*(3+2)-1$
-214971462	$-9^8(7-6)^5+4^3+2-1$	-215505744	$(-9^8-7^6+5+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-215077944	$(9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*(-3-2)+1$	-215505746	$(-9^8-7^6+5+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-215077946	$(9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*(-3-2)-1$	-215505904	$(-9^8-7*(6^5+4))^*(3+2)+1$
-215078049	$(-9^8+7+6^5+4)^*(3+2)+1$	-215505906	$(-9^8-7*(6^5+4))^*(3+2)-1$
-215078051	$(-9^8+7+6^5+4)^*(3+2)-1$	-215821831	$(-9^8-7^6)^5+4*(3+2)-1$
-215078224	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*(3+2)+1$	-215821869	$(-9^8-7^6)^5-4*(3+2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-216909312	$(9/(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-241061633	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/(5/(4-32))-1$
-217062476	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43-2))+1$	-241695846	$(-987+65)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-217062478	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43-2))-1$	-241696767	$((-987+65)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$
-219028824	$(((-9*8)*(7^{\wedge}6))*543)/21$	-241696769	$((-987+65)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1$
-220011493	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3/2))+1$	-241697690	$(-987+65)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-220011495	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3/2))-1$	-242121264	$((-98*(7^{\wedge}6))+54/3)*21$
-220591882	$9*((-8-7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4)/3+2)-1$	-242122020	$((-98*(7^{\wedge}6))-54/3)*21$
-220872968	$(-9^{\wedge}8-(7*6*5)^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}-2+1$	-242518329	$(-9/((87*(6-543))^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
-220872970	$(-9^{\wedge}8-(7*6*5)^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}-2-1$	-247165834	$9-(8/(7^{\wedge}(6+5)+4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-225991206	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)+3)*21$	-247165852	$-9-(8/(7^{\wedge}(6+5)+4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-225991332	$((((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)-3)*21$	-247673167	$9*(-8+7)-6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-225995321	$(9^{\wedge}8+7)*6*(5/4-3)/2+1$	-248204593	$-9^{\wedge}((8-7)*6)-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-225995323	$(9^{\wedge}8+7)*6*(5/4-3)/2-1$	-250870851	$(-987+(6*5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-226229409	$(-98-765)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-250871807	$((-987+(6*5))*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$
-226230271	$((-98-765)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-250871809	$((-987+(6*5))*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1$
-226230273	$((-98-765)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-250872765	$(-987+(6*5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-226231135	$(-98-765)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-250938566	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)*(3+2)+1$
-227988188	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)+1$	-250938568	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)*(3+2)-1$
-227988190	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)-1$	-251060229	$987*((6^{\wedge}5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-228064410	$((-98-76)*5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-251061215	$(987*((6^{\wedge}5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))+1$
-228065106	$(-98-76)*((5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-251061217	$(987*((6^{\wedge}5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))-1$
-228065279	$(((-98-76)*5)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$	-251062203	$987*((6^{\wedge}5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$
-228065281	$(((-98-76)*5)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1$	-252765128	$(-98/((76-(54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
-228065454	$(-98-76)*((5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-252965916	$-9^{\wedge}((8-7)+6*(54-3^{\wedge}2-2-1))$
-228066150	$((-98-76)*5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-253491357	$(98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432-1$
-229768424	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*43+2))+1$	-253533497	$98-(((7^{\wedge}6)*5)*432-1))$
-229768426	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*43+2))-1$	-253533693	$-98-(((7^{\wedge}6)*5)*432-1))$
-230399925	$9*(8*(7/6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)))-1$	-253575833	$(-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432-1$
-232001864	$(9+876)*(-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-254003556	$((9+8)*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(-4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
-232001866	$(9+876)*(-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-254004826	$((9+8)*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(-4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
-232945019	$-9*8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/2)+1$	-254028798	$-9^{\wedge}((8-7)+6*(54+3^{\wedge}2-2-1))$
-232945021	$-9*8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/2)-1$	-254079503	$((98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432)+1$
-234149696	$-9^{\wedge}8-((7-6+5)*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$	-254079504	$((98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432)*1$
-234149698	$-9^{\wedge}8-((7-6+5)*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$	-254079505	$(98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432-1$
-236109895	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5+(4-3)/2)+1$	-254164175	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432)+1$
-236109897	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5+(4-3)/2)-1$	-254164176	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432)*1$
-236195999	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7+6)/(5*4)^{\wedge}3*2)+1$	-254164177	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432)*1$
-236250135	$-9*(8*(7*6*5^{\wedge}4)+3+2)-1$	-254667651	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432)-1$
-236421382	$((9*(8+7)-6-5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)/-1$	-254670987	$98-(((7^{\wedge}6)*5)*432+1))$
-236714158	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-254710183	$-98-(((7^{\wedge}6)*5)*432+1))$
-236714160	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-254752519	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*5))*432+1)$
-236714235	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-255851568	$((-987+6)+5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-236714237	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-255852543	$(((-987+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1$
-236756519	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)*(4+3/2)+1$	-255852545	$(((-987+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1$
-236756521	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)*(4+3/2)-1$	-255853520	$((-987+6)+5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-236756541	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(6+5))*(-4-3/2)+1$	-256686002	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6)/54-3)*2+1$
-236756543	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(6+5))*(-4-3/2)-1$	-256686004	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6)/54-3)*2-1$
-236756838	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6*5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-257025328	$(-987*6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-236756840	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6*5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-257030263	$-987*((6*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-236756893	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6)*5*(4+3/2)+1$	-257031249	$((-987*6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2))+1$
-236756895	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6)*5*(4+3/2)-1$	-257031250	$((-987*6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2))*1$
-236756937	$(9^{\wedge}8/(7-6)-5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-257031251	$((-987*6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2))-1$
-236756939	$(9^{\wedge}8/(7-6)-5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-257032237	$-987*((6*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-236756992	$(9^{\wedge}8/(7-6)+5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-257037172	$(-987*6)*(((5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-236756994	$(9^{\wedge}8/(7-6)+5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-257157378	$(987-6)*((5-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$
-236757036	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7-6)*(5+(4-3)/2)+1$	-257159340	$(987-6)*5-((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-236757038	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7-6)*(5+(4-3)/2)-1$	-257167188	$((-987+6)*((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1))$
-236757168	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*6-5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-257168168	$((-987+6)*5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-236757170	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*6-5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-257168170	$((-987+6)*5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$
-236757388	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(6+5))*(-4-3/2)+1$	-257169150	$(-987+6)*((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$
-236757390	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(6+5))*(-4-3/2)-1$	-258003612	$((-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
-236799694	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-258004902	$((-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
-236799696	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-258275736	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)*(3+21)$
-236799771	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)+1$	-258276005	$((-9^{\wedge}8)*((7-6)+5))+4321$
-236799773	$(9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4-3/2)-1$	-258279953	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7)*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-237179123	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)+1$	-258279955	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7)*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-237179125	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)-1$	-258280037	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-237180243	$(9*8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)+1$	-258280039	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-237180245	$(9*8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)-1$	-258280613	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7)*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-237404034	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6)*5*(4+3/2)+1$	-258280615	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7)*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-237404036	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6)*5*(4+3/2)-1$	-258280697	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-241061631	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/(5/(4-32))+1$	-258280699	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-258284647	$((-9^8)^*((7-6)+5))-4321$	-271063288	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^*32-1$
-258284916	$((-9^8)-765)/4*(3+21)$	-271063304	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^*32+1$
-258422541	$(-987+(6/5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-271063306	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^*32-1$
-258472998	$((-987+6)-5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-271064863	$(-9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5)-4)^*32+1$
-258473983	$((-987+6)-5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-271064865	$(-9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5)-4)^*32-1$
-258473985	$((-987+6)-5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-274658121	$9/8*(76-5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3))-2-1$
-258474970	$((-987+6)-5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-275774436	$(-987-65)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-258670986	$987*((65-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-275775487	$((-987-65)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$
-258671972	$(987*(65-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$	-275775489	$((-987-65)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$
-258671974	$(987*(65-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-275776540	$(-987-65)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-258672960	$987*(65-((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-275817878	$9^{\wedge}8*(-76/54-3-2)+1$
-258705531	$987*((6^*5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-275817880	$9^{\wedge}8*(-76/54-3-2)-1$
-258706517	$(987*((6^*5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$	-276922872	$((9*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-258706519	$(987*((6^*5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-276922887	$((9*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^*2)/-1$
-258707505	$987*((6^*5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-278004586	$(9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-258724284	$987*((6+5)-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-278004588	$(9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-258726258	$987*((6+5)-((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-280004619	$(9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-32)+1$
-258734154	$(987*((65-5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1))$	-280004621	$(9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-32)-1$
-258735140	$(987*(6-(5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))))+1$	-282710475	$9*(8+((7^{\wedge}6)^*(54-32)))$
-258735142	$(987*(6-(5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))))-1$	-282710619	$-9*(8-((7^{\wedge}6)^*(54-32)))$
-258736127	$((-987*(6-5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1))$	-283476415	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+65^{\wedge}4+3^*2+1$
-258736129	$((-987*(6-5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-283476429	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+65^{\wedge}4-3^*2-1$
-258738102	$-987*((6-5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-291769528	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)+1$
-258745998	$-987*((6+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$	-291769530	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1$
-258746984	$(-987*((6+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$	-292707912	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}-6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$
-258746986	$(-987*((6+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-292707914	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}-6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1$
-258747972	$-987*((6+5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-292713510	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6)^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1$
-258764751	$-987*((6^*5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$	-292713512	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6)^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1$
-258765737	$(-987*((6^*5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$	-293364422	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-258765739	$(-987*((6^*5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-293364424	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-258766725	$-987*((6^*5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-296543757	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*(7-(6/54)))+321$
-258799296	$-987*((65+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-296544399	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*(7-(6/54)))-321$
-258801270	$-987*((65+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-298138400	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-6/54/3^*2)+1$
-258997284	$((-987-6)+5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-298138402	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-6/54/3^*2)-1$
-258998271	$((-987-6)+5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-299630591	$9^*8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}-3-2)+1$
-258998273	$((-987-6)+5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-299630593	$9^*8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}-3-2)-1$
-258999260	$((-987-6)+5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-300567671	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-259051689	$(-987-(6/5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-300567673	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-259874648	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-6)/54+3)^*2+1$	-301109318	$-9^{\wedge}8*7-6^{\wedge}5*(4-32)+1$
-259874650	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-6)/54+3)^*2-1$	-301109320	$-9^{\wedge}8*7-6^{\wedge}5*(4-32)-1$
-260144641	$(-9+8)/(7+6^*5^*4)^{\wedge}(-3-2+1)$	-301204166	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-260303034	$(987+6)*((5-(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-301204168	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-260305020	$(987+6)*((5-((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)))$	-301279516	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((6+5)^*4321)$
-260312964	$(-987-6)*((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-301294449	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((6+5)^*4321)$
-260313956	$(-987-6)*((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-301294461	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((6+5)^*4321)$
-260313958	$(-987-6)*((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-301298902	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((6+5)^*4321)$
-260314950	$(-987-6)*((5+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-301299032	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((6+5)^*4321)$
-261618714	$(-987-(6+5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-301301091	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((6+5)^*4321)$
-261619711	$(-987-(6+5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-301301151	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)-((6+5)^*4321)$
-261619713	$((-987-(6+5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-301304898	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-261620710	$(-987-(6+5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-301305465	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-262531854	$9^{\wedge}(8-7)+6)^*(-5+3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-301305922	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-262933532	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4-3+2)+1$	-301306442	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)-((65+4)^*321)$
-262933534	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*(4-3+2)-1$	-301306773	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-265142853	$(-9-8/7+6)*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2))-1$	-301307466	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-266004388	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^*2)+1$	-301307787	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-266004390	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^*2)-1$	-301310239	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-266410053	$-987*((6^{\wedge}5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1$	-301310241	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-266411039	$(-987*((6^{\wedge}5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))+1$	-301311351	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)+((65+4)^*321)$
-266411041	$(-987*((6^{\wedge}5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))))-1$	-301311639	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)-((6-54)^*321)$
-266412027	$-987*((6^{\wedge}5)+(4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1$	-301315275	$((-9^{\wedge}8)^*7)-((65+4)^*321)$
-266599431	$(-987-(6^*5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-301321421	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-266600447	$((-987-(6^*5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))+1)$	-301321423	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-266600449	$((-987-(6^*5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))-1)$	-301322660	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-266601465	$(-987-(6^*5))*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-301322662	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-269041924	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6)*(-5/4-3-2)+1$	-301322728	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^*5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-269041926	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-6)*(-5/4-3-2)-1$	-301322821	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6-5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-271061727	$(9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5)+4)^*32+1$	-301322823	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+(6-5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-271061729	$(9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5)+4)^*32-1$	-301322920	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-271061983	$(9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5)-4)^*32+1$	-301322922	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-271061985	$(9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5)-4)^*32-1$	-301322949	$-9^{\wedge}8*7+6-5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-271063286	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^*32+1$	-301322953	$-9^{\wedge}8*7-6+5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-301322980	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 + (4^3)^2 + 1$	-301348172	$((-9^8)^7) - (65 \cdot (4 + 321))$
-301322982	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 + (4^3)^2 - 1$	-301348629	$((-9^8)^7) - (654 \cdot (32 + 1))$
-301323268	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (5^4 + 3 + 2) - 1$	-301349196	$((-9^8)^7) - ((65 + 4) \cdot 321)$
-301323663	$((-9^8)^7) + (6^5 \cdot (543 + 21))$	-301352943	$((-9^8)^7) + (6^5 \cdot (5 - 4321))$
-301323921	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^{(3+2)} + 1$	-301353003	$((-9^8)^7) - (6^5 \cdot (5 + 4321))$
-301323923	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 - 5 + 4)^{(3+2)} - 1$	-301355062	$((-9^8)^7) - (65^5 \cdot (432 - 1))$
-301324797	$((-9^8)^7) + (6^5 \cdot (54 + 321))$	-301355192	$((-9^8)^7) - (65^5 \cdot (432 + 1))$
-301324866	$((-9^8)^7) + (6543 / (2 + 1))$	-301359633	$((-9^8)^7) - (6^5 \cdot (5432 - 1))$
-301325093	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 / 4 + 3^2 + 1$	-301359645	$((-9^8)^7) - (6^5 \cdot (5432 + 1))$
-301325445	$((-9^8)^7) - (6^5 \cdot (54 - 321))$	-301374578	$((-9^8)^7) - ((6 + 5) \cdot 4321)$
-301325617	$((-9^8)^7) + (65^5 \cdot (43 - 21))$	-301445144	$9^8 \cdot (-7 - (6/54)^{(3+2)}) + 1$
-301326208	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (4 - 32) - 1$	-301445146	$9^8 \cdot (-7 - (6/54)^{(3+2)}) - 1$
-301326317	$-9^8 \cdot (7 - (6/54)^{(3+2)}) + 1$	-301449926	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 + 1$
-301326319	$-9^8 \cdot (7 - (6/54)^{(3+2)}) - 1$	-301449928	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 - 1$
-301326320	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 + 5^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 + 1$	-301544774	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (4 - 32) + 1$
-301326332	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 + 5^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 + 1$	-301544776	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (4 - 32) - 1$
-301326334	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 + 5^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 - 1$	-302086421	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5 + 4)^{(3+2)} + 1$
-301326344	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1$	-302086423	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5 + 4)^{(3+2)} - 1$
-301326346	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1$	-304349183	$9^8 \cdot (7 + 6 - 5) \cdot (-4^4 - 3 - 2) + 1$
-301326502	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (5 + 43^2) - 1$	-304349185	$9^8 \cdot (7 + 6 - 5) \cdot (-4^4 - 3 - 2) - 1$
-301326514	$(9^8 - 76) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3^2) + 1$	-304946027	$(9^8 \cdot 7^6 - 5) \cdot (-4 - 32) + 1$
-301326516	$(9^8 - 76) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3^2) - 1$	-304946029	$(9^8 \cdot 7^6 - 5) \cdot (-4 - 32) - 1$
-301326656	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 65^5 \cdot 4^3 / 2 + 1$	-304946135	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^6 \cdot (5 + 4) \cdot 32) + 1$
-301326658	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 65^5 \cdot 4^3 / 2 - 1$	-304946137	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^6 \cdot (5 + 4) \cdot 32) - 1$
-301326743	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 + (5^4 - 3) / 2 - 1$	-304946279	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (5 + 4) \cdot 32) + 1$
-301326776	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (54 - 3^2) + 1$	-304946281	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (5 + 4) \cdot 32) - 1$
-301326952	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot 5 + 4^3 + 2 - 1$	-304947827	$9^8 \cdot (8^7 \cdot 6^5) \cdot (-4 - 32) + 1$
-301327142	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1$	-304947829	$9^8 \cdot (8^7 \cdot 6^5) \cdot (-4 - 32) - 1$
-301327318	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (54 - 3^2) - 1$	-309289670	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot 4^4 \cdot (3 + 2) + 1$
-301327351	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (5^4 - 3) / 2 + 1$	-309289672	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot 4^4 \cdot (3 + 2) - 1$
-301327424	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (54 + 3^2) + 1$	-310484538	$((-987^6) / 5) \cdot ((4^4 \cdot (3^2)) + 1)$
-301327426	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (54 + 3^2) - 1$	-312762134	$9 - (8 + 7^6)^5 - 4^4 \cdot 3^2 + 1$
-301327436	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 65^5 \cdot 4^3 / 2 + 1$	-312762136	$9 - (8 + 7^6)^5 - 4^4 \cdot 3^2 - 1$
-301327438	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 65^5 \cdot 4^3 / 2 - 1$	-319152302	$((-9 - 8)^7 \cdot 6 + 5) \cdot ((4/3)^2 - 1)$
-301327578	$(9^8 + 76) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3^2) + 1$	-319177665	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 65^4 + 3^2 + 1$
-301327580	$(9^8 + 76) \cdot (-5 + 4 - 3^2) - 1$	-319177679	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 65^4 - 3^2 - 1$
-301327592	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (5 + 43^2) + 1$	-322417931	$((9^8 + 7) \cdot 6 + 5)^4 \cdot (3 - 2) / -1$
-301327748	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^4 \cdot 3 + 2 + 1$	-322850354	$(9^8 - 7) \cdot 6^5 \cdot 4^4 \cdot (-3 + 2) + 1$
-301327750	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5) \cdot 4^4 \cdot 3 + 2 - 1$	-322850356	$(9^8 - 7) \cdot 6^5 \cdot 4^4 \cdot (-3 + 2) - 1$
-301327760	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 - 5^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 + 1$	-326181513	$-9 / (8 + 7) \cdot ((6^5 - 4)^3)^2 - 1$
-301327762	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 - 5^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 - 1$	-328005411	$(-9 - 8) \cdot 7^6 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (54^3 + 2) + 1$
-301327774	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 - 5^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 - 1$	-328005413	$(-9 - 8) \cdot 7^6 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (54^3 + 2) - 1$
-301327775	$9^8 \cdot (-7 - (6/54)^{(3+2)}) + 1$	-329277158	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^6) \cdot (5^4 - 3) / 2 + 1$
-301327777	$9^8 \cdot (-7 - (6/54)^{(3+2)}) - 1$	-329277160	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^6) \cdot (5^4 - 3) / 2 - 1$
-301327886	$-9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^5 \cdot (4 - 32) + 1$	-329321942	$9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6) \cdot (-5^4 + 3) / 2 + 1$
-301328477	$((-9^8)^7) - (65^5 \cdot (43 - 21))$	-329321944	$9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6) \cdot (-5^4 + 3) / 2 - 1$
-301328649	$((-9^8)^7) + (6^5 \cdot (54 - 321))$	-330887789	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) / 2 + 1$
-301329001	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 / 4 - 3^2 - 1$	-330887791	$9^8 \cdot (8 - 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) / 2 - 1$
-301329228	$((-9^8)^7) - (6543 / (2 + 1))$	-330887834	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) / 2 + 1$
-301329297	$((-9^8)^7) - (6^5 \cdot (54 + 321))$	-330887836	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) / 2 - 1$
-301330171	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 - 5 + 4)^{(3+2)} + 1$	-330887861	$9^8 \cdot (-8 - 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) / 2 + 1$
-301330173	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 - 5 + 4)^{(3+2)} - 1$	-330887863	$9^8 \cdot (-8 - 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) / 2 - 1$
-301330431	$((-9^8)^7) - (6^5 \cdot (543 + 21))$	-333606159	$((-9^8 + 765) / 4) \cdot (32 - 1)$
-301330826	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (5^4 + 3 + 2) + 1$	-333612141	$(-9^8 - 7) \cdot (6 + 5 / 4^3 - 2) + 1$
-301331271	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 - 5 + 4^3)^2 + 1$	-333612143	$(-9^8 - 7) \cdot (6 + 5 / 4^3 - 2) - 1$
-301331273	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 - 5 + 4^3)^2 - 1$	-336711509	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (5^5 \cdot 4^3 - 2)) + 1$
-301331366	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (4^3)^2 + 1$	-336711511	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + 7^6 \cdot (5^5 \cdot 4^3 - 2)) - 1$
-301331432	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot ((5 + 4)^3 + 2) + 1$	-339731883	$9^8 \cdot (8 - (((7^6) - 54) \cdot 321))$
-301331434	$-9^8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot ((5 + 4)^3 + 2) - 1$	-339732027	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + (((7^6) - 54) \cdot 321))$
-301332671	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5 + 4^3)^2 + 1$	-339856503	$(98 - ((7^6) \cdot (5 + 4))) \cdot 321$
-301332673	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5 + 4^3)^2 - 1$	-339919419	$(-98 - ((7^6) \cdot (5 + 4))) \cdot 321$
-301333819	$((-9^8)^7) + (654 \cdot (3 - 21))$	-340043895	$9^8 \cdot (8 - (((7^6) + 54) \cdot 321))$
-301341681	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5)^4 + 3^2 + 1$	-340044039	$-9^8 \cdot (8 + (((7^6) + 54) \cdot 321))$
-301341695	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5)^4 - 3^2 - 1$	-344308094	$9^8 \cdot (8^7 - (6 + 5 - 4)^{(3+2)}) + 1$
-301342455	$((-9^8)^7) + ((6 - 54) \cdot 321)$	-344308096	$9^8 \cdot (8^7 - (6 + 5 - 4)^{(3+2)}) - 1$
-301342743	$((-9^8)^7) - (654 \cdot (3 + 21))$	-344312536	$((-9^8) + 7654) \cdot ((3^2) - 1)$
-301343853	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5 - 4)^{(3+2)} + 1$	-344369447	$((-9^8) \cdot ((7 + 6) - 5)) + 4321$
-301343855	$-9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5 - 4)^{(3+2)} - 1$	-344373191	$(-9^8 + 7 + 65) / 4 \cdot 32 + 1$
-301346307	$((-9^8)^7) - ((6 + 54) \cdot 321)$	-344378089	$((-9^8) \cdot ((7 + 6) - 5)) - 4321$
-301346628	$((-9^8)^7) - ((65 - 4) \cdot 321)$	-344435000	$((-9^8) - 7654) \cdot ((3^2) - 1)$
-301347321	$((-9^8)^7) - (654 \cdot (32 - 1))$	-347300052	$(-9^8 \cdot 7^6 - 5) \cdot (43 - 2) + 1$
-301347652	$((-9^8)^7) + (65^5 \cdot (4 - 321))$	-347300054	$(-9^8 \cdot 7^6 - 5) \cdot (43 - 2) - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-347301692	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2)+1$	-387347365	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*5^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}2-1$
-347301694	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2)-1$	-387419484	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)*(5+4))+321$
-349360129	$(9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(-4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-387419501	$(987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
-349417601	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2))+1$	-387419503	$987-(((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-349417603	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2))-1$	-387419851	$(9^{\wedge}8-76+5)*(-4-3-2)-1$
-350578043	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7*6)^{\wedge}5)*4*(3-2)+1$	-387419966	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-65)*(-4-3-2)+1$
-350578045	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7*6)^{\wedge}5)*4*(3-2)-1$	-387419968	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-65)*(-4-3-2)-1$
-351715526	$-9^{\wedge}8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)*(3+2)+1$	-387420126	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+76)*(5+4))-321$
-351715528	$-9^{\wedge}8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)*(3+2)-1$	-387420173	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-352275352	$((9*8+(7+6)*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)*-1$	-387420175	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-352275356	$((9*8+(7+6)*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)*-1$	-387420281	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7+6*5)*4+3+2)+1$
-352275367	$((9*8+(7+6)*5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)*-1$	-387420299	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-352866347	$-9*((8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5)/(4/3+2))+1$	-387420301	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-352866349	$-9*((8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5)/(4/3+2))-1$	-387420316	$(98+76)-(((5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))+1$
-355129137	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)+765)/4)*(32+1)$	-387420662	$(-98-(76+((5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
-355135505	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6+5/4+3-2)+1$	-387420677	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-355135507	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6+5/4+3-2)-1$	-387420679	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5-4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-355147416	$(9/8-7)*((6^{\wedge}5-4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-387420697	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7-6*5)*(4+3+2)-1$
-355330152	$(9/8-7)*((6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-387420803	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-362796768	$9*8*((7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)/2-1)$	-387420805	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-5+4))/3^{\wedge}2-1$
-362797344	$9*8*((-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)/2+1)$	-387420852	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-76)*(5+4))+321$
-363505323	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)*76)/(5+4))+321$	-387421010	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+65)*(-4-3-2)+1$
-363505965	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)*76)/(5+4))-321$	-387421012	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+65)*(-4-3-2)-1$
-365897187	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6+5-4+3/2)+1$	-387421127	$(9^{\wedge}8+76-5)*(-4-3-2)+1$
-365897189	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*6+5-4+3/2)-1$	-387421475	$(-987-((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2)))+1$
-368777822	$-98*((((7^{\wedge}6)-54)*32)-1)$	-387421477	$-987-(((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-368778018	$-98*((((7^{\wedge}6)-54)*32)+1)$	-387421494	$(((-9^{\wedge}8)-76)*(5+4))-321$
-369116510	$-98*((((7^{\wedge}6)+54)*32)-1)$	-387538039	$98-7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-369116706	$-98*((((7^{\wedge}6)+54)*32)+1)$	-387538041	$98-7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-373027200	$-98*((76+(5^{\wedge}4)*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-387538120	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-373027297	$(-98*((76+(5^{\wedge}4)*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-387538122	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-373027299	$(-98*((76+(5^{\wedge}4)*3)^{\wedge}2))-1$	-387538136	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-373027396	$-98*((76+(5^{\wedge}4)*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-387538140	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-373301032	$((9+8+7)*6-5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)*-1$	-387682637	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-374837567	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-387682639	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-374837569	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-387889632	$(-987-6)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
-376029854	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-387890624	$((-987-6)*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))+1$
-376029856	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-387890626	$((-987-6)*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))-1$
-377487211	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7*6+5)*(4/3+2))-1$	-387891618	$(-987-6)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))+1)$
-378949760	$9*8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-388361671	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-378949762	$9*8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-388361673	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-381182534	$(9*8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(-43-2)+1$	-388361689	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-381182536	$(9*8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(-43-2)-1$	-388361691	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-381184784	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(-43-2)+1$	-390491192	$((-98*76)/5)*((4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))+1$
-381184786	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(-43-2)-1$	-397065307	$9*(8-((7^{\wedge}6)*5+321))$
-383202144	$(-987+6)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$	-397065447	$-9*(8+((7^{\wedge}6)*5+321))$
-383203124	$((-987+6)*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))+1$	-398811104	$9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-383203126	$((-987+6)*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))-1$	-398811106	$9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-383204106	$(-987+6)*((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))+1)$	-400003391	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-383828125	$((-9*8-7)-6)*5^{\wedge}(4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-400003393	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-384072189	$(-9*8*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3+2+1$	-400175072	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3-2)+1$
-385539966	$987*((6-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1)$	-400175074	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3-2)-1$
-385540952	$(987*(6-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-400235724	$((98-((7^{\wedge}6)*54))*3)*21$
-385540954	$(987*(6-(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))-1$	-400248072	$((-98-((7^{\wedge}6)*54))*3)*21$
-385541940	$987*(6-((5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1)$	-408943915	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*(6-(5-4*3)/2)+1$
-385551810	$-987*((6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1)$	-408943917	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7)*(6-(5-4*3)/2)-1$
-385552796	$(-987*(6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))+1$	-414444261	$-987*((((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-385552798	$(-987*(6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2)))))-1$	-414445247	$(-987*((((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-385553784	$-987*((6+(5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1)$	-414445249	$(-987*((((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-386479287	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-414446235	$-987*((((6^{\wedge}5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-386479289	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-418161595	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4-3*2)*-1$
-387158339	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-420901271	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6+5-(4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-387158341	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-420901273	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6+5-(4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-387158349	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-423536327	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-387158351	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-423536329	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-387302741	$98+7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-423536402	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-387302743	$98+7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-429922889	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*6^{\wedge}5)*4+3*2)+1$
-387302822	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-429922891	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*6^{\wedge}5)*4+3*2)-1$
-387302824	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-430390670	$((-9^{\wedge}8)+7654)*(3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-387302838	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-430466739	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*6+5)*4+3*2)+1$
-387302842	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-430466741	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7*6+5)*4+3*2)-1$
-387347363	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*5^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}2+1$	-430467029	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6+5)*4+3*2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-430467031	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-488280269	$(987-(6+((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)))^*1$
-430467125	$(-9^8+7^*6/5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488280270	$987-((6+((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1)$
-430467131	$(-9^8+7+6-5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-488282230	$((-987+6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$
-430467149	$(-9^8+7-6+5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488282231	$((-987+6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$
-430467169	$(-9^8-7+6+5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488282232	$(-987+6)-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$
-430467171	$(-9^8-7+6+5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-488282242	$(-987-(6+((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)))+1$
-430467289	$(-9^8-7-6+5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488282243	$(-987-(6+((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)))^*1$
-430467361	$(-9^8-76/5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488282244	$-987-((6+((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1)$
-430467363	$(-9^8-76/5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-488287171	$((-987^*6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$
-430467679	$(-9^8-7^*6-5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488287172	$((-987^*6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$
-430467681	$(-9^8-7^*6-5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-488287173	$(-987^*6)-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$
-430543750	$((-9^8)-7654)^*(3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-488288697	$((-98^*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$
-431011529	$(-9^8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-488288698	$((-98^*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$
-431011531	$(-9^8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-488288699	$(-98^*76)-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$
-434007160	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)+1$	-488291125	$(-9876-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$
-434007162	$(-9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)-1$	-488291126	$(-9876-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$
-441183788	$9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2+1$	-488291127	$-9876-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$
-441183790	$9-(-8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2-1$	-490733373	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7^*6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1)))$
-441183806	$-9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2+1$	-491161320	$(-9/8-7)^*(6^{\wedge}5-4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-441183808	$-9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2-1$	-491414040	$(-9/8-7)^*(6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-442050620	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^* -1$	-492884392	$((9+8)^*7+6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^* -1$
-451990559	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4-3/2)+1$	-492884396	$((9+8+7)^*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3-2/-1$
-451990561	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4-3/2)-1$	-492884407	$((9+8+7)^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^* -1$
-451990580	$(9^8+7-6)^*(5-4-3/2)+1$	-495037141	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5^*4+3)/2+1$
-451990582	$(9^8+7-6)^*(5-4-3/2)-1$	-495037143	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5^*4+3)/2-1$
-451990706	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4-3/2)+1$	-495037279	$(-9^8+7-6)^*(5^*4+3)/2+1$
-451990708	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4-3/2)-1$	-495037281	$(-9^8+7-6)^*(5^*4+3)/2-1$
-452125178	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-432))+1)$	-495037302	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5^*4+3)/2+1$
-452125180	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-432))-1)$	-495037304	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5^*4+3)/2-1$
-453225884	$(9^8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5-4-3/2)+1$	-499568524	$(-98/76)*(((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))-1)$
-453225886	$(9^8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5-4-3/2)-1$	-503317929	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-454371847	$((9*(8+7)+6+5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-506249995	$((9+8+7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^* -1$
-454371861	$((9*(8+7)+6+5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)/-1$	-506250006	$((9^*8-7^*6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^* -1$
-457416423	$-9*((8*(7^{\wedge}6))^*54-321)$	-509184862	$9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)+1$
-457422201	$-9*((8*(7^{\wedge}6))^*54)+321)$	-509184864	$9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)-1$
-466944345	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))^*3^*2+1$	-509184880	$-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)+1$
-466953417	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))^*3^*2-1$	-509184882	$-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)-1$
-468669656	$(-9^*8)*(((7654/3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-511777682	$-9^8*(7-6/5+4+3+2)+1$
-468669727	$((-9^*8)*(((7654/3)^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-511777684	$-9^8*(7-6/5+4+3+2)-1$
-468669728	$((-9^*8)*(((7654/3)^{\wedge}2))^*1)$	-512315980	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-468669729	$((-9^*8)*(((7654/3)^{\wedge}2))-1)$	-512315982	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-468669800	$((-9^*8)*(((7654/3)^{\wedge}2))+1)$	-512742149	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}5-4+3+2)+1$
-470595998	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3/2+1$	-512742151	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}5-4+3+2)-1$
-470596002	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3/2-1$	-512840268	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-472214853	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2+1$	-512840270	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-472219791	$(-9^8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4^*3/2)+1$	-512949630	$9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)+1$
-472219793	$(-9^8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4^*3/2)-1$	-512949632	$9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)-1$
-472332951	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2+1$	-512949648	$-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)+1$
-473509533	$((-9^8+7)^*(6+5))+4321$	-512949650	$-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)-1$
-473509687	$((-9^8+7)^*(6+5))+4321$	-516551451	$((((-9^8)+765)^*4)^*3)+2+1$
-473513094	$(-9^8+76)^*(5+4^*3/2)+1$	-516551493	$((((-9^8)+765)^*4)^*3)-2-1$
-473513096	$(-9^8+76)^*(5+4^*3/2)-1$	-516560147	$(9^8-7^*6)^*(5^*4-32)+1$
-473518175	$((-9^8+7)^*(6+5))-4321$	-516560149	$(9^8-7^*6)^*(5^*4-32)-1$
-473518329	$((-9^8+7)^*(6+5))-4321$	-516560331	$(9^8)^*(7^*6-54)+321$
-473626175	$(-9+8/7)^*(6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-516560807	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5^*4-32)+1$
-474236400	$(-9+8/7)^*(6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-516560809	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5^*4-32)-1$
-475947120	$(-9+8/7)^*(6^{\wedge}5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-516560973	$((9^8)^*(7^*6-54))-321$
-478684160	$-9^8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5*(-4/3-2)+1$	-516561155	$(9^8+7^*6)^*(5^*4-32)+1$
-478684162	$-9^8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5*(-4/3-2)-1$	-516561157	$(9^8+7^*6)^*(5^*4-32)-1$
-488271373	$(9876-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$	-516561563	$(9^8+76)^*(5^*4-32)+1$
-488271374	$(9876-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$	-516561565	$(9^8+76)^*(5^*4-32)-1$
-488271375	$9876-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$	-516569811	$((((-9^8)-765)^*4)^*3)+2+1$
-488273801	$((98^*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$	-516569853	$((((-9^8)-765)^*4)^*3)-2-1$
-488273802	$((98^*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$	-517788804	$(-9876/5)*((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))+1)$
-488273803	$(98^*76)-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$	-518832089	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-488275327	$((98^*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$	-518832091	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-488275328	$((98^*76)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$	-521213858	$(9^8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*(5-4+3-2)+1$
-488275329	$(98^*76)-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$	-521213860	$(9^8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*(5-4+3-2)-1$
-488280256	$((987+6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))+1$	-524348779	$-9^8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2))+1$
-488280257	$((987+6)-((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2))^*1$	-524348781	$-9^8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2))-1$
-488280258	$(987+6)-(((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)+1)$	-524531280	$-987*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^*2))-1$
-488280268	$(987-(6+((5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*2)))+1$	-524532266	$(-987/((6/54)^{\wedge}(3^*2)))+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-524532267	$-987/((6/54)^{(3+2)+1})$	-566120439	$-9*(8^7*6*(5-4^{(-3-2)}))-1$
-524532268	$(-987/((6/54)^{(3*2)}))-1$	-567952964	$(-9^8-7*6^{(5+4)})*(3+2)+1$
-524533254	$-987*((6/54)^{(-3*2)})+1$	-567952966	$(-9^8-7*6^{(5+4)})*(3+2)-1$
-525184825	$(-9*8^7*6+5)*(4^3-2)+1$	-570369145	$(-9^8-7)*(6+5/4+3^2)+1$
-525184827	$(-9*8^7*6+5)*(4^3-2)-1$	-570369147	$(-9^8-7)*(6+5/4+3^2)-1$
-525185445	$(-9*8^7*6-5)*(4^3-2)+1$	-574950402	$9*((8-((7^6)*543))+21)$
-525185447	$(-9*8^7*6-5)*(4^3-2)-1$	-574950546	$-9*((8+((7^6)*543))-21)$
-525525269	$-9^8-7*6*(5+4^{(3*2)})+1$	-574950570	$(9*(8-((7^6)*543)))+21$
-525525271	$-9^8-7*6*(5+4^{(3*2)})-1$	-574950612	$(9*(8-((7^6)*543)))-21$
-528519168	$(9^8)^{(7-(-6-5))}*(4/3-21)$	-574950714	$(-9*(8+((7^6)*543)))+21$
-531096741	$((98-((7^6)^5))^43)*21$	-574950756	$(-9*(8+((7^6)*543)))-21$
-531183177	$(98-(((7^6)^5)^43))^21$	-574950780	$9*(8-(((7^6)^543)+21))$
-531187293	$(-98-(((7^6)^5)^43))^21$	-574950924	$-9*((8+((7^6)*543))+21)$
-531273729	$((-98*((7^6)^5))^43)*21$	-585252863	$-9*(8*7*(6-54)^3)^2+1$
-538083849	$(-9^8+7+6)^5*(4-3/2)+1$	-585252865	$-9*(8*7*(6-54)^3)^2-1$
-538083851	$(-9^8+7+6)^5*(4-3/2)-1$	-591493832	$9^8*7*(6/(54^3)-2)+1$
-538083924	$(9^8-7)^*(6-5*4+3/2)+1$	-591493834	$9^8*7*(6/(54^3)-2)-1$
-538083926	$(9^8-7)^*(6-5*4+3/2)-1$	-597186252	$9*(8-((7^6)^543)+21))$
-538083999	$(-9^8+7-6)^5*(4-3/2)+1$	-597186396	$-9*(8+((7^6)^543+21))$
-538084001	$(-9^8+7-6)^5*(4-3/2)-1$	-602240750	$9^8*7*((6/54)^3-2)+1$
-538084024	$(-9^8+7+6)^5*(4-3/2)+1$	-602240752	$9^8*7*((6/54)^3-2)-1$
-538084026	$(-9^8+7+6)^5*(4-3/2)-1$	-602362882	$-9+8-7*6*5^4*(3+2)-1$
-540475496	$9^8*(7-6*5^4)^3-2+1$	-602647723	$(-9^8+7*65)*(4^3+2)+1$
-540475498	$9^8*(7-6*5^4)^3-2-1$	-602647725	$(-9^8+7*65)*(4^3+2)-1$
-545848956	$-9^8*(-8+7+6)^*(5^4*3^2-1)$	-602648773	$(-9^8+7*65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-550041434	$-9^8*(7-(6/54-3)^2)+1$	-602648775	$(-9^8+7*65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-550041436	$-9^8*(7-(6/54-3)^2)-1$	-602652959	$(-9^8+7*65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-550597319	$-9*8^7/7^6-6*5*(4+3^2)+1$	-602652961	$(-9^8+7*65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-550597321	$-9*8^7/7^6-6*5*(4+3^2)-1$	-602653085	$(-9^8+7+65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-552714930	$9*(8-((7^6)^543-21))$	-602653087	$(-9^8+7+65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-552715074	$-9*(8+((7^6)^543-21))$	-602653281	$(-9^8-7+65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-558899756	$(-9^8+7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-602653283	$(-9^8-7+65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-558899758	$(-9^8+7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-602653911	$(9^8-7-6)*(5-4^3)^2+1$
-559067717	$(9^8*7^6-5)^*(4^3-2)+1$	-602653913	$(9^8-7-6)*(5-4^3)^2-1$
-559067719	$(9^8*7^6-5)^*(4^3-2)-1$	-602654163	$(-9^8/(7-6)-5)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559553052	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+54321$	-602654415	$(-9^8+7-6*5)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559585768	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+5*(4321)$	-602654417	$(-9^8+7-6*5)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559590039	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+54*(321)$	-602654905	$(-9^8+7-65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559595970	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+543*21$	-602654907	$(-9^8+7-65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559601940	$(((-9^8)^*(7+6))+5432)+1$	-602655087	$(-9^8-7+65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559601941	$(((-9^8)^*(7+6))+5432)*1$	-602655089	$(-9^8-7+65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559601942	$(((-9^8)^*(7+6))+5432)-1$	-602655101	$(-9^8-7-65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559603047	$(((-9^8)^*(7+6))+5)+4321$	-602655103	$(-9^8-7-65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559603057	$(((-9^8)^*(7+6))-5)+4321$	-602655227	$(-9^8-7-65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559604642	$(-9^8+7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-602655229	$(-9^8-7-65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559604644	$(-9^8+7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-602659413	$(-9^8-7*65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559606384	$(9^8-76)^*(-5-4^3/2)+1$	-602659415	$(-9^8-7*65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559606386	$(9^8-76)^*(-5-4^3/2)-1$	-602660463	$(-9^8-7*65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559606809	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+543+21$	-602660465	$(-9^8-7*65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559606851	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+543+21$	-602664803	$(-9^8-7*65)^*(4^3+2)+1$
-559606998	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+54+321$	-602664805	$(-9^8-7*65)^*(4^3+2)-1$
-559607106	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-54+321$	-603067436	$9^8*7*((-6/54)^3-2)+1$
-559607640	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+54-321$	-603067438	$9^8*7*((-6/54)^3-2)-1$
-559607748	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-54+321$	-613814354	$9^8*7*(-6/(54^3)-2)+1$
-559607895	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-543+21$	-613814356	$9^8*7*(-6/(54^3)-2)-1$
-559607937	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-543+21$	-616992036	$(((-9^8)+765)^43)/(2+1)$
-559610102	$(-9^8-7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-617013966	$(((-9^8)-765)^43)/(2+1)$
-559610104	$(-9^8-7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-622598484	$((-98*(7^6))^54+3)+21$
-559611689	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))+5-4321$	-622598490	$((-98*(7^6))^54-3)+21$
-559611699	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-5+4321$	-622598494	$-98*((7^6)^54-(3/21))$
-559612804	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-5432+1$	-622598522	$-98*((7^6)^54+(3/21))$
-559612805	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-5432*1$	-622598526	$((-98*(7^6))^54+3)-21$
-559612806	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-5432+1$	-622598532	$((-98*(7^6))^54-(3+21))$
-559618776	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-543*21$	-622599095	$98*(-7^6*54-3^2)+1$
-559624707	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-54*321$	-622599097	$98*(-7^6*54-3^2)-1$
-559628978	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-5*4321$	-624177352	$(-9^8+7)^*(6^5-4+3)/2+1$
-559661694	$((-9^8)^*(7+6))-54321$	-624177354	$(-9^8+7)^*(6^5-4+3)/2-1$
-560314988	$(-9^8-7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)+1$	-627892784	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-32))+1$
-560314990	$(-9^8-7*6^5)^*(4+3^2)-1$	-627892786	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-32))-1$
-564351123	$((9^8)^{(7-(-6-5))}+4+3)^*-21$	-631351907	$-9^8*(7+6+5-4/3-2)+1$
-565968895	$-9*8^7*6^5+4^3^2+1$	-631351909	$-9^8*(7+6+5-4/3-2)-1$
-565968897	$-9*8^7*6^5+4^3^2-1$	-641715915	$((-9-8)^*((7^6)^54))^321$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-641809968	$((-9-8)*7^6+5^4)*321$	-710271112	$(9^8+7+6)*(5-43/2)-1$
-642211218	$((-9-8)*7^6-5^4)*321$	-722228319	$(9^8)*(((76/54)^3)-21)$
-642305271	$((-9-8)*((7^6)+5^4))*321$	-731794137	$(9^8-7)*(6+5+4-32)+1$
-645700794	$((9^8)*((7-65)+43))+21$	-731794139	$(9^8-7)*(6+5+4-32)-1$
-645700836	$((9^8)*((7-65)+43))-21$	-732411999	$9876-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652209606	$(9-8^7+6)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-732414427	$(98*76)-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652209608	$(9-8^7+6)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-732415953	$(987*6)-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652212396	$9-(8^7-6)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-732420882	$(987+6)-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652212398	$9-(8^7-6)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-732421796	$-9+87-6*5^4(4^3)/2+1$
-652212414	$-9-(8^7-6)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-732421798	$-9+87-6*5^4(4^3)/2-1$
-652212416	$-9-(8^7-6)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-732421829	$-9+8*7-6*5^4(4^3)/2-1$
-652213338	$(9-8^7-6)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-732421921	$9-8*7-6*5^4(4^3)/2+1$
-652213340	$(9-8^7-6)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-732421939	$-9-8*7-6*5^4(4^3)/2+1$
-652215204	$(9+8^7-6)*(5^4+3)/2+1$	-732422868	$-987-(6+((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1)))$
-652215206	$(9+8^7-6)*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-732427797	$(-987*6)-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652216128	$9-(8^7+6)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-732429323	$(-98*76)-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652216130	$9-(8^7+6)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-732431751	$-9876-((5^4(4^3))^*(2+1))$
-652216146	$-9-(8^7+6)*(5^4-3)/2+1$	-750224025	$(-9-8)/7*((6+5^4)^3)-1$
-652216148	$-9-(8^7+6)*(5^4-3)/2-1$	-753317389	$(-9^8+7+6)*5^4(4+3)/2+1$
-652218936	$(9+8^7+6)*(5^4+3)/2+1$	-753317391	$(-9^8+7+6)*5^4(4+3)/2-1$
-652218938	$(9+8^7+6)*(5^4+3)/2-1$	-755180748	$((98-((7^6)^5))^4)*321$
-656352447	$((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+4321$	-755275122	$98-(((7^6)^5)^4)*321$
-656355484	$((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+(4*321)$	-755338038	$(-98-(((7^6)^5)^4))*321$
-656355865	$((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+(43*21)$	-755432412	$((-98-((7^6)^5))^4)*321$
-656356335	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+432)+1$	-757069705	$9*((-8^7+6)*(5+4/3)^{\wedge 2})+1$
-656356336	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+432)*1$	-757069707	$9*((-8^7+6)*(5+4/3)^{\wedge 2})-1$
-656356337	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+432)-1$	-774703206	$(9^8-7654)*(3-21)$
-656356443	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+4)+321$	-774758574	$(9^8)-(7*654))*(3-21)$
-656356451	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-4)+321$	-774767106	$(9^8)-(76*54))*(3-21)$
-656356704	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+43)+21$	-774785898	$(9^8)-(765*4))*(3-21)$
-656356746	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+43)-21$	-774827136	$(9^8)-(765+4))*(3-21)$
-656356747	$(9/(87*-6))^{\wedge}(-5/(4-3))+21$	-774827280	$((9^8)-765)+4*(3-21)$
-656356790	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-43)+21$	-774829080	$((9^8)-(7+654))*(3-21)$
-656356832	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-43+21)$	-774829332	$((9^8)+7)-654*(3-21)$
-656357085	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})+4)-321$	-774829575	$(((-9^8)/7)^6)+543)*21$
-656357093	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-4)+321$	-774836657	$((-9^8)*((7+6)+5))+4321$
-656357199	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-432)+1$	-774838638	$(9^8)-(76+54))*(3-21)$
-656357200	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-432)*1$	-774839589	$(((-9^8)+76)^5*54)/3)+21$
-656357201	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-432+1)$	-774839631	$((((-9^8)+76)^5*54)/3)-21$
-656357671	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-43*21)$	-774840221	$(-9^8+7*6)*(5+4+3^{\wedge 2})+1$
-656358052	$(((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-4*321)$	-774840223	$(-9^8+7*6)*(5+4+3^{\wedge 2})-1$
-656361089	$((-9/(87*6))^{\wedge-5})-4321$	-774840582	$((9^8)-76)+54*(3-21)$
-656916480	$(9+8+7)^{\wedge 6}*(-5+(4/3)^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-774841374	$((9^8)+76)-54*(3-21)$
-661775667	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge 6}*5^4-3)+2+1$	-774841733	$(-9^8-7*6)*(5+4+3^{\wedge 2})+1$
-661775669	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge 6}*5^4-3)+2-1$	-774841735	$(-9^8-7*6)*(5+4+3^{\wedge 2})-1$
-677973807	$(((-9^8)+765)/4)^3)*21$	-774842325	$((((-9^8)-76)^5*54)/3)+21$
-677985965	$(9^8+7)*(65/4-32)+1$	-774842367	$((((-9^8)-76)^5*54)/3)-21$
-677985967	$(9^8+7)*(65/4-32)-1$	-774843318	$((9^8)+76)+54*(3-21)$
-688746548	$(987-((6/(54^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge-2}))+1$	-774845299	$((-9^8)*((7+6)+5))-4321$
-688746549	$(987-((6/(54^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge-2}))*1$	-774852381	$((((-9^8)/7)^6)-543)*21$
-688746550	$987-(((6/(54^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge-2}))+1$	-774852624	$((9^8)-7)+654*(3-21)$
-688748522	$(-987-((6/(54^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge-2}))+1$	-774852876	$((9^8)+7)+654*(3-21)$
-688748523	$(-987-((6/(54^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge-2}))*1$	-774854676	$((9^8)+765)-4*(3-21)$
-688748524	$-987-(((6/(54^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge-2}))+1$	-774854820	$((9^8)+765)+4*(3-21)$
-691216672	$-9*((8765-(4/3)^{\wedge 2})-1)$	-774896058	$((9^8)+765*4)*(3-21)$
-691216680	$(-9*((8765-(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))+1$	-774914850	$((9^8)+76*54)*(3-21)$
-691216681	$(-9*((8765-(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))*1$	-774923382	$((9^8)+7*654)*(3-21)$
-691216682	$(-9*((8765-(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))-1$	-774978750	$(9^8+7654)*(3-21)$
-691216690	$-9*((8765-(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))+1$	-785953124	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge 6}*(5+4/3^{\wedge 2}))+1$
-691637392	$-9*((8765+(4/3)^{\wedge 2})-1)$	-785953126	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge 6}*(5+4/3^{\wedge 2}))-1$
-691637400	$(-9*((8765+(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))+1$	-787218750	$(9*(8+7)^{\wedge-6}/(-5^4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-691637402	$(-9*((8765+(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))-1$	-796364097	$(-9^8+7+6)*(5*4-3/2)+1$
-691637410	$-9*((8765+(4/3)^{\wedge 2}))+1$	-796364099	$(-9^8+7+6)*(5*4-3/2)-1$
-705911756	$((98+(7+6)^5)^{\wedge 4-3-2})*-1$	-796364208	$(-9^8+7)*(6^5+4+3)/2+1$
-705911767	$((98+(7+6)^5)^{\wedge 4+3-2})/-1$	-796364210	$(-9^8+7)*(6^5+4+3)/2-1$
-707879411	$9^8*(7-(6+5))*(4+3^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-807072139	$-98*7^{\wedge 6}*5*(4^3+2)+1$
-707879413	$9^8*(7-(6+5))*(4+3^{\wedge-2})-1$	-807072141	$-98*7^{\wedge 6}*5*(4^3+2)-1$
-710270780	$(-9^8+7)*(6+5+4+3/2)+1$	-813189879	$9-8*(7^6)^{\wedge 5}*((4/3)^{\wedge 2}-1)$
-710270782	$(-9^8+7)*(6+5+4+3/2)-1$	-813189897	$-9-8*(7^6)^{\wedge 5}*((4/3)^{\wedge 2}-1)$
-710271011	$(-9^8-7)*(6+5+4+3/2)+1$	-835425252	$(-9^8)*(((76/54)-3)+21)$
-710271013	$(-9^8-7)*(6+5+4+3/2)-1$	-841802543	$9^8*(7-6-5*(4+3^{\wedge-2}))+1$
-710271110	$(9^8+7+6)*(5-43/2)+1$	-841802545	$9^8*(7-6-5*(4+3^{\wedge-2}))-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-846570468	$((9^8) - 765) * ((4/3) - 21)$	-903983115	$((-9^8) - (76 + (54/3))) * 21$
-846600558	$((9^8) + 765) * ((4/3) - 21)$	-903983436	$((-9^8) - (765 / (4+3))) * 21$
-847072799	$-9 * 8 * 7^6 * 5^4 * (3+2) + 1$	-903984375	$((-9^8) - (7 * (65 - 43))) * 21$
-847072801	$-9 * 8 * 7^6 * 5^4 * (3+2) - 1$	-903985670	$((-9^8) + ((7 - 654) / 3)) * 21$
-851368481	$-9^8 * (7 * (6/54 + 3) - 2) + 1$	-903985768	$((-9^8) - ((7 + 654) / 3)) * 21$
-851368483	$-9^8 * (7 * (6/54 + 3) - 2) - 1$	-903985866	$(9^8 + 7 + 654 / 3) * - 21$
-853633089	$(-9 / ((87654 - 3)^2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-903986468	$((-9^8) - ((765 - 4) / 3)) * 21$
-853749961	$(-9 / ((87654 + 3)^2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-903986524	$((-9^8) - ((765 + 4) / 3)) * 21$
-860932579	$((((-9^8) + 76) * 5)^4) + 321$	-903997017	$((-9^8) - (7 * (65 + 43))) * 21$
-860933221	$((((-9^8) + 76) * 5)^4) - 321$	-903997178	$(((-9^8) - 765) + (4/3)) * 21$
-860933479	$(9^8 - 7 * 6 - 5) * 4 * (-3 - 2) + 1$	-903997234	$((-9^8) - (765 + (4/3))) * 21$
-860933481	$(9^8 - 7 * 6 - 5) * 4 * (-3 - 2) - 1$	-904002561	$((-9^8) - ((765 * 4) / 3)) * 21$
-860934251	$(-9^8 + 7 * 6 / 5) * 4 * (3 + 2) + 1$	-904021902	$((-9^8) + ((7 - 654) * 3)) * 21$
-860934253	$(-9^8 + 7 * 6 / 5) * 4 * (3 + 2) - 1$	-904022784	$((-9^8) - ((7 + 654) * 3)) * 21$
-860934299	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6 + 5) * 4 * (3 + 2) + 1$	-904029084	$((-9^8) - ((765 - 4) * 3)) * 21$
-860934579	$(-9^8 - 7 - 6 + 5) * 4 * (3 + 2) + 1$	-904029588	$((-9^8) - ((765 + 4) * 3)) * 21$
-860934723	$(9^8 + 76 / 5) * 4 * (-3 - 2) + 1$	-904034719	$(9^8 + 7654 / 3) * - 21$
-860934725	$(9^8 + 76 / 5) * 4 * (-3 - 2) - 1$	-904041789	$((-9^8) + (76 * (5 - 43))) * 21$
-860935619	$((((-9^8) - 76) * 5)^4) + 321$	-904057749	$((-9^8) - (76 * (5 + 43))) * 21$
-860936261	$((((-9^8) - 76) * 5)^4) - 321$	-904060080	$((-9^8) + (7 * (6 - 543))) * 21$
-870500357	$9^8 * 7 * (6 * - 5 + 4) / 3^2 + 1$	-904061844	$((-9^8) - (7 * (6 + 543))) * 21$
-870500359	$9^8 * 7 * (6 * - 5 + 4) / 3^2 - 1$	-904062537	$((-9^8) - (76 * (54 - 3))) * 21$
-880066295	$-9^8 * (7 - 6 + 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} - 2)) + 1$	-904072113	$((-9^8) - (76 * (54 + 3))) * 21$
-880066297	$-9^8 * (7 - 6 + 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} - 2)) - 1$	-904076838	$((-9^8) - (7 * (654 - 3))) * 21$
-882442098	$((-9^8) + 765) * ((43/2) - 1)$	-904077720	$((-9^8) - (7 * (654 + 3))) * 21$
-882473463	$((-9^8) - 765) * ((43/2) - 1)$	-904093596	$((-9^8) - (765 * (4 + 3))) * 21$
-883786383	$(9^8) * ((76 / (54 * 3)) - 21)$	-904173921	$((-9^8) - ((765 * 4) * 3)) * 21$
-889632233	$-9^8 * (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 / 3^2) + 1$	-904239693	$((-9^8) - ((76 * 54) * 3)) * 21$
-889632235	$-9^8 * (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 / 3^2) - 1$	-904269555	$((-9^8) - ((7 * 654) * 3)) * 21$
-900544274	$(-9 - (8 + 7 + 6))^{\wedge} (-5 + 4 * 3) / 2 + 1$	-905009301	$((-9^8) - (765 * (4^{\wedge} 3))) * 21$
-900544276	$(-9 - (8 + 7 + 6))^{\wedge} (-5 + 4 * 3) / 2 - 1$	-916394966	$9 - (8 * 7 + 6)^{\wedge} 5 - 4^{\wedge} 3^2 + 1$
-902952981	$((-9^8) + (765 * (4^{\wedge} 3))) * 21$	-916394968	$9 - (8 * 7 + 6)^{\wedge} 5 - 4^{\wedge} 3^2 - 1$
-903692727	$((-9^8) + ((7 * 654) * 3)) * 21$	-916636171	$((9 + (8 + 7) * (6 + 5))^{\wedge} 4 - 3 - 2) * - 1$
-903722589	$((-9^8) + ((76 * 54) * 3)) * 21$	-916636182	$((9 + (8 + 7) * (6 + 5))^{\wedge} 4 + 3^2) * - 1$
-903788361	$((-9^8) + ((765 * 4) * 3)) * 21$	-924175899	$((-9^8) * ((76 / (54 * 3)) + 21))$
-903868686	$((-9^8) + (765 * (4 + 3))) * 21$	-925504221	$(9^8 - 7 - 6) * (-5 * 4 - 3 / 2) + 1$
-903884562	$((-9^8) + (7 * (654 + 3))) * 21$	-925504223	$(9^8 - 7 - 6) * (-5 * 4 - 3 / 2) - 1$
-903885444	$((-9^8) + (7 * (654 - 3))) * 21$	-927895985	$-9^8 * (7 - 6 + 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} - 2)) + 1$
-903890169	$((-9^8) + (76 * (54 + 3))) * 21$	-927895987	$-9^8 * (7 - 6 + 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} - 2)) - 1$
-903899745	$((-9^8) + (76 * (54 - 3))) * 21$	-932571414	$(-9 - 8) / 7 * 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge} (3^2) - 1)$
-903900438	$((-9^8) + (7 * (6 + 543))) * 21$	-936360000	$((9 * 8 * 7 + 6) * 5 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 * - 1$
-903902202	$((-9^8) - (7 * (6 - 543))) * 21$	-937890616	$((98 + 7 * (6 + 5))^{\wedge} 4 - 3^2) / - 1$
-903904533	$((-9^8) + (76 * (5 + 43))) * 21$	-937890631	$((98 + 7 * (6 + 5))^{\wedge} 4 + 3^2) * - 1$
-903920493	$((-9^8) - (76 * (5 - 43))) * 21$	-940956799	$-98 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge} 3 - 2) + 1$
-903927563	$(9^8 - 7654 / 3) * - 21$	-940956801	$-98 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge} 3 - 2) - 1$
-903932694	$((-9^8) + ((765 + 4) * 3)) * 21$	-941191996	$9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 * 4)^{\wedge} 3 + 2 + 1$
-903933198	$((-9^8) + ((765 - 4) * 3)) * 21$	-941192004	$-9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 * 4)^{\wedge} 3 - 2 - 1$
-903939498	$((-9^8) + ((7 + 654) * 3)) * 21$	-947017852	$((-9^8) + (7 * 65)) * (43 - 21)$
-903940380	$((-9^8) - ((7 - 654) * 3)) * 21$	-947026080	$(9^8 - 76 - 5) * (-43 + 21)$
-903959721	$((-9^8) + ((765 * 4) / 3)) * 21$	-947026300	$(9^8 - 76 + 5) * (-43 + 21)$
-903965048	$(((-9^8) + 765) + (4/3)) * 21$	-947027541	$((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) + 321$
-903965104	$(((-9^8) + 765) - (4/3)) * 21$	-947027575	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6) * (54 - 32) + 1$
-903965265	$((-9^8) + (7 * (65 + 43))) * 21$	-947027577	$(-9^8 + 7 + 6) * (54 - 32) - 1$
-903975758	$((-9^8) + ((765 + 4) / 3)) * 21$	-947027687	$(((-9^8) + 7) * (65 - 43)) + 21$
-903975814	$((-9^8) + ((765 - 4) / 3)) * 21$	-947027729	$(((-9^8) + 7) * (65 - 43)) - 21$
-903976416	$(9^8 - 7 - 654 / 3) * - 21$	-947027829	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) + 32) + 1$
-903976514	$((-9^8) + ((7 + 654) / 3)) * 21$	-947027830	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) + 32) * 1$
-903976612	$((-9^8) - ((7 - 654) / 3)) * 21$	-947027831	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) + 32) - 1$
-903977907	$((-9^8) + (7 * (65 - 43))) * 21$	-947027838	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) + 3) + 21$
-903978846	$((-9^8) + (765 / (4 + 3))) * 21$	-947027839	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6) * (54 - 32) + 1$
-903979167	$(((-9^8) + 76) + (54 / 3)) * 21$	-947027841	$(-9^8 + 7 - 6) * (54 - 32) - 1$
-903979544	$(-9^8 + 76) * (5 * 4 + 3 - 2) + 1$	-947027844	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) - 3) + 21$
-903979546	$(-9^8 + 76) * (5 * 4 + 3 - 2) - 1$	-947027880	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) + 3) - 21$
-903980231	$((-9^8) + ((76 + 54) / 3)) * 21$	-947027883	$(-9^8 - 7 + 6) * (54 - 32) + 1$
-903980987	$((-9^8) + ((76 - 54) / 3)) * 21$	-947027885	$(-9^8 - 7 + 6) * (54 - 32) - 1$
-903981113	$((-9^8) + (76 / (54 + 3))) * 21$	-947027886	$((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) - (3 + 21)$
-903981169	$((-9^8) - (76 / (54 + 3))) * 21$	-947027893	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) - 32) + 1$
-903981286	$(-9^8 * 7 + 6 - 54) * 3 - 2 + 1$	-947027894	$(((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) - 32) * 1$
-903981295	$((-9^8) - ((76 - 54) / 3)) * 21$	-947027895	$((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) - (32 + 1)$
-903981413	$(9^8 + 7 + 6) * (-5 * 4 - 3 + 2) + 1$	-947027995	$(((-9^8) - 7) * (65 - 43)) + 21$
-903981415	$(9^8 + 7 + 6) * (-5 * 4 - 3 + 2) - 1$	-947028037	$(((-9^8) - 7) * (65 - 43)) - 21$
-903982051	$((-9^8) - ((76 + 54) / 3)) * 21$	-947028183	$((-9^8) * (76 - 54)) - 321$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-947029424	$(9^8+76-5)^*(-43+21)$	-1109292254	$98+((76^5)^*((4/3)^{-2}-1))$
-947029644	$(9^8+76+5)^*(-43+21)$	-1109292450	$-98+((76^5)^*((4/3)^{-2}-1))$
-947037872	$((-9^8)-(7*65))^*(43-21)$	-1109914524	$(9^8-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/-2+1$
-960097367	$((-9*87)^{-6-(-5-4)+3})^{*2+1}$	-1109914526	$(9^8-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/-2-1$
-961359684	$((-9^8)+765)^*((4/3)+21)$	-1109914531	$(9^8+7+6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/-2+1$
-961393854	$((-9^8)-765)^*((4/3)+21)$	-1109914533	$(9^8+7+6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/-2-1$
-967458894	$9-87-(6^{\wedge}5^4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	-1118447108	$9^8*(7+6)^*((5+4)^{-3-2})+1$
-968486558	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$	-1118447110	$9^8*(7+6)^*((5+4)^{-3-2})-1$
-968486560	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	-1119214407	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5^4+3^2)+1$
-968534010	$((-9^8)+765)^*((43/2)+1)$	-1119214409	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5^4+3^2)-1$
-968551379	$(9^8+7)^*(6-54+3)/2+1$	-1119214771	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5^4+3^2)+1$
-968551381	$(9^8+7)^*(6-54+3)/2-1$	-1119214773	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5^4+3^2)-1$
-968568435	$((-9^8)-765)^*((43/2)+1)$	-1136027024	$-9*(8+7-6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-972537030	$(9^8)^*((76/54)-(3+21))$	-1136027026	$-9*(8+7-6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-990070262	$((9^8)^*(7-(6*5))) +4321$	-1139265008	$-9*(8+7+6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-990072834	$(9^8-76)^*(5+4-32)+1$	-1139265010	$-9*(8+7+6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-990072836	$(9^8-76)^*(5+4-32)-1$	-1140737761	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5+43/2)+1$
-990078904	$((9^8)^*(7-(6*5)))-4321$	-1140737763	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5+43/2)-1$
-991872036	$((9/((87*6)^*543))^{\wedge}-2)^*-1$	-1146119132	$(-9^8-7)^*6*(5-(4/3)^{-2})+1$
-999999927	$9^8+(-7+6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-1146119134	$(-9^8-7)^*6*(5-(4/3)^{-2})-1$
-999999929	$9^8+(-7+6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1149752464	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2*-1$
-999999984	$9+8-(7-6+5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-1162240812	$((9^8)-765)^*((4-32)+1)$
-1004423488	$-9^8*7/6*5^4+3-2+1$	-1162282122	$((9^8)+765)^*((4-32)+1)$
-1004423492	$-9^8*7/6*5^4-3+2-1$	-1176073704	$-9*(8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^2+1))$
-1011597778	$(9^8-7)^*(6+(5-4^{\wedge}3)/2)+1$	-1183784469	$(9^8-7-6)^*5*(4-3/2)+1$
-1011597780	$(9^8-7)^*(6+(5-4^{\wedge}3)/2)-1$	-1183784471	$(9^8-7-6)^*5*(4-3/2)-1$
-1032937608	$(9^8-7654)^*(-3-21)$	-1197473791	$9^8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-1033011432	$((-9^8)+(7*654))^*(3+21)$	-1197473793	$9^8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1033022808	$((-9^8)+(76*54))^*(3+21)$	-1205306031	$(9^8-7*(6+5))^*(4-32)+1$
-1033047864	$((-9^8)+(765*4))^*(3+21)$	-1205306033	$(9^8-7*(6+5))^*(4-32)-1$
-1033102848	$(((-9^8)+765)+4)^*(3+21)$	-1205307151	$(9^8-7*6+5)^*(4-32)+1$
-1033103040	$(((-9^8)+765)-4)^*(3+21)$	-1205307153	$(9^8-7*6+5)^*(4-32)-1$
-1033105440	$(((-9^8)+7)+654)^*(3+21)$	-1205307543	$(9^8+7-6*5)^*(4-32)+1$
-1033105776	$(((-9^8)-7)+654)^*(3+21)$	-1205307545	$(9^8+7-6*5)^*(4-32)-1$
-1033116714	$((-9^8)+(765/4))^*(3+21)$	-1205308047	$(9^8/(7-6)-5)^*(4-32)+1$
-1033118184	$(((-9^8)+76)+54)^*(3+21)$	-1205308049	$(9^8/(7-6)-5)^*(4-32)-1$
-1033120776	$(((-9^8)+76)-54)^*(3+21)$	-1205308154	$(-9^8*7+6+5)^*4-3^{\wedge}2-1$
-1033121832	$(((-9^8)-76)+54)^*(3+21)$	-1205308167	$((-9^8)^*(76-(5+43))) +21$
-1033124424	$((-9^8)-(76+54))^*(3+21)$	-1205308209	$((-9^8)^*(76-(5+43))) -21$
-1033125894	$((-9^8)-(765/4))^*(3+21)$	-1205308222	$(-9^8*7-6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2+1$
-1033136832	$(((-9^8)+7)-654)^*(3+21)$	-1205308327	$(9^8/(7-6)+5)^*(4-32)+1$
-1033137168	$(((-9^8)-7)+654)^*(3+21)$	-1205308329	$(9^8/(7-6)+5)^*(4-32)-1$
-1033139568	$(((-9^8)-765)+4)^*(3+21)$	-1205309223	$(9^8+7*6-5)^*(4-32)+1$
-1033139760	$(((-9^8)-765+4))^*(3+21)$	-1205309225	$(9^8+7*6-5)^*(4-32)-1$
-1033194744	$((-9^8)-(765*4))^*(3+21)$	-1205309503	$(9^8+7*6+5)^*(4-32)+1$
-1033219800	$((-9^8)-(76*54))^*(3+21)$	-1205309505	$(9^8+7*6+5)^*(4-32)-1$
-1033231176	$((-9^8)-(7*654))^*(3+21)$	-1205310343	$(9^8+7*(6+5))^*(4-32)+1$
-1033305000	$(9^8+7654)^*(-3-21)$	-1205310345	$(9^8+7*(6+5))^*(4-32)-1$
-1039122432	$(9+8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5+(4/3)^{-2}-1)$	-1205329607	$((9^8)+765)^*(4-32)+1$
-1049759995	$((9-8-7)^*6*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2/-1$	-1205329609	$((9^8)+765)^*(4-32)-1$
-1049760003	$((9-8-7)^*6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)^*(-2+1)$	-1220965269	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2))/-1$
-1066867803	$(9^8+7-6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/2+1$	-1224510000	$(9+8)^*(7*6*5)^{\wedge}4*-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1066867805	$(9^8+7-6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/2-1$	-1226815497	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7*(65-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$
-1066867810	$(9^8-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/2+1$	-1226831348	$(9^8-7)^*(-6-54+3)/2+1$
-1066867812	$(9^8-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/2-1$	-1226831350	$(9^8-7)^*(-6-54+3)/2-1$
-1069674670	$98-((76^5)/((4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-1248332724	$((9^8)-765)^*(4-(32+1))$
-1069674866	$-98-((76^5)/((4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-1248354879	$(9^8-7+6)^*(-5*4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-1070271225	$(-9/(((8+7)^*6543)^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-1248354881	$(9^8-7+6)^*(-5*4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1076168004	$(-9^8/((7-6)/5)+4)^*(3+2)+1$	-1248354888	$((-9^8)^*((7+65)-43))+21$
-1076168006	$(-9^8/((7-6)/5)+4)^*(3+2)-1$	-1248354930	$((-9^8)^*((7+65)-43))-21$
-1078959050	$-9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)))+1$	-1248354937	$(9^8+7-6)^*(-5*4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-1078959052	$-9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)))-1$	-1248354939	$(9^8+7-6)^*(-5*4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1085733963	$(-9^8)^*((76/54)^3)+21$	-1248377094	$((9^8)+765)^*(4-(32+1))$
-1086017562	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*543)-21$	-1249198264	$9^8-((7*6+5)^4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-1086018276	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6)^*543)+21$	-1249198336	$(-9+8)/((7*6+5)^4)^{\wedge}(-3-2+1)$
-1088391122	$-9+8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4+3)/2-1$	-1262704301	$9^8*7-(65+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-1088391214	$9-8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4+3)/2+1$	-1262704303	$9^8*7-(65+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-1090516751	$(((-9^8)*76)+543)/(2+1)$	-1272269691	$((((-9^8)*76)/54)+3)^*21$
-1090516893	$((((-9^8)*76)+54)/3)+21$	-1272269817	$((((-9^8)*76)/54)-3)^*21$
-1090516971	$((((-9^8)*76)-54)/3)-21$	-1273864077	$(9^8)^*((76/54)-32)+1$
-1090517113	$(((-9^8)*76)-543)/(2+1)$	-1277052722	$9^8*(7-65-4/3)/2+1$
-1097199376	$(-9+8)^*(7*(6*5-4))^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-1277052724	$9^8*(7-65-4/3)/2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1285811415	$((-987+6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)})-1$	-1377492129	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32-1$
-1285815339	$(-987+6)^*(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))-1$	-1377492479	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5)+4)^*32+1$
-1285816319	$((-987+6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$	-1377492481	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5)+4)^*32-1$
-1285816321	$((-987+6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)})-1$	-1377492735	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5)-4)^*32+1$
-1285817301	$(-987+6)^*(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$	-1377492737	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5)-4)^*32-1$
-1285821225	$((-987+6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$	-1377493055	$(-9^8+7/6^5)^*32+1$
-1291397099	$(((-9^8)+7)^6)^5+4321$	-1377493057	$(-9^8+7/6^5)^*32-1$
-1291397519	$(((-9^8)-7)^6)^5+4321$	-1377493887	$(9^8+7-(6+5)^4)^*-32+1$
-1291405741	$(((-9^8)+7)^6)^5-4321$	-1377493889	$(9^8+7-(6+5)^4)^*-32-1$
-1291406161	$(((-9^8)-7)^6)^5-4321$	-1377496255	$(-9^8+7-(6+5)^4)^*32+1$
-1293669783	$987^*(6-(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))-1))$	-1377496257	$(-9^8+7-(6+5)^4)^*32-1$
-1293673731	$987^*((6-(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))))+1$	-1377497087	$(-9^8-7/6^5)^*32+1$
-1293674717	$987^*(6-(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))))+1$	-1377497089	$(-9^8-7/6^5)^*32-1$
-1293674719	$987^*(6-(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))))-1$	-1377497407	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5)+4)^*32+1$
-1293675705	$987^*(6-((5^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1))$	-1377497409	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5)+4)^*32-1$
-1293679653	$987^*(6-(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1))$	-1377497663	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5)-4)^*32+1$
-1293681627	$-987^*(6+(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))-1))$	-1377497665	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5)-4)^*32-1$
-1293685575	$-987^*((6+(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))))-1$	-1377498015	$9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32+1$
-1293686561	$(-987^*(6+(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))))+1$	-1377498017	$9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32-1$
-1293686563	$(-987^*(6+(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))))-1$	-1377500895	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5^4))^*32+1$
-1293687549	$-987^*((6+(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1))$	-1377500897	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5^4))^*32-1$
-1293691497	$-987^*(6+(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1))$	-1378489503	$9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32+1$
-1295028979	$((-9/((8+7)^{654}))^{\wedge-3})+21$	-1378489505	$9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32-1$
-1295029021	$((-9/((8+7)^{654}))^{\wedge-3})-21$	-1378491295	$(-9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*32+1$
-1300967449	$(9+8)^*(7+(-6^5)^{\wedge(-3-2)})^{\wedge-1}$	-1378491297	$(-9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*32-1$
-1301539995	$((-987-6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)})-1$	-1379235999	$(-9^8-7^*(6^5-4))^*32+1$
-1301543967	$(-987-6)^*(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))-1$	-1379236001	$(-9^8-7^*(6^5-4))^*32-1$
-1301544959	$((-987-6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$	-1379237791	$(-9^8-7^*(6^5+4))^*32+1$
-1301544961	$((-987-6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)})-1$	-1379237793	$(-9^8-7^*(6^5+4))^*32-1$
-1301545953	$(-987-6)^*(5^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$	-1399018204	$(-9^8+7)^*(6+5+43/2)+1$
-1301549925	$((-987-6)^5)^*(4^{(3^2)}))+1$	-1399018206	$(-9^8+7)^*(6+5+43/2)-1$
-1334211077	$((-9^8)+7654)^*(32-1)$	-1416468487	$(9^*(8+7+6)+5)^{\wedge4-3^2})/(-1)$
-1334306433	$((-9^8)+7^654)^*(32-1)$	-1416468493	$(9^*(8+7+6)+5)^{\wedge4-3})/(-2+1)$
-1334321127	$((-9^8)+76^54)^*(32-1)$	-1416659375	$(-9^8+7^6)^*(5-4+32)+1$
-1334353491	$((-9^8)+765^4)^*(32-1)$	-1416659377	$(-9^8+7^6)^*(5-4+32)-1$
-1334424512	$((-9^8)+765)+4)^*(32-1)$	-1420289211	$((-9^8)+7654)^*(32+1)$
-1334424760	$((-9^8)+765)-4)^*(32-1)$	-1420390719	$((-9^8)+7^654)^*(32+1)$
-1334427860	$((-9^8)+7)+654)^*(32-1)$	-1420406361	$((-9^8)+76^54)^*(32+1)$
-1334428294	$((-9^8)-7)+654)^*(32-1)$	-1420440813	$((-9^8)+765^4)^*(32+1)$
-1334444321	$((-9^8)+76)+54)^*(32-1)$	-1420516416	$((-9^8)+765)+4)^*(32+1)$
-1334447669	$((-9^8)+76)-54)^*(32-1)$	-1420516548	$((-9^8)+765)^*(4^3+21)$
-1334448319	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4-32)+1$	-1420516680	$((-9^8)+765)-4)^*(32+1)$
-1334448321	$(9^8+7+6)^*(5-4-32)-1$	-1420519980	$((-9^8)+7)+654)^*(32+1)$
-1334449033	$((-9^8)-76)+54)^*(32-1)$	-1420520442	$((-9^8)-7)+654)^*(32+1)$
-1334452381	$((-9^8)-76+54)^*(32-1)$	-1420537503	$((-9^8)+76)+54)^*(32+1)$
-1334468408	$((-9^8)+7)-654)^*(32-1)$	-1420540406	$9^8-7^6)^*(-5+4-32)+1$
-1334468842	$((-9^8)-7+654)^*(32-1)$	-1420540408	$9^8-7^6)^*(-5+4-32)-1$
-1334471942	$((-9^8)-765)+4)^*(32-1)$	-1420541067	$((-9^8)+76)-54)^*(32+1)$
-1334472190	$((-9^8)-765+4)^*(32-1)$	-1420541759	$(9^8+7+6)^*(-5+4-32)+1$
-1334543211	$((-9^8)-765^4)^*(32-1)$	-1420541761	$9^8+7+6)^*(-5+4-32)-1$
-1334575575	$((-9^8)-76^54)^*(32-1)$	-1420542519	$((-9^8)-76)+54)^*(32+1)$
-1334590269	$((-9^8)-7^654)^*(32-1)$	-1420543178	$9^8+7^6)^*(-5+4-32)+1$
-1334685625	$((-9^8)-7654)^*(32-1)$	-1420543180	$9^8+7^6)^*(-5+4-32)-1$
-1348963434	$(-98^*(7^6))^*(54+(3^21))$	-1420544300	$(-9^8-76)^*(5-4+32)+1$
-1355971931	$(-9^8-7)^*(6+5+3)/2+1$	-1420544302	$(-9^8-76)^*(5-4+32)-1$
-1355971933	$(-9^8-7)^*(6+5+3)/2-1$	-1420546083	$((-9^8)-(76+54))^*(32+1)$
-1359957519	$(9^8)^*((76/54)-(32+1))$	-1420563144	$((-9^8)+7)-654)^*(32+1)$
-1367795539	$((9+8)^{\wedge7-6-5})^*(-4/3-2)+1$	-1420563606	$((-9^8)-(7+654))^*(32+1)$
-1367795541	$((9+8)^{\wedge7-6-5})^*(-4/3-2)-1$	-1420566906	$((-9^8)-765)+4)^*(32+1)$
-1372712102	$9^8^*((7-6)/(5+4)-32)+1$	-1420567038	$((-9^8)-765)^*(4^3+21)$
-1372712104	$9^8^*((7-6)/(5+4)-32)-1$	-1420567170	$((-9^8)-(765+4))^*(32+1)$
-1375752351	$(-9^8+7^*(6^5+4))^*32+1$	-1420642773	$((-9^8)-(765^4))^*(32+1)$
-1375752353	$(-9^8+7^*(6^5+4))^*32-1$	-1420677225	$((-9^8)-(76^54))^*(32+1)$
-1375754143	$(-9^8+7^*(6^5-4))^*32+1$	-1420692867	$((-9^8)-(7^654))^*(32+1)$
-1375754145	$(-9^8+7^*(6^5-4))^*32-1$	-1420794375	$((-9^8)-7654)^*(32+1)$
-1376498847	$(9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*-32+1$	-1426232925	$(98-((76^5)/((4/3)^2)))+1$
-1376498849	$(9^8-(7+6^5)^4)^*-32-1$	-1426232926	$(98-((76^5)/((4/3)^2)))+1$
-1376500639	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32+1$	-1426232927	$98-(((76^5)/((4/3)^2)))+1$
-1376500641	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32-1$	-1426233121	$(-98-((76^5)/((4/3)^2)))+1$
-1377489247	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5^4))^*32+1$	-1426233122	$(-98-((76^5)/((4/3)^2)))+1$
-1377489249	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5^4))^*32-1$	-1426233123	$-98-(((76^5)/((4/3)^2)))+1$
-1377492127	$(-9^8-(7-6^5)^4)^*32+1$	-1431303040	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5/4+32)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1431303042	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5/4+32)-1$	-1592700372	$((-9^8)+765)^*((4+32)+1)$
-1439673668	$-9^8*((7+6)/(5+4)+32)+1$	-1592724356	$((-9^8)^*(7+(6^5)))+4321$
-1439673670	$-9^8*((7+6)/(5+4)+32)-1$	-1592725864	$(9^8-76)^*(-5-4^3/2)+1$
-1463588071	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5^4-3)^2+1$	-1592725866	$(9^8-76)^*(-5-4^3/2)-1$
-1463588073	$(-9^8+7+6)^*(5^4-3)^2-1$	-1592728417	$(-9^8+7)^*(65+4-32)+1$
-1463588547	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5^4-3)^2+1$	-1592728419	$(-9^8+7)^*(65+4-32)-1$
-1463588549	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5^4-3)^2-1$	-1592732998	$((-9^8)^*(7+(6^5)))-4321$
-1464843649	$(9+8)^*7-6^*(5^4(4^3)+2+1)$	-1592756982	$((-9^8)-765)^*((4+32)+1)$
-1481126067	$(-9^8)^*((76/54)+32)+1$	-16000000003	$((9^*(8+7)+65)^4+3)/(-2+1)$
-1485111908	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5+4^3)/2+1$	-1612796985	$9^*(8^7*(6-(5^4)^{(3+2)}))-1$
-1485111910	$(-9^8-7+6)^*(5+4^3)/2-1$	-1614251774	$(9^8-7)^*6^5/-4^*(3+2)+1$
-1499897315	$(-9+8)^*7*((6+5)^4-3)^2+1$	-1614251776	$(9^8-7)^*6^5/-4^*(3+2)-1$
-1506608460	$((-9^8)+765)^*((4+32)-1)$	-1628860662	$(-9-(8+7)^6)^*((5+4+3)^2-1)$
-1506634989	$(9^8-7)^*(6-5-4-32)+1$	-1633640409	$-9-8^*(7^6)^5*(4/3)^2+1$
-1506634991	$(9^8-7)^*(6-5-4-32)-1$	-1635772489	$((9^8)-76)^*(5-43)+21$
-1506635213	$(-9^8+7+6)^*5-4-3-2+1$	-1635772531	$((9^8)-76)^*(5-43)-21$
-1506635257	$(-9^8+7-6)^*5+4+3+2-1$	-1635778265	$((9^8)+76)^*(5-43)+21$
-1520999990	$((-9^8)-765)^*((4+32)-1)$	-1635778307	$((9^8)+76)^*(5-43)-21$
-1520999992	$9-(-8+(7^6-5^4)/3)^2+1$	-1641599487	$(9-8^7)^*((5^4)^{(3+2)}-1)$
-1520999992	$9-(-8+(7^6-5^4)/3)^2-1$	-1644167217	$-98^*((7-6-5)^{(4^3+2)^{-1}})$
-1521000008	$-9-(-8+(7^6-5^4)/3)^2+1$	-1650124304	$-9^8*(7-6/(5+4)+32)+1$
-1521000010	$-9-(-8+(7^6-5^4)/3)^2-1$	-1650124306	$-9^8*(7-6/(5+4)+32)-1$
-1526726665	$-9-8^7*((6-5-4)^{(3^2)}-1)$	-1656225791	$(9+8+7)^6*(-5^4/3-2)+1$
-1535333048	$-9^8*(7/6+(5+4^3)/2)+1$	-1656225793	$(9+8+7)^6*(-5^4/3-2)-1$
-1535333050	$-9^8*(7/6+(5+4^3)/2)-1$	-1657466944	$((9/((8^7)^6543))^2)^*-1$
-1544898986	$9^8*(-7-65^4/3^2)+1$	-1666598968	$9-(8/(7^6)^{(5+4-3)}))^2-1$
-1544898988	$9^8*(-7-65^4/3^2)-1$	-1669856593	$98^*(7-65^4)^3+1$
-1549679039	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1669856595	$98^*(7-65^4)^3-1$
-1549679041	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1700345755	$(-9^8-7)^*(6^5/4+32)+1$
-1549679183	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5))^*(4+32)+1$	-1700345757	$(-9^8-7)^*(6^5/4+32)-1$
-1549679185	$(-9^8+7^*(6+5))^*(4+32)-1$	-1713387747	$9-((8^7)^6-5)-4)/(-3+21)$
-1549679363	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1721838240	$((-9^8)+765)^*(43-(2+1))$
-1549679365	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1721868559	$(-9^8+7)^*(6^5+4+3^2)+1$
-1549681307	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1721868561	$(-9^8+7)^*(6^5+4+3^2)-1$
-1549681309	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1721899440	$((-9^8)-765)^*(43-(2+1))$
-1549681667	$(-9^8+7+6-5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1728028512	$(-9-8)^*(7^6)^5*(4/3)^2-1$
-1549681669	$(-9^8+7+6-5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1738524060	$-9/8^*((7+(6^5+4)^3)^2-1)$
-1549681739	$(-9^8+7-6+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1743392483	$(-9^8-7)^*(6+(5+4^3)/2)+1$
-1549681741	$(-9^8+7-6+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1743392485	$(-9^8-7)^*(6+(5+4^3)/2)-1$
-1549681745	$(-9^8+7/6^5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1764912239	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
-1549681747	$(-9^8+7/6^5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1764912241	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
-1549681775	$(-9^8/(7-6)+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1764912608	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
-1549681777	$(-9^8/(7-6)+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1764912610	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
-1549681817	$(-9^8-7/6+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1764914822	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
-1549681819	$(-9^8-7/6+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1764914824	$(-9^8+7+6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
-1549682135	$(-9^8/(7-6)-5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1764915027	$(9^8-7-6)^*(-5-4-32)+1$
-1549682137	$(-9^8/(7-6)-5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1764915029	$(9^8-7-6)^*(-5-4-32)-1$
-1549682243	$(-9^8-7-6+5)^*(4+32)+1$	-1764915240	$((9^8)^*((7+6)-54))+321$
-1549682245	$(-9^8-7-6+5)^*(4+32)-1$	-1764915765	$(9^8/(7-6)+5)^*(-43+2)+1$
-1549684727	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5))^*(4+32)+1$	-1764915767	$(9^8/(7-6)+5)^*(-43+2)-1$
-1549684729	$(-9^8-7^*(6+5))^*(4+32)-1$	-1764915882	$((9^8)^*((7+6)-54))-321$
-1551100131	$((-987^6)+5)^*((4^4(3^2)))-1$	-1766100616	$((9-8-7^6)^5)^4-3^2)/-1$
-1551106047	$((-987^6)+5)^*(4^4(3^2))+1$	-1766100620	$((9-8-7^6)^5)^4-3-2)^*-1$
-1551106049	$((-987^6)+5)^*(4^4(3^2))-1$	-1779264467	$9^8*(7-6/54)^*-3^2+1$
-1551111965	$((-987^6)+5)^*((4^4(3^2))+1)$	-1779264469	$9^8*(7-6/54)^*-3^2-1$
-1551641507	$(-9^8-7^6)^5*(4+32)+1$	-1779688827	$(987-(6^5))^*((4^4(3^2)))-1$
-1551641509	$(-9^8-7^6)^5*(4+32)-1$	-1779695615	$((987-(6^5))^*(4^4(3^2)))+1$
-1552381236	$(987^6)^*(5-(4^4(3^2)))+1$	-1779695617	$((987-(6^5))^*(4^4(3^2)))-1$
-1552386171	$987^*((6^*(5-(4^4(3^2)))))+1$	-1779702405	$(987-(6^5))^*((4^4(3^2))+1)$
-1552388145	$987^*((6^*(5-(4^4(3^2)))))-1$	-1798196656	$-9^8*7^6+5^4(4^3-2)+1$
-1552393080	$(987^6)^*(5-(4^4(3^2))+1)$	-1798196658	$-9^8*7^6+5^4(4^3-2)-1$
-1552440456	$(-987^6)^*((5+(4^4(3^2)))-1)$	-1807930152	$((-9^8)+765)^*((43-2)+1)$
-1552445391	$-987^*((6^*(5+(4^4(3^2)))))-1$	-1807960823	$-9^8*7^6+(5+4)^3+2+1$
-1552447365	$-987^*((6^*(5+(4^4(3^2)))))+1$	-1807960825	$-9^8*7^6+(5+4)^3+2-1$
-1552452300	$(-987^6)^*((5+(4^4(3^2)))+1)$	-1807961992	$-9^8*7^6+(5^4-3)^2+1$
-1553721561	$((-987^6)-5)^*(4^4(3^2))-1$	-1807962572	$-9^8*7^6-(5^4-3)^2-1$
-1553727487	$((-987^6)-5)^*(4^4(3^2))+1$	-1807963739	$-9^8*7^6-(5+4)^3+2+1$
-1553727489	$((-987^6)-5)^*(4^4(3^2))-1$	-1807963741	$-9^8*7^6-(5+4)^3+2-1$
-1553733415	$((-987^6)-5)^*((4^4(3^2))+1)$	-1807994412	$((-9^8)-765)^*((43-2)+1)$
-1563641576	$(9^8+(7^6)^5)^*(-4-3-2)+1$	-1817528219	$9^8*76/(-5-4)^*(3+2)+1$
-1563641578	$(9^8+(7^6)^5)^*(-4-3-2)-1$	-1817528221	$9^8*76/(-5-4)^*(3+2)-1$
-1576329926	$((-9^8)^*(765+4))+3/21$	-1817727906	$-9^8*7^6-5^4(4^3-2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1817727908	$-9^8 * 7 * 6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3 - 2) - 1$	-1977064581	$9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1823990994	$(-98 * (76 - 5)) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1)$	-1977064583	$9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1823997854	$-98 * (((76 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))) - 1$	-1977064597	$9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1823997951	$((-98 * (76 - 5)) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) + 1$	-1977064601	$-9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1823997953	$((-98 * (76 - 5)) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) - 1$	-1977588869	$9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1823998050	$-98 * (((76 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))) + 1$	-1977588871	$9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1824004910	$(-98 * (76 - 5)) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1)$	-1977588885	$9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1829453130	$((-9^8) + 765) * (43 - (2^{\wedge} - 1))$	-1977588889	$-9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1829485344	$(9^8 - 7) * ((-6 - 5) * 4 + 3/2) + 1$	-1977588903	$-9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1829485346	$(9^8 - 7) * ((-6 - 5) * 4 + 3/2) - 1$	-1977588905	$-9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1829485939	$(9^8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5) * 4 + 3/2) + 1$	-1977588958	$-9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1829485941	$(9^8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5) * 4 + 3/2) - 1$	-1977588960	$-9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1829518155	$((-9^8) - 765) * (43 - (2^{\wedge} - 1))$	-1980113976	$((-9^8) + 765) * ((43 + 2) + 1)$
-1841443064	$-9^8 * 7 * (6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge}(-3 + 2)) + 1$	-1980145669	$(-9^8 + 76) * (5 + 43 - 2) + 1$
-1841443066	$-9^8 * 7 * (6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge}(-3 + 2)) - 1$	-1980145671	$(-9^8 + 76) * (5 + 43 - 2) - 1$
-1864650312	$(-9^8 * ((7 * 6543)^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-1980184356	$((-9^8) - 765) * ((43 + 2) + 1)$
-1872499086	$((-9^8) + 765) * (43 + (2^{\wedge} - 1))$	-1987681063	$-9 + ((-87 - 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4) / (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-1872532058	$-9^8 * 7 * ((-6 - 5/4) * 3^2 + 1)$	-1987856694	$-9^8 - ((7 * 6^5) / 4 - 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
-1872532060	$(9^8 - 7) * (-6 - 5/4) * 3^2 - 1$	-1987856748	$-9^8 - ((7 * 6^5) / 4 + 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
-1872565641	$((-9^8) - 765) * (43 + (2^{\wedge} - 1))$	-1995385029	$9^8 - 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1878112494	$(((-9^8) * 76) / 54) * (32 - 1)$	-1995385031	$9^8 - 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1882384002	$-9^8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1$	-1999281042	$(((-9^8) * 76) / 54) * (32 + 1)$
-1894022064	$((-9^8) + 765) * ((43 + 2) - 1)$	-2012434533	$(-9^8 - 7) * (65 / 4 * 3 - 2) + 1$
-1894089384	$((-9^8) - 765) * ((43 + 2) - 1)$	-2012434535	$(-9^8 - 7) * (65 / 4 * 3 - 2) - 1$
-1927733388	$-98 * ((((-6 - 5) + 4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1)$	-2023191566	$((-9^8) * ((7 * 6) + 5)) + 4321$
-1927734374	$(-98 * ((((-6 - 5) + 4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) + 1)$	-2023200208	$((-9^8) * ((7 * 6) + 5)) - 4321$
-1927734376	$(-98 * ((((-6 - 5) + 4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) - 1)$	-2029209952	$(-98^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5)) * (43 - 21)$
-1927735362	$-98 * ((((-6 - 5) + 4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1)$	-2036033594	$(9 + 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
-1937098799	$(9^8 - 76 - 5) * (-43 - 2) + 1$	-2036072447	$(9^{\wedge}(8 - 7) - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937098801	$(9^8 - 76 - 5) * (-43 - 2) - 1$	-2036072449	$(9^{\wedge}(8 - 7) - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937098979	$(-9^8 + 7 * (6 + 5)) * (43 + 2) + 1$	-2036334582	$9 + 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937098981	$(-9^8 + 7 * (6 + 5)) * (43 + 2) - 1$	-2036334584	$9 + 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937099204	$(9^8 - 7 - 65) * (-43 - 2) + 1$	-2036334600	$-9 + 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937099206	$(9^8 - 7 - 65) * (-43 - 2) - 1$	-2036334602	$-9 + 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937100554	$(-9^8 + 7 * 6) * (54 - 3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-2036596718	$9 + 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937100556	$(-9^8 + 7 * 6) * (54 - 3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-2036596720	$9 + 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937101634	$(9^8 - 7 - 6 - 5) * (-43 - 2) + 1$	-2036596734	$9 - 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937101636	$(9^8 - 7 - 6 - 5) * (-43 - 2) - 1$	-2038422981	$987 - ((6^{\wedge}5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1))$
-1937101859	$(9^8 - 7 - 6) * -5 * (4 + 3 + 2) + 1$	-2038424955	$-987 - ((6^{\wedge}5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1))$
-1937101861	$(9^8 - 7 - 6) * -5 * (4 + 3 + 2) - 1$	-2038430960	$9 * 87 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937102066	$(-9^8 + 7 * 6 / 5) * (43 + 2) + 1$	-2038430962	$9 * 87 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937102068	$(-9^8 + 7 * 6 / 5) * (43 + 2) - 1$	-2038431057	$98 * 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937102219	$(-9^8 / (7 - 6) + 5) * (43 + 2) + 1$	-2038431059	$98 * 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937102221	$(-9^8 / (7 - 6) + 5) * (43 + 2) - 1$	-2038431239	$9 * 8 * 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937102669	$(-9^8 / (7 - 6) - 5) * (43 + 2) + 1$	-2038431241	$9 * 8 * 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937102671	$(-9^8 / (7 - 6) - 5) * (43 + 2) - 1$	-2038431638	$98 + 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937104334	$(-9^8 - 7 * 6) * (54 - 3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-2038431640	$98 + 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937104336	$(-9^8 - 7 * 6) * (54 - 3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-2038431647	$9 + 87 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937105909	$(-9^8 - 7 * (6 + 5)) * (43 + 2) + 1$	-2038431649	$9 + 87 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937105911	$(-9^8 - 7 * (6 + 5)) * (43 + 2) - 1$	-2038431652	$98 - 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1937364588	$-9^{\wedge}(8 + 7 - 6) * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-2038431654	$98 - 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1937364590	$-9^{\wedge}(8 + 7 - 6) * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-2038431767	$-9 - 8 - 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1939551884	$(-9^8 - 7 * 6^{\wedge}5) * (43 + 2) + 1$	-2038431821	$9 - 87 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1939551886	$(-9^8 - 7 * 6^{\wedge}5) * (43 + 2) - 1$	-2038438533	$987 - ((6^{\wedge}5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1))$
-1951130349	$((-98 * 76) + 5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1)$	-2038440507	$-987 - ((6^{\wedge}5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1))$
-1951137791	$(((-98 * 76) + 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) + 1$	-2040033660	$(9 + 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$
-1951137793	$(((-98 * 76) + 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) - 1$	-2040266734	$9 + 8 + (-7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1951145235	$((-98 * 76) + 5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1)$	-2040266736	$9 + 8 + (-7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1952403824	$(98 * 76) * ((5 - (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) + 1)$	-2040266750	$9 - 8 + (-7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1952411174	$98 * ((76 * (5 - (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))) + 1)$	-2040528886	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1952411370	$98 * ((76 * (5 - (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))) - 1)$	-2040528888	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1952418720	$(98 * 76) * (5 - ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1))$	-2040528904	$-9 - 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1952478304	$(-98 * 76) * ((5 + (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) - 1)$	-2040528906	$-9 - 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1952485654	$-98 * ((76 * (5 + (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))) - 1)$	-2040791039	$(-9^{\wedge}(8 - 7) - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1952485850	$-98 * ((76 * (5 + (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)))) + 1)$	-2040791041	$(-9^{\wedge}(8 - 7) - 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1952493200	$(-98 * 76) * ((5 + (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) + 1)$	-2056033924	$(-9 - 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$
-1953124013	$987 - (((6 * (5^{\wedge}4)) / 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$	-2058033956	$(9 + 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (-5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2)) + 1$
-1953125987	$-987 - (((6 * (5^{\wedge}4)) / 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$	-2058033958	$(9 + 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (-5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2)) - 1$
-1953751779	$((-98 * 76) - 5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) - 1)$	-2060033990	$(9 + 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (-5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$
-1953759231	$(((-98 * 76) - 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) + 1$	-2066238939	$(((-9^8) + 76) * (5 + 43)) + 21$
-1953759233	$(((-98 * 76) - 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))) - 1$	-2066238981	$(((-9^8) + 76) * (5 + 43)) - 21$
-1953766685	$((-98 * 76) - 5) * ((4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)) + 1)$	-2066241951	$(((-9^8) - 7) * (6 - 54)) + 321$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2066242593	$((9^8)-7)*(6-54)-321$		
-2066242623	$((9^8)+7)*(6-54)+321$		
-2066243265	$((9^8)+7)*(6-54)-321$		
-2066246235	$((-9^8)-76)*(5+43)+21$		
-2066246277	$((-9^8)-76)*(5+43)-21$		
-2080891134	$(-98*(76+5))*((4^(3^2))-1)$		
-2080907010	$(-98*(76+5))*((4^(3^2))+1)$		
-2109284751	$(((-9^8)^7)+654)/3)^*21$		
-2109293907	$(((-9^8)^7)-654)/3)^*21$		
-2117681999	$-9/8*7^6*(5^4)^3*2+1$		
-2117682001	$-9/8*7^6*(5^4)^3*2-1$		
-2136750616	$((9-8+7*6)^5)^4-3^2)/-1$		
-2136750620	$((9-8+7*6)^5)^4-3-2)^*-1$		